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**Taxonomie génomique des souches bactériennes et
émergence de l'antibiorésistance**

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Sommaire

REMERCIEMENTS.....	1
SOMMAIRE.....	3
INTRODUCTION.....	5
1. INTRODUCTION SUR LES PATHOGENES D'INTÉRÊT ET LEUR RÉSISTANCE AUX ANTIBIOTIQUES	7
1.1. <i>Corynebacterium diphtheriae</i>	7
1.1.1. La diphtérie.....	7
1.1.2. Caractérisation génomique.....	9
1.1.3. Microbiologie classique revisitée par la génomique	10
1.1.4. Résistance aux antibiotiques	16
1.1.5. Outil précurseur de DIPHTOSCAN.....	18
1.2. <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	19
1.2.1. Caractérisation génomique.....	21
1.2.2. Écologie	21
1.2.3. Résistance aux antibiotiques	22
1.2.4. Pathogénicité et virulence	23
2. CONCEPTS ET APPROCHES DE LA TAXONOMIE BACTÉRIENNE	24
2.1. <i>Classification bactérienne</i>	25
2.1.1. Historique des méthodes de classification bactérienne	25
2.1.2. Les méthodes de classification bactérienne.....	26
2.1.3. Les rangs de classification, de l'espèce à la 'souche'.....	29
2.1.4. Les espèces monomorphes.....	32
2.2. <i>Nomenclature</i>	33
2.2.1. Nomenclature bactérienne aux rangs de l'espèce bactérienne et supérieurs.....	33
2.2.2. Nomenclature sous le rang de la sous-espèce bactérienne	34
2.3. <i>Identification bactérienne</i>	49
2.3.1. L'identification au rang des espèces	49
2.3.2. L'identification des souches sur la base de classifications génomiques.....	50
2.4. <i>La taxonomie des espèces et des souches chez C. diphtheriae et K. pneumoniae</i>	51
2.4.1. Diversité des Corynébactéries du complexe <i>diphtheriae</i>	51
2.4.2. Diversité du complexe d'espèces <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	52
VUE D'ENSEMBLE DU PROJET.....	55
PARTIE I : L'ÉMERGENCE ET ÉVOLUTION DE LA RÉSISTANCE BACTÉRIENNE AUX ANTIBIOTIQUES.....	57
CHAPITRE 1 : GÉNOMIQUE DES POPULATIONS ET RÉSISTANCE AUX ANTIMICROBIENS CHEZ <i>C. DIPHTHERIAE</i>	58
<i>Résumé</i>	58
<i>Contributions personnelles</i>	58
<i>Article</i>	59
CHAPITRE 2 : DIPHTOSCAN, UN PIPELINE POUR DÉTECTER LA RÉSISTANCE ET LA VIRULENCE DANS LE COMPLEXE DES ESPÈCES <i>DIPHTHERIAE</i>	77
<i>Résumé</i>	77
<i>Contributions personnelles</i>	78
<i>Article</i>	79
PARTIE II : TAXONOMIE GÉNOMIQUE ET DIVERSITÉ DES SOUCHES CHEZ LES ESPÈCES BACTÉRIENNES PATHOGÈNES	113
CHAPITRE 3 : UNE TAXONOMIE GÉNOMIQUE DES SOUCHES DE <i>KLEBSIELLA PNEUMONIAE</i>	114

<i>Résumé</i>	114
<i>Contributions personnelles</i>	114
<i>Article</i>	116
CHAPITRE 4 : UNE TAXONOMIE GÉNOMIQUE DES SOUCHES DE <i>CORYNEBACTERIUM DIPHTHERIAE</i>	132
<i>Résumé</i>	132
<i>Contributions personnelles</i>	132
<i>Article</i>	133
CHAPITRE 5 : <i>CORYNEBACTERIUM ROUXII</i> SP. NOV., UN NOUVEAU MEMBRE DU COMPLEXE D'ESPÈCES <i>DIPHTHERIAE</i>	149
<i>Résumé</i>	149
<i>Contributions personnelles</i>	149
<i>Article</i>	150
PARTIE III : APPLICATIONS DE LA TAXONOMIE GÉNOMIQUE ET DE LA RÉSISTANCE AUX ANTIBIOTIQUES A DES ÉTUDES DE CAS.....	156
CHAPITRE 6 : ÉPIDÉMIE DE DIPHTÉRIE AU YEMEN.....	157
<i>Résumé</i>	157
<i>Contributions personnelles</i>	158
<i>Article</i>	159
CHAPITRE 7 : ÉTUDE DU SL453 DE <i>C. DIPHTHERIAE</i>	170
<i>Résumé</i>	170
<i>Contributions personnelles</i>	170
<i>Article</i>	171
CHAPITRE 8 : ÉPIDÉMILOGIE GÉNOMIQUE DE <i>C. DIPHTHERIAE</i> EN NOUVELLE-CALEDONIE	195
<i>Résumé</i>	195
<i>Contributions personnelles</i>	195
<i>Article</i>	196
CHAPITRE 9 : SÉRIE DE CAS D'INFECTIONS DUES À DES MEMBRES <i>DU COMPLEXE DIPHTHERIAE</i> CHEZ DES ANIMAUX DE COMPAGNIE EN FRANCE	220
<i>Résumé</i>	220
<i>Contributions personnelles</i>	220
<i>Article</i>	221
DISCUSSION GÉNÉRALE ET PERSPECTIVES.....	247
BIBLIOGRAPHIE	253
TABLE DES FIGURES.....	266
TABLE DES TABLEAUX	267

INTRODUCTION

Les maladies infectieuses et leur impact significatif sur la santé publique font partie des principales préoccupations mondiales. Les agents pathogènes sont très variés et incluent les bactéries, les virus, les parasites (eucaryotes unicellulaires ou pluricellulaires), les prions et les champignons. Alors que la seconde moitié du 20^{ème} siècle avait connu une période triomphaliste où l'élimination des maladies infectieuses était une perspective considérée comme atteignable, certains de ces pathogènes (en particulier les bactéries) sont maintenant de plus en plus redoutés en raison de leur résistance aux antimicrobiens (RAM). Ce phénomène est l'une des plus grandes menaces sur la santé globale identifiées par l'Organisation Mondiale de la Santé (OMS, [1, 2]). En 2019, *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* et *Klebsiella pneumoniae* étaient les trois premiers agents pathogènes responsables des décès associés à la RAM [3] et ces bactéries ont été identifiées comme pathogènes prioritaires par l'OMS [4]. Elles sont toutes impliquées dans les infections nosocomiales, même si deux d'entre elles (*E. coli* et *S. aureus*) sont également responsables d'intoxications alimentaires. D'autres pathogènes bactériens sont moins concernés par la RAM, tels que *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* (responsable de la diphtérie) ou *Bordetella pertussis* (agent de la coqueluche), car ils sont largement contrôlés par les vaccins. Néanmoins, lorsque la couverture vaccinale est insuffisante, ces agents pathogènes peuvent émerger à nouveau. Par exemple, en 2017, l'agence nationale Santé publique France (SpF) a lancé une alerte concernant la réapparition de la diphtérie dans le département de Mayotte en raison de la défaillance des services de la protection maternelle et infantile [5]. Par ailleurs, la baisse de la couverture vaccinale est devenue un phénomène mondial en raison de la pandémie de COVID-19 [6]. À terme, la diminution de l'immunité vaccinale combinée à l'augmentation de la RAM chez les bactéries pourraient représenter une perspective réellement menaçante pour la santé globale.

Parmi les moyens de contrôle des maladies infectieuses, leur détection rapide est un enjeu primordial pour freiner la propagation des infections et empêcher les phénomènes épidémiques. En conséquence, les systèmes de surveillance de l'émergence des maladies infectieuses doivent être significativement améliorés, comme l'a montré si nettement la pandémie de COVID-19. Un autre outil de surveillance est le séquençage du génome des souches. Sa mise en œuvre a révolutionné l'identification bactérienne grâce à son haut pouvoir discriminant, qui permet la distinction des agents pathogènes à l'échelle des souches, bien au-delà des méthodes traditionnelles d'identification et même de typage. Le séquençage génomique permet la détection des variants et de leurs caractéristiques importantes comme la virulence, la RAM, l'échappement partiel aux vaccins, ou leur transmissibilité accrue. Cependant, pour conduire la surveillance des souches bactériennes à l'échelle mondiale, de leur émergence jusqu'à leur propagation (entre environnement, alimentation, animaux et humains), des stratégies de nomenclatures universelles de souches sont nécessaires.

Un des apports principaux de cette thèse est la mise en place d'un système innovant de nomenclatures génomiques des souches. Cette nouvelle approche a été appliquée à un groupe de bactéries pathogènes, le complexe d'espèces *K. pneumoniae*. Il a été pour cela conceptualisé,

implémenté et appliqué à un jeu de données génomiques massif, une nouvelle approche de taxonomie (classification) et de nomenclature des souches bactériennes afin de répondre à un problème critique, qui est celui de la stabilité de la taxonomie.

K. pneumoniae représente un excellent modèle pour explorer de nouvelles approches taxonomiques des souches, en raison de sa diversité génétique et écologique, et de sa capacité à infecter les humains comme les animaux et à coloniser divers environnements. De plus, le problème majeur de sa résistance aux antibiotiques rend urgent le développement de méthodes efficaces permettant le suivi de la dissémination des souches multirésistantes.

Un second pathogène bactérien, *C. diphtheriae*, a également été étudié dans le cadre de cette thèse pour mettre en lumière les mécanismes de résistance aux antibiotiques prévalents à l'échelle populationnelle. En complément, une méthode de nomenclature des souches du complexe d'espèce *diphtheriae* a été implémentée.

La suite de cette introduction comporte deux parties. La première partie résume les caractéristiques fondamentales pour chacun des deux pathogènes modèles *K. pneumoniae* et *C. diphtheriae*, depuis leur découverte jusqu'à leurs propriétés de résistance aux antibiotiques. La seconde partie présente un état de l'art des concepts et approches de taxonomie génomique des souches bactériennes.

1. Introduction sur les pathogènes d'intérêt et leur résistance aux antibiotiques

1.1. *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*

1.1.1. La diphtérie

La diphtérie, du grec « diphthera » (qui signifie « peau, cuir, membrane », décrivant la formation d'une pseudomembrane observée chez les patients), est une maladie infectieuse causée par l'espèce bactérienne *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*. Certaines souches de cette espèce bactérienne sont capables de produire la toxine diphtérique, principale responsable des formes graves de la maladie. La toxine diphtérique peut également être présente dans d'autres espèces du genre *Corynebacterium*, regroupées phylogénétiquement en un ensemble appelé *Corynebactéries* du complexe *diphtheriae* (Cdc), comprenant : *C. diphtheriae*, *C. belfantii*, *C. rouxii*, *C. ulcerans*, *C. silvaticum* et *C. pseudotuberculosis* [7–10]. Les souches toxigènes du Cdc appartiennent très principalement à deux espèces : *C. diphtheriae* et *C. ulcerans*.

La diphtérie : son histoire et ses épidémies

L'agent pathogène de la diphtérie, *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*, a été décrit pour la première fois par Edwin Klebs en 1883 et isolé par Friedrich Löffler en 1884. En 1888, Émile Roux et Alexandre Yersin observent qu'un poison produit par les bactéries provoque les symptômes de la maladie. C'est ainsi que la première toxine (diphtérique) est découverte, conférant un rôle important à la diphtérie dans l'histoire de la microbiologie médicale.

En 1890, Emil von Behring et Shibasaburo Kitasato démontrent l'existence d'une substance (antitoxine), produite chez certains animaux, qui neutralise la toxine. C'est ainsi que le sérum antitoxique est découvert. Des essais cliniques (assez limités à l'époque) sont alors menés afin de démontrer l'efficacité chez l'homme d'un traitement de la diphtérie par le sérum antitoxique. Dès 1891, Émile Roux et ses collaborateurs commencent à le mettre au point en France. Ce premier sérum sera testé en 1894 à l'hôpital des Enfants malades (Paris).

En 1913, Emil Von Behring propose un vaccin contre la diphtérie basé sur un mélange de toxine et d'antitoxine. Cependant, il ne s'avère efficace qu'en laboratoire. Toutefois, un vaccin à partir de la toxine diphtérique inactivée par du formol (un dérivé inoffensif qui conserve son pouvoir vaccinal) est mis au point en 1923 par Gaston Ramon. Ainsi, le vaccin par l'anatoxine diphtérique est né.

En France, la vaccination devient obligatoire en 1931 durant le service militaire, puis est étendue à toute la population en 1938. Des campagnes massives ont été organisées en 1942 et appliquées principalement en zone occupée ; la vaccination diphtérique fut également obligatoire en Allemagne en 1941.

Après la mise en œuvre, en 1974, du programme élargi de vaccination (PEV) de l'Organisation Mondiale de la Santé (OMS), l'incidence mondiale de la diphtérie a considérablement diminué grâce à la bonne couverture vaccinale atteinte. Seules des épidémies relativement réduites et locales ont persisté, par exemple en Jordanie, en Suède et en Thaïlande.

Cette situation favorable a toutefois brusquement changé avec l'effondrement de l'ancienne Union des Républiques Socialistes Soviétiques (URSS), lorsqu'une épidémie à grande échelle s'est produite entre 1990 et 1998, entraînant une pandémie de diphtérie causant plus de 157 000 cas signalés et plus de 5000 décès. Cette épidémie a pris fin grâce à une campagne de vaccination de masse, en particulier des adultes. Cet événement a montré de manière impressionnante que la diphtérie est toujours un danger pour la santé publique, et a stimulé en France (ainsi qu'ailleurs) la création d'un Centre National de Référence (CNR) pour renforcer sa surveillance.

Depuis, quelques épidémies de diphtérie respiratoire ont été signalées dans plusieurs pays, dont le Nigeria en 2011 [11] et l'Inde entre 2011 et 2016 [12, 13]. Entre 2015 et 2019, des épidémies de diphtérie se sont aussi produites au Bangladesh [14, 15] en Haïti, en Afrique du Sud [16] et au Venezuela [17]. La dernière grande épidémie a actuellement lieu au Yémen [18, 19] en raison d'une crise socio-économique et d'une guerre ayant entraîné un accès limité aux soins de santé et à la vaccination.

Symptômes, transmission et écologie de la diphtérie

La forme classique est la diphtérie respiratoire, qui se caractérise dans un premier temps par une légère fièvre et une pharyngite. Au cours de l'infection, une pseudo-membrane blanc-grisâtre peut se former sur les amygdales, le pharynx ou le larynx, entraînant une toux. Selon l'ampleur, les voies respiratoires peuvent s'obstruer, provoquant la suffocation, voire la mort par asphyxie. La diphtérie respiratoire est très contagieuse et se transmet généralement par les gouttelettes respiratoires produites par une personne infectée. La période d'incubation est habituellement de deux à cinq jours, et les patients atteints demeurent infectieux pendant deux à trois semaines. Par ailleurs, les personnes asymptomatiques peuvent également contribuer à la propagation de la maladie. Dans le cas de sécrétion de la toxine diphtérique, des complications peuvent être observées au niveau du cœur et du système nerveux. Au début du 20^{ème} siècle, le taux de décès était de 10 à 25% des cas, et touchait surtout les enfants.

Une autre forme est la diphtérie cutanée, plus fréquente dans les pays endémiques. La pauvreté, le manque d'hygiène et les plaies fréquentes et lentes à cicatriser favorisent les infections. La transmission se fait par le contact de plaies infectées. La diphtérie cutanée est souvent localisée dans la partie inférieure des jambes, aux pieds ou aux mains. Les plaies peuvent se transformer rapidement en ulcères qui ne cicatrisent pas. Toutefois, la diphtérie cutanée n'est généralement pas fatale.

C. diphtheriae est un pathogène qui se transmet uniquement entre humains. Quelques rares cas ont été décrits chez des animaux comme le chien, le chat et le cheval [20, 21], mais ces exceptions pourraient être des cas de zoonose inverse plutôt que la traduction de l'existence d'un réservoir non-humain.

Vaccination et traitements

Le vaccin est la résultante de la purification de la toxine diphtérique et de son inactivation par réticulation au formaldéhyde. Ce procédé convertit la toxine potentiellement mortelle en un

agrégat de protéines totalement inoffensif, qui est toujours immunogène et induit la production d'anticorps chez la personne vaccinée. En France, la vaccination est obligatoire pour tous les nourrissons, mais également pour les professionnels de santé. Selon le schéma actuel (en France, depuis 2014), la primo-vaccination des nourrissons est composée de deux injections à deux mois d'intervalle, aux âges de 2 et 4 mois, suivies d'un rappel à l'âge de 11 mois. Chez les enfants, les rappels sont recommandés à 6 ans, puis entre 11 et 13 ans. Ensuite, chez l'adulte, les rappels sont recommandés aux âges de 25 ans, 45 ans et 65 ans, puis tous les 10 ans. Le vaccin anatoxine protège contre l'action de la toxine de la réponse immunitaire, mais il ne prévient pas l'infection ou la colonisation. Par conséquent, le vaccin n'empêche pas le portage asymptomatique et donc la transmission de la diphtérie entre les hôtes.

La prise en charge thérapeutique de la diphtérie s'effectue suivant deux axes principaux : la sérothérapie et l'antibiothérapie. Le sérum antidiphtérique est administré dans le cas de symptômes toxiques observés ou suspectés, uniquement en cas de diphtérie toxine positive, c'est-à-dire lors d'une infection avec une souche porteuse du gène codant la toxine diphtérique. Ce sérum contient des anticorps obtenus à partir du sérum de chevaux immunisés contre la toxine diphtérique. Par conséquent, cela neutralise la toxine diphtérique circulante et réduit la progression de la maladie. Néanmoins, le traitement doit être effectué très tôt pour être efficace, et doit être évité s'il n'est pas absolument nécessaire, à cause d'importants effets secondaires indésirables (anaphylaxie).

Par ailleurs, les infections diphtériques sont traitées par les antibiotiques, la pénicilline ou l'amoxicilline étant ceux de première intention. Pour les patients allergiques à la pénicilline, les macrolides comme l'érythromycine sont une bonne alternative. Le traitement par antibiotiques est généralement efficace, bien que des souches résistantes aient été signalées. Toutefois, l'importance de la résistance aux antibiotiques, sa distribution géographique et les mécanismes de résistance prévalents sont mal définis chez *C. diphtheriae*.

1.1.2. Caractérisation génomique

Le premier séquençage complet du génome de *C. diphtheriae* a été effectué en 2003 [22]. La souche bactérienne considérée, NCTC 13129, est désormais utilisée comme référence pour les analyses génomiques. Cette souche a été isolée en 1997 dans la membrane pharyngée d'une femme de 72 ans atteinte de diphtérie clinique qui était revenue au Royaume-Uni après une croisière en Baltique ; il s'agit d'une souche associée à l'épidémie survenue en ex-URSS. Les caractéristiques générales du génome de *C. diphtheriae* sont présentées dans le Tableau 1.

Tableau 1. Caractéristiques générales du génome de *C. diphtheriae* NCTC 13129.

Taille en paire de bases (pb)	2 488 635
Contenu Guanine + Cytosine (%)	53,48
CDS (coding sequence)	2 320
dont pseudogènes	45
Densité de codage (%)	87,9
Longueur moyenne des gènes (pb)	962
ARN ribosomiques	5× (16S-23S-5S)
ARN de transfert	54

La séquence génomique de la souche type de *C. diphtheriae* NCTC 11397^T (= ATCC 27010^T = DSM 44123^T = CIP 100721^T), soit la souche servant à décrire l'espèce bactérienne, est disponible depuis 2015. Par ailleurs, au sein de la base de données publique *NCBI* (National Center for Biotechnology Information, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/data-hub/genome/>), un ensemble de 668 génomes a été trouvé en requête le 16 septembre 2022 (termes de recherche : « *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* »). Le séquençage génomique peut permettre d'établir des liens entre les caractéristiques microbiennes et les éléments génomiques, tels que des clusters de gènes ou des mutations ; certains de ces liens feront l'objet d'une étude dédiée (cf. Partie I).

1.1.3. Microbiologie classique revisitée par la génomique

C. diphtheriae est un bacille Gram positif non mobile, non encapsulé, en forme de massue. *C. diphtheriae* présente différents biovars, définis comme des sous-groupes qui diffèrent légèrement par leur morphologie coloniale et leurs propriétés biochimiques. Les biovars ont été suspectés de causer des maladies plus ou moins sévères. Le biovar Gravis a ainsi été nommé pour refléter un caractère supposément plus pathogène [23]. Toutefois, il n'existe pas de données récentes supportant ou infirmant des différences systématiques de virulence entre biovars.

Biovar

Les quatre biovars décrits chez *C. diphtheriae* sont Gravis, Mitis, Belfanti et Intermedius [21–23], bien que ce dernier ne soit presque jamais rapporté dans la littérature récente. La distinction entre biovars est basée sur la morphologie des colonies et certaines caractéristiques biochimiques (Tableau 2), notamment la réduction des nitrates, l'utilisation de l'amidon ou du glycogène, et la fermentation des sucres [27].

Tableau 2. Propriétés phénotypiques des biovars de *C. diphtheriae* (extrait et traduit du livre « *Corynebacterium diphtheriae and Related Toxigenic Species* » [7]).

	Tests phénotypiques conventionnels											
	Hémolyse	ADNase	Cystinase (H ₂ S) ^p	Pyrazina- midase	Réduction des nitrates	Hydrolyse de l'urée	Glucose	Maltose	Sucrose	Glycogène	Amidon	Réaction CAMP
<i>C. diphtheriae</i>												
Biovar Gravis	-	+	+	-	+	-	+	+	-/+	+	+	-
Biovar Mitis	+/-	+	+	-	+	-	+	+	-/+	-	-	-
Biovar Intermedius	-	+	+	-	+	-	+	+	-/+	-	-	-
Biovar Belfanti	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	+	-/+	-	-	-

La structure de la population des souches de *C. diphtheriae* a été étudiée afin d'expliquer d'éventuelles relations phylogénétiques entre les trois principaux biovars (Mitis, Gravis et Belfanti). Ces différents travaux [28–31] ont suggéré qu'il n'existe aucun lien entre les biovars et la structure phylogénétique de *C. diphtheriae*. Cependant, les analyses phylogénétiques présentées dans cette thèse (cf. Chapitre 1) révèlent que Gravis et Mitis, les deux principaux biovars de *C. diphtheriae*, sont clairement séparés en deux lignées phylogénétiques distinctes. Quelques études [29, 32, 33] ont également été conduites afin d'identifier des marqueurs moléculaires potentiels sous-tendant les différences biochimiques entre les biovars.

Les biovars Mitis et Gravis se distinguent par leur capacité à utiliser le glycogène (positif chez Gravis, négatif chez Mitis ; Tableau 2). Santos *et al.* [32] ont proposé que les souches du biovar

Gravis fermentent le glycogène grâce à la présence d'un orthologue du gène *spuA*, codant une alpha-1,6-glycosidase. Cette enzyme hydrolyse le glycogène ou l'amidon en dehors de la cellule, permettant à des oligomères plus petits d'être transportés dans la cellule bactérienne, expliquant la capacité de fermenter le glycogène. L'association entre *spuA* et biovar Gravis est revisitée dans le Chapitre 1.

Les souches du biovar Belfanti se caractérisent par leur incapacité à réduire les nitrates. Chez l'espèce *C. glutamicum*, l'activité nitrate réductase implique le groupe de gènes *narIJHGK* [30, 32]. Les analyses génomiques de Santos *et al.* [32] révèlent que le cluster *narIJHGK* (DIP0497-DIP0502) est présent chez tous les biovars de *C. diphtheriae*. Néanmoins, le phénotype nitrate-négatif des souches biovar Belfanti semble être expliqué par un état non-fonctionnel du cluster *narIJHGK*, causé par exemple par l'absence du gène *narG* [32] ou par la présence d'une mutation dans *narJ* [29]. Dans le Chapitre 1, il est montré que la présence d'un codon-stop au sein de *narG* semble expliquer l'absence de réduction des nitrates au sein du biovar Belfanti. Un autre gène, codant pour l'enzyme de biosynthèse de la molybdoptérine *MoaB*, et qui est un cofacteur de l'activité de la nitrate réductase, pourrait aussi être impliqué dans l'évolution vers le biovar Belfanti lors d'un décalage du cadre de lecture [32].

Facteurs de virulence

Le principal facteur de virulence des souches de *C. diphtheriae* est la toxine diphtérique. Cependant, les souches exemptées de toxine diphtérique peuvent également provoquer des infections graves chez les animaux et les humains, indiquant la présence de facteurs de virulence supplémentaires.

Toxine diphtérique (DT). DT est un polypeptide de 535 acides aminés et d'un poids moléculaire d'environ de 62 kDa. Cette toxine est codée par un cadre de lecture unique et composée de deux fragments (A et B) qui restent liés par deux liaisons disulfure [35]. Les deux fragments sont fonctionnellement différents. Le fragment A (situé à l'extrémité N-terminale) comprend un domaine catalytique (domaine C) qui porte la toxicité intracellulaire. Le fragment B (situé à l'extrémité C-terminale) est constitué de deux domaines, un domaine transmembranaire (domaine T) et un domaine de liaison au récepteur (domaine R).

Lors de l'intoxication d'une cellule, la DT se lie à son récepteur à la surface de la cellule par le récepteur '*heparin-binding epidermal growth factor*' (HB-EGF). Le domaine R reconnaît le récepteur HB-EGF sur les cellules épithéliales humaines, conduisant à l'endocytose de l'ensemble du complexe récepteur-toxine. Ensuite, le domaine T participe à la translocation du domaine C de l'endosome au cytosol. Dans le cytosol, le domaine C se lie d'abord au nicotinamide dinucléotide (NAD), puis transfère une fraction ADP-ribose au facteur d'élongation 2 (EF-2), ce qui l'inactive et inhibe la synthèse des protéines (Figure 1).

La régulation de l'expression de la DT est assurée par un répresseur activé par le fer, *dtxR*, qui est un gène présent chez toutes les souches de *C. diphtheriae*. En cas de dépassement d'une

faible concentration intracellulaire de fer, le régulateur DtxR est inhibé, ce qui entraîne une augmentation de la production de DT par les souches de *C. diphtheriae*.

Figure 1. Mécanisme d'action de la toxine diphtérique (figure extraite de la revue « Diphtheria » de Sharma et al. [36]).

La toxine diphtérique est codée par le gène *tox*, qui est porté par un ou plusieurs prophages (appelés corynebactériophages) intégrés dans le chromosome. Dans les souches *tox*-positives, le prophage semble toujours intégré à la même position (gène ARNt-Arg). La souche vaccinale PW8 comporte deux prophages en tandem, ce qui expliquerait l'expression plus importante de la toxine chez cette souche. Il existe une diversité génétique des prophages mais celle-ci est mal connue [37].

La présence du gène de la toxine diphtérique (gène *tox*) est déterminée dans les laboratoires de diagnostic (ainsi qu'au CNR dans l'unité BEBP de l'Institut Pasteur) par un test PCR *tox*. Cette procédure permet la séparation des souches *tox* + et *tox* - en fonction de la présence ou de l'absence du gène *tox*. De plus, sa production est évaluée phénotypiquement par le test d'Elek, qui permet de distinguer les souches porteuses du gène *tox* mais non-productrices de la toxine (dites NTTB, pour non-toxicogenic *tox*-bearing) [38].

La détection du gène *tox* peut aussi s'effectuer directement sur un génome assemblé. Par ailleurs, l'état NTTB peut être aussi déduit par analyse génomique, par exemple lorsque les souches NTTB sont déterminées par un décalage du cadre de lecture causé par une mutation dans la séquence nucléotidique du gène *tox*. Cette capacité à prédire le statut toxigène à partir des séquences génomiques est abordée dans le Chapitre 2.

De même que pour les biovars, la distribution phylogénétique du gène *tox* au sein des populations de *C. diphtheriae* doit être précisément décrite afin d'en comprendre la dynamique évolutive. Cependant, peu d'études ont abordé cette question [28, 30]. Dans le Chapitre 1, il est montré que les souches *tox*-positives appartiennent majoritairement à la lignée Mitis, et aux branches à divergence précoce de la lignée Gravis.

Les facteurs d'adhésion aux surfaces

L'adhésion à la cellule hôte était principalement considérée comme l'étape initiale de l'interaction hôte-pathogène. L'adhésion de *C. diphtheriae* est un processus multifactoriel [39]. *C. diphtheriae* est capable de se lier à différents types de cellules épithéliales d'une manière spécifique à la souche. Plusieurs protéines impliquées dans ce processus ont été identifiées, soulignant la complexité de cet événement. Néanmoins, la délétion ou la perturbation de l'une de ces protéines n'entraîne pas une perte complète de la capacité d'adhésion, indiquant qu'une combinaison de protéines peut être cruciale pour cet événement. La Figure 3 illustre les protéines impliquées dans l'adhésion et qui sont présentées brièvement dans cette section.

Figure 2. Adhésion de *C. diphtheriae* : un processus multifactoriel (figure extraite de la revue « Adhesion properties of toxigenic corynebacteria » de Lisa Ott, 2018 [39]).

Pili. L'adhésion chez *C. diphtheriae* est médiée principalement par les pili (ou fimbriae) qui sont attachés de manière covalente à la paroi cellulaire bactérienne. L'analyse génomique de Ton-That et Schneewind [40] a révélé la présence de trois groupes de gènes chromosomiques, contenant neuf gènes de protéines de pilus (*spaA-I*), ainsi que cinq gènes de sortase (*srtA-E*) (Figure 2). Un sixième gène de sortase (*srtF*) a également été identifié dans une autre région du chromosome.

Le premier groupe de gènes de fimbriae caractérisé chez *C. diphtheriae* (*spaA-srtA-spaB-spaC*) code pour les pili de type SpaA [40]. Ce pilus est assemblé par la réticulation covalente de la piline majeure SpaA formant la tige. SpaA semble être la sous-unité de piline la plus abondante et est répartie uniformément le long de la tige du pilus ; cependant elle se produit à intervalles et avec moins d'abondance que SpaA. Contrairement à SpaA et SpaB, SpaC est positionné à la pointe du pilus [40, 41]. Les autres types de pili (SpaD et SpaH) ont été étudiés par Mandlik *et al.* [42]. Ces auteurs concluent que

les pili SpaA sont responsables de l'adhésion aux cellules épithéliales pharyngées, alors que SpaD et SpaH interagissent avec les cellules épithéliales laryngées et pulmonaires.

Figure 3. Les clusters de gènes de fimbriae de la souche NCTC 13129

DIP0733 (67-72p). Le gène DIP0733 code pour une protéine connue sous le nom de protéine non-fimbriale 67-72p, nommée ainsi car présentant deux chaînes polypeptidiques principales avec des masses moléculaires de 67 et 72 kDa qui ont été détectées par SDS-PAGE (électrophorèse en gel de polyacrylamide contenant du dodécylsulfate de sodium ; [43]). Cette protéine non-fimbriale est exposée en surface et est caractérisée comme une adhésine impliquée dans l'interaction des souches de *C. diphtheriae* avec les érythrocytes humains [43] et les cellules épithéliales humaines HEp-2 [44]. L'étude de Sabbadini *et al.* [45] a permis de conclure que la séquence de la protéine 67-72p est codée par un seul gène, DIP0733. En plus des différentes propriétés attribuées à cette protéine (à savoir l'hémagglutination, la liaison aux récepteurs de la cellule hôte et l'induction de l'apoptose), l'interaction entre souches de type 67-72p sauvage et mutante a été étudiée sur le modèle *Caenorhabditis elegans*. Il a été montré que DIP0733 est également impliqué dans des interactions avec les composants de la matrice extracellulaire, telles que le collagène et la fibronectine. En résumé, ces différents travaux soutiennent l'idée que DIP0733 est un facteur de virulence multifonctionnel de *C. diphtheriae* [46].

DIP1281. La protéine codée par le gène DIP1281 est impliquée dans l'organisation de la surface cellulaire, l'adhésion et l'internalisation dans les cellules épithéliales [47]. Cette protéine a été identifiée lors d'une analyse complète des protéines sécrétées par *C. diphtheriae* [48]. La protéine DIP1281, associée à la surface, est homologue à CE1659 chez *C. efficiens*, qui est annotée comme membre de la famille NlpC/P60 et prédite comme associée à l'invasion [47, 48]. Ott *et al.* [47] ont étudié la fonction de la protéine DIP1281. Ils concluent qu'elle est principalement impliquée dans l'organisation de la couche protéique de la surface externe de *C. diphtheriae* plutôt que dans la séparation de la paroi cellulaire et du peptidoglycane des bactéries en division. De plus, les résultats obtenus dans cette étude suggèrent que la protéine DIP1281 est cruciale pour la localisation et la fonction des facteurs d'adhésion et d'invasion.

DIP1621. Hansmeier *et al.* ont prédit la fonction de DIP1621 comme une hydrolase associée à l'invasion, homologue à CG2401 chez *C. glutamicum* [48]. Cette protéine appartient également à la famille des protéines NlpC/P60 et a été étudiée par Kolodkina *et al.* [49]. Les résultats montrent que la perturbation du gène DIP1621 chez *C. diphtheriae* entraîne une diminution de l'adhérence aux cellules épithéliales.

DIP2093. La protéine codée par le gène DIP2093 fonctionne comme un composant de surface reconnaissant les molécules de la matrice adhésive (MSCRAMM) et peut être incluse parmi les facteurs qui contribuent à la pathogénicité de *C. diphtheriae* [50].

DIP0543. Le séquence DIP0543 code pour la protéine NanH, qui est une protéine extracellulaire associée à la surface cellulaire. Il a été montré que le gène de sialidase putatif, *nanH*, a une activité sialidase [51].

DIP1546. Ott *et al.* [52] ont montré que la protéine DIP1546 agit comme facteur de colonisation dans un système modèle *Caenorhabditis elegans*.

Le Tableau 3 résume les déterminants connus qui contribuent à l'adhésion de *C. diphtheriae*. Comme la détermination de ces facteurs de virulence (et d'autres putatifs non-introduits ici) dans les génomes de *C. diphtheriae*, représente une source d'information précieuse dans le suivi épidémiologique de ces souches, ils ont été intégrés dans un outil bioinformatique, DIPHTOSCAN, développé pour extraire des éléments génétiques d'intérêt dans les séquences génomiques. Ce développement logiciel facilite les études visant à comprendre la dynamique et la structure de populations de ces différents éléments génomiques (cf. Chapitre 2).

Tableau 3. Résumé des facteurs expérimentalement vérifiés impliqués dans le processus d'adhésion de C. diphtheriae.

Nom	Fonction	Référence
Pili		
Type SpaA	adhérence aux cellules D562	[40, 53, 42, 41, 54]
Type SpaD	adhérence aux cellules HEp-2 et D562	[55, 42, 54]
Type SpaH	adhérence aux cellules HEp-2 et D562	[56, 42, 54]
DIP0733 (67-72p)	hémagglutination adhérence aux cellules HEp-2 et aux cellules HeLa liaison au collagène et au fibrinogène colonisation de <i>C. elegans</i>	[43–46]
DIP1281	adhérence aux cellules D562	[48, 47]
DIP1621	adhérence aux cellules HEp-2	[48, 49]
DIP0543 (NanH)	activité sialidase	[51]
DIP1546	colonisation de <i>C. elegans</i> adhérence aux cellules D562	[52]
DIP2093	liaison au collagène de type I adhérence aux cellules HeLa	[50]

1.1.4. Résistance aux antibiotiques

C. diphtheriae est généralement sensible aux antibiotiques, bien que certaines souches résistantes aient été décrites [57–67]. La pénicilline est la molécule de première intention pour traiter la diphtérie dans de nombreux pays, mais l’amoxicilline, plus efficace, est utilisée en France en première intention. L’érythromycine est recommandée en cas d’allergie aux bêta-lactamines [68]. Ces deux classes antimicrobiennes sont généralement efficaces pour le traitement de la diphtérie [57, 58].

Des gènes de résistance aux antimicrobiens ont été décrits chez *C. diphtheriae* [69, 70]. Cependant, la prévalence et la distribution phylogénétique de ces gènes dans les isolats de *C. diphtheriae* étant mal connues, le Chapitre 1 de cette thèse aborde cette question.

Pénicilline

Les pénicillines constituent une sous-classe des antibiotiques appelés bêta-lactamines. Elles agissent sur la synthèse du peptidoglycane de la paroi cellulaire en inhibant les protéines liant la pénicilline (*penicillin binding protein*, PBP, ou PLP en français, pour protéine liant la pénicilline). Les PBP ont une activité transpeptidase, carboxypeptidase et transglycosylase. L’inhibition des PBP aboutit à l’inhibition de la formation des ponts pentamériques responsables de la structure réticulée de la paroi, et aboutit donc à la lyse bactérienne.

Sept protéines chromosomiques de liaison à la pénicilline (PBP) ont été décrites chez *C. diphtheriae* (48, Figure 4) mais, jusqu’à présent, aucune association entre un gène *pbp* (ou une autre variation génétique) et une résistance à la pénicilline n’a été décrite. Cependant, les analyses génomiques présentées dans cette thèse (cf. Chapitre 1) révèlent qu’une protéine (PBP2m, nommée ainsi lors de l’étude) liant la pénicilline, faisant partie du génome accessoire, et située dans divers contextes génomiques, explique la résistance à la pénicilline dans certains cas. Le gène *pbp2m* est présent chez d’autres espèces du genre *Corynebacterium*, et son expression chez *C. glutamicum* a pour effet d’augmenter la concentration minimale inhibitrice de plusieurs bêta-lactamines (cf. Chapitre 1).

Figure 4. Répartition des gènes *pbp* sur le génome de la souche NCTC13129.

Erythromycine

Le traitement par l'érythromycine est recommandé en cas d'allergie à la pénicilline. L'érythromycine est un antibiotique de la famille des macrolides. Il agit en inhibant la synthèse des protéines bactériennes en se liant à la sous-unité 50S du ribosome des micro-organismes sensibles, et en empêchant la translocation peptidique [71].

La résistance à l'érythromycine peut être expliquée par le gène *ermX* initialement décrit sur le plasmide pNG2 [69]. *ermX* code pour une méthyltransférase d'ARNr 23S qui inactive le site de liaison des macrolides (<https://card.mcmaster.ca/ontology/36735>). Un autre gène, *ermC*, a également été détecté dans une souche (cf. Chapitre 2), qui est également une méthyltransférase d'ARNr 23S. Cependant il est fréquemment retrouvé chez certaines espèces du genre *Staphylococcus* (<https://card.mcmaster.ca/ontology/36389>).

Triméthoprim, sulfaméthoxazole et co-trimoxazole

Le triméthoprim est un antibiotique de la famille des diaminopyrimidines, et est principalement utilisé en association avec le sulfaméthoxazole (famille des sulfamides). Cette association, le cotrimoxazole, agit en synergie pour bloquer les étapes séquentielles du métabolisme de l'acide folique bactérien :

- le triméthoprim inhibe la réduction du dihydrofolate en tétrahydrofolate ;
- le sulfaméthoxazole inhibe la conversion de l'acide p-aminobenzoïque en dihydroptéroate.

Cette synergie induit une activité antibactérienne optimale, souvent bactéricide.

Barraud *et al.* ont découvert un élément génétique bactérien qui semblerait être un intégron de classe 1 (Figure 5). Ces travaux ont montré qu'il hébergeait les gènes *dfrA16* (résistance au triméthoprim), *qacL* (ou *qacH*, conférant la résistance aux composés d'ammonium quaternaire), *qacEΔ1* (typiquement présent sur les intégrons de classe 1, tronqué mais dont la troncature ne l'empêche pas de conférer une résistance aux composés d'ammonium quaternaire), et *sul1* (résistance au sulfaméthoxazole), mais qu'il n'est pas associé à un motif attC.

Figure 5. Carte physique de l'intégron de classe 1 de *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* FRC24 (inspirée de l'article de Barraud *et al.* [70]).

Une étude récente (développement de l'outil IntegronFinder v2) a toutefois remis en question la présence d'intégrons fonctionnels chez les Actinobactéries [72]. Par un communiqué personnel avec deux des auteurs (Eloi Littner et Eduardo Rocha), cette question souhaitait être éclairée. L'utilisation d'IntegronFinder 2.0 a montré que l'élément génétique décrit par Barraud *et al.* [70] correspond bien à l'ensemble des caractéristiques d'un intégron complet. La séquence de *intI1* est décrite, dans l'article de référence, comme ayant été interrompue par une IS6100. Toutefois, l'intégrase a bien été reconnue en tant que telle par le modèle

d'IntegronFinder 2 (elle n'est logiquement pas reconnue lors de l'insertion d'une séquence d'insertion (IS). Cela peut s'expliquer si l'interruption par l'IS est suffisamment en aval, voire en dehors du gène de l'intégrase. En conclusion, rien ne semble prouver que *intI1* n'est pas fonctionnelle, et donc que les cassettes *dfrA16* et *qacL* puissent être mobilisées.

Multirésistance

Une sensibilité réduite ou une résistance totale de *C. diphtheriae* à la pénicilline, à l'érythromycine et à d'autres agents antimicrobiens (parfois combinés dans des souches multirésistantes) a été signalée dans plusieurs régions du monde. Les souches de *C. diphtheriae* multirésistantes n'ont été reconnues que très rarement dans la littérature internationale récente [57]. Les phénotypes de résistance les plus multiples ont été observés parmi les isolats de *C. diphtheriae* au Brésil où 95,7 % des souches étaient résistantes à plusieurs (entre quatre et sept) médicaments testés. Plus spécifiquement, 8,5 % de ces isolats présentaient une résistance multiple à sept médicaments : mupirocine, pénicilline et/ou ampicilline, oxacilline, ceftazidime, aztréonam, tétracycline et/ou lincomycine, clindamycine et érythromycine [59]. Une analyse de 130 souches de *C. diphtheriae* (toxigènes et non-toxigènes) isolées à Saint-Pétersbourg (Russie) ont révélé 2,3 % d'isolats résistants à huit médicaments : benzylpénicilline, ampicilline, oxacilline, chloramphénicol, érythromycine, lincomycine, triméthoprime et nitroxoline [73]. La première souche toxigène de *C. diphtheriae* multirésistante au Canada a été isolée d'un abcès cutané en 2011 ; cette souche était résistante à la clindamycine, à l'érythromycine, à la tétracycline et au triméthoprime-sulfaméthoxazole, et intermédiaire à la ceftriaxone et au céfotaxime [74]. Des souches multirésistantes ont également été identifiées au Vietnam [58] et en France [67].

Bien que plusieurs souches soient signalées comme multirésistantes, les mécanismes génétiques sous-jacents et leur distribution restent largement inconnus. Par ailleurs, les seuils critiques (en particulier pour la pénicilline) ne sont pas standardisés et ont évolué avec le temps, ce qui complique la représentation de l'image globale de la résistance chez *C. diphtheriae*. Dans le cadre de cette thèse (cf. Chapitre 1), un plasmide a été découvert dans une souche multirésistante aux antibiotiques. D'autre part, l'outil développé dans le Chapitre 2 contient plusieurs fonctionnalités permettant la détection et la caractérisation des souches (multi)résistantes par la détection des gènes de résistance et la détermination de leur contexte génomique.

1.1.5. Outil précurseur de DIPHTOSCAN

En raison de l'augmentation de cas et de la résistance aux antimicrobiens, de *C. diphtheriae* fait de plus en plus l'objet d'efforts de surveillance et d'études d'épidémiologie moléculaire. La résolution ultime du séquençage du génome entier permet l'accès à l'ensemble des marqueurs moléculaires cliniquement pertinentes, néanmoins l'extraction et l'interprétation des caractéristiques importantes sont difficiles. Afin de répondre à ce besoin, un outil a été développé, nommé DIPHTOSCAN, et fait l'objet du Chapitre 2.

Brièvement, l'outil DIPHTOSCAN est né à partir d'un outil nommé Kleborate [75]. Kleborate, un outil de génotypage conçu spécifiquement pour *Klebsiella pneumoniae* et le complexe d'espèces associé, détectant les principaux locus de virulence et de RAM, le MLST et les sérotypes d'antigènes directement à partir des assemblages de génomes. L'ensemble de ses spécificités sont présentés dans le Tableau 4.

Tableau 4. Caractéristiques du génome rapportées par Kleborate. (extrait de « A genomic surveillance framework and genotyping tool for *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and its related species complex » [75]).

Genome features reported by Kleborate.	
Feature	Description
Assembly quality	Contig count, N50, largest contig, ambiguous bases
Identification	Species ¹⁶ , multi-locus sequence typing (MLST) ^{29,85} (if <i>K. pneumoniae</i> species complex)
Acquired virulence determinants	Presence, genotypes, associated mobile genetic elements (MGEs), truncations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • yersiniabactin³⁴, • colibactin³⁴, • aerobactin³⁵, • salmochelin³⁵, • hypermucoidy loci <i>rmpADC</i> and <i>rmpA2</i>
Virulence score	0 = no yersiniabactin, colibactin or aerobactin; 1 = yersiniabactin only; 2 = yersiniabactin and colibactin (or colibactin only); 3 = aerobactin without yersiniabactin or colibactin; 4 = aerobactin with yersiniabactin (no colibactin); 5 = yersiniabactin, colibactin and aerobactin
Serotype prediction	<i>wzi</i> allele and associated K locus ⁷⁷ (default), Full K and O locus typing via <i>Kaptive</i> ³⁶ (optional)
AMR determinants (optional)	
Acquired genes	Total count, alleles grouped by drug class, truncations
Mutations in core genes	SHV beta-lactamase (extended-spectrum beta-lactamase/ESBL or inhibitors) ⁸⁶ , OmpK35/OmpK36 osmoporins ^{41,42} (carbapenems), MgrB/PmrB ⁵⁷⁻⁵⁹ (colistin), GyrA/ParC ⁷⁶ (fluoroquinolones)
Number of drug classes	Excludes penicillins since resistance is intrinsic
Resistance score	1 = ESBL; 2 = Carbapenemase; 3 = Carbapenemase plus colistin resistance; 0 otherwise

L'outil est disponible à l'adresse suivante : <https://github.com/katholt/Kleborate>. Quelques scripts sont utilisés et sont adaptés afin de développer l'outil DIPHTOSCAN, présenté en détails dans le Chapitre 2.

1.2. *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

L'espèce *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (Kp) a été décrite pour la première fois par Carl Friedlander en 1882. Il s'agissait d'un bacille Gram négatif capsulé, isolé dans les poumons d'un patient mort de pneumonie. En 1887, cette bactérie fut nommée « *Klebsiella pneumoniae* » par Vittore Trevisan, en hommage au microbiologiste allemand Edwin Klebs [76].

Kp est une bactérie pathogène opportuniste qui appartient à la famille *Enterobacteriaceae* et est l'un des agents pathogènes nosocomiaux les plus fréquents au niveau mondial [77]. Les infections causées par Kp sont devenues un problème majeur de santé publique, principalement en raison de l'augmentation des niveaux de résistance aux antimicrobiens (RAM) qui y sont associés, et de la perspective d'infections impossibles à traiter dans les années à venir [77]. En effet, Kp est l'une des espèces reconnues comme faisant partie du groupe ESKAPE (six agents pathogènes bactériens multirésistants de première importance : *Enterococcus faecium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, et plusieurs autres espèces du genre *Enterobacter*). Ces espèces bactériennes sont reconnues non seulement pour leur rôle majeur dans les infections nosocomiales, mais aussi

parce qu'elles représentent des paradigmes de la pathogénèse, de la transmission et de la RAM [77].

Dans une étude récente, les Kp multirésistantes se classaient au troisième rang parmi les six principaux agents pathogènes responsables d'environ 1,27 million de décès en 2019 attribuables à la RAM [3]. Les tendances à la hausse du nombre d'infections à Kp multirésistantes ont conduit à sa reconnaissance en tant que pathogène prioritaire critique par différentes agences internationales de santé publique, telle que l'OMS (<https://www.who.int/fr/news/item/27-02-2017-who-publishes-list-of-bacteria-for-which-new-antibiotics-are-urgently-needed>), dans le but de favoriser la recherche et le développement de nouvelles stratégies de traitement.

Au fil des années, deux principaux pathotypes de Kp ont été reconnus : Kp classique ou multirésistant (cKp ou mdrKp), et Kp hypervirulent (hvKp) [77–79] (bien que la plupart des infections liées à Kp sont actuellement associées aux souches cKp [80]). Les cKp sont à l'origine d'une série d'infections opportunistes, telles que l'infection des voies urinaires, la pneumonie et les infections des plaies ou des tissus mous qui surviennent majoritairement chez les nouveau-nés, les personnes âgées et les personnes immunodéprimées. Ces cKp sont souvent associées à la production de β -lactamases à spectre étendu (BLSE) et de carbapénémases (cf. section 1.2.2), causant de multiples épidémies nosocomiales dans le monde entier [77].

Figure 6. Facteurs de virulence caractérisés dans les souches classiques (cKp) et hypervirulentes (vKp) de *K. pneumoniae* (figure extraite de la review de Paczosa et Meccas [79]).

Les hvKp ont été détectées pour la première fois à Taïwan dans les années 1980, et sont à l'origine de maladies invasives communautaires telles que des abcès hépatiques ou des méningites [79]. Les cKp et les hvKp peuvent être distinguées par la présence de facteurs de virulence spécifiques (Figure 6) qui seront discutés plus en détail dans la section 1.2.3. Les souches hvKp constituent une menace sérieuse et un problème croissant en santé publique, notamment dans les pays asiatiques, car les alertes sur la convergence des phénotypes de multirésistance et d'hypervirulence sont de plus en plus nombreuses, ainsi que les rapports sur les souches toti-résistantes (pandrug-résistant, PDR) [77, 81, 82].

Ces préoccupations cliniques distinctes et croissantes ont suscité un regain d'intérêt pour la recherche sur Kp, notamment l'emploi des analyses génomiques. Ici, l'écologie, la RAM et la virulence de Kp sont introduites brièvement.

1.2.1. Caractérisation génomique

Le premier séquençage complet publiquement disponible (*NCBI*) du génome de Kp a été soumis en 2005 et publié en 2009 [83]. La souche bactérienne correspondante, NTUH-K2044, a été isolée chez un patient souffrant d'un abcès hépatique primaire (acquis en communauté) et d'une méningite métastatique. Toutefois, les auteurs relatent que la séquence du génome d'une autre souche, MGH78578, était déjà disponible. Les travaux relatifs à MGH78578 ont été publiés en 2005 [84] mais le génome n'a été publiquement disponible (*NCBI*) qu'en 2007. Cette souche a la caractéristique d'être multirésistante aux antibiotiques.

Les caractéristiques générales de ces deux génomes sont présentées dans le Tableau 5.

Tableau 5. Caractéristiques générales des génomes de K. pneumoniae.

Strains	NTUH-K2044	MGH 78578
Taille en paire de bases (pb)	5 472 672	5 694 894
Contenu Guanine + Cytosine (%)	57,37	57,15
CDS (coding sequence)	5 170	5 460
Pseudogènes	141	161
ARN ribosomiques	9, 8, 8 (5S, 16S, 23S)	9, 8, 8 (5S, 16S, 23S)
ARN de transfert	87	86

Par ailleurs, au sein de la base de données publique *NCBI* (National Center for Biotechnology Information, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/data-hub/genome/>), un ensemble de 47,359 génomes a été trouvé en requête le 28 février 2023 (termes de recherche : « *Klebsiella pneumoniae* »). Le séquençage génomique peut permettre d'établir des liens entre les caractéristiques microbiennes et les éléments génomiques, tels que des clusters de gènes ou des mutations ; certains de ces liens feront l'objet d'une étude dédiée (Partie I).

1.2.2. Écologie

Kp peut survivre dans une multitude de niches écologiques, à la fois libres et associées à l'hôte. Ces niches comprennent le sol, l'eau, une gamme d'espèces végétales, certains insectes, oiseaux et reptiles, et de nombreux mammifères chez lesquels cette bactérie peut être soit un organisme commensal, soit un agent pathogène potentiel [80]. Cependant, un déficit dans l'entreprise d'échantillonnage systématique à grande échelle a limité les connaissances sur la prévalence et les caractéristiques de Kp dans ces différentes niches. De plus, étant donnée la large distribution écologique de Kp chez les animaux et dans l'environnement [80], ainsi que sa capacité à contaminer les aliments [85], il devient important d'explorer la contribution possible de sources non-cliniques en tant que réservoirs de gènes RAM et dans la transmission de lignées importantes à l'homme. Inversement, la prévalence de la résistance dans les hôpitaux pourrait entraîner une contamination en milieu communautaire, chez les animaux, ou même dans l'environnement.

La plupart des études datant d'avant 2010 se sont appuyées sur des techniques d'identification standard (sans séquençage) et n'ont pas distingué Kp des autres membres du complexe *K. pneumoniae* (KpSC, qui comprend entre autres *K. variicola* et *K. quasipneumoniae*, discuté en détail dans la Partie 2).

Kp est une bactérie bien établie du microbiote intestinal humain, et plusieurs études ont montré que la plupart des infections à Kp sont causées par des souches endogènes qui ont colonisé l'hôte de manière asymptomatique. Cependant, le portage de Kp a été principalement analysé dans le contexte nosocomial et en se concentrant sur les souches RAM. La colonisation commensale de l'intestin et des voies respiratoires par Kp est courante, mais, malgré certains progrès [86], on connaît encore peu ses déterminants et sa dynamique [87]. La prévalence et la diversité des cKp ou hvKp reste également mal connues.

1.2.3. Résistance aux antibiotiques

Kp représente aujourd'hui l'un des agents pathogènes les plus problématiques à l'échelle mondiale en raison de son association avec un phénotype de résistance cumulative à de nombreux antibiotiques cliniquement importants, tels que : les β -lactamines à spectre étendu (y compris les céphalosporines de troisième génération et les antibiotiques de dernière ligne de cette famille - les carbapénèmes), les fluoroquinolones, les aminoglycosides, et plus récemment aussi, les options thérapeutiques de dernier recours, telles que la colistine, la tigécycline et la fosfomycine. Ce scénario est principalement le résultat de l'expansion mondiale des bêta-lactamases à médiation plasmidique, en particulier des β -lactamases à spectre étendu (BLSE) et des carbapénémases, qui se produit par des mécanismes de transmission vertical et/ ou transfert horizontal de gènes.

Kp est intrinsèquement résistante à l'ampicilline grâce à la production de SHV, une enzyme β -lactamase de classe A, codée dans le chromosome de Kp par le gène core blaSHV. Les orthologues de cette β -lactamase de classe A sont une caractéristique conservée des chromosomes des autres membres du KpSC (désignés LEN chez *K. variicola* et *K. quasivariicola*, et OKP chez d'autres espèces du complexe). Le gène blaSHV a été capturé plusieurs fois à partir du chromosome de Kp par une transposase formant un élément génétique mobile (MGE) qui a facilité la diffusion à d'autres espèces par transfert horizontal (surtout plasmidique). Notamment, les variants mobiles de blaSHV qui en résultent portent souvent des mutations ponctuelles qui se traduisent par une activité BLSE (conférant une résistance aux céphalosporines de troisième génération), et sont sous des promoteurs plus puissants que les formes chromosomiques [88]. Par conséquent, certains génomes de Kp portent désormais deux copies de blaSHV : un variant du gène core chromosomique et un variant BLSE acquis (généralement d'origine plasmidique). Cela peut créer des difficultés pour identifier avec précision les allèles blaSHV présents dans Kp en n'utilisant que des données de séquençage à lecture courte, ce qui peut avoir un impact sur la prédiction correcte de la résistance associée.

A part les blaSHV et en ce qui concerne l'expansion des BLSE, l'épidémiologie des Kp était dominée jusqu'à la fin des années 2000 par des épidémies hospitalières associées à la production d'enzymes du type TEM et SHV, et alors que les SHV-BLSE sont encore fréquemment identifiées (surtout SHV-2 ; SHV-5, SHV-12), les TEM-BLSE sont aujourd'hui devenues résiduelles. Toutefois, au début des années 2000, un changement dans cette épidémiologie a été observé avec l'expansion mondiale de CTX-M (principalement CTX-M-15 et -14 parmi les Kp), soit à l'hôpital mais aussi dans la communauté.

Depuis 2006, l'émergence et l'augmentation continue de la résistance aux carbapénèmes ont été observées au niveau mondial, en raison de l'expansion des carbapénémases dans le contexte clinique. Dans les pays américains et européens, les enzymes KPC sont prédominantes, tandis que dans les pays asiatiques et africains, l'épidémiologie est surtout dominée par OXA-48-like et NDM, les enzymes IMP étant également fréquemment détectées en Asie.

Dans ce scénario d'escalade de la résistance aux carbapénèmes, les antibiotiques de dernier recours, telles que la colistine, la tigécycline et la fosfomycine, sont devenus essentiels dans la gestion des infections à Kp multirésistantes. Cependant, des taux croissants de résistance à ces antibiotiques ont aussi été observés parmi la population de Kp, cette résistance étant principalement associée à des mutations chromosomiques et plus récemment à des gènes à médiation plasmidique (mcr dans le cas de la résistance à la colistine).

La plupart des résistances observées chez Kp sont associées à des gènes de RAM accessoires acquis horizontalement, plutôt qu'à des mutations dans les gènes chromosomiques. Ceux-ci sont le plus souvent d'origine plasmidique, mais peuvent également être intégrés au chromosome. Le comptage des gènes RAM acquis dans les isolats de Kp à partir des données génomiques n'est pas une tâche triviale, à moins que des séquences génomiques complètes soient disponibles, condition nécessaire pour différencier les gènes core chromosomiques comme blaSHV, fosA et oqxAB des formes codées par des éléments génétiques mobiles comme détaillé ci-dessus.

1.2.4. Pathogénicité et virulence

De nombreux facteurs génétiques contribuent à la capacité des souches de Kp à provoquer des maladies chez l'homme. Ces facteurs de virulence peuvent être codés dans le chromosome ou dans certains plasmides.

Toutes les souches de Kp ont un sous-ensemble de facteurs de pathogénicité fondamentaux qui constituent les conditions de base pour l'établissement d'infections opportunistes chez les hôtes mammifères. Quelques gènes peuvent être cités : le gène *ent* codant pour la biosynthèse du sidérophore entérobactine, des loci core *fim* et *mrk* codant respectivement pour les fimbriae de type 1 et de type 3, ainsi que des loci variables de biosynthèse des polysaccharides capsulaires (antigène K) et des LPS (antigène O)[80].

De nombreux facteurs de virulence sont connus chez Kp pour accroître encore la gravité des infections et/ou la propension à provoquer des maladies plus sévères. Quatre principaux loci de virulence acquis (et associés à des infections invasives) se retrouvent avec une prévalence élevée parmi les souches hvKp : les sidérophores aérobactine (*iuc*) et salmochéline (*iro*), la génotoxine colibactine (*clb*), et le locus d'hypermucoïdie (*rmpADC*). Le sidérophore yersiniabactine (*ybt*) est tout aussi important, mais est également enrichi dans les populations hvKp et cKp [77–79]. Les systèmes sidérophores comprennent des molécules chélatrices du fer (qui peuvent piéger de manière compétitive le fer des protéines hôtes ou d'autres sources) et des récepteurs de surface pour l'internalisation. La colibactine polykétide génotoxique, qui induit des dommages à l'ADN dans les cellules eucaryotes, a été décrite pour la première fois chez *E. coli*. La colibactine favorise la colonisation des muqueuses et de l'intestin, la diffusion dans le sang et d'autres organes, et peut contribuer au cancer colorectal [89] (Figure 6).

Plusieurs travaux montrent que les gènes associés à la RAM et à la virulence sont chacun concentrés dans des sous-populations distinctes de Kp [90, 80]. Cependant, cette structuration pourrait être en train de disparaître, entraînant l'apparition de souches potentiellement dangereuses, à la fois hautement virulentes et résistantes à la plupart des antibiotiques disponibles [82].

Les analyses génomiques permettent aujourd'hui de comparer l'ensemble des éléments génétiques (plasmides, gènes, SNPs, ...) de Kp afin d'inférer des informations clés sur la structure de la population qui participent à mieux comprendre son évolution, sa propagation et sa capacité infectieuse. Sachant les nombreuses problématiques majeures associées à Kp, il devient donc nécessaire de disposer de méthodes taxonomiques (au sens de classification et nomenclature) précises et stables afin d'identifier ses différentes sous-populations (souvent appelées souches).

2. Concepts et approches de la taxonomie bactérienne

La taxonomie est la science de la classification des organismes. Elle est traditionnellement divisée en trois étapes successives et complémentaires : (i) la classification, c'est-à-dire l'arrangement ordonné des organismes en groupes sur la base de similarités, (ii) la nomenclature, c'est-à-dire l'étiquetage des groupes définis en (i), et (iii) l'identification des organismes inconnus, c'est-à-dire le processus consistant à déterminer si un organisme appartient à l'un des groupes définis en (i) et étiquetés en (ii) [91–96].

L'objectif majeur de la taxonomie est de fournir à la fois une classification, une nomenclature et une technique d'identification qui puissent être utilisées à des fins très diverses [95]. Ici, ces trois composantes sont passées en revue, suivies de la situation taxonomique des deux agents pathogènes modèles de cette thèse.

2.1. Classification bactérienne

2.1.1. Historique des méthodes de classification bactérienne

La classification est l'arrangement des organismes vivants (ou, au sens large, de tout objet d'intérêt) en groupes, appelés taxons, qui sont idéalement définis sur la base de similitudes ou de relations phylogénétiques. Bien qu'il existe de nombreuses manières de classer les organismes vivants, la communauté des sciences de la vie convient actuellement que cette classification doit être basée sur les proximités phylogénétiques [97, 95, 98, 99].

Les premières tentatives de classifications microbiennes étaient uniquement basées sur des propriétés phénotypiques, qui, pour la plupart, ne révèlent pas les relations évolutives. Un système de classification phénétique, publié en 1923 dans l'ouvrage *Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology* (Figure 7), a permis de fournir un cadre unifié afin de reconnaître les taxons bactériens.

Au début des années 1960, les progrès dans la connaissance des propriétés de l'ADN et dans le développement des techniques de biologie moléculaire ont pu fournir des informations sur certaines propriétés génotypiques. Ainsi, plusieurs méthodes basées sur l'ADN ont été développées, notamment la teneur en guanine et cytosine de l'ADN (G+C mol%) et l'hybridation ADN-ADN (DDH). Cependant, tout comme les précédentes méthodes phénotypiques, ces différentes approches ne conduisent pas à des classifications phylogénétiques précises, notamment dans les embranchements anciens.

Dans les années 1980, l'utilisation courante de la séquence d'ARNr 16S a permis de conduire de nombreuses analyses phylogénétiques relativement précises [100]. En conséquence, à la fin des années 1990, la redéfinition de la taxonomie procaryote à travers l'usage des séquences nucléotidiques (principalement l'ARNr 16S) a permis de compléter les approches traditionnelles (basées sur le phénotype) par l'adoption générale du cadre phylogénétique plus informatif. Ce basculement dans les concepts de classification bactérienne fût concrétisé par la deuxième édition (2001–2012) du *Bergey's Manual of Systematic Bacteriology* (Figure 7).

Actuellement, les taxonomistes des espèces bactériennes s'accordent sur le principe qu'une classification fiable ne peut être déterminée que par l'exploration de la diversité interne des taxons via un large éventail de techniques, généralement appelé « approche polyphasique » [92]. Proche du principe du réquisit des données globales ('requirement of total evidence', e.g. Carnap 1950, Hempel 1965, Davidson 1985), cette approche consiste en l'utilisation d'un maximum de données (incluant les informations génotypiques, phénotypiques et phylogénétiques recueillies sur la souche bactérienne) pour déterminer les groupes taxonomiques. Les méthodes de classification phénotypiques et génotypiques sont présentées dans la section suivante.

Figure 7. Historique des approches taxonomiques (gauche) et nomenclaturales (droite) de 1920 (en haut) à aujourd'hui (en bas) (figure extraite de la revue « Prokaryotic taxonomy and nomenclature in the age of big sequence data » de Hugenholtz et al. [98]).

2.1.2. Les méthodes de classification bactérienne

En pratique, la classification des souches bactériennes s'articule sur plusieurs critères de nature phénotypiques ou génotypiques.

Les méthodes phénotypiques

Les méthodes phénotypiques s'appuient sur l'analyse des caractéristiques morphologiques, physiologiques et biochimiques des bactéries [101]. Les caractéristiques morphologiques regroupent les spécificités des cellules et des colonies, telles que la forme des cellules, la formation d'endospores, la présence de flagelles, la coloration de Gram, la couleur de la colonie, le diamètre, l'opacité, la production de mucus et la consistance. D'autre part, les caractéristiques

physiologiques et biochimiques décrivent la culture dans différentes conditions de croissance, telles que la plage de températures, le pH, la tolérance à la salinité, les besoins en oxygène ou dioxyde de carbone, la tolérance à différents antibiotiques, l'activité enzymatique (par exemple, l'uréase) et le métabolisme des composés (par exemple, la source de carbone et la source d'azote). Un autre test phénotypique couramment employé est la caractérisation chimique des cellules ; cette dernière évalue les éléments extracellulaires (peptidoglycane, acides téichoïques et acides mycoliques), la composition de la membrane cellulaire (acides gras, lipides polaires, lipoquinones respiratoires et pigments) ou les composés du cytoplasme (polyamines). Ces caractéristiques chimiques, souvent nommées marqueurs chimiotaxonomiques, sont particulièrement utilisées lorsque les caractères morphologiques et physiologiques ont échoué à fournir une classification satisfaisante.

Bien que ces caractérisations fournissent des informations importantes sur les bactéries considérées, elles ne permettent pas la classification au rang de l'espèce, car insuffisamment discriminantes. De plus, les résultats de ces méthodes peuvent se révéler difficiles à interpréter ou à reproduire.

Dans la majorité des laboratoires de microbiologie, les tests phénotypiques classiques sont encore couramment utilisés pour l'identification de bactéries cliniquement pertinentes et constituent la base de la description formelle des groupes taxonomiques (espèces).

Les méthodes génotypiques

Les méthodes génotypiques ciblent directement les molécules d'ADN (y compris l'ADN ribosomal) ou d'ARN (y compris ARNr). Elles sont actuellement les méthodes dominantes de la taxonomie moderne.

Détermination du pourcentage guanine + cytosine (% G + C)

La détermination de la teneur en guanine-cytosine (G+C) dans l'ADN a été la première technologie d'acide nucléique utilisée en taxonomie bactérienne. Elle varie entre 20 et 80% chez les procaryotes. Empiriquement, il a été montré que les organismes qui diffèrent de plus de 10% en moles n'appartiennent pas au même genre, et que 5% en moles est la variation maximale commune au sein d'une même espèce [102]. Toutefois, il est important de noter que deux organismes présentant des teneurs en G+C similaires n'appartiennent pas nécessairement à la même espèce.

Avantages	Désavantages
La méthode permet de distinguer les souches non apparentées.	La méthode ne permet pas de considérer que les souches appartiennent à la même espèce.

L'hybridation ADN-ADN

Les techniques de réassociation ADN-ADN (ou hybridation ADN-ADN ; DDH) reposent sur une tentative de comparaison brute des génomes de différents organismes afin de calculer une similarité génomique globale. Il existe plusieurs méthodologies pour quantifier le taux de réassociation ADN-ADN, mais toutes reposent sur le même principe. Les ADN de deux organismes différents sont mélangés et dénaturés pour obtenir un mélange de molécules d'ADN

simple brin. Dans des conditions expérimentales contrôlées, la réassociation de l'ADN se produit et donne lieu à des molécules hybrides. Dans ce contexte, plus la similarité génomique des deux organismes est élevée, plus la formation d'hybrides (hybridation) sera importante. La comparaison entre les résultats obtenus avec l'ADN hybride et l'ADN de référence pur (ADN homoduplex) conduit ainsi à une mesure de similarité. Deux indicateurs sont généralement utilisés : le rapport de liaison relatif (RBR) et la différence du point médian de dénaturation thermique (ΔT_m). Le RBR reflète le pourcentage d'hybridation ADN-ADN et la ΔT_m est un reflet de la stabilité thermique de l'hybride. Sur la base de nombreuses analyses d'espèces procaryotes bien définies, une valeur RBR d'au moins 70% (et ΔT_m d'au plus 5°C) est recommandée pour déterminer que deux organismes procaryotes appartiennent à la même espèce [103].

Ce critère standard pour la délimitation des espèces présente toutefois de nombreux inconvénients qui remettent en question son caractère incontournable. En effet, la technique DDH s'avère fastidieuse à mettre en œuvre, et les résultats ne sont pas toujours simples d'interprétation, ni comparables entre laboratoires du fait de l'absence d'une technique universelle.

Avantages	Limites
Norme de référence actuelle pour la délimitation des espèces.	Décrit seulement une mesure approximative de la relation génétique moyenne.
Les souches avec des valeurs de DDH supérieures à 70 % dans des conditions standardisées et/ou une différence de température de fusion inférieure à 5 % appartiennent à la même espèce.	Seules les espèces ou sous-espèces étroitement apparentées peuvent être distinguées (similitude génomique supérieure à 90%).
Les souches avec des valeurs de similarité DDH inférieures à 70 % sont bien corrélées avec l'ARNr 16S. Les souches avec une identité de séquence d'ARNr 16S inférieure à 98,7 % peuvent généralement être considérées comme des membres d'espèces différentes.	Les méthodes sont plutôt fastidieuses et chronophages et les bases de données incrémentales ne peuvent pas être développées. Non applicable pour les bactéries non cultivées.

L'analyse de l'ARN ribosomique (ARNr)

Les techniques d'analyse des ARNr ou des gènes codant pour les ARNr (*rrs* en particulier, codant pour l'ARNr 16S) ont révolutionné la taxonomie procaryote, et sont encore à ce jour très largement utilisées en taxonomie microbienne. En conséquence, de très nombreuses séquences d'ARNs 16S (représentatives d'une large variété de souches bactériennes, dont les souches types) sont actuellement disponibles (environ 3 400 000 en 2022) via des banques de données publiques, telles que Ribosomal Database Project (RDP) II (<http://rdp.cme.msu.edu/>) ou NCBI Reference Sequence Database (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/224725>).

Les classifications phylogénétiques obtenues à partir de ces séquences ont significativement contribué à la restructuration de la systématique bactérienne. A ce jour, il est encore largement recommandé d'utiliser l'ARNr 16S en tant que partie intégrante d'une « approche polyphasique » pour de nouvelles descriptions d'espèces bactériennes ou de taxons supérieurs, sachant que deux séquences d'ARNr 16S alignées présentant >95% ou >97% d'identité

nucléotidiques sont considérées comme appartenant au même genre ou à la même espèce, respectivement [104, 105].

Avantages	Limites
Les ARNr remplissent toutes les propriétés des marqueurs moléculaires utiles (ubiquitaires, fonctionnellement constants, conservés).	La résolution au niveau de l'espèce n'est souvent pas suffisante, car le gène est trop conservé.
Les ARNr sont des marqueurs stables. Ils sont moins soumis aux évènements de transfert latéral.	
Bonne congruence pour le modèle de ramification des arbres phylogénétiques dérivés de gènes conservés, principalement informationnels, impliqués dans la traduction et la transcription, respectivement.	Plusieurs gènes d'ARNr 16S existent (montrant dans la plupart des cas une plage de divergence de séquence de 1 à 2%, mais parfois même plus).
Les études basées sur le génome sont souvent en accord avec les données sur l'ARNr.	
Facilite l'identification des procaryotes non cultivés.	Au niveau du phylum, il est souvent difficile d'organiser des ordres de branchement relatifs.

L'identité nucléotidique moyenne (Average Nucleotide Identity; ANI)

L'ANI est une mesure computationnelle de l'identité nucléotidique moyenne entre deux génomes [106–108]. Ces dernières années, l'ANI est devenue une mesure standard pour estimer la proximité génétique entre souches bactériennes [109]. Il a été observé qu'une valeur d'ANI de 95 % correspond très souvent au seuil de 70 % d'hybridation ADN-ADN (DDH) recommandé pour délimiter les espèces bactériennes [110, 106, 111, 107, 109].

Par cette convention, deux génomes induisant une valeur d'ANI ≥ 96 % peuvent être considérés comme appartenant à la même espèce. Depuis sa description initiale, un certain nombre d'ajustements ont été apportés, soit pour améliorer la corrélation avec les valeurs expérimentales DDH [112, 107, 108], soit pour accélérer le calcul des valeurs ANI [111, 113, 114, 109].

Avantages	Limites
Norme de référence actuelle pour la délimitation des espèces.	Différentes définitions et implémentations conduisant à des valeurs d'ANI différentes entre deux mêmes génomes.
Les souches avec des valeurs d'ANI supérieures ou égale à 96 % appartiennent à la même espèce.	
Les souches avec des valeurs de similarité d'ANI supérieur ou également à 70% sont bien corrélées avec les valeurs expérimentales DDH.	

2.1.3. Les rangs de classification, de l'espèce à la 'souche'

Il est généralement admis que les rangs actuels de classification du vivant sont hérités des propositions de Carl von Linné (né Carl Linnæus) [115]. C'est au 18^{ème} siècle qu'il a formalisé les principes de la taxonomie biologique moderne (arrangement en catégories hiérarchiques) et

de la nomenclature (règles de dénomination des groupes taxonomiques). Ces principes constituent aujourd'hui la base de la classification bactérienne. Les différents rangs taxonomiques, du plus général au plus spécifique, sont : domaine, phylum, classe, ordre, famille, genre, espèce et sous-espèce.

Aucun rang inférieur à la sous-espèce n'est couvert par cette taxonomie, et ce sujet fera l'objet d'une partie de cette thèse (cf. Chapitre 3 et 4).

Espèce

L'unité taxonomique de base, sans doute la plus importante en classification bactérienne, est l'espèce. La délimitation de ce rang taxonomique, autrement dit la définition des espèces (existantes), est une approche pragmatique qui ne doit pas être confondue, même si elle s'en inspire, avec le concept d'espèce, autrement dit la définition de l'espèce (conceptuelle). Le concept d'espèce résulte d'approches théoriques qui proposent une description logique de ce qui devrait être considéré comme une espèce en tant qu'unité de biodiversité, et le pourquoi de leur existence. Ainsi, la notion de cohérence génétique maintenue par la recombinaison entre individus d'une même espèce a été mise en avant par analogie au concept d'espèce biologique chez les eucaryotes multicellulaires [116]. Dans une autre approche, l'espèce bactérienne en tant qu'écotype a été proposée [117].

La définition actuelle de l'espèce est pragmatique, opérationnelle et universellement applicable. Elle est décrite comme : "*une catégorie qui circonscrit un groupe (de préférence) génomiquement cohérent de souches / d'isolats individuel(le)s partageant un degré élevé de similarité dans de nombreuses caractéristiques indépendantes, testées comparativement dans des conditions hautement standardisées*" [102, 118]. Les avancées en biologie moléculaire ont permis de circonscrire des unités biologiques en fonction de leurs cohérences phylogénétique, génomique et phénotypique. Par conséquent, la définition pragmatique des espèces a évolué, et est définie comme "*une catégorie qui circonscrit des populations d'individus monophylétiques, génomiquement et phénotypiquement cohérentes, qui peuvent être clairement distinguées d'autres entités de ce type au moyen de paramètres standardisés*" [119].

En pratique, la compilation de différents paramètres génomiques et phénotypiques doit permettre sa distinction sans équivoque.

Sous-espèce

La sous-espèce est le rang officiel le plus bas dans la taxonomie des procaryotes. Au sein des espèces bactériennes, on peut parfois distinguer des sous-espèces, qui sont idéalement des organismes génotypiquement démarqués, mais qui, en pratique, sont le plus souvent des groupes distingués pour leurs propriétés phénotypiques ou médicales. Par exemple, chez *K. pneumoniae*, les sous-espèces *rhinoscleromatis* et *ozaenae* sont distinguées (impliquant de nommer les autres membres de l'espèce, *K. pneumoniae* subsp. *pneumoniae*). Toutefois les études de structure des populations de *K. pneumoniae* ont montré que ces deux sous-espèces sont en réalité deux lignées parmi plusieurs milliers, devant donc plutôt être considérées comme des 'pathotypes'. Il n'existe pratiquement aucune convention permettant l'établissement de sous-espèces, qui, bien que parfois utiles, sont généralement désignées selon des critères divers (par exemple l'expression clinique associée).

Variants (ou types)

Les rangs inférieurs aux sous-espèces (e.g. biovars, sérovars, phagovars, pathovars) sont souvent utilisés pour désigner des groupes de souches qui peuvent être distinguées par certains caractères spécifiques, tels que la composition antigénique (sérovar) ou les réactions aux bactériophages (phagovar). Ces rangs n'ont pas de statut officiel dans la nomenclature mais ont souvent une grande utilité pratique. Une liste de certaines catégories infraspécifiques communes est donnée dans le Tableau 4. Il est à noter que ce type de rang ne repose généralement pas sur une classification phylogénétique, ce qui induira souvent une non-concordance avec les classifications génomiques ultérieures.

Tableau 6. Désignations des variants.

Nom privilégié	Synonyme	Appliqué aux souches ayant :
Biovar	Biotype	Propriétés biochimiques ou physiologiques particulières
Sérovar	Sérotype	Propriétés antigéniques distinctives
Pathovar	Pathotype	Propriétés pathogènes pour certains hôtes
Phagovar	Phagotype	Capacité à être lysé par certains bactériophages
Morphovar	Morphotype	Particularités morphologiques

Souche

En microbiologie, un niveau très utilisé d'organisation et de nomenclature est la souche, qui est (dans la plupart des cas) définie comme issue d'une culture bactérienne unique (une population de cellules génotypiquement identiques, du moins initialement). D'après la première édition de *Bergey's Manual of Systematic Bacteriology* : "*une souche est constituée des descendants d'un seul isolement en culture pure, et est généralement constituée d'une succession de cultures finalement issues d'une seule colonie initiale*".

L'identification au rang de souche devient de plus en plus importante, et sa distinction a connu un réel progrès grâce aux avancées technologiques. Ce niveau d'identification est généralement appelé typage. Le typage bactérien présente plusieurs champs d'intérêts, tels que les études épidémiologiques, le diagnostic individuel, ou, plus fondamentalement, les études de la diversité des souches au sein d'une même espèce, objet de la biologie des populations.

Dans le cadre d'études épidémiologiques, le typage permet le suivi des souches à l'échelle locale ou mondiale, et durant leur propagation entre environnement, aliments, animaux et humains. Sur le plan du diagnostic individuel, le typage permet de traiter le patient en fonction des caractéristiques de la souche infectieuse (e.g. résistance aux antibiotiques ou pathogénicité). De plus, l'identification précise d'une souche permet de différencier une récurrence d'une réinfection par une nouvelle souche.

Isolat

Un concept souvent confondu avec celui de souche, bien que distinct, est celui d'isolat. L'isolat peut être défini comme une souche (comme définie ci-dessus : groupe génétiquement identique) qui a été isolée d'une source unique bien définie par un lieu, une date et un échantillon précis. Il est souhaitable de distinguer les notions d'isolat et de souche, cette dernière devant plutôt être

vue comme un ensemble d'isolats partageant des caractéristiques phénotypiques ou génotypiques communes.

Clone

Le terme de clone a beaucoup été utilisé pour désigner un ensemble de souches (ou d'isolats) descendant d'un ancêtre commun (considéré comme une bactérie unique) par division binaire sans recombinaison avec d'autres clones. Même si ce concept reste très utile, il tend à disparaître à l'ère de la génomique qui a révélé de nombreux événements de recombinaison, même à des échelles évolutives fines. En focalisant sur leurs relations phylogénétiques, le concept de clone présente toutefois l'intérêt de définir le niveau de similarité entre les souches (ou isolats) d'un même clone, permettant ainsi de déterminer l'âge du clone, ainsi que sa vitesse d'évolution ou de propagation. La notion de 'clonal frame' a été proposée pour réconcilier la clonalité (évolution verticale) de la majorité du chromosome avec le remplacement de certaines régions délimitées (par transfert horizontal ou recombinaison homologue) définie ici comme remplacement allélique ou conversion génique [120].

Lignées (« sublineage »)

Une lignée phylogénétique désigne, au sens générique, tout groupe monophylétique de souches. Toutefois, le terme « lignée » est souvent utilisé (y compris au sein de cette thèse) pour désigner les groupes phylogénétiques les plus profonds au sein de l'espèce (ou de la sous-espèce, quand elle correspond à un ensemble divers et bien délimité). Cette définition de la lignée sera utilisée dans le Chapitre 2 pour *C. diphtheriae* et en Partie II.

2.1.4. Les espèces monomorphes

Toutes les espèces n'ont pas été définies et nommées suivant les conventions actuelles. En effet, les premières espèces bactériennes décrites étaient principalement celles causant des maladies spécifiques chez l'homme (d'où leur nom caractéristique, tels que *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, *Yersinia pestis*, ou *Shigella dysenteriae*). Achtman *et al.* [121] ont proposé le terme d'espèce monomorphe pour désigner des groupes bactériens qui ont le statut d'espèce dans la taxonomie procaryote, mais dont le niveau de diversité génétique est très restreint (ANI > 99.9%). Ces espèces ont évolué relativement récemment (après l'apparition d'*Homo sapiens* il y a ~200 000 ans) à partir d'espèces 'valides' (par exemple, *Yersinia pestis* n'est en réalité qu'une lignée au sein de l'espèce *Y. pseudotuberculosis* [122]). Dans ces cas, il existe donc un découplage entre la taxonomie et la classification phylogénétique, en ce sens que le concept d'espèce génomique (définie entre autres par le seuil de 95% d'ANI) n'a pas été appliqué. Or, un renommage suivant les conventions actuelles est considéré comme coûteux et dangereux pour la santé publique. Un archétype d'une telle discordance est la situation de *Shigella*, genre bactérien inclus phylogénétiquement dans l'espèce (génomique et taxonomique) *Escherichia coli*, et dont les quatre espèces (*S. dysenteriae*, *S. sonnei*, *S. flexneri* et *S. boydii*) sont elles-mêmes polyphylétiques (chacune est associée à différentes lignées de *E. coli*) [118, 119].

Pour réconcilier ces discordances, il a été proposé d'intégrer la notion de clone en complément de la nomenclature procaryote (par exemple, *Yersinia pseudotuberculosis* clone Pestis [125]). Cette proposition n'a toutefois pas connu de succès. Un certain nombre d'espèces monomorphes bien connues en infectiologie représentent donc des anomalies taxonomiques, et doivent recevoir un traitement à part dans les études de biologie des populations ou de taxonomie génomique des souches (voir plus bas, cf. section « Approches phylogénétiques chez les pathogènes monomorphes »).

2.2. Nomenclature

La nomenclature fait référence aux propositions de dénomination universelle des organismes selon un ensemble de principes, règles et recommandations. Il existe plusieurs systèmes de nomenclatures, qui se distinguent principalement par leurs champs d'application phylogénétiques (par exemple, le Code International de Nomenclature Zoologique, de Botanique, des Virus, des Procaryotes). La nomenclature des procaryotes la plus utilisée est celle régie par le Code International de Nomenclature [125] des Procaryotes ([126, 127] ; anciennement nommé le Code International de Nomenclature des Bactéries, puis complété avec les Archées).

Des modifications peuvent être apportées à ce Code, mais ce rôle est réservé au Comité International sur la Systématique des procaryotes (ICSP). L'*International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology* (IJSEM) est la revue de référence pour la publication officielle de nouveaux taxons microbiens (journal officiel de l'ICSP). Seuls les noms d'espèce (ou autres taxons) publiés dans l'IJSEM sont considérés comme valides et reconnus [128].

2.2.1. Nomenclature bactérienne aux rangs de l'espèce bactérienne et supérieurs

La nomenclature des organismes utilisée aujourd'hui dans le système ICSP découle du système proposé par Carl Von Linné. Le nom d'une espèce est une combinaison binominale composée du nom du genre suivi d'une épithète d'espèce. Ce système de nommage 'genre espèce' est appelé nomenclature binominale (ou binomiale, selon les auteurs [129]).

Les noms scientifiques de tous les taxons (espèce, genre, rangs taxonomiques supérieurs jusqu'au phylum, suivant une proposition récente [130, 131]) sont des mots latins ou latinisés (traités comme latins quelle que soit leur origine). Le nom d'un genre ou d'un sous-genre est un substantif (ou un adjectif utilisé comme substantif) au singulier et écrit avec une majuscule initiale. L'épithète spécifique doit être traitée de l'une des trois manières suivantes : (i) comme un adjectif qui doit s'accorder en genre avec le nom générique, (ii) comme un substantif (nom) en apposition au nominatif, ou (iii) comme un substantif (nom) au génitif. Si une épithète spécifique est formée de deux mots ou plus, alors ces derniers doivent être joints [126]. Si ces règles présentent l'avantage d'harmoniser la nomenclature des nouveaux taxons, elles sont souvent critiquées pour leur rigidité et pour l'impossibilité d'automatiser la création de nouveaux noms, représentant un frein à la description de très nombreux nouveaux taxons. Pour

pallier en partie cette critique, une liste de plusieurs millions de noms grammaticalement corrects, prédéfinis et prêts à l'emploi a été récemment proposée [132].

2.2.2. Nomenclature sous le rang de la sous-espèce bactérienne

Il n'existe actuellement pas de règle de nomenclature régie par un code universel pour définir les variants, souches ou clones au sein des espèces. Il devient pourtant nécessaire de pouvoir nommer les souches bactériennes de manière précise, les agents de santé publique et les cliniciens s'appuyant de plus en plus souvent sur une identification précise des souches pour prendre des décisions sur la manière de contrôler la transmission ou de traiter un patient. Une nomenclature universelle permettrait une meilleure communication entre les différents acteurs de santé publique, comme l'a illustré le récent système de nomenclature des variants du SARS-CoV-2 (alpha, delta, omicron) [133].

Bien que distincte conceptuellement, la nomenclature est étroitement liée à la manière de classer et d'identifier les souches. Il existe actuellement plusieurs systèmes de classification des variants (ou souches). Les nomenclatures correspondantes sont discutées ci-dessous avec leurs méthodes respectives.

2.2.2.1. Typage des souches

Dans cette section, le terme de souche sera tacitement entendu comme : tout groupe d'isolats aux caractéristiques génomiques ou phénotypiques différentielles au sein des espèces, du niveau le plus haut (lignées majeures au sein des espèces) au plus bas (isolats uniques et chaînes de transmission récentes).

Les méthodes de typage peuvent être divisées en deux principales catégories, basées respectivement sur des méthodes phénotypiques ou génotypiques. Les techniques de typage phénotypique comptent, parmi les plus utilisées, le biotypage (basé sur les profils biochimiques, morphologiques ou les tolérances environnementales), le sérotypage (fondé sur la présence ou l'absence de déterminants antigéniques somatiques, flagellaires et capsulaires, et de leur réaction avec des antisérums spécifiques), et l'antibiotypage (basé sur l'évaluation *in vitro* des profils de sensibilité ou de résistance à des agents antimicrobiens). Toutefois, les méthodes de typage génotypique, tels que le ribotypage et le *Pulsed-Field Gel Electrophoresis* (PFGE), ont suscité une attention accrue ces dernières années en tant qu'outils pratiques pour analyser l'épidémiologie moléculaire des souches et contrôler les infections. Le ribotypage est une analyse de *Southern blot* basée sur l'hybridation des fragments d'ADN avec l'opéron ribosomique codant pour les ARNr 16S et 23S, hautement conservés chez les différentes espèces bactériennes. La méthode PFGE est une technique d'électrophorèse en champ pulsé, basée sur l'utilisation d'enzymes de restriction reconnaissant des sites de coupure sur l'ADN bactérien, générant un nombre restreint d'ADN de grande taille. Ces deux méthodes ont prouvé leur utilité dans l'investigation de groupes d'infections (clusters) ou d'épidémies. Toutefois, la plupart de ces techniques sont très spécifiques à chaque espèce, et les nomenclatures associées

sont généralement circonscrites à l'espèce, tel qu'illustré par le biotypage spécifique de *C. diphtheriae* (cf. Partie 1 de l'introduction, section 1.1.3).

L'avènement des méthodes de biologie moléculaire, du séquençage et du développement d'outils analytiques bioinformatiques, a permis de révolutionner l'identification des bactéries. Le séquençage du génome entier (*whole-genome sequencing*; WGS) des agents pathogènes est devenu une approche courante, et son pouvoir hautement discriminant permet la détermination de la proximité phylogénétique entre souches, même aux niveaux les plus fins. Pour ces raisons, les méthodes basées sur les données WGS tendent à remplacer les précédentes approches. Depuis une quinzaine d'années, la production de données WGS est mise en œuvre dans le monde entier et dans tous les secteurs (médical, vétérinaire, alimentaire, environnemental) pour l'investigation des épidémies, l'attribution des sources et l'amélioration des modèles de caractérisation des risques. En fonction de la question scientifique, de la complexité de l'ensemble de données et de leurs compétences en bioinformatique, les utilisateurs ont la possibilité d'utiliser une grande variété d'outils pour l'analyse des données WGS.

Dans cette partie, quelques principes et approches sont mis en lumière, des approches génomiques globales jusqu'aux approches à l'échelle du SNP, en passant par les approches courantes à l'échelle du gène. Un aperçu des outils pour la caractérisation et l'identification des agents pathogènes à partir de données WGS est aussi présenté. L'harmonisation et la normalisation de ces outils de typage demeurent néanmoins nécessaires pour permettre une comparaison aisée des souches entre les laboratoires, afin de faciliter la communication entre agents de la santé publique dans des contextes de surveillance sanitaire à l'échelle internationale. Cet aspect sera détaillé, car il fait l'objet d'une part significative de cette thèse.

Approches basées sur les *k*-mers

Les outils basés sur les *k*-mers décomposent les séquences nucléotidiques en segments (oligonucléotides) d'une longueur fixée *k* (généralement inférieure à 31). L'ensemble des fréquences des *k*-mers distincts au sein d'un génome capture les caractéristiques de sa composition nucléotidique spécifique. Plusieurs analyses ont montré que la distribution des fréquences des *k*-mers est spécifique à chaque espèce, définissant ainsi une forme de « signature génomique » [134]. Alternativement, un génome peut aussi être défini par l'énumération de tous les *k*-mers distincts qui le compose. Ces approches ont conduit au développement de nombreux outils permettant d'estimer des mesures de proximité entre génomes, sans alignement ni annotation. Parmi ces outils, le logiciel Mash [135] (permettant d'approximer très rapidement le pourcentage de différences nucléotidiques — linéairement corrélé à l'ANI — entre deux génomes non alignés à partir de la proportion de *k*-mers distincts communs) a ouvert la voie au développement de plusieurs techniques de classifications hiérarchique [136, 137] ou phylogénétique [138, 139].

PopPUNK (Population Partitioning Using Nucleotide K-mers)

Bien que pertinentes dans un paradigme phylogénétique, les classifications de génomes uniquement basées sur des dissimilarités dérivées des différences nucléotidiques observées

entre régions homologues (estimées à partir du contenu en *k-mers*) ne sont pas complètement représentatives de la diversité génomique induite par le ‘pan-génome’ (i.e. union du *core* génome et du génome accessoire). L’outil PopPUNK [141] a ainsi été développé pour proposer une classification des génomes bactériens basée à la fois sur leur dissimilarité au sein des régions homologues (proportion π de différences nucléotidiques) et sur leurs différences en termes de distribution du ‘pan-génome’ (proportion a de régions génomiques spécifiques). La proportion p de *k-mers* identiques entre deux génomes proches pouvant être approximée par une relation mathématique simple entre a , π , et k , PopPUNK estime rapidement les deux valeurs (π , a) pour chaque paire de génomes en utilisant le logiciel Mash pour approximer p avec différentes longueurs de *k-mer*. À partir de ces mesures de proximité génomique à deux paramètres, des clusters sont ensuite inférés, à l’aide d’un modèle de mélange gaussien bidimensionnel ou d’un clustering hiérarchique basé sur la densité (HDBSCAN ; Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise). PopPUNK s’est avéré capable de partitionner efficacement diverses populations bactériennes en souches (et de détecter des complexes clonaux similaires à l’approche cgMLST ; cf. section « Approches gène par gène »). Un avantage de l’approche implémentée par PopPUNK est que de nouveaux génomes peuvent être facilement et rapidement assignés à des clusters existants. Contrairement aux méthodes gène par gène, PopPUNK peut être exécuté sur une nouvelle espèce ou collection sans nécessiter une définition et une évaluation minutieuses d’un schéma de typage.

Avantages	Limites
Il est rapide et évolutif à plus 100000 génomes en un seul batch	Les bases de données peuvent être mises à jour en ligne, au fur et à mesure que les séquences arrivent cependant revient à repartir des bases de données à partir de zéro
Les noms de cluster restent cohérents entre les études, et d’autres étiquettes de cluster telles que MLST peuvent être ajoutées	
Les bases de données peuvent rester petites et gérables en ne conservant que des isolats représentatifs	Aucune nomenclature associée à la classification
Les bases de données permettent naturellement une analyse approfondie de clusters uniques, mais en conservant le contexte complet de l’ensemble de la base de données	
La définition des clusters est biologiquement pertinente	
Un prétraitement, tel que la génération d’un alignement, n’est pas nécessaire	

Les approches basées sur les *k-mers* sont attractives car elles permettent de conduire des classifications rapides et pertinentes à partir d’un large ensemble de génomes bactériens. En revanche, ces classifications demeurent difficilement traduisibles en nomenclatures standardisées des souches. À ce jour, il ne semble pas exister de taxonomie des souches basées sur les *k-mer* qui soit adoptée au-delà de quelques laboratoires de recherche (<https://poppunk.net/pages/databases.html>).

Approches basées sur les SNPs

Le polymorphisme nucléotidique (Single Nucleotide Polymorphism; SNP) est, en génétique, la variation (polymorphisme) d'une seule paire de bases du génome entre individus d'une même espèce (ou entre un individu et la référence de l'espèce). Les SNPs déduits de la comparaison des données WGS fournissent une résolution très fine.

Le concept de 'SNP address' et le package SnapperDB

SnapperDB [142] est un ensemble d'outils permettant de stocker des données sur les variants bactériens afin de faciliter une analyse reproductible et évolutive des populations bactériennes. La nomenclature 'SNP address' a été introduite pour décrire la relation entre les isolats dans une population d'agents pathogènes. Pour chaque souche, SnapperDB détermine les SNPs par rapport à une référence puis les stocke dans une base de données. Au fur et à mesure que de nouvelles souches sont ajoutées, les SNPs dérivés sont comparés à la base de données et une matrice de distances entre vecteurs de SNPs est maintenue. Ces distances sont ensuite utilisées pour effectuer un clustering de type "lien simple" (Single linkage ; *Slink*) des souches. Une nomenclature au niveau de l'isolat pour chaque séquence génomique en est finalement dérivée, permettant une analyse efficace de la population de pathogènes étudiée et facilitant la détection automatisée de groupes en temps réel.

L'innovation majeure de l'approche 'SNP address' est que le clustering *Slink* est effectué à sept seuils décroissants de distance SNP (250, 100, 50, 25, 10 et 0 SNPs). Ce système se traduit par l'attribution, à chaque souche, d'un code à sept nombres où chaque valeur représente l'appartenance au groupe déterminé par chaque seuil de distance SNP décroissant. La 'SNP address' résultante fournit une nomenclature au niveau de l'isolat, induisant la propriété intéressante que deux isolats identiques (distance SNP = 0) sont associés à la même adresse. Ce système est utilisé pour la surveillance des agents pathogènes d'origine alimentaire (Public Health England ; actuellement UKSHA). Toutefois, SnapperDB étant uniquement conçu pour capturer la variation SNP par rapport à un génome de référence, il est recommandé de l'utiliser conjointement avec des méthodologies quantifiant le génome accessoire afin d'obtenir une caractérisation génomique plus informative.

Figure 8. Système SnapperDB.

(A) Illustration de la différence SNP entre une séquence de référence (rangée du haut) et un ensemble de séquences isolées (rangée restante). (B) Regroupement à liaison unique des différences de SNP en 0, 5 et 10 niveaux de SNP pour un ensemble d'isolats. (C) Exemples d'adresses SNP basées sur les sept seuils SNP descendants ; 250, 100, 50, 25, 10, 5, 0. (figure extraite de l'article « SnapperDB: a database solution for routine sequencing analysis of bacterial isolates » de Dallman et al. [142].

Avantages	Limites
Nomenclature automatique	Nécessite un génome de référence
Possibilité d'être standardisé à d'autres espèces	Nécessite de relancer le <i>Slink</i> à chaque ajout de souches faisant évoluer la nomenclature

Les méthodes basées sur les SNPs représentent des approches de choix lorsque (i) le degré de variation de séquence entre les génomes à comparer est très modéré, (ii) les organismes considérés sont monomorphes, ou (iii) des lignées uniques (ou des clones d'organismes plus divers) sont examinées (épidémie). Par conséquent, les analyses à l'échelle des SNPs sont souvent utilisées pour comparer les génomes d'agents pathogènes spécifiques pour tracer la transmission entre humains dans les hôpitaux.

La cartographie des SNPs des génomes de plusieurs isolats sur un génome de référence est relativement rapide et discriminante. Toutefois, certaines technologies de séquençage étant relativement sujettes aux erreurs (plus ou moins bien compensées par les solutions bioinformatiques dédiées à l'inférence des SNPs), cette approche peut conduire à des adresses parfois non-reproductibles. Un autre problème est qu'elle nécessite de disposer d'un génome de référence qui doit être complet et finalisé. Enfin, l'approche est également problématique lorsque certains gènes ne sont pas présents dans le génome de référence.

Approches phylogénétiques chez les pathogènes monomorphes

GenoTyphi

Un outil de typage spécifique de la population de *Salmonella enterica* sérotype Typhi a été développé par Wong *et al.* [143], basé sur un ensemble de 68 SNPs spécifiques. Ces SNPs sont analysés pour identifier la présence d'allèles SNP définissant un cluster, un clade et/ou un sous-clade. Les clusters primaires, clades et sous-clades sont étiquetés en utilisant un système de nomenclature hiérarchique structuré (le cluster 1 est subdivisé en clades 1.1 et 1.2 ; le clade 1.1 est subdivisé en sous-clades 1.1.1, 1.1.2, 1.1.3).

Avantages	Limites
	Méthode difficilement applicable à toutes les espèces
	Formalisation de la nomenclature

D'autres nomenclatures similaires ont été développées pour *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* [144], *Shigella sonnei* [145] ou *Yersinia pestis* [146].

Ce type d'approche est très dépendante de chaque (sous-)espèce, et les concepts et méthodologies associés demeurent complètement non-standardisés. Une telle approche est difficilement applicable à *K. pneumoniae* ou *C. diphtheriae*, espèces très variables qui comportent plusieurs centaines ou milliers de lignées comparables en diversité aux espèces monomorphes.

Approches gène par gène

Des alternatives aux approches précédentes sont les méthodes pour laquelle l'unité de comparaison et d'analyse est le gène (plutôt que le génome complet ou chaque variation nucléotidique).

Le mot « gène » peut être étendu ici pour inclure toute chaîne de séquence identifiable : les séquences couramment trouvées à un locus génétique particulier, des séquences codantes données (CDS), ou tout autre motif de séquence définissable (nucléotidique ou peptidique). Les approches gène-par-gène répertorient et décrivent la variation (au sein des collections de génomes) d'un « gène » au moyen d'un ensemble de séquences alléliques de référence qui décrivent la variation connue pour ce gène. Quelques méthodes de classification où l'unité est le gène sont présentées ci-dessous, ainsi que les nomenclatures qui en sont dérivées.

Typage MLST (Multi-Locus Sequence Typing) et la nomenclature ST

Dans un article fondateur, Maiden *et al.* [147] ont mis au point une méthode non-ambiguë d'identification et de typage de groupes bactériens en utilisant les séquences de fragments de gènes de ménage (généralement sept). Pour chaque locus, les différentes séquences présentes parmi les isolats d'une espèce bactérienne se voient chacune attribuer un numéro d'allèle distinct et, pour chaque isolat, la suite des numéros d'allèles aux différents loci considérés définit son profil allélique (Figure 9). Si un nouvel allèle est découvert pour un locus donné, sa

séquence sera ajoutée à la base de données de définitions alléliques avec un nouveau numéro d'allèle. Dans cette approche, chaque nouvel allèle (pour chaque locus) reçoit un numéro d'identification distinct, indépendamment du nombre de différences nucléotidiques. La logique sous-jacente est qu'un événement génétique unique résultant en un nouvel allèle peut se produire soit par une mutation ponctuelle (modifiant souvent un seul site nucléotidique), soit par un remplacement par recombinaison (changeant souvent plusieurs sites). Un poids identique est donc donné à ces deux types d'évènements évolutifs.

On attribue alors un identifiant numérique unique, appelé ST (Sequence Type), à chaque profil allélique complet distinct. Les STs se sont imposés comme des identifiants de référence en biologie des populations et en épidémiologie moléculaire des bactéries.

Figure 9. Principe de la méthode MLST (Multi-Locus Sequence Typing).

Représentation sur un ensemble de sept gènes. Chaque numéro présent sous une séquence représente l'allèle correspondant à la séquence. Les délétions induisent des données manquantes. La succession de l'ensemble des numéros d'allèles ou données manquantes pour un isolat représente son profil allélique.

Un inconvénient de cette approche typologiste est que les relations phylogénétiques entre STs ne sont pas identifiables à partir du simple identifiant ST. L'approche par arbre couvrant minimal (*Minimum Spanning tree*; MStree) est souvent utilisée pour représenter les proximités entre STs, avec des ajustements parfois nécessaires pour faire face à la fusion des groupes lorsque des génotypes équidistants entre groupes sont échantillonnés. Les classifications par MStree sont ensuite utilisées pour déterminer des regroupements de profils apparentés (e.g. différant d'un seul locus) appelés complexes clonaux (*clonal complexes*; CC). Chez certaines espèces, cette approche montre toutefois des limites de résolution importantes ; par exemple, chez *K. pneumoniae*, une grande fraction des ST (> 5000 sont actuellement décrits) fusionnent en un seul complexe clonal (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Minimum spanning tree des 7,388 profils MLST (Multi-Locus Sequence Typing). Chaque cercle est un ST. Le diamètre de chaque cercle est proportionnel au nombre d'isolat ayant ce même ST.

Avantages	Limites
Plusieurs gènes fournissent des sites nucléotidiques plus informatifs et des tampons contre les effets déformants de la recombinaison de l'un des loci.	Les séquences de 7 (ou même 12) gènes ne correspondent qu'à une fraction mineure du génome, qui résulte en un manque de résolution.
Les gènes domestiques sont essentiels et évoluent relativement lentement mais plus rapidement que les gènes ARNr.	La méthode ne peut pas être appliquée à des bactéries non cultivées.
Résout à des niveaux taxonomiques inférieurs à l'ARNr.	
La méthode se prête à l'automatisation et de grandes bases de données organisées peuvent être développées.	Aucune typage (ST non défini) en présence de données manquantes
Méthode portable et reproductible	La nomenclature ne permet pas l'établir de lien entre la proximité des souches
Nomenclature simple, largement adoptée	

Typage cgMLST (core genome Multi-Locus Sequence Typing)

L'approche cgMLST étend l'approche MLST (basée sur moins d'une dizaine de gènes de ménage) à des centaines ou des milliers de loci [148].

Cette méthodologie est très populaire en raison de sa reproductibilité et de sa portabilité. De plus, cette simple extension de l'approche MLST a permis d'améliorer significativement le degré de discrimination entre souches. Son adoption a aussi grandement bénéficié de la démocratisation du séquençage (et de l'assemblage) des génomes en routine. Toutefois, la différence majeure par rapport à la nomenclature ST est la gestion des éventuelles délétions de gène (induisant des identifiants alléliques manquants dans un profil cgMLST), rendant plus

complexe (voire moins robuste) la définition des types de profils alléliques (souvent appelés cgST). En effet, des cgSTs ne différant que par des identifiants alléliques manquants peuvent coexister dans une nomenclature, impliquant qu'un même isolat puisse être classé dans plusieurs cgSTs. Ainsi, contrairement à l'approche MLST où chaque profil distinct détermine un ST, les profils cgMLST se comparent via une distance (dites allélique) définie par la proportion d'allèles attribués différemment entre une paire d'échantillons. En tenant compte ou pas, des loci où au moins un allèle est manquant, on obtient une distance allélique relative ou absolue, respectivement. A partir des distances alléliques calculées entre chaque paire de profils cgMLST, des approches standards de classification peuvent être appliquées (e.g. *Slink* hiérarchique, MStree), permettant de déterminer des regroupements de profils similaires.

Avantages	Limites
Typage en présence de données manquantes	Besoin d'un schéma prédéfini
Méthode portable et reproductible	Le schéma prédéfini est variable selon le jeu de données initial, il est donc important d'établir le schéma sur un jeu de donnée qui représente la diversité globale de l'espèce
Plusieurs niveaux de classification possibles	
Résolution à l'échelle fine, épidémiologique	
Une distance évolutive peut être déclinée sur la base des séquences des allèles	

Classification *SLink* dérivée du typage cgMLST

Le regroupement des profils cgMLST peut être réalisé de la même manière que pour les données MLST, sur la base du nombre de différences alléliques entre les profils. Toutefois, pour gérer les (éventuels) allèles manquants, un groupe clonal (clonal group ; CG) se définit comme étant un ensemble de profils alléliques similaires (et non identiques, comme se définit un ST dans une approche MLST). Autrement dit, deux profils cgMLST sont considérés comme appartenant au même CG si leur dissimilarité (estimée par la proportion d'allèles différents) est inférieure à un seuil prédéfini. L'approche de choix pour déterminer les seuils définissant les CGs est basée sur une classification hiérarchique (généralement *Slink*) d'un ensemble de profils cgMLST, le seuil optimal étant celui conduisant à une partition « naturelle » et robuste de ces profils (Figure 11).

Figure 11. Les étapes de la classification Single Linkage.

Attribution d'un profil cgMLST à chaque isolat puis une matrice distance de paire de profils cgMLST est calculée. Enfin, les groupe clonaux (CG) sont créés à la suite d'une classification Single Linkage.

Avantages	Limites
Attribution d'une nomenclature à un seuil choisi	Instable à l'ajout de nouveaux génomes intermédiaires
Nomenclature très populaire car simple à mettre en œuvre, reproductible et portable	Nécessité de relancer le <i>Slink</i> à chaque ajout de souches

Nomenclature MLSL (*MultiLevel Single Linkage*) dérivée du typage *cgMLST*

Sachant que différents seuils peuvent partitionner les profils *cgMLST* plus ou moins finement, plusieurs niveaux hiérarchiques de classification peuvent être utilisés. Dans une logique multi-niveaux (proche des '*SNP address*', cf. ci-dessus), la nomenclature MLSL ne s'articule plus sur un seuil unique (nomenclature CG), mais sur un ensemble de différents seuils prédéfinis (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Nomenclature MLSL (*MultiLevel Single Linkage*).

Ces différents niveaux de partitionnement (associés à chaque seuil) peuvent être déterminés (i) soit de manière arbitraire, (ii) soit empiriquement à partir de la structure de population des souches considérées, (iii) soit pour correspondre à des groupes d'isolats issus d'une même épidémie [149]. Toutefois, quelques approches d'optimisation de seuils ont été développées. Dans ce but, l'outil *MSTclust* s'articule sur un MStree inféré à partir des distances alléliques entre chaque paire de profils *cgMLST*. Etant donné un seuil spécifique, *MSTclust* considère le partitionnement des profils induit par la suppression de toutes les arêtes du MStree dont la longueur est supérieure au seuil. La qualité du partitionnement obtenu étant quantifié par le coefficient de Silhouette [151], les meilleurs seuils sont définis comme ceux qui conduisent à des optima locaux de ce coefficient. En complément, *MSTclust* quantifie (pour chaque seuil) la robustesse du partitionnement en effectuant un grand nombre de sous-échantillonnages (de type *jackknife*) des profils *cgMLST* ; cette dernière approche détermine des intervalles de confiance pour le coefficient de Silhouette, mais permet également de quantifier le degré d'adéquation [152, 153] entre le partitionnement des profils sous-échantillonnés et le partitionnement de l'ensemble initial de profils, déterminant ainsi la capacité d'un seuil à produire un partitionnement robuste (relativement indépendant de l'échantillonnage des profils). Un autre outil, *HCCeval* [154], recherche également des seuils pertinents par optimisation du coefficient de Silhouette à partir d'un clustering hiérarchique (HC). Il se distingue toutefois de *MSTclust* en mesurant la stabilité induite par un seuil en comparant le degré de d'adéquation

entre la partition inférée et celles obtenues à partir de seuils voisins via le coefficient d'adéquation NMI [150], déterminant ainsi la capacité d'un seuil à se trouver au sein d'un plateau d'extrema locaux.

Ces classifications multi-niveaux présentent l'excellente propriété de fournir des informations sur le degré de proximités entre les éléments de la nomenclature. L'exemple le plus avancé de cette approche est le HierCC [154] qui est détaillé plus bas.

Avantages	Limites
Nomenclature avec plusieurs niveaux de précision	Instable à l'ajout de nouveaux génomes intermédiaires
Flexible sur le choix des seuils	
Fournit des informations sur les relations de proximités	
Nomenclature indépendante à chaque seuils	

Typage HierCC (Hierarchical Clustering of cgMLST)

HierCC [154] est une approche très similaire à MSL. HierCC calcule d'abord un MSTree basé sur une distance calculée à l'aide du nombre d'allèles cgMLST partagés entre les génomes et qui minimise certains biais causés par les allèles manquants. L'arbre MSTree résultant est utilisé pour attribuer chaque génome à des clusters dans plusieurs HC. Une propriété intéressante de HierCC est de proposer une solution au problème de fusion des groupes du MSTree. Pour ce faire, HierCC associe une première étape de *Slink* (mode développement) à une seconde étape (mode production), où les nouveaux profils sont agrégés aux groupes préexistants résultant de la première étape. Les génomes équidistants à plusieurs clusters sont automatiquement affectés au cluster le plus ancien (identifiant de cluster le plus petit) afin d'assurer la stabilité à long terme des désignations de nomenclature.

Avantages	Limites
Nomenclature avec plusieurs niveaux de précision	Etape de rodage nécessaire pour créer des groupes SL représentatifs de la diversité
Flexible sur le choix des seuils	Nécessite d'attendre d'avoir échantillonné largement les populations pour stabiliser la nomenclature avant de passer à l'étape 'production mode'.
Fournit des informations sur les relations de proximités	
Nomenclature indépendante à chaque seuils	
Stabilité de la nomenclature	

Static founder concept et Cluster Type (CT)

Cette approche est implémentée dans l'outil Ridom SeqSphere+ 8.3 (https://www.ridom.de/seqsphere/ug/latest/Core_Genome_MLST_Complex_Type.html). Les 'cgMLST Complex Type' (CT) fonctionnent comme un identifiant unique additionnel à des fins de communication humaine. Attribuer un identifiant unique à chaque profil cgMLST distinct (équivalent au ST pour les profils MLST) n'est pas pertinent car presque chaque souche

correspond à un profil allélique unique (indépendamment des allèles manquant). Par conséquent, de manière similaire aux complexes clonaux (CC) déduits des approches MLST, les CTs regroupent les souches associées à des profils cgMLST très similaires. Bien entendu, la taille moyenne d'un CT est beaucoup plus petite que celle d'un CC. Les fondateurs de CC sont toujours définis *ad hoc* au cours de l'analyse comme étant le ST ayant le plus grand nombre de variants à locus unique (SLV) des ST de la descendance. Ainsi, le fondateur CC peut changer et les complexes clonaux peuvent fusionner lorsque l'analyse est répétée à un moment ultérieur. En revanche, le statut de "fondateur CT" n'est attribué qu'une seule fois et reste statique, ce qui garantit une nomenclature stable. De même, contrairement aux CC du MLST, le seuil de CT est spécifique à l'espèce. Comme pour les ST ou les CC, l'identifiant d'un CT n'exprime aucune proximité phylogénétique. Le contenu informatif des CTs consiste exclusivement à signifier l'identité (ou la non-identité).

L'attribution des CTs se réalise pendant le processus de soumission des souches. Si la distance entre une nouvelle souche et un fondateur CT est inférieure ou égale à seuil pré-établi, l'identifiant CT de ce fondateur est attribué à cette nouvelle souche. Sinon, un nouveau CT est établi et la nouvelle souche devient le fondateur de ce CT. Si un échantillon soumis se trouve dans les limites de deux (ou plus) fondateurs CT, la souche se voit attribuer le CT avec l'identifiant numérique le plus petit (qui n'appartient pas nécessairement au fondateur de CT le plus proche). Cette règle sur l'égalité a été introduite afin d'éviter la possibilité d'attributions différentes de CT pour des profils alléliques identiques en fonction de l'ordre des soumissions et du moment où les fondateurs de CT sont créés. Ainsi, il est garanti qu'un profil allélique exactement identique qui est soumis plusieurs fois se voit toujours attribuer le même CT.

Comme, par définition, la nomenclature est en continuelle expansion et en raison de l'ordre d'entrée des échantillons et/ou des données de génotypage manquantes, des résultats CT différents peuvent parfois se produire.

Avantages	Limites
Stabilité de la nomenclature	Ne fournit aucune information sur les relations de proximités

Méthode du typage du génome à plusieurs niveaux (Multilevel genome typing; MGT)

La méthode MGT est un système basé sur un ensemble de différents schémas MLST méthodologiquement connectés, qui offrent un gradient de résolutions pour la comparaison des isolats ([155]; Figure 13A). Les auteurs de la méthode proposent neuf schémas (cg)MLST qui composent les niveaux MGT. MGT1 est le schéma MLST classique (sept gènes de ménage). Les niveaux MGT1 à MGT7 s'excluent mutuellement et constituent un partitionnement de MGT8 (cgMLST). Enfin, MGT9 est composé de tous les loci (y compris les régions intergéniques) et englobe tous les autres niveaux. Pour un schéma MGT donné, son nombre de niveaux et la taille (nombre de nucléotides) de ces niveaux dépendent de la résolution attendue et de la diversité génétique de la population de l'espèce individuelle (ou des clones). Dans le but que chaque niveau ait une résolution adéquate pour le traçage épidémiologique des clones de différentes longévités, il a été proposé d'utiliser le taux d'évolution pour définir la taille des niveaux [146].

Figure 13. Structure et concept du système de typage génomique multiniveau (MGT)

(A) Représentation schématique des neuf schémas MLST qui composent les niveaux MGT. (B) Un exemple de phylogénie illustrant la relation entre 11 souches. (C) MGT6-9 ST superposés sur la phylogénie. Chaque ST pour chaque niveau MGT est représenté par un triangle dont la couleur correspond au niveau MGT. Au fur et à mesure que les niveaux augmentent en résolution (augmentation du nombre de loci), des sous-clades plus petites sont définies par chaque ST. (D) Des exemples de ST pour MGT 6-9 sont superposés sur chaque clade. (E) La relation entre les isolats exprimés uniquement en MGT 6-9 ST. La parenté d'un groupe d'isolats est représentée par le plus grand niveau auquel ils partagent une ST (par exemple, les isolats A et B partagent une ST MGT9 et sont donc plus étroitement liés que A et E qui ne partagent qu'une ST MGT7). (figure extraite de l'article « Multilevel genome typing: genomics-guided scalable resolution typing of microbial pathogens » de Payne et al. [155]).

La classification des génomes à chacun des niveaux permet de fournir à chaque isolat une identité définie par une série de ST, chacun défini par des profils alléliques distincts, du plus petit au plus grand. Ce vecteur de STs est appelé un type de génome (*genome type*; GT).

Un système de nomenclature peut être associé à un typage de génomes à plusieurs niveaux, les notations flexibles du système de nommage améliorant l'utilité de l'approche MGT. Un GT complet composé de neuf identifiants ST séparés par des traits d'union donne la définition précise d'une souche (e.g. GT 19-2-11-27-115-274-365-435-501). Un GT partiel peut être utilisé pour décrire un ensemble plus large d'isolats (e.g. GT 19-2-11-27-115-274-X, le symbole X représentant un ST indéfini). Un ST à n'importe quel niveau MGT peut également être utilisé pour définir un groupe (e.g. MGT4 ST27), similaire au MLST traditionnel mais avec un nombre flexible de loci. Enfin, dans les situations où plusieurs GTs liés doivent être communiqués, un GT dégénéré peut être utilisé (e.g. GT 19-2-11-(27/32)-115-274-365-435-501).

Les STs définis par les différents niveaux du système MGT définissent également des relations entre les GT qui se rapprochent des relations phylogénétiques. Les plus faibles niveaux de résolution (e.g. MGT1, MGT2) produisent des STs qui sont (pour la plupart) subdivisés aux niveaux supérieurs. Ce processus se poursuit avec la division des isolats en clades de plus en plus réduits. De cette façon, les relations entre GTs sont s à plusieurs échelles simultanément

et se rapprochent d'une classification phylogénétique (Figure 1B-E). Quelques exceptions sont toutefois possibles, car les loci des niveaux MGT sont mutuellement exclusifs, à l'exception des deux plus grands (MGT8 et MGT9). Par conséquent, une unique mutation dans un niveau de résolution inférieur (e.g. MGT3) peut produire deux ST distincts, alors qu'un niveau de résolution supérieur (e.g. MGT4) ne présenterait qu'un seul ST. Cette situation est définie comme une incohérence hiérarchique et résulte de l'emplacement aléatoire des mutations et de la nature non-chevauchante des niveaux. Toutefois, cette incohérence hiérarchique peut être résolue en interrogeant les niveaux supérieurs et inférieurs à celui qui est incohérent, ce qui permet de décrire la véritable relation entre les isolats.

Avantages	Limites
Plusieurs niveaux de précision	Plusieurs schémas doivent être définis
Flexible	Sensible aux variations insignifiantes des ST
Fournit une nomenclature au niveau des clones et des souches	
Étant donné que les niveaux du MGT sont indépendants et augmentent en résolution, ils offrent une flexibilité pour tracer les identités des clones ou des GT au fil du temps	
MGT est basé sur une correspondance exacte à chaque niveau et évite donc les problèmes que les méthodes basées sur le clustering à liaison unique (par exemple HierCC et SNP address peut rencontrer, comme les effets fondateurs ou la fusion de clusters	

Méthodes basées sur les similarités globales entre génomes

Life Identification Numbers (LINs)

Une méthode de nomenclature originale a été également proposée dans laquelle chaque génome se voit attribuer un code LIN (*Life Identification Number*) basé sur une similarité globale (ANI) avec le membre le plus proche parmi ceux précédemment encodés [156–160]. Ces codes sont constitués d'un ensemble de positions p , chacune correspondant à un seuil de similarité ANI $s_p \in [0,1]$. Ces seuils étant triés par ordre croissant (i.e. $s_p < s_{p+1}$), les premières positions du code (à gauche) correspondent à des niveaux de similarité faible, alors qu'à une position plus à droite correspond une similarité plus importante.

L'encodage LIN d'un ensemble de génomes se formalise comme suit (Figure 14) :

(étape 1) Le code est initialisé, le premier génome étant encodé par la valeur "0" à toutes les positions ;

(étape 2) La règle d'encodage d'un nouveau génome i à partir du plus proche j déjà encodé se définit à partir de la similarité $s_{ij} \in]s_{p-1} ; s_p]$:

- 1) identique au code j jusqu'à la position $p - 1$ (incluse) ;
- 2) pour la position p : valeur maximale observée à cette position (au sein du sous-ensemble des codes ayant le même préfixe à la position $p - 1$) incrémentée de 1 ;
- 3) valeur "0" à partir de la position $p + 1$ (incluse) jusqu'à la dernière.

En conséquence, les organismes avec des génomes très différents ont trivialement des préfixes LIN différents dès les premières positions du code. Les génomes avec une similarité intermédiaire ont des préfixes LIN identiques jusqu'à une position intermédiaire, alors que les génomes très similaires ont des codes LIN identiques jusqu'à une position proche de l'extrémité droite. Autrement dit, deux génomes sont d'autant plus similaires qu'ils présentent de plus longs préfixes identiques dans leur code LIN respectif. Ainsi une proximité entre souches peut se déterminer par la longueur de leur préfixe commun, d'autant plus que deux isolats identiques ont (par définition) exactement le même code LIN.

Notons que les valeurs numériques associées à chaque position n'ont qu'un aspect catégoriel. Par exemple, deux génomes ayant un "1" et un "2" à une position ne sont pas nécessairement plus semblables l'un à l'autre que deux autres ayant un "2" et un "10" à cette position.

Figure 14. Les LIN et leur assignation.

*L'attribution d'un LIN à une séquence génomique nouvellement soumise (par exemple, la séquence génomique G2 ou la séquence génomique G3 dans cette figure) est basée sur le LIN du génome dans la base de données qui a l'ANI le plus élevé par rapport à la séquence génomique nouvellement soumise. Dans l'exemple illustré, lorsque G2 est soumis, la seule séquence de génome déjà dans la base de données est G1 (qui a tous les zéros à toutes les positions puisqu'il s'agissait du tout premier génome ajouté à la base de données). Par conséquent, le génome de la base de données avec l'ANI le plus élevé par rapport à G2 est nécessairement G1. Par conséquent, le LIN de G2 est attribué en fonction du LIN de G1. Au moment où G3 est soumis, G1 et G2 sont déjà dans la base de données. Après le calcul de l'ANI, l'ANI entre G3 et G2 est calculé et trouvé supérieur à l'ANI entre G3 et G1. Par conséquent, le LIN de G3 est attribué en fonction du LIN de G2. *T_G : Seuil ANI en position LIN G. (figure extraite de l'article « A proposal for a portal to make earth's microbial diversity easily accessible and searchable » de Vinatzer et al. [159]).*

Avantages	Limites
Méthode rapide et universelle pour l'ensemble du vivant	Nécessite un génome de départ
Approche adaptable avec toutes distances de parenté	L'ordre peut avoir un impact sur la définition des LIN
Le nombre et les valeurs de seuils sont modifiables	L'encodage LIN dépend des génomes précédemment encodés donc ce qui peut être vu comme un génome de référence ; S'il y a une erreur dans un code LIN, le système est non robuste
Apporte des informations sur le lien de parenté entre les génomes	
Code attribué à un génome et non à un groupe de génomes ce qui rend l'approche stable	Approche basée sur des distances ANI qui ne sont pas adaptées pour de la classification de souches
La définition de groupes de LIN est possible	
Accessible sur une plateforme internet	

2.3. Identification bactérienne

La caractérisation et l'identification des espèces et des souches sont d'une importance cruciale dans de nombreux domaines (fondamental, industriel, santé). La caractérisation peut être définie comme la description des propriétés des taxons, tandis que l'identification consiste en l'emploi de méthodes pour placer un isolat dans le système taxonomique.

Il existe une grande variété de méthodes de caractérisation et d'identification, et il est primordial de comprendre à quel niveau taxonomique ces méthodes sont porteuses d'information. Le type d'informations apporté par chaque technique est directement lié à sa résolution, c'est-à-dire la capacité à discriminer des isolats appartenant à des rangs taxonomiques plus ou moins profonds. L'application de différentes techniques à la taxonomie des procaryotes est décrite ci-dessous, ainsi que leur pouvoir de résolution. Quelques techniques couramment utilisées pour la circonscription des espèces sont résumées, ainsi que des méthodes d'identification des souches.

2.3.1. L'identification au rang des espèces

Les tests phénotypiques classiques en microbiologie comprennent les analyses morphologiques, physiologiques et biochimiques. Ces caractéristiques peuvent être testées avec des systèmes commerciaux standardisés, tels que les Galeries API (bioMérieux) ou BIOLOG (Biolog, Inc.), qui ont pour atout de minimiser les discordances de résultats entre laboratoires.

Les espèces bactériennes peuvent aussi être identifiées en utilisant la technique de biologie moléculaire PCR (*Polymerase Chain Reaction*). Une des stratégies possibles est d'utiliser la PCR pour amplifier un gène spécifique à une espèce recherchée. Une amplification signera la présence de la bactérie recherchée dans le produit analysé. Cette méthode est souvent utilisée en routine dans les laboratoires de microbiologie. Les développements récents de la PCR multiplex permettent d'identifier, de géotyper et de quantifier rapidement plusieurs cibles d'ADN simultanément dans une seule réaction. La qPCR multiplex est particulièrement bien adaptée à des applications telles que le diagnostic syndromique (e.g. détection des souches toxigènes chez *C. diphtheriae* [161]). L'avantage principal des méthodes PCR est leur grande sensibilité et leur flexibilité dans le choix des cibles.

Plus récemment, la spectrométrie de masse MALDI-TOF (*Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption Ionization-Time Of Flight*) a révolutionné le flux d'analyse de nombreux laboratoires de microbiologie clinique pour l'identification bactérienne au niveau de l'espèce. La spectrométrie de masse est une technique d'analyse à haut débit basée sur l'ionisation et la séparation des ions. Elle est basée sur la détermination de profils de composants bactériens (essentiellement les protéines des ribosomes), sous forme de protéines directement extraites de bactéries intactes, qui sont comparés à une base de données de référence pour l'identification [162].

2.3.2. L'identification des souches sur la base de classifications génomiques

Les méthodes d'identification des souches sont très dépendantes du système de classification utilisé. Par exemple, les classifications phylogénétiques impliquent la définition de variations (SNPs canoniques ou diagnostics) qui sont des marqueurs de branches, lignées ou variants, et qui peuvent être utilisés pour des tests moléculaires ou une détection bioinformatique automatisée dans les séquences génomiques.

Des approches *ad hoc* peuvent également être utilisées pour les groupes clonaux importants ; des tests moléculaires ont ainsi été développés à partir de gènes spécifiques à la lignée ST258 chez *K. pneumoniae* [163].

Toutefois, les méthodes d'identification des souches reposent le plus souvent sur des outils bioinformatiques effectuant également la classification et la nomenclature. C'est le cas par exemple des plateformes EnteroBase [164] (<https://enterobase.warwick.ac.uk/>) ou BIGSdb [165] (<https://bigfdb.pasteur.fr/> et <https://pubmlst.org/software/bigfdb/>), qui comprennent des fonctions d'identification des génomes en les comparant au contenu de bases de données MLST ou cgMLST.

Notons aussi l'existence d'autres plateformes dédiées à l'identification génomique des souches (mais découplées des plateformes de définition des souches), telles que PathogenWatch (<https://pathogen.watch/>) ou la plateforme *Center for Genomic Epidemiology* du DTU (<https://www.genomicpidemiology.org/>). Pour ces dernières, les nomenclatures sources de BIGSdb ou PathogenWatch sont synchronisées, l'identification automatique des STs ou groupes clonaux étant effectuée par des fonctions *ad hoc*.

Dans le cadre de cette thèse, un nouveau système de classification des souches (sur la base des génomes) a été développé, puis intégré dans la plateforme BIGSdb (<https://bigfdb.pasteur.fr/klebsiella/>) en collaboration avec son développeur

(Keith Jolley - University of Oxford). Cette réalisation fournit à la communauté scientifique un moyen simple et efficace pour identifier des groupes nouvellement définis (groupes de LIN codes définis par leur préfixe, cf. Chapitre 3).

2.4. La taxonomie des espèces et des souches chez *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* et *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

2.4.1. Diversité des Corynébactéries du complexe *diphtheriae*

L'espèce *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* fait partie de la famille des *Corynebacteriaceae*. Cette espèce appartient au groupe taxonomique appelé *Corynebacterium* du complexe *diphtheriae* (ou *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* complex, Cdc). Cette appellation fait référence à l'ensemble des espèces responsables de la diphtérie et ayant la capacité à porter la toxine diphtérique.

Ce groupe taxonomique regroupe six espèces :

- *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*
- *Corynebacterium belfantii* (décrite en 2018, [8])
- *Corynebacterium rouxii* (décrite en 2020, cf. Chapitre 5)
- *Corynebacterium ulcerans*
- *Corynebacterium silvaticum* (décrite en 2020, [10])
- *Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis*

Figure 15. Arbre phylogénétique du genre *Corynebacterium* montrant les relations phylogénétiques entre *C. diphtheriae*, les membres du groupe Cdc (branches rouges) et plusieurs espèces représentatives (branches noires). Cet arbre a été inféré à partir de 148 génomes de souches types du genre *Corynebacterium* et enraciné à l'aide d'un groupe externe de 13 espèces de *Corynebacteriales* (branches grises). La barre d'échelle représente 0.025 substitutions nucléotidiques par position chromosomique.

2.4.2. Diversité du complexe d'espèces *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

Klebsiella pneumoniae appartient à la famille des *Enterobacteriaceae*, qui comprend également les genres bien connus *Salmonella* et *Escherichia*. Depuis la description des premières souches de *K. pneumoniae* dans les années 1880, plusieurs espèces ont été décrites et rattachées au genre *Klebsiella*, la définition taxonomique du genre ayant évolué continuellement. Initialement basée sur des critères phénotypiques et sur les pathologies associées aux isolats, cette nomenclature a été progressivement affinée grâce à l'apport des tests d'hybridation ADN-ADN et du séquençage génomique.

Le complexe *K. pneumoniae* (KpSC) comprend actuellement différentes espèces et sous-espèces, appelées phylogroupes. L'appellation KpSC n'est pas une désignation taxonomique formelle. Cependant elle fait généralement référence aux espèces étroitement apparentées et qui partagent une ANI de 95 à 96 % avec *K. pneumoniae sensu stricto*.

2.4.2.1. Les phylogroupes du complexe

Le complexe d'espèces *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (KpSC) inclut sept membres [80] :

- *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (Kp1)
- *Klebsiella quasipneumoniae* subsp. *quasipneumoniae* (Kp2, décrit en 2014 [78])
- *Klebsiella quasipneumoniae* subsp. *similipneumoniae* (Kp4, décrit en 2014 [78])
- *Klebsiella variicola* subsp. *variicola* (Kp3, décrit en 2004 [166, 167])
- *Klebsiella variicola* subsp. *tropica* (Kp5, décrit en 2019 [167])
- *Klebsiella quasivariicola* (Kp6, décrit en 2017 [168])
- *Klebsiella africana* (Kp7, décrit en 2019 [167])

Figure 16. Arbre phylogénétique du genre *Klebsiella* montrant les relations phylogénétiques entre *K. pneumoniae*, les membres du groupe KpSC (branches rouges), plusieurs espèces représentatives du genre *Klebsiella* (branches noires) et différents autres genres de la famille *Enterobacteriaceae* (branches grises). La barre d'échelle représente 0.02 substitutions nucléotidiques par position chromosomique.

2.4.2.2. Lignées ou clones au sein des phylogroupes

L'application à large échelle des techniques MLST a amené à définir plus de 5000 STs pour le complexe d'espèces *K. pneumoniae* (Kp). Parmi ceux-ci, un certain nombre de ST majeurs ont été identifiés de par leur importance médicale et épidémiologique. Ils sont typiquement considérés comme appartenant à deux groupes, les clones multirésistants et les clones dit hypervirulents (voir intro 1.2. *K. pneumoniae*).

Nous donnons ici un exemple en discutant les limitations de l'approche MLST pour la classification des souches de *K. pneumoniae*.

Groupe clonal 258. L'augmentation mondiale des souches de cKP ou mdrKp est surtout lié à l'expansion des souches appartenant à un nombre réduit de CG à haut-risque (CG14, CG15, CG101, CG147 ou CG258). Elles sont signalées dans le monde entier et sont liées à la propagation des BLSE et des carbapénémases, avec des associations spécifiques (par exemple, CG15 et CTX-M-15 ; CG258 et KPC ; CG101 et OXA-48) [80].

CG258 est un groupe clonal intrigant en raison de sa forte diffusion et de son succès, et est l'un des CG les mieux étudiées parmi Kp. Ce CG inclut différents STs, les plus fréquents étant ST258, ST11 et ST512 [169]. Le plus répandu, ST258, est apparu cliniquement en 2000. Il s'agit d'un hybride apparu après un événement de méga-recombinaison entre deux clones parentaux de *K. pneumoniae* (ST11 et ST442)[170]. ST258 est lui-même divisé en deux clades en fonction du type de capsule. ST512 est issu du clade II de ST258 via une seule variation de locus, et héberge principalement le gène bla_{KPC-3}. La majorité des membres du CG258 sont multirésistants en raison de la présence de nombreux gènes de RAM dans leurs génomes [169].

Comprendre les caractéristiques uniques épidémiques des clones (et des ST qui les composent) contribue à comprendre leur succès et aidera à prévenir leur propagation.

Des limitations à la nomenclature basée sur les 7-gènes MLST sont apparentes dans le cas du CG258. En effet, il existe de nombreuses lignées au sein du ST11, et ce nom unique ne permet pas de les différencier. Par ailleurs, des ST distincts ont évolué au sein du groupe CG258 (ST340 par exemple). Or ces dénominations basées sur les sept gènes MLST ne permettent pas de se rendre compte des relations évolutives, de la diversité ou de la similarité entre les souches.

Figure 17. Minimum spanning tree (MSTree) sur la base des profils alléliques de *Kp*. (A) Minimum spanning tree sur la base du schéma 7-gènes MLST. (B) Minimum spanning tree sur la base du schéma 629-gènes cgMLST. Coloration en fonction des espèces.

La Figure 17 illustre que la résolution basée sur les sept gènes MLST (Figure 17A) ne permet pas de distinguer la diversité du CG258, perceptible via le cgMLST (Figure 17B). De plus, la nomenclature ST ne reflète pas du tout les relations phylogénétiques (cf. Chapitre 2).

VUE D'ENSEMBLE DU PROJET

Ce projet comporte trois parties liées.

La **première partie** est l'étude des souches résistantes aux antibiotiques grâce à la génomique comparative, en utilisant l'espèce *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* comme modèle. *C. diphtheriae* demeure actuellement peu étudié en comparaison avec d'autres pathogènes tels que *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. Un grand nombre de génomes ont donc été analysés afin de mieux décrire la diversité des populations et de la dynamique évolutive de *C. diphtheriae*.

La **seconde** (et principale) **partie** consiste en l'élaboration d'un concept de nomenclature de souches, accompagné du développement d'outils bioinformatiques dédiés. Le nouveau système de nomenclature proposé a été ensuite employé pour mieux caractériser les souches des deux agents pathogènes modèles de cette thèse.

Enfin, la **troisième partie** consiste en l'application des nomenclatures et l'étude de la résistance aux antibiotiques dans divers cas de figure liés à la surveillance épidémiologie.

La première partie est organisé en deux chapitres.

Le **Chapitre 1** est l'étude des bases moléculaires de la résistance chez *C. diphtheriae*. Dans ce contexte, une analyse des associations de phénotypes de sensibilité aux antimicrobiens, la production de toxine diphtérique et les caractéristiques génomiques chez *C. diphtheriae* a été réalisée.

Le **Chapitre 2** présente le développement d'un outil de génotypage conçu spécifiquement pour *C. diphtheriae*. Cette réalisation bioinformatique consolide la détection et le génotypage des principaux facteurs de virulence et des gènes de résistance, des nomenclatures (ST, MLSL, ...) à partir d'assemblages de génomes. Cet outil permet également de prédire les biovars, ainsi que le degré de toxicité du gène *tox*.

La deuxième partie est organisé en trois chapitres.

Le **Chapitre 3** présente une approche de classification et de nomenclature génomique largement applicable pour les souches bactériennes, en utilisant comme modèle l'important pathogène *K. pneumoniae*. Il détaille la conception d'un système de code-barres double qui combine le regroupement par Single Linkage Multilevel (MLSL) et les LINs (Life Identification Number), sur la base d'un schéma de typage de séquence multilocus du core génome (cgMLST) de 629 gènes.

Le **Chapitre 4** repose sur l'étude de la structure phylogénétique de *C. diphtheriae* grâce à la mise en œuvre du schéma cgMLST. Il présente également une redéfinition de sa taxonomie génomique et de la nomenclature de ses souches.

Le **Chapitre 5** met en évidence (par analyses génomiques et caractérisations biochimiques) la découverte d'une nouvelle espèce au sein du complexe diphtérique, *Corynebacterium rouxii*.

Enfin la dernière partie est organisée en trois chapitres.

Le **Chapitre 6** est l'étude de l'épidémie de diphtérie déclarée au Yémen en octobre 2017.

Le **Chapitre 7** est l'étude de la sous-lignée SL453 de *C. diphtheriae*.

Le **Chapitre 8** est l'étude d'une cohorte de patients en Nouvelle-Calédonie.

Le **Chapitre 9** est l'étude d'une série de cas de souches de *Corynebacterium* du complexe *diphtheriae* chez les animaux.

PARTIE I : L'ÉMERGENCE ET ÉVOLUTION DE LA RÉSISTANCE BACTÉRIENNE AUX ANTIBIOTIQUES

Chapitre 1 : Génomique des populations et résistance aux antimicrobiens chez *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*

Titre de l'article

Population genomics and antimicrobial resistance in *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*

Résumé

Corynebacterium diphtheriae, l'agent de la diphtérie, est une espèce bactérienne génétiquement diverse. Bien que la résistance aux antimicrobiens soit apparue contre plusieurs médicaments, y compris la pénicilline de première intention, les déterminants génomiques et la dynamique de la population de la résistance sont largement inconnus pour ce pathogène humain négligé.

Ici, nous avons analysé les associations entre des phénotypes de sensibilité aux antimicrobiens, de production de toxine diphtérique et des caractéristiques génomiques chez *C. diphtheriae*. Nous avons utilisé 247 souches collectées sur plusieurs décennies dans plusieurs régions du monde, dont les 163 isolats cliniques collectés prospectivement de 2008 à 2017 en France métropolitaine et DOM-TOM.

L'analyse phylogénétique a révélé plusieurs sous-lignées à ramification profonde, regroupées en une lignée Mitis fortement associée à la production de toxine diphtérique et une lignée Gravis largement négative au gène de la toxine avec peu d'isolats producteurs de toxines, y compris la souche épidémique de l'ex-Union soviétique des années 1990. La distribution des phénotypes de sensibilité a permis de proposer des seuils écologiques pour la plupart des 19 agents testés, définissant ainsi la résistance antimicrobienne acquise. La résistance à la pénicilline a été trouvée dans 17,2 % des isolats prospectifs. Dix-sept (10,4 %) isolats prospectifs étaient multirésistants (≥ 3 catégories d'antimicrobiens), dont quatre isolats résistants à la pénicilline et aux macrolides. La recombinaison homologue était fréquente ($r/m = 5$) et le transfert horizontal de gènes a contribué à l'émergence de la résistance antimicrobienne dans plusieurs sous-lignées. La cartographie des associations à l'échelle du génome a révélé des facteurs génétiques de résistance, notamment une protéine accessoire de liaison à la pénicilline (PBP2m) située dans divers contextes génomiques. Le gène *pbp2m* est répandu dans d'autres espèces de *Corynebacterium* et son expression dans *C. glutamicum* a démontré son effet contre plusieurs bêta-lactamines. Un nouveau plasmide multirésistant de *C. diphtheriae* de 73 kb a été découvert.

Ce travail révèle la dynamique de la résistance antimicrobienne chez *C. diphtheriae* dans le contexte de la structure phylogénétique, du biovar et de la production de toxine diphtérique et fournit un cadre pour analyser la diphtérie réémergente.

Contributions personnelles

- Réalisation de l'ensemble des analyses bio-informatiques : analyse des données génomiques des isolats de l'étude, construction de la phylogénie, étude d'association pan-génomique (à l'échelle des gènes et des SNPs)
- Réalisation des figures 1 à 6 et des figures S2 à S10 et de la figure S12
- Réalisation des tableaux S1 à S6

RESEARCH

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Population genomics and antimicrobial resistance in *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*

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Abstract

Background: *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*, the agent of diphtheria, is a genetically diverse bacterial species. Although antimicrobial resistance has emerged against several drugs including first-line penicillin, the genomic determinants and population dynamics of resistance are largely unknown for this neglected human pathogen.

Methods: Here, we analyzed the associations of antimicrobial susceptibility phenotypes, diphtheria toxin production, and genomic features in *C. diphtheriae*. We used 247 strains collected over several decades in multiple world regions, including the 163 clinical isolates collected prospectively from 2008 to 2017 in France mainland and overseas territories.

Results: Phylogenetic analysis revealed multiple deep-branching sublineages, grouped into a Mitis lineage strongly associated with diphtheria toxin production and a largely toxin gene-negative Gravis lineage with few toxin-producing isolates including the 1990s ex-Soviet Union outbreak strain. The distribution of susceptibility phenotypes allowed proposing ecological cutoffs for most of the 19 agents tested, thereby defining acquired antimicrobial resistance. Penicillin resistance was found in 17.2% of prospective isolates. Seventeen (10.4%) prospective isolates were multidrug-resistant (≥ 3 antimicrobial categories), including four isolates resistant to penicillin and macrolides. Homologous recombination was frequent ($r/m = 5$), and horizontal gene transfer contributed to the emergence of antimicrobial resistance in multiple sublineages. Genome-wide association mapping uncovered genetic factors of resistance, including an accessory penicillin-binding protein (PBP2m) located in diverse genomic contexts. Gene *pbp2m* is widespread in other *Corynebacterium* species, and its expression in *C. glutamicum* demonstrated its effect against several beta-lactams. A novel 73-kb *C. diphtheriae* multiresistance plasmid was discovered.

Conclusions: This work uncovers the dynamics of antimicrobial resistance in *C. diphtheriae* in the context of phylogenetic structure, biovar, and diphtheria toxin production and provides a blueprint to analyze re-emerging diphtheria.

Keywords: *C. diphtheriae*, Antibiotic resistance, Genome-wide association study, Phylogeny, Mobile genetic element, Biovar

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Background

Diphtheria, if untreated, is one of the most severe bacterial infections of humans. It typically affects the upper respiratory tract causing pseudomembrane formation, sometimes leading to suffocation and death. The infection can be complicated by systemic symptoms, caused by the diphtheria toxin. Other forms of disease are skin and invasive infections, including endocarditis [1, 2].

The agent of diphtheria is *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*, a member of the phylum Actinomycetes [3, 4]. The diphtheria toxin, encoded by the *tox* gene, is carried by lysogenized corynephages within the chromosome of some *C. diphtheriae* strains [5, 6]. Concern exists about the possibility of lysogenic conversion of previously non-toxigenic strains during colonization, infection, or transmission chains [7]. However, knowledge on the microevolutionary dynamics between *tox*-positive and *tox*-negative strains is limited. The high genetic diversity of *C. diphtheriae* strains underlies their variable colonization, adhesion, and pathogenicity properties [8–10]. Although three main biovars (Mitis, Gravis, and Belfanti) are distinguished since the 1950s, their phylogenetic relationships are poorly defined [11–13].

Diphtheria used to be one of the deadliest infections in young children but has been largely controlled by vaccination with the highly effective toxoid vaccine [14]. Even so, thousands of cases of diphtheria are still reported annually [15], and large outbreaks can quickly follow the disruption of public health systems [14, 16–18]. In countries with high vaccination coverage, diphtheria cases are associated with travel and migration from endemic regions [19–21]. As diphtheria vaccination is performed using an inactivated form of diphtheria toxin, it is not considered to prevent asymptomatic colonization and silent transmission of the pathogen, which still circulates and is the object of intense epidemiological surveillance [4]. However, vaccine preparations may include other antigens, and the impact of vaccination on *C. diphtheriae* evolution deserves further studies [22].

Clinical management of infections with toxigenic isolates includes treatment with diphtheria antitoxin (DAT), which can prevent or reduce the systemic effects of the toxin [4]. Nevertheless, antimicrobial treatment is critical in the clinical management of both *tox*-positive and *tox*-negative infections, as it contributes to the elimination of the bacteria within the patient and limits transmission to novel individuals [23]. With DAT production being threatened [24], antimicrobial treatment might become even more critical in diphtheria therapy.

Penicillin is the first-line therapeutics to treat diphtheria, with erythromycin being recommended in case of allergy [25]. Both antimicrobial agents are generally effective for the treatment of diphtheria [23, 26]. However, reduced susceptibility or full resistance of *C. diphtheriae* to

penicillin, erythromycin, and other antimicrobial agents, sometimes combined in multidrug-resistant strains, has been reported from multiple world regions [23, 26–35].

Antimicrobial resistance genes have been described in *C. diphtheriae*, including the erythromycin resistance gene *ermX* on plasmid pNG2 [36] and genes *dfrA16*, *qacH*, and *sul1* carried on a class 1 integron, mobilized by IS6100 [37]. However, the prevalence and phylogenetic distribution of resistance genes in *C. diphtheriae* clinical isolates are unknown. Six chromosomal penicillin-binding proteins (PBPs) have been reported in *C. diphtheriae* [38], but so far, no association between *pbp* or other genetic variation and penicillin resistance has been described. Understanding the genetic basis of antimicrobial resistance in *C. diphtheriae* would improve our ability to diagnose and track its spread.

The aims of this study were (i) to characterize antimicrobial resistance phenotypes in a large collection of *C. diphtheriae* strains with diverse geographical and temporal origins and to uncover genomic determinants of resistance and (ii) to analyze the population structure of *C. diphtheriae* and define the associations between antimicrobial resistance, diphtheria toxin production, biovars, and phylogenetic sublineages.

Methods

Corynebacterium diphtheriae isolates and strains

A collection of 247 *C. diphtheriae* isolates were included (Additional file 1: Table S1), corresponding to three subsets. First, we included 163 clinical isolates (recent clinical isolates subset, Additional file 1: Table S1) collected prospectively between 2008 and 2017 by the French National Reference Center for Corynebacteria of the *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* complex (NRC-CCD). These isolates represented all isolates received at the NRC-CCD that corresponded to the *C. diphtheriae* species (*C. belfantii*, *C. ulcerans*, *C. pseudotuberculosis*, or other corynebacteria were excluded). They were collected from cutaneous ($n = 136$), respiratory ($n = 23$), and other (bones, blood; $n = 4$) infections. Of these, 74 were from Mainland France and 89 from French overseas territories, including Mayotte ($n = 50$), New Caledonia ($n = 19$), La Réunion Island ($n = 11$), French Guiana ($n = 4$), French Polynesia ($n = 3$), and Guadeloupe ($n = 1$); one isolate received from Institut Pasteur in Madagascar was also included (Fig. 1). Four isolates from New Caledonia collected between 2002 and 2006 (02-0322, 02-0338, 03-1641, and 06-1569) were included in a previous study [39]; the trimethoprim- and sulfamethoxazole-resistant isolate FRC0024 was previously shown to harbor an integron with gene *drfA16* [37].

Second, we included 15 clinical isolates collected in France between 1981 and 1991, 11 of which had been deposited in the Collection de l'Institut Pasteur (CIP;

historical clinical isolates subset in Additional file 1: Table S1).

Third, to increase the genetic diversity and geographic range of the sample, the 65 available reference strains of ribotypes that belong to *C. diphtheriae* were included [40]. These reference strains represent an international collection of isolates collected over several decades and originating from multiple world regions including the Americas, Europe, Asia, Africa, and Oceania. Our subcultures of these strains were controlled for *tox* gene presence, toxin production, and biovar, leading to modifications of published characteristics in some instances (Additional file 1: Table S1; Fig. 1). Finally, four reference strains were included: strain NCTC13129, which is used as genomic sequence reference [38]; strain NCTC10648, which is used as the *tox*-positive and toxinogenic reference strain in PCR and Elek tests, respectively; strain NCTC11397^T, which is the taxonomic type strain of the *C. diphtheriae* species; and the vaccine production strain PW8, which corresponds to CIP A102 [41]. This third subset is referred to as “ribotype and reference strains” subset (Additional file 1: Table S1).

Bacterial cultures, identification, and biovar

Bacteria were cultivated on Trypto-Casein-Soy (TCS) agar for 24 h at 35–37 °C. Bacterial identification was performed at the NRC-CCD as described previously [42] by multiplex polymerase chain reaction (PCR) combining a *dtxR* gene fragment specific for *C. diphtheriae* and a multiplex PCR that targets a fragment of the *pld* gene specific for *C. pseudotuberculosis*, the gene *rpoB* (amplified in all species of the *C. diphtheriae* complex) and a fragment of 16S rRNA gene specific for *C. pseudotuberculosis* and *C. ulcerans*, respectively. Isolates collected since 2014 were confirmed as *C. diphtheriae* by matrix-assisted laser desorption-ionization time-of-flight mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS) using Bruker technology. In order to exclude strains initially identified as *C. diphtheriae* but now classified as *C. belfantii* [42] or *C. rouxii* [43], genome-wide average nucleotide identity (ANI) was used as described previously [42]. Strains were characterized biochemically for pyrazinamidase, urease, and nitrate reductase and for utilization of maltose and trehalose using API Coryne strips (BioMérieux, Marcy l’Etoile, France) and the Rosco Diagnostica reagents (Eurobio, Les Ulis, France). The Hiss serum water test was used for glycogen fermentation. The biovar of isolates was determined based on the combination of nitrate reductase (positive in Mitis and Gravis, negative in Belfanti) and glycogen fermentation (positive in Gravis only). The rare biovar Intermedius was not identified, as its distinction from other biovars is based on colony morphology, which is considered subjective, or on lipophily, which was not tested.

Determination of the presence of the *tox* gene

Determination of the diphtheria toxin gene (*tox* gene) presence was achieved by a conventional *tox* PCR assay [44], while its phenotypic production was assessed by the modified Elek test [45]. We also confirmed *tox* PCR results by BLASTN (query: *tox* gene sequence from strain NCTC13129, RefSeq accession number: DIP_RS12515) analysis of the genomic assemblies.

Antimicrobial susceptibility testing

Phenotypic susceptibility was tested for the following agents: penicillin G (10 IU), amoxicillin, oxacillin, cefotaxime, imipenem, erythromycin, azithromycin, clarithromycin, spiramycin, pristinamycin, kanamycin, gentamicin, rifampicin, tetracycline, ciprofloxacin, clindamycin, sulfonamide, trimethoprim, and trimethoprim + sulfamethoxazole. The 19 antimicrobial agents tested (Table S1) corresponded to seven classes, as described hereafter: β -lactams: penicillin G (PEN), amoxicillin (AMX), oxacillin (OXA), cefotaxime (CFT), imipenem (IMP); macrolides: azithromycin (AZM), clarithromycin (CLR), erythromycin (ERT), and spiramycin (SPR); lincosamides: clindamycin (CLD); streptogramins: pristinamycin (PRT); aminoglycosides: gentamicin (GEN) and kanamycin (KAN); folate pathway inhibitors: sulfonamide (SUL), trimethoprim (TMP), and trimethoprim + sulfamethoxazole (cotrimoxazole, TMP-STX); ansamycins: rifampicin (RIF); tetracyclines: tetracycline (TET); and fluoroquinolones: ciprofloxacin (CIP).

Antimicrobial susceptibility was determined using the disk diffusion method with impregnated paper disks (Bio-Rad, Marnes-la-Coquette, France) on Mueller Hinton agar plates supplemented with 5% of sheep blood and 20 mg/L β -NAD, as recommended. Minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) were determined using E-test strips (BioMérieux, Marcy l’Etoile, France). The control strain used is *Streptococcus pneumoniae* ATCC 49619. The zone diameter (ZD) data were interpreted into S, I, and R categories in the following way. First, we used the CA-SFM/EUCAST V.1.0 (January 2019) document (https://www.sfm-microbiologie.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/CASFM2019_V1.0.pdf), which contains interpretative criteria for *Corynebacterium* spp. only for CIP, GEN, CLD, TET, RIF, and TMP-STX. Second, for the other agents, we used the interpretative criteria published in Table III of the CA-SFM 2013 recommendations (https://resapath.anses.fr/resapath_uploadfiles/files/Documents/2013_CASFM.pdf). Note that for RIF, we used the 2013 breakpoints, as they fitted better with the observed distribution of ZD values. Clarithromycin breakpoints were taken from those for erythromycin, as recommended. The breakpoint for oxacillin was derived from the one used for *Staphylococcus* spp. ZD interpretation breakpoints are given in Additional file 1: Table S2.

Penicillin susceptibility was initially determined using 10-UI (6 µg) disks (resistance breakpoint, 18 mm), but CA-SFM/EUCAST recommendations were changed in 2014 to use 1-UI disks, while the resistance breakpoint was increased from 18 to 29 mm. As all *C. diphtheriae* strains end up in the resistant category following this recommendation, E-test strips were used to define the penicillin MIC since 2014 (Additional file 1: Table S2: isolates starting from FRC0259); the EUCAST breakpoint of 0.125 g/L was used as a cutoff. Penicillin E-test was also performed systematically for strains tested as resistant before 2014 (using 10-UI disks), as well as for some susceptible isolates (Additional file 1: Table S1).

Multidrug-resistant *C. diphtheriae* (MDR-DIP) were defined as strains resistant to three or more antimicrobial agent categories (defined in Additional file 1: Table S2), excluding intrinsic resistance to fosfomycin [46]. Note that we used ecological cutoffs rather than currently proposed clinical breakpoints (see Additional file 1: Table S2 for a comparison of both types of breakpoints).

Whole-genome sequencing by Illumina and Oxford Nanopore Technologies

DNA was extracted from broth cultures, by making use of DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit (QIAGEN, Hilden, Germany). However, a lysis step was added to the extraction protocol described by the manufacturer as previously described [47]: a 1-µL loopful of bacterial colonies was emulsified in 180 µL of lysis buffer containing 20 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8, 2 mM EDTA, 1.2% Triton X-100, and 20 mg/mL lysozyme, in a DNase/RNase-free 1.5-mL Eppendorf tube and incubated in a heating block at 37 °C for 1 h, with mixing every 20 min. After extraction, DNA concentration was measured with the Qubit 3.0 Fluorometer (Invitrogen), employing the Qubit dsDNA BR Assay Kit (Invitrogen). Besides, the DNA quality was verified using a D-One spectrophotometer (Nanodrop). Multiplexed paired-end libraries (2 × 150 bp) were prepared using the Nextera XT DNA kit (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA) and eventually sequenced with an Illumina NextSeq-500 instrument at a minimum of 50× coverage depth. Trimming and clipping were performed using AlienTrimmer v0.4.0 [48]. Redundant or over-represented reads were reduced using the khmer software package v1.3 [49]. Finally, sequencing errors were corrected using Musket v1.1 [50]. A de novo assembly was performed for each strain using SPAdes v3.12.0 [51]. The genomic sequences of the four reference strains were retrieved from public repositories (Additional file 1: Table S1).

Additionally, the multidrug-resistant isolate FRC0402 was subjected to long-read sequencing using Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT). Genomic DNA was extracted using the phenol-chloroform protocol combined

with Phase Lock Gel tubes (Qiagen GmbH). Libraries were prepared using a 1D ligation sequencing kit (SQK-LSK-108) without fragmentation and sequenced using a MinION FLO-MIN-106 flow cell. Finally, ONT and Illumina short reads were combined to generate a hybrid assembly using Unicycler v0.4.4 (normal assembly mode, default parameters).

Phylogeny, recombination, and genomic sequence analyses

We built a core genome multiple sequence alignment (cg-MSA) from the assembled genome sequences. For this, the genome sequences were annotated using PROKKA v1.14.2 [52] with default parameters, resulting in GFF files. Roary v3.6 [53] was used to define protein-coding gene clusters, with a threshold set at 70% amino acid identity. Core genes were defined as being present in 95% of genomes and were concatenated into a cg-MSA by Roary. ClonalFrameML v1.11 [54] was used to build a phylogenetic tree based on the cg-MSA, which quantifies and accounts for the effects of recombination events. PhyML v20131022 [55] was used to build an initial tree. To evaluate bootstrap support, IQtree version 2 [56] with best-fit model GTR+F+R10 was used.

We used Kleborate v1.0.0-beta (<https://github.com/katholt/Kleborate>), with the --resistance option, to identify (identity > 80% and coverage > 90%) known resistance genes in *C. diphtheriae* genomic sequences, based on the August 1, 2019, update of the ARG-Annot database. We used BLASTN (identity > 80% and coverage > 95%) to search for the presence of the *tox* gene and of genes associated with biovar Gravis (DIP351, DIP354, and DIP357) and for nitrate utilization (*narKGHJI*).

MLST genotypes were defined using the international MLST scheme for *C. diphtheriae* and *C. ulcerans* [12].

Genome-wide association studies

The software treeWAS [57] was used to find genome-wide associations between either antimicrobial resistance phenotypes or biovar on the one hand and genetic variants (both core-genome SNPs and accessory genome gene presence/absence) on the other hand. Core-genome SNPs were derived either from a mapping approach (Samtools v1.9 and GATK v3.4-0), which comprises intergenic regions, or from the alignment of core coding sequences found using Roary. We ran treeWAS v1.1 with default parameters, using as input the previously computed ClonalFrameML phylogenetic tree and distribution of homoplasies, in order to account for both the population structure and effect of recombination. For this analysis, susceptibility phenotypes were classified into resistant or susceptible categories based on zone diameter phenotypes using the CA-SFM/EUCAST 2019 cutoffs (Fig. 3, Additional file 3: Table S3). The

seven chromosomal PBP coding sequences (including gene with locus tag RS14485 in RefSeq NC_002935.2, or DIP0637 in the original GenBank file, renamed by us as PBP4b) were extracted from the genomic sequences and translated into amino acid (AA) sequences, which were also analyzed for association with penicillin resistance.

Cloning and transformation experiments

For ectopic expression in *C. glutamicum*, the *pbp2m* gene was amplified from *C. diphtheriae* strain FRC0402 and put under the control of the inducible P_{gntK} promoter on the shuttle vector pTGR5 [58] (Additional file 4: Fig. S1). *pbp2m* was assembled in this plasmid by Gibson assembly using the primers PBPdi_Fw (CAA AGA AAG GAT AAG ACC ATA TGA TGA CTA AGC ACA ATC GTT TCC GTC), PBPdi_Rv (TAC CTT AAG CGG CCG CTT TAT TGA ATT CCA GAG AAT TTC TGA ACA TCC G), pTGRdi_Fw (TAA AGC GGC CGC TTA AGG TAC C), and pTGRdi_Rv (ATG GTC TTA TCC TTT CTT TGG TGG CG).

Escherichia coli CopyCutter EPI400 (Lucigen) was used for the cloning of the *pbp2m* gene and was grown in Luria-Bertani (LB) broth or agar plates at 37 °C supplemented with 50 µg/mL kanamycin. The pTGR5_ *pbp2m* plasmid was sequenced and electroporated into *Corynebacterium glutamicum* ATCC 13032. Positive colonies were grown in brain heart infusion (BHI) at 30 °C and 120 rpm supplemented with 25 µg/mL kanamycin and 1% (w/v) gluconate when required for ectopic expression of Pbp2m.

Mapping of SNPs on *C. diphtheriae* PBP sequences

Functional annotation of the different sequences was performed with InterPro [59]. Conserved transpeptidation motifs SxxK, SxN, and KTG were identified and mapped on the PBP sequences from *Corynebacteriales* based on the results of multiple sequence alignments performed with Clustal Omega [60]. When uncertainty between a transmembrane domain and a signal peptide existed, a decision was made based on the previous characterization of the homologous PBP in other *Corynebacteriales* in the literature.

Results

Provenance and microbiological characteristics of *C. diphtheriae* isolates

We studied 247 *C. diphtheriae* strains of diverse geographic and temporal origins (Fig. 1). This collection included 163 isolates prospectively collected between 2008 and 2017 from French mainland and overseas territories, 15 older (1981–2006) French clinical isolates, 65 ribotype reference strains [40], and 4 other reference strains. All isolates were confirmed as *C. diphtheriae* (excluding *C. belfantii* and *C. rouxii*) based on an average

nucleotide identity (ANI) value higher than 96% with the *C. diphtheriae* type strain NCTC11397^T.

Approximately one third ($n = 78$, 32%) of isolates were *tox*-positive (as defined by the detection of the *tox* gene by PCR), whereas the remaining 169 isolates (68%) were *tox*-negative. The proportions of *tox*-positive isolates were 42%, 34%, and 2% among reference strains, 2008–2017 clinical isolates, and older clinical isolates, respectively (Additional file 4: Fig. S2). Of the 78 *tox*-positive isolates, 17 (21.8%) were negative for toxin production and thus correspond to non-toxigenic toxin gene-bearing (NTTB) isolates. Six of the NTTB isolates had a stop codon within the *tox* gene sequence (Additional file 1: Table S1, Additional file 5: Table S4). However, for the 11 remaining strains, we found no explanation for the observed lack of toxin production.

Upon biotyping, 154 (62.3%) isolates belonged to biovar Mitis, 87 to biovar Gravis (35.2%), and 6 (2.4%) to biovar Belfanti (Additional file 1: Table S1). Biovar proportions were similar among the three datasets. Mitis isolates were more frequently *tox*-positive than Gravis isolates (56/154 versus 18/87, chi-squared test, p value 0.01; Additional file 4: Fig. S2). Among *tox*-positive isolates, NTTB were more frequent among Mitis isolates (13/56, 23.2%) than among Gravis isolates (1/18, 5.6%) although this difference was not statistically significant (p value 0.09). Three out of four *tox*-positive Belfanti isolates were NTTB.

Phylogenetic structure of *C. diphtheriae* and distribution of the toxin gene

To infer a phylogenetic tree, we first aimed to detect and remove homologous recombination events among *C. diphtheriae* genomic sequences. ClonalFrameML inferred a relative rate of recombination to mutation (R/θ) of 0.86, with an average length of recombination segments (δ) of 287 bp. The mean genetic distance between donor and recipient of recombination (ν) was estimated by ClonalFrameML to be 0.02, resulting in a relative impact of recombination to mutation in genomic diversification ($r/m = R/\theta \times \delta \times \nu$) of 5.01 [61].

The recombination-corrected phylogeny was similar to the uncorrected phylogeny but with shorter branches, as expected (Additional file 4: Fig. S3). The phylogeny, rooted with *C. belfantii* and *C. rouxii* (Additional file 4: Fig. S4), was star-like, with a multitude of sublineages branching off deeply. The deepest branching sublineages corresponded to two ribotype reference strains of biovar Mitis: CIP107521 (ribotype Dagestan) and CIP107534 (ribotype Kaliningrad). Remarkably, isolates of biovars Mitis and Gravis were mostly distributed in two distinct branches of the tree. We therefore named the two major branches, lineage Mitis (156 strains, of which 86% were of biovar Mitis) and lineage Gravis (91 strains, of which

77% were of biovar Gravis). The Gravis lineage branched off from within the Mitis lineage (Fig. 2; Additional file 4: Fig. S5). However, although most shallow branches were strongly supported, bootstrap support values of the deep nodes of the phylogeny were generally weak, implying that the position of the Gravis branch within the Mitis diversity was uncertain, as were the relative positions of the early-branching Gravis and Mitis sublineages (Additional file 4: Fig. S5, Fig. S6). Reference strains PW8 and NCTC11297^T belonged to the Mitis lineage, whereas NCTC13129 (from the ex-Soviet Union 1990's outbreak) and NCTC10648 belonged to the Gravis lineage. The Belfanti isolates were scattered in three distinct sublineages within the Mitis lineage and one within the Gravis lineage.

The isolates carrying the *tox* gene belonged mostly to the Mitis lineage (68 of 78, 87.2%), in which they were distributed in multiple sublineages. In the Mitis lineage, 69 (44.2%) were *tox*-positive. In contrast, within the Gravis lineage, only 10 (11%) isolates were *tox*-positive, and they corresponded to the earliest-branching Gravis sublineages with only one exception. Interestingly, this exception corresponded to the large ex-Soviet Union outbreak in the 1990s (Fig. 2; Additional file 4: Fig. S5). This phylogenetic pattern is consistent with an evolutionary scenario where Mitis is the ancestral biovar of *C. diphtheriae* and where Gravis evolved from the Mitis lineage as an initially *tox*-positive sublineage, with subsequent loss of the toxin gene. In this scenario, the ex-Soviet Union outbreak sublineage would have re-acquired the *tox* gene. All NTTB isolates belonged to the Mitis lineage except strain CIPA99 (ribotype Rhone, biovar Belfanti; Fig. 2), and they were distributed in multiple sublineages, showing convergent evolution towards the loss of toxin production.

Genetic events linked to biovar status

Biovar Mitis and Gravis are distinguished by the ability to utilize glycogen (positive in Gravis, negative in Mitis). The *spuA* gene, which codes for a putative alpha-1,6-glycosidase, was reported as being specific for biovar Gravis isolates [62]. Our genome-wide association study (GWAS) of accessory genes with the biovar phenotype revealed a strong association of a cluster of genes that includes *spuA* (DIP357; Additional file 4: Fig. S7) with biovar Gravis isolates, providing statistical support to the discovery of Santos et al. [62]. This association was stronger within the Gravis lineage; in contrast within the Mitis lineage, few (5 out of 17) of the biovar Gravis isolates possessed *spuA* (Fig. 2). GWAS analysis of core SNPs further demonstrated that a SNP (at position 324,487, Additional file 4: Fig. S7) downstream of the *spuA* cluster insertion point was also associated with biovar, suggesting homologous

recombination among core genes as a mechanism for the *spuA* cluster insertion event.

The nitrate reductase activity differentiates Mitis and Gravis isolates, which are positive, from Belfanti isolates, which are nitrate-negative. We found that the nitrate reduction *narKGHJI* gene cluster [62] was disrupted in three of the six isolates assigned to the biovar Belfanti: strains FRC0480 and FRC0481 had a G to A mutation at position 675 of the *narG* gene, leading to a stop codon, whereas in strain CIPA99, approximately 100 nucleotides were inserted at position 446 in *narG*. No molecular explanation was found for the lack of nitrate reductase ability of the three other Belfanti strains when scrutinizing the *narKGHJI* gene cluster and adjacent molybdenum cofactor biosynthesis genes [63].

Antimicrobial susceptibility variation

Susceptibility to 19 antimicrobial agents was determined for the 247 clinical isolates and reference strains (Additional file 3: Table S3). For each agent, the distribution of zone diameter (ZD) values (Fig. 3) revealed a predominant mode located towards the right end of the distribution. This mode likely corresponds to the natural susceptibility distribution within the *C. diphtheriae* population and was used to define tentative epidemiological cutoffs (ECOFFs, also called ecological cutoff [64]). The proposed ECOFFs and their comparison with clinical breakpoints are presented in Additional file 2: Table S2. For each antimicrobial agent except cefotaxime, this approach led to the identification of strains that had ZD values smaller than those in the main mode, thus potentially corresponding to acquired resistance (Fig. 3).

Penicillin was exceptional in that the predominant mode (centered around 36 mm) was less neatly defined, due to the partial overlap with a second mode of smaller diameter values centered around 24 mm. This second mode corresponds mostly to the "intermediate" interpretative category ($18 \leq \text{ZD} < 29$ mm) but also overlaps with the "resistant" category (< 18 mm). The distribution of ZD values for tetracycline also showed a clear second mode. For multiple other agents (amoxicillin, oxacillin, imipenem, kanamycin, rifampicin, ciprofloxacin, clindamycin and more evidently sulfonamide, trimethoprim, and the trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole combination), some strains had the minimal diameter (6 mm, corresponding to growth at the disk contact). For trimethoprim, we observed both a second mode centered around 14 mm and a group of even more resistant strains with growth at disk contact.

Antimicrobial resistance levels were similarly distributed between *tox*-positive and *tox*-negative isolates (Additional file 4: Fig. S8) as well as between the two main phylogenetic lineages or biovars (Additional file 4: Fig. S9; Additional file 1: Table S1). In particular, the

proportion of multidrug-resistant strains was not statistically different between biovars Mitis ($n = 14$) and Gravis ($n = 4$; chi-square test p value 0.2) or between *tox*-positive and *tox*-negative isolates (6 versus 12, p value 0.87).

Resistance rates were 17.2%, 2.5%, and 2.5% for penicillin, amoxicillin, and erythromycin, respectively, among the prospectively collected 2008–2017 clinical isolates (Fig. 4). Reference strains were generally susceptible to most agents, including penicillin, but were partially resistant to tetracycline (18%) and sulfonamide (35%). The resistance profile distribution showed that approximately half (121/247) of the strains had a fully susceptible phenotype, whereas 18 isolates (7.3%) were multidrug-resistant (Table S1). Notably, four isolates were resistant at the same time to penicillin and macrolides (Fig. 4 inset), and two of them (FRC0402 and FRC0466) additionally had a reduced susceptibility to amoxicillin. Two of these isolates (FRC0475 and FRC0478) were collected from a foot arch wound and in respiratory carriage in the same patient (French mainland, with recent travel from New Caledonia). The two others came from a

patient living in La Réunion Island (FRC0402) and from a patient living in Paris, who had recently traveled to Tunisia (FRC0466). Of the 18 multidrug-resistant isolates, 1 was a 1994 isolate from India and 17 belonged to the 2008–2017 prospective subset of clinical isolates (representing 10.4% of these). Isolates from La Réunion Island and mainland France showed resistance to multiple antimicrobial agents more often than isolates from other geographic origins (Fig. 1a, inset).

Genomic associations with antimicrobial resistance phenotypes

We first searched for the presence in the genomic sequences, of previously described antimicrobial resistance genes (ARGs). This approach led to the detection of 12 ARGs (Additional file 6: Table S5). We identified three tetracycline resistance genes (*tetW*, *tet33*, and *tetO*), four aminoglycoside resistance genes [*aph* (3′)-Ia, *aph* (3′)-Ib, *aph* (6)-Id, and *aadA1* = ant (3′)-Ia], and also *ermX*, *dfrA16*, *dfrA15b*, *dfrA1*, and *sulI* genes. We observed a strong correlation between the presence of ARGs and the

expected resistance phenotypes (Additional file 4: Fig. S10), particularly for *ermX* (macrolide resistance; phi coefficient = 0.66 with erythromycin resistance), *sul1* (sulfonamide resistance; phi = 0.80), and *aph (3')-Ia* (kanamycin resistance; phi = 0.84). In strains FRC0137 and FRC0375, this latter gene was linked to *aph (3')-Ib* (*strA*), *aph (6)-Id* (*strB*), and *ermX* on a Tn5432-like genomic region with an IS1249 insertion sequence [65]. The phylogenetic distribution of ARGs (Fig. 5; Additional file 4: Fig. S6) revealed their presence in multiple unrelated sublineages, consistent with independent acquisitions by horizontal gene transfer. Gene *ermX* was present either in proximity to gene *pbp2m* (see below) or in a fragmented insertion-sequence rich accessory region. Gene *dfrA16* was associated with *sul1* on a reported [37] class 1 integron (see the “Discovery of a multidrug-resistant conjugative plasmid carrying the gene *pbp2m*” section). Tetracycline resistance was associated either with the ribosomal protection protein genes *tet(O)* or *tet(W)* or with the efflux pump gene *tet33*. These three genes were present in distinct strain subsets and appear to contribute independently to tetracycline resistance in *C. diphtheriae* (Fig. 5); they were mostly associated with insertion sequences but not with other ARGs.

Next, in order to identify novel genetic determinants potentially associated with antimicrobial resistance in *C. diphtheriae*, a GWAS approach was followed, based on either core genome SNPs or accessory gene presence/absence. SNPs that were strongly associated with ciprofloxacin, trimethoprim, and rifampicin resistance were identified within genes for gyrase subunit A, dihydrofolate reductase, and RNA polymerase subunit B, respectively (Additional file 6: Table S5; Additional file 4: Fig. S11), consistent with known mechanisms and validating our approach. SNPs were also found to be associated with penicillin, kanamycin, and tetracycline resistance (Additional file 6: Table S5), but based on the annotations of the genes where they are located, the functional implications of these SNPs are unclear in these cases. No association was found for penicillin resistance within the core PBP genes using the genome-wide approach. However, using a concatenation of the amino acid sequences of the seven identified putative PBPs of *C. diphtheriae*, we identified amino acid positions that were statistically associated with penicillin resistance (Additional file 4: Fig. S12). The identified positions were mapped onto the predicted functional domains of the different PBPs (Additional file 4: Fig. S13) revealing several mutation hotspots. A number of significant SNPs were

Fig. 5 (See legend on next page.)

(See figure on previous page.)

Fig. 5 Phylogenetic distribution of antimicrobial resistance phenotypes and genes. The phylogenetic tree is the same as in Fig. 1; the Mitis branch is in purple, the Gravis branch in green. To the right of the tree, each bloc indicates first the phenotype (red, resistant; see key) and relevant corresponding genotypes (orange, gene or mutation presence)

found within the transpeptidase (TP) domains of the different PBPs, but none of the mutations mapped to the conserved transpeptidation motif. Other mutations were found outside the TP domains, for instance, in the transglycosylase and PASTA domains of PBP1b or in the dimerization domain of PBP2b.

GWAS analysis of accessory genes demonstrated significant associations with phenotypic resistance. Associated genes included those mentioned above for erythromycin, tetracycline, kanamycin, sulfonamide, and trimethoprim (Additional file 6: Table S5), showing that these genes are the main mechanisms of resistance to these antimicrobial agents in *C. diphtheriae* populations. In addition, an accessory penicillin-binding protein gene (which we name *pbp2m*) was strongly associated with penicillin resistance. This gene is described in more detail below.

Discovery of a penicillin-binding protein (PBP2m) associated with penicillin resistance

The PBP gene *pbp2m* was observed in 11 isolates, 8 of which were penicillin resistant with minimum inhibitory concentrations (MIC) ranging from 0.19 to 1.5 mg/L. Two of these isolates were also resistant to amoxicillin and one was in addition resistant to oxacillin

(Additional file 2: Table S2). The phylogenetic distribution of *pbp2m*-positive strains was compatible with multiple independent acquisitions of the gene through horizontal gene transfer (Fig. 5). Sequence analysis showed that the newly identified PBP2m is almost identical (3 differences out of 593 amino acids, 99.5%) to PBP2c from *C. jeikeium*, a class B PBP with an N-terminal signal peptide followed by a lipobox domain and the C-terminal transpeptidase domain (Additional file 4: Fig. S13). The *C. jeikeium* PBP2c is a low-affinity PBP and was associated with beta-lactam resistance in *C. jeikeium* [66].

To demonstrate the role of PBP2m in penicillin resistance, its gene was PCR amplified from FRC0402 and cloned into the pTGR5 plasmid (Additional file 4: Fig. S1). Transformation of the plasmid into *C. glutamicum* strain ATCC 13032 raised the MIC for penicillin from 0.125 to 1.5 mg/L, and the MICs of the other beta-lactams amoxicillin, oxacillin, and cefotaxime also increased importantly (Fig. 6; Additional file 7: Table S6). In contrast, MICs of non-beta-lactam agents were not changed. Imipenem was less effective against the transformant based on disk diffusion but not based on E-test. Transformation with the empty plasmid used as control

did not affect the MIC of any agent. These results show that PBP2m confers resistance to a broad range of beta-lactams.

Discovery of a multidrug-resistant conjugative plasmid carrying the gene *pbp2m*

Strain FRC0402, a *tox*-negative isolate from La Réunion Island, stood out as being resistant to 12 agents (Fig. 4 inset). In addition to *pbp2m*, this isolate carried genes *sul1*, *ermX*, and *dfrA16* and a *tetA* family *tet(Z)*-like (71%) tetracycline efflux gene. To define the genomic

context of resistance genes, a complete genome sequence was obtained. The assembly revealed a chromosome of 2,397,465 bp and a circular plasmid of 73,763 bp (Fig. 7), which we propose to name pLRPD (for large resistance plasmid of *C. diphtheriae*).

The *pbp2m* gene was located on the large plasmid in a region comprising three other genes, a *blaB* beta-lactamase family gene, a LysR family regulator gene, and the *ermX* gene, flanked by two insertion sequences (IS1628) of the IS6 family (Fig. 7). With disparate direct repeat sequences, it remains unclear if this region

represents a single transposable unit or a mosaic of gene acquisition events in pLRPD. A nearly identical PBP was observed in 78% of publicly available *C. jeikeium* genomes, in 57% of *C. striatum* genomes and in multiple other *Corynebacterium* genomes (Additional file 8: Table S7). However, the genetic context of PBP2m was highly variable in *C. diphtheriae* and among other *Corynebacterium* species (Additional file 4: Fig. S14). A putative transposable PBP-containing unit (PCU) comprising genes *pbp2m*, *blaB*, and *lysR*, commonly flanked by IS3503 (IS256 family) with a fragment identified in pLRPD (Fig. 7), appeared to be highly conserved and was associated variably with *ermX* in *C. diphtheriae* and with a helicase in *C. diphtheriae* and other *Corynebacterium* species. The PCU was sometimes found in 2 or 3 tandem copies and was chromosomally located in most genomes.

Further elements carried by pLRPD included an integron carrying genes *dfrA16*, *qacL*, and *sull*, as well as elements of a putative conjugation apparatus gene cluster (Fig. 7). Our conjugation experiments aiming to demonstrate the transfer of pLRPD into recipient *C. diphtheriae* isolates failed. This plasmid was not found in other *C. diphtheriae* strains.

Discussion

Strains of *C. diphtheriae* that are resistant to antimicrobial therapy may compromise the management of diphtheria cases and the control of pathogen transmission. Here, we aimed to define the genomic determinants of resistance to penicillin and other antimicrobial agents in *C. diphtheriae* and to analyze the relationships of resistance with diphtheria toxin production, biochemical variants, and phylogenetic sublineages. To this aim, we characterized phenotypically and genotypically a large sample of *C. diphtheriae* isolates from diverse geographic and temporal origins. We confirmed that the species is made of multiple phylogenetic sublineages [9, 13, 67] and showed that homologous recombination contributes five times more to their diversification than mutation, consistent with previous evidence of recombination in *C. diphtheriae* populations [12, 13].

Historically, *C. diphtheriae* isolates have been classified into three main biovars, but the links between biovars and phylogenetic structure have remained obscure. Whereas previous work concluded on the absence of an association [11], our phylogenetic analyses reveal that Gravis and Mitis, the two main biovars of *C. diphtheriae*, are associated strongly with two phylogenetic lineages. Lineage Gravis appears to have acquired ancestrally a gene cluster comprising the extracellular glycogen debranching enzyme gene *spuA* [62]. Although the Gravis phenotype was associated with *spuA* within lineage Gravis, other genomic determinants of glycogen

utilization remain to be discovered within the Mitis lineage. Whereas most of our biovar Belfanti isolates were excluded from this work because they belonged to *C. belfantii* or *C. rouxii*, a few Belfanti isolates did belong to *C. diphtheriae*. For three of them, mutations leading to a non-functional nitrate reductase were uncovered, explaining the phenotypic switch to biovar Belfanti. Our results show that biotyping is subject to parallel evolution, perhaps due to a yet-unknown selective pressure, and has limited species-level identification (as Belfanti is found in the three species *C. diphtheriae*, *C. belfantii*, and *C. rouxii*) or epidemiological typing value.

The most important factor of *C. diphtheriae* pathogenicity is the diphtheria toxin. Despite early realization that it is encoded on a prophage [5], few studies have investigated the phylogenetic distribution of the *tox* gene in *C. diphtheriae* [8, 9]. Here, we show that *tox*-positive strains mainly belong to the Mitis lineage and to early-diverging branches of the Gravis lineage. The distribution of *tox*-positive isolates into multiple Mitis sublineages is strongly indicative of independent acquisitions of the toxin gene. Alternately, this pattern might result from initial acquisition of the *tox* gene, followed by secondary loss in multiple sublineages. The phylogenetic pattern is also consistent with an ancestral presence of the *tox*-bearing phage in the Gravis lineage, with subsequent loss of the *tox* gene in the branch leading to the ancestor of most Gravis isolates. Future work should investigate the dynamics of the lysogenic corynephages and molecular determinants of their sublineage distribution. One important open question is the likelihood of *tox*-negative strains acquiring the *tox* gene during colonization, infection, or short-term epidemiological timeframes [7].

Remarkably, except for early-diverging sublineages, only one Gravis sublineage was found to carry the *tox* gene. This sublineage happens to correspond to the largest outbreak in recent times, which occurred in Newly Independent States of the ex-Soviet Union in the 1990s [13, 14, 38]. This sublineage, which comprises the ST8 reference strain NCTC13129, is genetically distant from other *tox*-positive lineages, which belong to the Mitis lineage. Hence, its antigenic structures or other pathogenicity properties may have diverged from those of more common *tox*-positive isolates, which might have contributed to its exceptional transmission in the 1990s, in addition to the decline in vaccine coverage [14]. Of note, biovar Gravis was named to reflect a perceived higher severity of infection compared to diphtheria cases caused by biovar Mitis isolates [68, 69]. Recently, it was shown that most diphtheria vaccines contain, besides the anatoxin, multiple other *C. diphtheriae* immunogens [22]. The impact of vaccination on the evolution of *C.*

diphtheriae populations, and possible variations of cross-protection as a function of strain diversity, is currently undefined. This work provides a framework onto which future studies can build to address this important question.

Although antimicrobial-resistant *C. diphtheriae* strains have been reported on numerous occasions [23, 32], knowledge on antimicrobial resistance in *C. diphtheriae* is largely fragmented and suffers from the lack of harmonization. Breakpoints used to define resistance vary according to world region and have changed over time within single countries [70]. The lack of consensus on the definition of resistance restricts our ability to define the magnitude of the problem and its global significance.

We aimed to define biologically meaningful cutoffs [64] based on susceptibility phenotype distributions, taking advantage of our large and diverse sample. Our data allowed us to propose tentative ecological cutoffs for *C. diphtheriae*. This approach should in the future be extended to MIC values [71] and should use larger and more diverse strain collections. Nevertheless, our analyses suggest that non-susceptibility to at least one antimicrobial agent was acquired by half of *C. diphtheriae* strains, regardless of lineage, biovar, or toxigenic status. This study further suggests that acquired resistance to penicillin, the first-line therapy against diphtheria, is far from being rare, affecting >15% of *C. diphtheriae* isolates collected in the last decade in France and its overseas territories. Besides, 10.4% of these isolates were multidrug-resistant. The high prevalence of resistance to penicillin, tetracycline, and trimethoprim/sulfamethoxazole found here is consistent with susceptibility surveys of recent *C. diphtheriae* isolates in Algeria [29], Indonesia [31, 72], and India [73]. Many high-income countries such as France have chosen to use amoxicillin as the first choice for antibiotic therapy [74], as this molecule remains highly active. Still, widespread penicillin resistance is concerning, since diphtheria mainly occurs in resource-poor settings where penicillin G is largely used. In contrast, resistance to erythromycin and other macrolides remains rare. Our results call for concerted research into the magnitude of the antimicrobial resistance threat in *C. diphtheriae*.

Knowledge of the genetic mechanisms of antimicrobial resistance is critical for defining appropriate treatments, refining diagnostics, and conducting epidemiological studies of antimicrobial resistance. Resistance genes to several antimicrobial classes have been described in *C. diphtheriae* [36, 37, 75], while additional genes described in other *Corynebacterium* species [76] might also be present in *C. diphtheriae*. Here, we defined the prevalence and phylogenetic distribution of previously reported and newly identified resistance determinants in

C. diphtheriae. We demonstrate the co-occurrence of resistance phenotypes and genes, suggesting a causative link in multiple instances. We further show that resistance genes have been acquired independently in multiple sublineages, demonstrating a dynamic resistome in *C. diphtheriae*. In addition, we demonstrate an association between alterations in chromosomally encoded targets and phenotypic resistance for quinolone, trimethoprim, and rifampicin. Fluoroquinolone resistance was previously linked to mutations in the *gyrA* gene in *C. amycolatum* [77], *C. striatum* [78], and *C. belfantii* [79] but seemingly never for *C. diphtheriae*. Finally, we demonstrate the co-occurrence within some strains of multiple resistance determinants and uncover a previously undescribed large resistance plasmid in *C. diphtheriae*. The mechanism of genetic transfer of this plasmid remains to be investigated. This work provides the first overview of the *C. diphtheriae* resistome and will facilitate further studies into the evolutionary emergence of multiresistant *C. diphtheriae* strains.

Here, we discovered an accessory PBP (PBP2m) and experimentally showed it to confer resistance to penicillin and other beta-lactam antimicrobial agents. Its distribution in multiple sublineages, and its presence in other *Corynebacterium* species, clearly demonstrates its horizontal transfer, and we revealed a multiplicity of genomic contexts in which it is found within *Corynebacterium*. PBP2m is a putative low-affinity PBP, which would explain why it is less affected by beta-lactam antibiotics. Very recently, Forde et al. [80] have reported high-level penicillin resistance (MIC > 256 g/L) in *C. diphtheriae* strain BQ11 and have attributed this phenotype to a penicillin-binding protein located on transposon Tn3503. We found that the *pbp2m*-containing unit is 99.92% similar to Tn3503, which additionally harbors a helicase (Additional file 4: Fig. S14). Besides, PBP2m is 100% identical to the PBP from BQ11 and therefore also possesses the V361A alteration (using *C. jeikeium* as reference) that was hypothesized to confer high-level penicillin resistance [80]. Further studies on the expression of *pbp2m* in its variable genetic backgrounds are required to understand the observed difference in penicillin resistance levels. The location of *pbp2m* on a mobile element and its association with beta-lactam and carbapenem resistance represents a public health threat.

The seven chromosomal PBPs of *C. diphtheriae* (including the newly annotated PBP4b) were investigated to identify amino acid sequence polymorphisms associated with penicillin resistance. Although several alterations were significantly associated, none was directly implicated with the catalytic residues of the transpeptidase or transglycosylase domains. The association with resistance may not be directly linked to these catalytic residues but could be due to secondary sites that are

thought to interfere with beta-lactam ligand binding. While biochemical and structural studies are necessary to understand how these mutations affect penicillin susceptibility, we postulate that some changes in these domains could lead to allosteric effects ultimately resulting in beta-lactam resistance, as described for *Staphylococcus aureus* PBP2a [81, 82] or *Streptococcus pneumoniae* PBP2x [83]. Other SNPs might simply have been hitchhiking due to their physical linkage with functionally important SNPs [84].

Conclusions

Our phylogenetic analyses showed that *C. diphtheriae* is highly diverse and comprises multiple sublineages that are grouped into two major lineages, characterized by distinctive associations with biovars Mitis and Gravis and with the diphtheria toxin gene. Antimicrobial resistance remains rare in France and its overseas territories, but multidrug-resistant strains were found and have a wide phylogenetic distribution. Analyses of the genetic bases of antimicrobial resistance defined the contribution of previously described mechanisms of resistance and uncovered a penicillin-binding protein, PBP2m, associated at the population level with penicillin resistance and shown experimentally to confer resistance to several beta-lactam antimicrobial agents. PBP2m is encoded in diverse genetic contexts, including on a large putatively conjugative resistance plasmid. This study reveals how biovars, diphtheria toxin gene, and antimicrobial resistance are associated with the phylogenetic diversity of *C. diphtheriae* strains, and provides novel data into the evolutionary dynamics of these medically important features. This framework will facilitate future studies investigating the emergence of sublineages of *C. diphtheriae* involved in diphtheria outbreaks, antimicrobial resistant infections, and the patterns and drivers of global spread of *C. diphtheriae* sublineages.

Supplementary Information

Supplementary information accompanies this paper at <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13073-020-00805-7>.

Additional file 1: Table S1. Strains used in this study and their characteristics.

Additional file 2: Table S2. Antimicrobial agents and zone diameters interpretative breakpoints used.

Additional file 3: Table S3. Susceptibility data and interpretative categories based on current EUCAST recommendations (SIR) and proposed ecological cutoffs (ECOFF).

Additional file 4. Contains Supplementary Figures S1 to S14.

Additional file 5: Table S4. Molecular explanations for non-toxigenic *tox* gene-bearing (NTTB) strains.

Additional file 6: Table S5. Associations with resistance phenotypes based on treeWAS results for accessory genes, SNPs in core genes and whole-genome SNPs; or based on Kleborate or direct analysis of potential target sequences.

Additional file 7: Table S6. Susceptibility phenotypes of transformed *C. glutamicum* ATCC 13032 strains.

Additional file 8: Table S7. Detection of the *pbp2m* gene in other *Corynebacterium* genomes.

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Authors' contributions

S.B. conceived, designed, and coordinated the study. A.C.-L., E.B., M.B., and M.D. performed the microbiological cultures of the isolates and their biochemical and molecular characterizations. M.H., L.G.P., C.R., S.L.B., M.B.-P., M.D., and S.B. analyzed the genomic and phenotypic data. J.T. reviewed the clinical source data of the isolates. Q.G. and A.-M.W. performed the *pbp2m* cloning experiments and analyzed the PBP sequences. X.D. provided help with the phylogenetic, recombination, and GWAS analyses. S.B. wrote the initial version of the manuscript. All authors provided input to the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Availability of data and materials

The genomic sequencing data generated in this study were deposited in the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) database and are accessible through the BioProject PRJEB22103 (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/view/PRJEB22103>) [85].

Ethics approval and consent to participate

To conduct the research, we used bacterial strains, which are not considered human samples. Accordingly, this research was not considered human research and is out of the scope of the decree n° 2016-1537 of November 16, 2016, implementing law n° 2012-300 of March 5, 2012, on research involving human subjects. Therefore, no ethics approval was needed and no informed consent was required.

All French bacteriological samples were collected in the frame of the French national diphtheria surveillance and are collected, coded, shipped, managed, and analyzed according to the French National Reference Center protocols that received approval from the French competent body CNIL (Commission Nationale Informatique et Libertés; approval number: 1474671). Other strains were obtained from culture collections.

The research conformed to the principles of the Helsinki Declaration.

Consent for publication

Not applicable

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Chapitre 2 : DIPHTOSCAN, un pipeline pour détecter la résistance et la virulence dans le complexe des espèces *diphtheriae*

Titre de l'article

A genomic study and a genotyping tool for *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*

Résumé

La diphtérie est classiquement causée par la bactérie *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*, et est largement contrôlée par la vaccination à l'aide de toxine diphtérique inactivée. Le séquençage génomique peut fournir des informations sur les génotypes des souches et leurs gènes de résistance aux antimicrobiens et de virulence, mais il n'existe actuellement aucun outil permettant d'extraire et d'interpréter facilement les caractéristiques génomiques pertinentes pour le diagnostic clinique ou les interventions de santé publique.

Nous avons développé DIPHTOSCAN, un pipeline bioinformatique qui extrait des informations sur l'espèce, la sous-lignée, le génotype et la présence de gènes d'intérêt à partir de génomes appartenant à des *Corynébacteries* du complexe *diphtheriae*. Le gène *tox* est analysé pour détecter les perturbations de séquence conduisant à des souches non-toxigènes porteuses du gène *tox* (NTTB). DIPHTOSCAN a été utilisé pour analyser 870 génomes provenant de dépôts publics et 380 nouvelles séquences génomiques de *C. diphtheriae* principalement collectées de 2018 à 2021 en France.

La diversité génomique de la population de *C. diphtheriae* est structurée en 246 sous-lignées qui présentent de fortes différences dans leurs caractéristiques de virulence et de résistance aux antimicrobiens, certaines sous-lignées à plus haut risque combinant les deux types de gènes. Le gène toxine diphtérique *tox* était présent dans environ un tiers (331 ; 33,9%) des génomes non redondants (977 isolats). DIPHTOSCAN a détecté une troncature et a donc prédit la non-toxinogénicité dans 16,0% d'entre eux. La prédiction de la toxicité par DIPHTOSCAN a montré une concordance de 93,7% sur la base de 126 isolats français avec des données phénotypiques (test d'Elek). La résistance aux antimicrobiens était omniprésente, 38,2% des isolats présentant au moins une caractéristique de résistance génomique et 12,1% étant multirésistants ; des caractéristiques de résistance à 10 classes d'agents antimicrobiens ont été détectées. Nous avons découvert 584 clusters génomiques, qui correspondent à une définition large des chaînes de transmission, reflétant l'énorme diversité génétique des génotypes de *C. diphtheriae* en circulation. La structure phylogénétique profonde de *C. diphtheriae* montre une division primaire entre une branche Gravis et une branche Mitis, qui diffèrent fortement par leur complément de fimbriae Spa et leurs systèmes d'acquisition du fer ou de l'hème.

Le séquençage génomique est une source importante de données pour prédire les phénotypes des agents pathogènes bactériens qui posent un problème de santé publique, ainsi que pour la recherche sur les relations génotype-phénotype. DIPHTOSCAN est disponible à l'adresse <https://gitlab.pasteur.fr/BEBP/diphotoscan> et permettra de soutenir la surveillance génomique et la recherche sur la diphtérie dans les milieux universitaires et de santé publique. Ce travail permet de découvrir des sous-lignées de *C. diphtheriae* préoccupantes, qui devraient

faire l'objet d'une surveillance renforcée, et de découvrir des variations phylogénétiques structurées dans les caractéristiques génomiques associées à la pathogénie.

Contributions personnelles

- Analyse des données génomiques des isolats de l'étude
- Réalisation de l'ensemble des analyses bioinformatiques
- Développement de l'outil DIPHTOSCAN
- Analyse de la phylogénie, de la recombinaison et des séquences génomiques
- Réalisation de l'ensemble des figures et des tableaux
- Ecriture de la première version du manuscrit

1 **Genomic surveillance of antimicrobial resistance, virulence and sublineages**
2 **of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae***

3

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19 **Keywords:** diphtheria, genomic sequencing, antimicrobial resistance, virulence, epidemiology,
20 transmission

21

22 **Running Title:** DIPHTOSCAN for genomic surveillance of diphtheria

23

Abstract

24 Diphtheria is classically caused by the bacterium *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*, and is largely
25 controlled by vaccination using inactivated diphtheria toxin. Genomic sequencing can provide
26 information on strain genotypes and their antimicrobial resistance and virulence genes, but no
27 tool currently exists to readily extract and interpret the genomic features relevant to clinical
28 diagnostic or public health interventions.

29

30 We developed DIPHTOSCAN, a bioinformatics pipeline that extracts information on species,
31 sublineage, genotype and the presence of genes of interest from genomes belonging to
32 *Corynebacteria* of the *diphtheriae* complex. The *tox* gene is analyzed for sequence disruptions
33 leading to *tox* gene-bearing, non-toxigenic (NTTB) strains. DIPHTOSCAN was used to analyze
34 870 genomes from public repositories and 380 novel *C. diphtheriae* genomic sequences mainly
35 collected from 2018 to 2021 in France.

36

37 The genomic diversity of the *C. diphtheriae* population is structured into 246 sublineages that
38 show sharp differences in their virulence and antimicrobial resistance features, with some
39 higher-risk sublineages combining both types of genes. The diphtheria toxin gene *tox* was
40 present in approximately one third (331; 33.9%) of non-redundant genomes (977 isolates).
41 DIPHTOSCAN detected a truncation and hence predicted non-toxigenicity in 16.0% of these.
42 Toxigenicity prediction by DIPHTOSCAN showed 93.7% concordance based on 126 French
43 isolates with phenotypic data (Elek's test). Antimicrobial resistance was pervasive, with 38.2%
44 isolates having at least one genomic resistance feature and 12.1% being multidrug-resistant;
45 resistance features against 10 classes of antimicrobial agents were detected. We uncovered 584
46 genomic clusters, which correspond to a broad definition of transmission chains, reflecting the
47 huge genetic diversity of circulating *C. diphtheriae* genotypes. The deep phylogenetic structure
48 of *C. diphtheriae* shows a primary divide between a Gravis branch and a Mitis branch, which
49 differ sharply by their complement of Spa fimbriae and iron or heme acquisition systems.

50

51 Genomic sequencing is an important source of data to predict phenotypes of bacterial pathogens
52 of public health concern, as well as for research on genotype-phenotype relationships.
53 DIPHTOSCAN is available at <https://gitlab.pasteur.fr/BEBP/diphtoscan> and will support genomic
54 surveillance and research on diphtheria in academic and public health settings. This work
55 uncovers *C. diphtheriae* sublineages of concern, which should be the focus of strengthened
56 surveillance, and uncovers phylogenetically structured variation in genomic features associated
57 with pathogenesis.

Introduction

59 Diphtheria has been a leading cause of infant mortality before the roll-out of mass
60 vaccination programs. The disease is mainly due to infection by the pathogen *C. diphtheriae*
61 and is classically a respiratory infection, characterized by the presence of a pseudomembrane
62 on the tonsils, pharynx and larynx. Some strains of *C. diphtheriae* can produce the diphtheria
63 toxin (DT), which is encoded by the *tox* gene carried by a prophage. The toxigenic strains can
64 cause severe infections with systemic, sometimes lethal, symptoms. Other forms of diphtheria
65 are cutaneous and invasive infections, most often caused by non-toxicogenic strains.

66 Diphtheria is largely controlled by large-scale vaccination. However, the pathogen
67 circulates widely and silently among human populations, and the disease can reemerge in non-
68 vaccinated persons. Recent years have seen large epidemics in Bangladesh, Haiti, South Africa
69 and Venezuela and Yemen (du Plessis et al., 2017; Lodeiro-Colatosti et al., 2018; Hsan et al.,
70 2020; Badell et al., 2021; Ikejezie et al., 2022); in all cases, health care systems were disrupted
71 and vaccination had dropped significantly.

72 *C. diphtheriae* is a genetically diverse species (Sangal and Hoskisson, 2016; Seth-Smith
73 and Egli, 2019; Hennart et al., 2020). The links between strain genotypes and clinical
74 phenotypes of diphtheria, and underlying mechanisms of virulence other than for diphtheria
75 toxin, are still poorly understood. Early literature has suggested heterogeneity in clinical forms
76 associated with biovars (Barksdale, 1970). Uncharacterized genetic features of the bacterium
77 may also be associated with the cutaneous versus respiratory tropism. In addition, the dynamics
78 of *tox*-positive *versus* *tox*-negative isolates remain poorly understood, and concern has been
79 repeatedly expressed that *tox*-negative may convert into *tox*-positive strains by lysogenic
80 conversion during infection or outbreaks. Nontoxicogenic *tox*-bearing (NTTB) *C. diphtheriae*
81 isolates are being observed and represent 5-15% of *tox*-positive isolates, but the drivers of *tox*
82 disruption, and our capacity to predict toxigenicity from genomic sequences, remain unclear.

83 Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in *C. diphtheriae* is rare but it is increasingly being
84 reported. Antimicrobial susceptibility testing and guidelines for the interpretation of
85 susceptibility data lack standardization and stability over time, which confuses the global
86 picture and clinical importance of resistance in *C. diphtheriae*. The prevalent mechanisms of
87 resistance are not well known, and their genomic context and association with mobile genetic
88 elements could provide important clues as to the emergence of *C. diphtheriae* resistant strains.

89 Fimbriae, iron-acquisition systems including siderophores and heme-acquisition
90 systems, as well as other virulence factors have been described in *C. diphtheriae* (Ott, 2018).
91 The taxonomy of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* and related potentially toxigenic species has
92 recently been updated; besides the three classical species *C. diphtheriae*, *C. ulcerans* and

93 *C. pseudotuberculosis*, three novel species are now included in the Corynebacteria of the
94 *diphtheriae* complex: *C. belfantii* (Dzas et al., 2018), *C. rouxii* (Badell et al., 2020) and
95 *C. silvaticum* (Dangel et al., 2020).

96 Whole genome sequencing (WGS) of *C. diphtheriae* clinical isolates is increasingly
97 performed by reference microbiology laboratories, as it provides information on clinically
98 relevant molecular targets; however, extraction and interpretation of important genomic
99 features is difficult for non-bioinformaticians, and no simple tool currently exists for
100 *C. diphtheriae* genomic analyses in surveillance and research contexts. Besides, the analyses of
101 *C. diphtheriae* genomes remain largely unstandardized, which complicates interpretation of
102 reported genomic features across studies. Recent advances towards standardization include the
103 development of an MLST scheme and the related nomenclature of Sequence Types (Bolt et al.,
104 2010), and a cgMLST scheme and the associated nomenclature of sublineages and genomic
105 clusters (Guglielmini et al., 2021).

106 Here, we have developed DIPHTOSCAN, a genotyping tool designed specifically for
107 Corynebacteria of the *C. diphtheriae* species complex. This tool consolidates identification at
108 species level, detects key virulence and AMR genomic loci, and provides genotyping and
109 classifications into sequence types, sublineages and genomic clusters. Toxigenic or non-
110 toxigenic status prediction is attempted based on presence and sequence of the *tox* gene coding
111 for diphtheria toxin, and biovar prediction is also proposed. We illustrate the use of
112 DIPHTOSCAN by analyzing 380 novel genomic sequences from prospective isolates mainly
113 collected by the French national surveillance laboratory, and a curated collection of 870
114 publicly available genomic sequences of *C. diphtheriae*. We showcase the utility of
115 DIPHTOSCAN and derive novel insights into the global population structure of *C. diphtheriae*
116 and its resistance and virulence genomic features.

117

Results

118 1. Development of the genotyping tool diphtOscan

119 To provide a tool to rapidly extract information from genomes of *C. diphtheriae* and other
120 members of the Corynebacteria of the diphtheriae species complex (Cdc), we developed
121 DIPHTOSCAN. This tool starts (**Figure S1**) with taxonomic assignment of species and, if the
122 genome is confirmed to belong to Cdc, it proceeds to cgMLST lineage and genomic cluster
123 assignment, determination of the sequence type based on MLST at seven loci. The detection of
124 AMR determinants (mutations and horizontally acquired genes) and virulence factors are
125 performed regardless of the species. In addition, DIPHTOSCAN includes a predictive function for
126 the *tox* gene, the most important virulence factor of Cdc isolates, by investigation of the
127 presence of stop codons (nonsense mutations). It also detects genomic markers associated with
128 biovars Gravis, Mitis and Belfanti, a biochemical-based classification that was initiated in the
129 1930s (Anderson et al., 1931; McLeod, 1943) and which is still used in diphtheria surveillance
130 laboratories.

131 DIPHTOSCAN was developed using the code from Kleborate v2.2.0 (Lam et al., 2021),
132 AMRfinderPlus (Feldgarden et al., 2021) and BIGSdb (Jolley and Maiden, 2010) with some
133 modifications (**Figure S2**). A custom code was created for DIPHTOSCAN initiation,
134 interpretation and for displaying results. The *C. diphtheriae* specific genes (genomic markers,
135 AMR determinants and virulence factors) for which the genomes are screened by DIPHTOSCAN
136 are provided in a custom database similar in its structure to the AMRfinderPlus database; this
137 database can be further enriched with novel features in the future. During the initiation of
138 DIPHTOSCAN, the AMRfinderPlus
139 (https://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pathogen/Antimicrobial_resistance/) and custom databases are
140 merged (**Figure S3**). We used the functions of species determination, MLST genotyping, and
141 full CDS prediction from Kleborate. A script from BIGSdb
142 (https://github.com/kjolley/BIGSdb/tree/develop/scripts/rest_examples) updates the allele
143 sequence list and MLST profiles. AMRfinderPlus v3.10.36 is used within DIPHTOSCAN with no
144 modifications.

145 DIPHTOSCAN performs rapid and accurate species identification based on k-mer-derived
146 Mash distances. This approach was validated by comparing DIPHTOSCAN species assignments
147 with those obtained by average nucleotide identity (ANI; Konstantinidis and Tiedje, 2005)
148 using FastANI (Jain et al., 2018); 100% concordance was achieved.

149 To perform the identification of AMR or virulence genes or mutations, we targeted a panel
150 of priority genetic features for which published experimental evidence exists in *C. diphtheriae*
151 or closely related species for their clinical relevance (*i.e.*, increased virulence in animal models,

152 or decreased antimicrobial susceptibility *in vitro*). A second panel of genetic features with no
153 experimental evidence but with strong suspicion for a role in virulence, based on homology
154 with other pathogens, was also included for broader screening of virulence features. The priority
155 target genes are resistance genes (**Table S1**) and the following virulence genes: the *tox* gene,
156 SpaA-, SpaD-, and SpaH-type pili, DIP0733 (*67-72p*), the genes DIP1281 and DIP1621 that
157 code for proteins of the NlpC/P60 family, DIP0543 (*nanH*), DIP1546 and DIP2093 (Ott, 2018).

158 The three main biovars of *C. diphtheriae* are distinguished by their abilities to reduce nitrate
159 and metabolize glycogen. Previously, a strong concordance between the biovar of isolates and
160 the presence in *C. diphtheriae* genomes of several genomic markers including *spuA*, coding for
161 a putative alpha-1,6-glycosidase, and *narKGHJI* genes for nitrate reductase, was found (Sangal
162 et al., 2014; Santos et al., 2018; Hennart et al., 2020). We therefore included in the custom
163 DIPHTOSCAN query database, the *spuA* marker and its adjacent genes (DIP0351; DIP0353;
164 DIP0354; DIP0357=*spuA*), which are strongly associated with biovar Gravis, and the
165 *narIJHGK* cluster, which is typically absent or partly disrupted, mainly due to mutations in the
166 *narG* (Hennart et al., 2020) or *narI* (Sangal et al., 2014) gene in isolates of biovar Belfanti.

167 To facilitate readability and downstream analyses, the output of DIPHTOSCAN is generated
168 in a tab-delimited format. The technical characteristics of DIPHTOSCAN are summarized in
169 **Figure S2** and the methodological details for genotyping are provided in "Methods". The
170 execution time of DIPHTOSCAN increases linearly with the number of input genomes. As an
171 indication, 40 seconds are needed to scan a single genome with 1 cpu.

172

173 **2. Genome-based phylogenetic structure and classification of *C. diphtheriae* isolates**

174 We collated a dataset of 1250 *C. diphtheriae* isolates (**Table S2, Figure S4_A**), of which
175 870 belonged to public repositories and 380 were newly sequenced isolates. The dataset
176 included 600 isolates collected at the NRC for Corynebacteria of the *diphtheriae* complex
177 (noted French NRC genomes), 71 ribotype reference strains (Grimont et al., 2004); **Table S3**),
178 and 579 other isolates from public genome databases. Note that the dataset referred to as “non-
179 French NRC genomes” aggregates the isolates from public genome databases and the ribotype
180 reference strains (n=650).

181 Nearly four-fifths (532; 88.7%) of the isolates from the French NRC were prospectively
182 collected between 2008 and 2021 from French mainland and overseas territories, 54 isolates
183 (9.0%) were collected between 1990 and 2007 from France and Algeria and 14 (2.3%) isolates
184 collected between 1951 and 1987 from France. We included 251 genome sequences from our
185 previous studies (Hennart et al., 2020; Guglielmini et al., 2021), and sequenced for the present
186 study 380 additional isolates, including 304 collected between 2018 and 2021, 17 strains

187 collected between 2008 and 2017, 53 historical clinical isolates (mostly from the 1990s), and 6
188 ribotype strains (**Table S2**).

189 All isolates were confirmed as *C. diphtheriae* based on a MASH distance smaller than 0.05
190 with either the *C. diphtheriae* type strain NCTC11397^T, the reference genome strain
191 NCTC13129, or the vaccine strain PW8 (Park-Williams 8). A phylogenetic analysis was
192 performed based on the concatenation of individual alignments of the 1948 core genome loci
193 identified using Panaroo, for a total alignment length of 1,986,172 bp (79.8% of NCTC13129
194 genome length, of 2,488,635 bp). The tree was rooted using *C. belfantii* strain FRC0043^T. The
195 phylogenetic structure within *C. diphtheriae* revealed a star-like phylogeny with multiple
196 deeply-branching sublineages, as previously reported (Berger et al., 2019; Seth-Smith and Egli,
197 2019; Hennart et al., 2020; Guglielmini et al., 2021) (**Figure 1**).

198 The 7-gene MLST analysis showed that almost all (n=1,233; 98.6%) of the genomes were
199 assigned to an ST, with an observed diversity of 365 distinct STs. A previous core genome
200 MLST (cgMLST) scheme was defined based on 1,305 loci (Guglielmini et al., 2021) and it was
201 used to define the alleles of the 1250 genomic sequences. The mean number of missing alleles
202 per profile was 12 (0.9%; standard deviation: 12; 0.9%), and almost all (n=1,242; 95.2%)
203 isolates had a cgMLST profile with fewer than 65 (4.98%) missing alleles. New cgMLST
204 profiles (n=1249) have received a cgST identifier (one genome had 219 missing alleles whereas
205 the admissible threshold is of 130). There were 1170 distinct cgSTs, *i.e.*, profiles differing at
206 one or more of the 1305 loci.

207 To classify *C. diphtheriae* genomes based on cgMLST, two thresholds were previously
208 defined; sublineages are defined with a threshold of 500 cgMLST mismatches, whereas a
209 threshold of 25 mismatches defines genomic clusters, which comprise documented
210 epidemiological clusters of related isolates (Guglielmini et al., 2021). Here, DIPHTOSCAN
211 grouped the isolates into 246 sublineages and 584 genomic clusters.

212 Overall, 106 (43.1%) sublineages comprised at least two genomic clusters. Almost all
213 (360/365; 98.6%) of the 7-gene MLST STs corresponded one-to-one with the sublineage level,
214 *i.e.*, all isolates of these STs belonged to the same sublineage. However, 71 sublineages (28.9%)
215 comprised at least two ST, indicating that sublineages are useful classifiers for closely related
216 STs. Sublineages were attributed numbers by using an ST inheritance rule (Hennart et al.,
217 2022), which was applied from SL1 to SL744, after which the numbers are attributed
218 consecutively with no reference to MLST identifiers, starting at 10,000 (see column
219 'Mapping_sublineage' in **Table S2**).

220 One genomic cluster (GC456) comprised 43 isolates (all from a Vancouver inner city
221 outbreak), and 46 clusters had between 5 and 27 isolates; whereas the 537 remaining ones had
222 between 1 and 4 isolates (**Figure S5A**). This illustrates that our sample comprised sets of

223 isolates from single outbreaks, and we therefore created a non-redundant subset by randomly
224 selecting one genome per genomic cluster, isolation year and city (if city was unavailable, the
225 country was used instead) with the same resistance genes profile and *tox* status (see column
226 ‘dataset_Deduplicated’ in **Table S2**). This subsampling resulted in a deduplicated subset of 977
227 genomes. Within this subset, four predominant 7-gene MLST sequence types were ST8 (55
228 isolates), ST5 (41 isolates), ST50 (38 isolates) and ST228 (29 isolates) (**Figure S6B**, see
229 **Figure S6A** for distribution of the all dataset). The effectiveness of genomic cluster and
230 sublineages with a breakdown by country are represented in **Figure S5B** and **Figure S7B**,
231 respectively.

232 To estimate the phylogenetic consistency of classification groups, we quantified the
233 proportion of monophyletic (single ancestor, exclusive group), paraphyletic (single ancestor,
234 nonexclusive group), and polyphyletic (two or more distinct ancestors) groups. Regarding the
235 365 distinct STs, 167 (45.8%) were nonsingleton STs (*i.e.*, comprised at least two isolates). Of
236 these, 134 (79.8%) were monophyletic, 28 (16.7%) were polyphyletic and 5 were paraphyletic
237 (3.0%). The monophyletic STs comprised only 57.9% (n=599) of all genomes in non-singleton
238 STs (1035) (**Table S4**). In contrast, among the 246 distinct sublineages, 146 (59.3%) were non-
239 singleton, and most (140; 95.8%) of these were monophyletic; only three (2.1%) were
240 polyphyletic and only three (2.1%) were paraphyletic. The monophyletic sublineages
241 comprised a large majority (1040/1249; 83.3%) of genomes in nonsingleton STs (**Table S5**).
242 Therefore, while concordance with phylogeny was low for 7-gene MLST, it was much higher
243 for cgMLST sublineages.

244 Biovars Mitis and Gravis were mainly distributed into two distinct branches of the
245 phylogenetic tree, which were defined by the distribution of the *spuA* gene (involved in starch
246 utilization) of the isolates (**Table S2**), consistent with previous results (Hennart et al., 2020;
247 Guglielmini et al., 2021). Within the non-duplicated subset, the Gravis lineage contains 513
248 isolates, of which 405 (78.9%) are *spuA*-positive. A few sublineages within the Gravis branch
249 were *spuA*-negative: SL625, SL130, SL102, and SL377. In contrast, the Mitis lineage
250 comprised 734 isolates, of which the majority were *spuA*-negative: only 42 (5.7%) were *spuA*-
251 positive and belonged mainly to SL5 (an important sublineage involved in the ex-USSR 1990s
252 outbreak), SL466, and SL120 (mainly isolated in New Caledonia).

253

254 **3. Frequency and distribution of the diphtheria toxin gene**

255 For almost all isolates from the French NRC (594/600; 99.0%), experimental data were
256 available for the detection of the *tox* gene by PCR; nearly a quarter (141/594; 23.7%) of the
257 isolates were *tox*-positive by this reference method. DIPHTOSCAN detected the *tox* gene in 140
258 of 141 PCR *tox*-positive isolates. No explanation was found to explain the discordance for the

259 only exception, isolate FRC0119. Similarly, of 453 PCR *tox*-negative isolates, 446 (98.5%) had
260 a negative genomic result, while 7 had a *tox* gene sequence detected. As there was no sequence
261 variation in the PCR priming sites, no direct explanation was found to explain the discordances.

262 Experimental data were also available for the production of the diphtheria toxin for 129 of
263 the 140 *tox*-positive isolates. Of these, 18 (14.0%) were Elek negative, of which 8 (44%) were
264 predicted as non-toxigenic by DIPHTOSCAN. Among the 111 Elek positive isolates, 110 (99.1%)
265 were predicted to be toxigenic by DIPHTOSCAN, whereas one isolate was predicted to be non-
266 toxigenic. DIPHTOSCAN was unable to determine the toxigenic status of 3 *tox*-positive isolates,
267 because the *tox* gene was located at the end of a contig and therefore incomplete. In these cases,
268 DIPHTOSCAN reported a result with a '\$' suffix, indicating genomic assembly truncation.
269 Overall, DIPHTOSCAN agreed with the Elek test in 93.7% (118/126) of the cases.

270

271 Within the deduplicated genomic dataset (977 isolates), approximately one third (331;
272 33.9%) of isolates were *tox*-positive, as defined using DIPHTOSCAN; in the redundant (global)
273 dataset, this proportion was 35.2% (440/1250). DIPHTOSCAN detected a truncation and hence
274 predicted non-toxigenicity in 16.0% of the non-redundant *tox*-positive genomes (52/331).

275

276 Regarding the non-French NRC genomes, among the 235 for which data were available,
277 112 strains were *tox*-positive by PCR; for 109 of these, the DIPHTOSCAN output was *tox*-positive
278 too. Inversely, 123 strains were *tox*-negative by PCR, and genomic sequence analysis by
279 DIPHTOSCAN was concordant for 121 strains (CIP107544 and CIP80-56 were discordant).
280 Experimental data were also available for the production of the diphtheria toxin for 53 (47.3%)
281 of the 112 *tox*-positive isolates. Of these, 23 (42.6%) were Elek negative, of which 16 (69.6%)
282 were predicted as non-toxigenic by DIPHTOSCAN. Among the 30 Elek positive isolates, all were
283 predicted to be toxigenic by DIPHTOSCAN.

284

285 The distribution of *tox*-positive genomes across sublineages was investigated. 173 (70.3%)
286 sublineages were entirely *tox*-negative. Hence, less than one third (73/246; 29.7%) of
287 sublineages had at least 1 *tox*-positive strain. Of these 73 sublineages, 50 were homogeneous
288 for *tox* status, i.e., included only *tox*-positive genomes. Hence, nearly one in ten sublineages
289 (23; 9.3%) included both potentially toxigenic and non-toxigenic genomes (**Table S2,**
290 **Figure S8**).

291

292 4. Other virulence-associated genes

293 We have incorporated into DIPHTOSCAN the ability to detect the presence of genes known
294 or suspected to be involved in diphtheria infections, and we scanned the 1250 genomes for their

295 presence (**TableS2_diphtOscan**). We found that a number of virulence factors are conserved
296 within the species: DIP1546 was present in all genomes except in 28_DSM43988, and
297 DIP0733, DIP1281, DIP1621, and DIP1880 were fully conserved. Similarly, the *htaA*-
298 *hmuTUV-htaBC* cluster genes for heme acquisition were largely present (98.4%; 1230
299 genomes; **Table S6**).

300 In contrast, other virulence-associated genes were variably present (**Table S6**).
301 Remarkably, cluster *irp2ABCDEFGHI-irp2JKLMN* appears to be strongly associated with the
302 Mitis lineage; 671 of 734 Mitis isolates were *irp2*-positive, whereas only 2 of 513 Gravis
303 isolates were *irp2*-positive (chi-square p-value < 0.00001). Furthermore, we note that the
304 *irp1ABCD* cluster is also mainly present in the Mitis lineage (chi-square p-value < 0.00001),
305 although some Mitis sublineages, including the Vancouver outbreak sublineage, are *irp1*-
306 negative. Contrary to *irp2*, which is nearly totally absent from the Gravis lineage, the *irp1*
307 cluster appears to have been acquired several times in the Gravis lineage, especially in its early-
308 diverging branches (**Figure 1**).

309 In sharp opposition, *chtAB* (coding for a system involved in heme acquisition) was very
310 strongly associated with the Gravis lineage: 408 of 513 Gravis isolates were *chtAB*-positive,
311 whereas only 11 of 734 Mitis isolates were *chtAB*-positive (chi-square p-value < 0.00001). It
312 was nevertheless absent in a few sublineages of the Gravis branch, and present in three branches
313 of the Mitis lineage. This cluster seems to have been acquired exactly concomitantly to the loss
314 of *irp2ABCDEFGHI-irp2JKLMN* and at the time of the evolutionary emergence of the Gravis
315 lineage (**Figure 1**).

316 The *iusABCDE* cluster was present in multiple branches of the tree, some of which
317 encompassing a few sublineages of either Gravis or Mitis isolates. There is strong phylogenetic
318 structure in the distribution of this cluster (**Figure 1**), but its acquisition appears sporadic and
319 then maintained for a time sufficiently long to enable the differentiation of sublineages. The
320 *cdtQP-sidBA-ddpABCD* cluster was present in 66.4% (830 genomes) and seems to have been
321 lost independently in multiple small branches of the tree.

322 Three main types of fimbriae have been described in *C. diphtheriae*, and experimental
323 data suggests that they induce distinct adhesion properties to larynx, pharynx or pulmonary
324 human cells (Mandlik et al., 2007; Ott, 2018). Whereas SpaABC was reported as being largely
325 conserved in *C. diphtheriae*, SpaDEF and SpaGHI are more variably present (Mandlik et al.,
326 2007; Ott, 2018; Santos et al., 2018). Here, we found that spaABC was present in only 72.0%
327 of non-duplicate isolates, and whereas it was totally present in the Gravis lineage, it was present
328 in only half of isolates of the Mitis lineage (296 spaABC-positive of 568 Mitis isolates; chi-
329 square p-value < 0.00001). The output of DIPHTOSCAN further shows that the two other Spa
330 clusters were almost exclusively present within the Gravis lineage. Whereas spaDEF was nearly

331 conserved in the Gravis branch, it was present in only a few isolates of the Mitis branch (131
332 spaDEF-positive of 568 Mitis isolates; chi-square p-value < 0.00001). Cluster spaGHI was
333 totally absent in the Mitis branch, and largely present (70.4% of isolates) in the Gravis branch;
334 interestingly the presence of both clusters complemented each other in the Gravis branch:
335 86.0% isolates had either one, or the other, or both. This complementary pattern of
336 presence/absence of spaGHI and spaDEF gene clusters was evident in a large part of the Gravis
337 lineage phylogeny (**Figure1**). Similarly, the collagen-binding protein DIP2093 (Peixoto et
338 al.,2017) appears to be strongly associated with the Gravis lineage; 356 of 513 Gravis isolates
339 were DIP2093-positive, whereas only 9 of 734 Mitis isolates were DIP2093-positive (chi-
340 square p-value < 0.00001).

341 Last, two gene clusters appeared to be infrequent in *C. diphtheriae*: the DIP2014 gene was
342 detected in only a few sublineages of the Gravis branch (133 isolates), and the *nanH* gene
343 (DIP0543) was present in only a few sublineages distributed along the phylogeny.

344

345 **5. Antibiotic resistance genes of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae***

346 We used DIPHTOSCAN to analyze the *C. diphtheriae* genomes for the presence of AMR-
347 related features. Resistance genes or mutations belonging to ten distinct classes of antibiotics
348 were detected (**Figure2; TableS6**). We identified four tetracycline resistance genes (*tetO*, *tet33*,
349 *tetW* and *tetZ*), nine aminoglycoside resistance genes (*aac(3)-XI*, *aph (3')-Ia*, *aph (3')-Ib*, *aph*
350 *(6)-Id*, *aadA1*, *aadA2*, *aadA5*, *aadA13* and *aadA15*), three quaternary ammonium compounds
351 resistance genes (*qacEA1*, *qacE* and *qacL*), three trimethoprim resistance genes (*dfrA1*, *dfrA15*
352 and *dfrA16*), two chloramphenicol resistance genes (*cmlA4* and *cmx*), *erm(X)* gene (macrolide
353 resistance), *sulI* gene (sulfonamide resistance) and gene *pbp2m* (penicillin resistance). We also
354 detected chromosomal mutations that can cause resistance: quinolone resistance due mutation
355 in the *gyrA* gene (D93A or D93Y or S89F or S89V) and rifampicin resistance due mutation in
356 the *rpoB* gene (S442F or S442V).

357 The highest frequencies of resistance genes rates were sulfonamide resistance features
358 (exclusively gene *sulI*; sometimes present in two copies; 260 non-redundant isolates; 26.6%)
359 and tetracycline resistance features (mostly tet(O), tet(W) and tet(33), in approximately equal
360 proportions; 132 isolates; 13.5%) (**Figure 2; Table S6**). Phenicol resistance-associated gene
361 *cmx* was also commonly found. *pbp2m* was present in 34 isolates, and *ermX* in 36 isolates.
362 *pbp2m* and *ermX* were found together in 14 isolates (1.4% of 977 isolates).

363 DIPHTOSCAN also outputs a score of resistance that corresponds to the number of
364 antimicrobial classes for which a resistance gene or mutation is detected. The score varied from
365 0 to 8 in our dataset, with more than half of the genomes (61.8%; 604/977) having no resistance
366 genes or mutations (score: 0); this figure is 758 of 1250 (60.6%) in the non-duplicated

367 genomic dataset (**Figure S9**). In other words, 38.2% non-redundant isolates had at least one
368 genomic resistance feature.

369 We found that 118 isolates (12.1%) were multidrug resistant (acquired resistance to ≥ 3
370 drug classes). As penicillin and erythromycin are first-line antimicrobial agents, we looked
371 more specifically at the distribution of the resistance genes against these agents. We found that
372 multiple sublineages harbored *ermX* or *pbp2m*, and that the presence of these genes was not
373 always found in multiresistant sublineages (**Figure S10**, is represent for the all dataset).

374 The distribution of resistance at the sublineage level showed that just above half of the
375 sublineages (128; 52.0%) comprised at least one strain with a resistance genomic feature
376 (**Figure S11**). The two sublineages with the most resistant strains are SL8 (46 strains) and
377 SL377 (17 strains). 19 sublineages carried multiresistant strains, and SL377 and SL405 are the
378 ones with the highest number of reported multiresistant isolates (14 and 10 isolates,
379 respectively).

380 The combination in the same isolates of multidrug resistance and toxigenicity could
381 cause particularly concerning infections. We therefore looked for co-occurrence of these two
382 phenotypes. Among non-duplicate isolates, 57 (5.8%) were MDR and *tox*-positive (70 of 1250;
383 5.6% of non-duplicated isolates). A few sublineages comprised most of the isolates with both
384 the presence of the non-disrupted *tox* gene and a high resistance score (**Figure 3**). The two main
385 sublineages were SL377 (10 multidrug resistant strains and 9 *tox*-positive; mostly from India
386 but also from France) and SL301 (8 multidrug resistant strains and all *tox*-positive; from India,
387 Austria and Syria). SL453 had three MDR *tox*-positive isolates, which were isolated in Spain
388 and France with links to Afghanistan (see chapter 7).

389 The global sample of genomes is largely uncontrolled and is likely to suffer from distinct
390 sampling biases in different countries or time periods. Nevertheless, a descriptive analysis of
391 the geographic and temporal distribution of resistance was made. We found that multidrug
392 resistant isolates came mostly from a few locations: Mainland France (n=18 isolates), India
393 (n=17), Spain (n=4), Germany (n=3), Somalia (n=2), Austria (n=2) and La Réunion (n=1)
394 (**Figure S12**, is represent for the all dataset). The countries most affected by the presence of
395 resistance genes in proportion of the isolates collected are India (47/49; 95.9%), Algeria (15/21;
396 71.4%), Austria (28/45; 62.2%), Russia (7/13; 53.9%) Spain (10/20; 50.0%) and France
397 (123/248; 49.6%). Note that in France for example, isolates may come from migrants or
398 travelers and this was not considered in this analysis.

Discussion

400 We developed DIPHTOSCAN and applied this tool to extract clinically important genomic
401 features from 1250 *C. diphtheriae* genomes. As whole genome sequencing is increasingly used
402 on *C. diphtheriae* and related species from clinical samples, a simple and rapid genome
403 scanning tool will enable microbiology laboratories to extract relevant features, and it will have
404 the additional advantage of harmonizing the way these features are reported and interpreted.

405 This work provides an overview of the population diversity of *C. diphtheriae* based on
406 currently available genomic sequences. As previously reported (Berger et al., 2019; Seth-Smith
407 and Egli, 2019; Hennart et al., 2020; Guglielmini et al., 2021), *C. diphtheriae* is made up of
408 multiple sublineages that appear to be related through a star-like phylogeny. We previously
409 defined sublineages by single-linkage clustering using a maximal distance of 500 cgMLST
410 mismatches, and here described the existence of (at least) 246 sublineages. The stability of
411 sublineages resulting from single-linkage clustering is an important question (Zhou et al.,
412 2021). Here, we noted that compared to previous datasets, there was no sublineage fusion upon
413 adding our present genomes, which indicated an excellent stability of *C. diphtheriae*
414 sublineages definition. We here uncovered 123 additional sublineages, 114 of which was given
415 an identifier (number) in reference to MLST, whereas 9 were attributed an arbitrary number.
416 The latter option is automatable and may become the general case in the future.

417 The diagnostic and surveillance of diphtheria is largely organized around the detection
418 of the *tox* gene and its toxigenicity potential. In France, any *tox*-positive isolate from a human
419 clinical sample should be reported to health authorities, who oversee the evaluation of the public
420 health risk posed by such cases and who plan appropriate actions accordingly. In other
421 countries, such as England and as recommended by WHO, the expression of the diphtheria
422 toxin, rather than mere *tox* gene presence, is used as the diagnostic cornerstone of diphtheria,
423 and only toxigenicity is considered a worthy starting point for public health action (WHO,
424 2018). We found that the determination of the *tox* gene presence by DIPHTOSCAN was highly
425 concordant with the qPCR experimental approach in our reference laboratory (DIPHTOSCAN
426 detected the *tox* gene in 140 of 141 PCR *tox*-positive isolates, and reported its absence in almost
427 all qPCR *tox*-negative isolates). We also found that DIPHTOSCAN can predict some non-
428 toxigenic *tox* gene-bearing (NTTB) isolates. Still, a substantial proportion of NTTB isolates
429 could not be predicted by DIPHTOSCAN. These cases may be due to a lower level of expression
430 of the toxin gene in some strains or to technical issues in the Elek test (false NTTB), or to yet
431 unknown genetic mechanisms that abort *tox* gene expression entirely (unexplained true NTTB).
432 Future work to define the genotype-phenotype links underlying toxigenicity will improve the
433 predictive capacity for non-toxigenicity from genomic sequences. In the non-redundant dataset,

434 16.0% of tox-positive isolates were predicted as NTTB, showing that this issue is far from being
435 anecdotal, which underlines the importance of differentiating *tox* gene presence from
436 toxigenicity.

437 The Elek test, used to define toxigenicity, relies on the availability of antisera and on
438 technical expertise that are largely restricted to a few reference laboratories. This works opens
439 interesting perspectives as to the rapid diagnostic of diphtheria based on genomic sequencing;
440 as the Elek test typically takes at least 48h to perform, rapid sequencing of isolates could
441 represent an interesting alternative to rule-out toxigenicity in some cases, avoiding unnecessary
442 public health action around falsely concerning cases.

443 We found that approximately one third of non-redundant genomes harbored the *tox*
444 gene, but there were striking differences of this proportion among countries (**Figure S12**, is
445 represent for the all dataset). Surveillance systems of diphtheria are highly heterogeneous.
446 Whereas in some countries, including France, any *C. diphtheriae* isolate (including from
447 asymptomatic forms or non-specific wounds) is typically referred to the NRC for *tox* testing, in
448 many other countries, only clinical diphtheria leads to isolates testing, whereas *C. diphtheriae*
449 isolates from wounds or other non-specific infections are rarely detected and tested for *tox* gene
450 presence. This clinically-oriented surveillance, which focuses on classical respiratory
451 diphtheria forms, may be associated with a higher proportion of *tox*-positives among reported
452 isolates.

453 Biovars represent an early attempt to discriminate among *C. diphtheriae* strains
454 (Anderson et al., 1931). Here, we confirm our previous proposal (Hennart et al., 2020) that the
455 population structure of *C. diphtheriae* is primarily divided into two deep lineages corresponding
456 largely to Gravis and Mitis biovars, which we hence have labelled Gravis and Mitis lineages
457 (or branches) for convenience. This is in sharp contrast to initial studies, based on only few
458 genomes (Sangal et al., 2014), that suggested the absence of phylogenetic differentiation of
459 biovars. We note that the phylogenetic separation of the two lineages is subtle, and that the
460 rooting of the phylogeny is uncertain. It is therefore yet unclear whether Gravis derived from
461 within the Mitis diversity, as suggested here by our phylogenetic analysis, or if Gravis is the
462 ancestral branch from which Mitis evolved, as found using other outgroup genomes
463 (Guglielmini et al., 2021). This lack of phylogenetic resolution may in the future be resolved
464 by the analysis of the *spuA* locus and scars of its genetic integration (or loss). Minor groups of
465 Gravis isolates (defined here as possessing the *spuA* gene) are clearly embedded within the
466 Mitis lineage, suggesting multiple acquisitions of the *spuA* gene cluster. The mobility of the
467 *spuA* cluster within *C. diphtheriae* populations may lead to its acquisition by novel sublineages
468 in the future, which may then be converted from Mitis to Gravis biovar. The polyphyly of

469 Gravis clearly calls for caution in interpreting biovar status for strain classification and
470 epidemiological tracing.

471 Several virulence-associated genes were largely conserved in the entire *C. diphtheriae*
472 species; these genomic features may therefore be central for *C. diphtheriae* colonization and
473 transmission among humans, as there appears to be a strong selective pressure to maintain them.
474 The distribution of other, more variably present virulence-associated genes uncovers an
475 interesting structuration of *C. diphtheriae* populations, previously undescribed to our
476 knowledge. The two Spa systems SpaD and SpaH were almost exclusively observed in
477 sublineages of the Gravis branch. Perhaps even more strikingly, the differential association of
478 Mitis and Gravis lineages with iron-capture systems *irp1*, *irp2* and heme acquisition genes
479 *chtAB* and *htaB* (which are all under the regulation of the same iron-dependent transcriptional
480 repressor as the *tox* gene, DtxR) was very neat. Whereas the two *irp* clusters were largely
481 conserved in the Mitis branch and absent in the Gravis branch, the reverse was true for heme-
482 acquisition genes.

483

484 These observations open intriguing questions on possible differential ecology, transmission,
485 virulence or association with clinical forms of the two major lineages that divide *C. diphtheriae*
486 populations, since adhesion and iron acquisition are important features of most bacterial
487 pathogens. Iron acquisition is an important driver of the evolution of bacterial pathogens, and
488 bacteria have evolved multiple systems that are optimized in different types of infections (*e.g.*,
489 yersiniabactin in *Klebsiella* and its association with lung infections). As another example, two
490 iron acquisition mechanisms that show similarity to those found in *C. diphtheriae* have been
491 described in *Y. pestis* (Iteman et al., 1993): hemin storage (*hmsAB* locus) and iron-regulated
492 protein synthesis (*irp* locus). Similarly to what was observed in *C. diphtheriae* with *chtB/htaB*
493 double mutants (Allen et al., 2013), Δ *hmsAB* in *Y. pestis* showed reduced growth (Iteman,
494 1993). In addition, *irp2* was associated uniquely with highly pathogenic *Y. pestis* isolates. The
495 importance of *irp2* in *C. diphtheriae* virulence has not yet been investigated *in vivo*, however
496 our results suggest a critical role of both *irp2* and *chtAB/htaB* in the evolution of *C. diphtheriae*
497 main lineages: a switch of iron acquisition systems, from *irp1/irp2* to *chtAB* (or vice-versa if
498 the Gravis branch is ancestral), may have impacted the biology of infection of the Gravis and
499 Mitis branches. Whether the apparent mutually exclusive pattern of iron acquisition systems
500 reflect functional incompatibility, simple redundancy, or adaptations to different niches, stands
501 out as an interesting question for future studies.

502 The three Spa systems of *C. diphtheriae* were shown experimentally to be involved in
503 adhesion to different human tissues. The presence in the Gravis branch of the SpaD and SpaH
504 fimbriae, which enable adhesion to the larynx and pulmonary cells (Mandlik et al., 2007), may

505 have implications on the infection tropism of this lineage and the ensuing clinical forms.
506 Interestingly, the Gravis biovar was initially defined following a shift in diphtheria
507 epidemiology in the 1930s, when more severe forms of the disease were observed that reacted
508 less well to antitoxin treatment and were observed in school rather than pre-school children
509 (McLeod, 1943). It was also noted by then, that laryngeal obstruction was associated with Mitis,
510 whereas the pharyngeal and more severe form was associated with the Gravis type. Of note, the
511 1930s epidemics may have been caused by *C. diphtheriae* sublineages distinct from those
512 observed currently; in this respect, the availability of historical isolates would be extremely
513 valuable.

514 The Gravis/Mitis dichotomy in Spa-type fimbriae and iron acquisition systems may
515 have important consequences regarding the pathophysiology by these two main lineages of
516 *C. diphtheriae*. Our work opens interesting hypotheses as to the underlying mechanisms of
517 variation in clinical severity and forms of diphtheria. Here we also note that Gravis isolates
518 were less frequently *tox*-positive than Mitis isolates, which would suggest that the risk of
519 acquiring a toxigenic infection by Gravis is lower than by Mitis. However, we have no detailed
520 clinical data corresponding to most of the isolates in this study, and it cannot be excluded that
521 *tox*-positive Gravis infections are more severe than Mitis ones.

522 Antimicrobial resistance remains of moderate clinical concern in *C. diphtheriae* (WHO,
523 2018; Zasada, 2014). Although resistant strains have been described, including multidrug
524 resistant ones, their origin and dissemination patterns are largely unknown. Here, we provide
525 an overview of the prevalence and distribution of resistance genes or mutations across
526 sublineages, leading to identify sublineages that carry multiple resistance genes and/or
527 resistance genes that threaten first-line treatment. Because antimicrobial resistance phenotypes
528 are typically unattached to publicly available genomic sequences, it is not possible to link these
529 genomic features complements to resistance phenotypes systematically. However, previous
530 works clearly showed that most resistance genetic features identified here may impact
531 resistance phenotypes (Tauch et al., 1995, 2003; Hennart et al., 2020; Forde et al., 2020).

532 Clearly, antimicrobial resistance genes distribution across geography and time should
533 be taken with great caution, given that most cases in European countries, for example, are
534 imported from other world regions. The country of recent travel or origin of migrants would
535 provide a more relevant picture of the geographic distribution of resistant strains. Similarly,
536 although our data suggest that the resistance score did not increase dramatically over recent
537 times (**Figure S10**), isolates inclusion criteria and their possible dependency on resistance
538 phenotypes should be controlled in future studies. The DIPHTOSCAN tool will facilitate future
539 studies on the genetic determinants of resistance in *C. diphtheriae* and the emergence of
540 sublineages of concern.

541 Future updates of the DIPHTOSCAN tool will include a description of the genetic context
542 of resistance features, which will facilitate the identification of multi-resistance elements and
543 their horizontal transfer within *C. diphtheriae* populations.

544 In conclusion, we have developed the bioinformatics tool DIPHTOSCAN, to conveniently
545 extract and interpret genomic features that are relevant to the clinical and public health
546 management of diphtheria cases. This dedicated tool is also applicable to the other members of
547 the Corynebacteria of the *diphtheriae* complex, such as *C. ulcerans* (data not shown). We
548 expect this tool to facilitate harmonization of genomic studies in this group of pathogens, which
549 have been largely forgotten but currently undergo renewed interest due to re-emergence of
550 diphtheria in Europe and elsewhere. DIPHTOSCAN will not only support genomic surveillance
551 of diphtheria but should also prove useful for future investigations into the links between strain
552 genotypes and clinical phenotypes, which remain a mysterious but highly promising avenue of
553 future research and would contribute to enhance understanding of the pathogenesis of modern
554 diphtheria.

Material & Methods

555

556 **Strain selection**

557 A total of 1250 isolates (**Table S1**) were included into the study dataset.

558 First, we sequenced 374 isolates for this study and to which we then added 226 strains from
559 previous articles (Hennart et al., 2020; Badell et al., 2021; Guglielmini et al., 2021). This set
560 represents data from the French Reference Center.

561 Second, 650 isolates from previously published genomic studies in South Africa (du
562 Plessis et al., 2017), Germany-Switzerland (Meinel et al., 2016), Germany (Berger et al., 2019;
563 Dangel et al., 2018), France (Pivot et al., 2019), Canada (Chorlton et al., 2019) Austria
564 (Schaeffer et al., 2020), the USA (Williams et al., 2020; Xiaoli et al., 2020), Spain (Hoefer et
565 al., 2020), India (Will et al., 2021) and Australia (Timms et al., 2018) and Rybotype (Grimont
566 et al., 2004) were included.

567 From this global set of 1250 genomes, we created a non-redundant subset of genomes
568 by randomly selecting one genome per genomic cluster (threshold: 25 cgMLST mismatches;
569 see below), isolation year and city (if city was unavailable, the country was used instead); this
570 deduplicated subset comprised 977 genomes.

571

572 **Basic principles of DIPHTOSCAN**

573 To develop DIPHTOSCAN, we combined code from Kleborate, NCBI database of AMR
574 genes, the tool's execution AMRfinderPlus. The structure of pipeline and database custom are
575 presented in **Figure_1** and **Figure_2**. The functionalities is presented in **Figure_S0**

576

577 **Pan and core genome analysis**

578 In this study, the panaroo v1.2.3 tool was used to generate the pan-genome. This tool
579 allowed us to construct a multiple sequence alignment of the core genome (cg-MSA) from the
580 assembled genomic sequences. For this, the genome sequences were annotated using PROKKA
581 v1.14.5 with default parameters, resulting in GFF files. Protein-coding gene clusters were
582 defined with a threshold of 70% amino acid identity, and core genes were concatenated into a
583 cg-MSA when present in 95% of genomes. IQtree version 2 was used to build a phylogenetic
584 tree based on the cg-MSA, with the best fitting model TVM+F+R5. The tree is available at:
585 <https://itol.embl.de/tree/1579917435471751662784292>.

586

587 **Assignment of species, MLST and Sequence Types (ST)**

588 The species prediction function of DIPHTOSCAN provides a convenient way to confirm
589 species. DIPHTOSCAN calculates Mash distances (Mash v2.2) between the query genomes and

590 a collection of reference assemblages of the diphtheria complex and reports the species with
591 the smallest distance. Mash distance ≤ 0.05 is reported as a strong match, ≤ 0.1 as weak. We
592 have used and adapted the structure of the Kleborate tool for this function.
593 MLST profiles and ST were defined using the international MLST scheme for *C. diphtheriae*
594 and *C. ulcerans*. DIPHTOSCAN scan these genotypes, using the script of this Kleborate function.
595 The update MLST profiles and alleles database used a script of BIGSdb.

596

597 **Identification virulent and antibiotic resistant genes in genome**

598 The antibiotic resistant gene were identified by AMRfinderPlus, with the database at :
599 https://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pathogen/Antimicrobial_resistance/. They are detected by a blast
600 whose identity and coverage depends on the families of antibiotics (fam.tab). Some genes:
601 *pbp2M* and mutation points of *rpoB* and *gyrA* genes were added.

602 The virulent resistant gene were identified by AMRfinderPlus but we have add the
603 sequence in database.

604 For the main virulence factor, *tox* gene, we used as reference (WP_014654963.1;
605 WP_014835773.1; WP_003850266.1), that is to say one sequence per Cdc species being able
606 to carry the *tox* gene. DIPHTOSCAN predicts the toxicity of a strain from the *tox* gene sequence
607 in the following way (4 outputs are possible): (i) if the sequence is identical to a reference, the
608 output is identical to the name of the sequence with the denomination of the species (ex:
609 *tox_diphtheriae*), (ii) if it has a coverage identical to the reference but a different identity then
610 a star (*) is present (ex: *tox_diphtheriae**), (iii) if the coverage is lower than the reference then
611 the mention '-NTTB?- xx%' (where xx is the percentage of the truncated sequence) is present;
612 (iv) finally if the symbol '\$' is present it means that the truncated part is located at the end of
613 the contigs (this means that the prediction is to be taken with precaution because it is probably
614 due to an error of assembly of the genome). The gene of virulence, they are detected by BlastN
615 with 80% identity and 50% coverage.

616

617 **Merging of the Oxford and Pasteur MLST databases**

618 Two BIGSdb databases were originally designed separately for distinct purposes: while
619 Oxford's PubMLST database mainly offered MLST, the Pasteur database was used for the
620 *Corynebacterium* cgMLST typing.

621 To merge the data available in the two databases, we proceeded as follows. As per
622 BIGSdb dual design, isolates genomes and provenance data were imported into the "isolates"
623 database, whereas allelic definitions of MLST were imported into the "seqdef" database.
624 Regarding the isolates database, we first downloaded the Oxford database. Secondly, we
625 imported MLST alleles definitions and profile into Pasteur and launch MLST analysis on all

626 Pasteur isolates. Then, we imported Oxford isolates into this new database. To avoid isolate
627 entries duplication, we first identified common isolates between the two databases and check
628 ST assignments. Duplicate isolate with same ST were not imported in Pasteur database. At the
629 end, 684 out of 934 Oxford's isolate were kept (73%). To facilitate the understanding of
630 historical origins of each entry, isolates identification numbers
631 (BIGSdb ID number) were defined as follows: isolates from the original Oxford database
632 were numbered from 1520 to 2003. We also added them to a single public project called
633 "Oxford" (project ID 13).

634 As the September 22th, 2022, the platform resulting from the merger comprises 1,478
635 public isolates entries with 794 genomes, and 2,392 isolates in total when considering private
636 entries. The number of entries varied across species: *Corynebacterium* species *C. diphtheriae*
637 (n = 1,291 or 87.4%) and *C. ulcerans* (n = 131 or 8.9%, and 127 imported from Oxford
638 database), *C. belfantii* (n = 45 or 3.0%) and *C. rouxii* (n = 10 or 0.7%). The MLST have now
639 854 registered ST.

640 A nomenclature of the diphtheria toxin gene alleles was developed in the following
641 way: ([https://bigsdbs.pasteur.fr/cgi-](https://bigsdbs.pasteur.fr/cgi-bin/bigsdbs/bigsdbs.pl?db=pubmlst_diphtheria_seqdef&page=schemeInfo&scheme_id=4)
642 [bin/bigsdbs/bigsdbs.pl?db=pubmlst_diphtheria_seqdef&page=schemeInfo&scheme_id=4](https://bigsdbs.pasteur.fr/cgi-bin/bigsdbs/bigsdbs.pl?db=pubmlst_diphtheria_seqdef&page=schemeInfo&scheme_id=4)).

643

644 **Code availability**

645 The code was made available at <https://gitlab.pasteur.fr/BEBP/diphotoscan>.

646

Figure legends

647 **Figure 1. Phylogenetic tree of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae***

648 The tree was obtained using a multiple sequence alignment of the core genome (see
649 supplementary material). The main lineages Mitis and Gravis are labeled, and their branches
650 are drawn using purple and green, respectively. The first ten colored circles around the tree
651 correspond to the different classes of antibiotics. The following seven circles, with a blue
652 gradient, correspond to the different clusters or genes of virulence. For each circle, the darkest
653 color indicates the presence of the genomic determinants (gene or mutation) and the lightest
654 color represents the absence of the genomic determinant. The scale bar gives the number of
655 nucleotide substitutions per site.

656

657 **Figure S2. Resistance genes frequencies**

658 The number of strains per antibiotics families. The bars are colored according to their presence
659 of determinant resistance gene (see keys).

660

661 **Figure S14. SL distribution of isolates**

662 (Top) The number of strains per SL (All dataset, i.e. 1250 isolates). Red is the color that
663 represents predicted toxigenic strains, classic orange are predicted non-toxigenic strains, orange
664 with dots are strains where the prediction is uncertain and white are strains that do not have the
665 *tox* gene. (Bottom) The number of strains per SL (All dataset, i.e. 1250 isolates). The bars are
666 colored according avec the score number, i.e. the number de resistance families present in the
667 strains (see keys).

Supplementary figure legends

668

669

670 **Figure S1. Flowchart of diphtOscan**

671 Description of the diphtOscan features.

672

673 **Figure S2. Structure of diphtOscan**

674 Description of the structure of the diphtOscan tool.

675

676 **Figure S3. Structure of database**

677 Description of the structure of the diphtOscan database.

678

679 **Figure S4. Temporal distribution of isolates**

680 (A) All dataset, i.e. 1250 isolates. The number of strains per year, only strains isolated between
681 1950 and 2021 are represented. The dataset “French NRC genomes” includes the dataset
682 “Recent clinical isolates” and “Historical clinical isolates” are represented in dark- or light-
683 blue, whereas the ribotype strains are in gray and the public strains in green (both compose
684 “non-French NRC genomes”).

685 (B) Subdataset, i.e. 977 isolates (for the selection see supplementary material). The number of
686 strains per year, only strains isolated between 1950 and 2021 are represented. The dataset
687 “French NRC genomes” includes the dataset “Recent clinical isolates” and “Historical clinical
688 isolates” are represented in dark- or light-blue, whereas the ribotype strains are in gray and the
689 public strains in green (both compose “non-French NRC genomes”).

690

691 **Figure S5. Genomic cluster distribution of isolates**

692 (A) All dataset, i.e. 1250 isolates. The number of strains per genomic cluster (only with at least
693 5 strains). The bars are colored according to their presence in the countries (see keys)

694 (B) Subdataset, i.e. 977 isolates (for the selection see supplementary material). The number of
695 strains per genomic cluster. The bars are colored according to their presence in the countries
696 (see keys).

697

698 **Figure S6. ST distribution of isolates**

699 (A) All dataset, i.e. 1250 isolates. The number of strains per ST. The bars are colored according
700 to their presence in the countries (see keys).

701 (B) Subdataset, i.e. 977 isolates (for the selection see supplementary material). The number of
702 strains per ST (only with at least 6 strains). The bars are colored according to their presence in
703 the countries (see keys).

704

705 **Figure S7. Sublineage (SL) distribution of isolates**

706 (A) All dataset, i.e. 1250 isolates. The number of strains per SL. The bars are colored according
707 to their presence in the countries (see keys)

708 (B) Subdataset, i.e. 977 isolates (for the selection see supplementary material). The number of
709 strains per SL (only with at least 6 strains). The bars are colored according to their presence in
710 the countries (see keys).

711

712 **Figure S8. Sublineage (SL) distribution of isolates**

713 (A) All dataset, i.e. 1250 isolates. The number of strains per SL. The bars are colored according
714 to their presence of *tox* gene by diphtOscan. Red is the color that represents predicted toxigenic
715 strains, classic orange are predicted non-toxigenic strains, orange with dots are strains where
716 the prediction is uncertain and white are strains that do not have the *tox* gene.

717 (B) Subdataset, i.e. 977 isolates (for the selection see supplementary material).

718

719

720 **Figure S9. Temporal distribution of isolates**

721 The number of strains per year, only strains isolated between 1950 and 2021 are represented
722 and on the all dataset, i.e. 1250 isolates. The bars are colored according avec the score number,
723 i.e. the number de resistance families present in the strains (see keys).

724

725 **Figure S10. Sublineage (SL) distribution of isolates**

726 (Top) The number of strains per SL (All dataset, i.e. 1250 isolates). The bars are colored
727 according avec the score number, i.e. the number de resistance families present in the strains
728 (see keys).

729 (Bottom) The number of strains per SL (All dataset, i.e. 1250 isolates). Penicillin- and/or
730 erythromycin-resistant strains are colored with darker green (see key).

731

732 **Figure S11. Sublineage (SL) distribution of isolates**

733 (A) All dataset, i.e. 1250 isolates. The number of strains per SL. The bars are colored according
734 avec the score number, i.e. the number de resistance families present in the strains (see keys).

735 (B) Subdataset, i.e. 977 isolates (for the selection see supplementary material). The bars are
736 colored according avec the score number, i.e. the number de resistance families present in the
737 strains (see keys).

738

739 **Figure S12. Country distribution of isolates**

740 The number of strains per country (All dataset, i.e. 1250 isolates). The bars are colored
741 according avec the score number, i.e. the number de resistance families present in the strains
742 (see keys).

743

744

745

746

Supplementary tables

747

748 **Table S1. List of antimicrobial resistance features detected by diphtOscan**

749

750 **Table S2. Characteristic of the isolates**

751

752 **Table S3. Ribotype reference strains and their genomic classification**

753

754 **Table S4. Characteristics of the ST groups**

755

756 **Table S5. Characteristics of the SLs groups**

757

758 **Table S6. Raw diphtOscan results for 1250 *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* genomes**

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772

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776 have applied a CC-BY public copyright license to any Author Manuscript version arising from
777 this submission.

778

779 **Declaration of interest statement**

780 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

781

782 **Ethical approval statement**

783 To conduct the research, we used bacterial strains, which are not considered human samples.
784 Accordingly, this research was not considered human research and is out of the scope of the
785 decree n° 2016-1537 of November 16, 2016 implementing law n° 2012-300 of March 5, 2012
786 on research involving human subjects. Therefore, no ethics approval was needed and no
787 informed consent was required.

788 All French bacteriological samples were collected in the frame of the French national diphtheria
789 surveillance and are collected, coded, shipped, managed and analyzed according to the French
790 National Reference Center protocols that received approval by French competent body CNIL
791 (Commission Nationale Informatique et Libertés; approval number: 1474671). Other strains
792 were obtained from culture collections.

793 The research conformed to the principles of the Helsinki Declaration.

794

795 **Author contributions**

796 S.B. conceived, designed, and coordinated the study. M.H. developed the diphtOscan tool.
797 M.H. and S.B. analyzed the genomic data. M.H. created the figures and tables. S.B. and M.H.
798 contributed to the first draft of the manuscript, worked together to improve it and reviewed the
799 final version.

800

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Figure 1. Phylogenetic tree of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*

Figure 2. Resistance genes frequencies

Figure 3. SL distribution of isolates

**PARTIE II : TAXONOMIE GÉNOMIQUE ET DIVERSITÉ
DES SOUCHES CHEZ LES ESPÈCES BACTÉRIENNES
PATHOGÈNES**

Chapitre 3 : Une taxonomie génomique des souches de *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

Titre de l'article

A dual barcoding approach to bacterial strain nomenclature: Genomic taxonomy of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains

Résumé

Les sous-lignées (SLs) au sein des espèces microbiennes peuvent différer considérablement dans leur écologie et leur pathogénicité, et leur définition précise est importante dans la recherche fondamentale et les applications industrielles ou de santé publique. Des stratégies largement acceptées pour définir les SLs manquent actuellement, ce qui rend la communication confuse en biologie des populations et en surveillance épidémiologique. Nous proposons ici une approche de classification et de nomenclature génomique largement applicable pour les souches bactériennes, en utilisant la principale menace pour la santé publique *Klebsiella pneumoniae* comme modèle. Sur la base d'un schéma de typage de séquences multilocus du génome central (cgMLST) de 629 gènes, nous avons conçu un système de double codes-barres qui combine le single linkage à multi-niveaux (MLSL) et les numéros d'identification de la vie (LIN). Les analyses phylogénétiques et de regroupement de plus de 7 000 séquences génomiques ont permis de capturer des discontinuités de la structure de la population, qui ont été utilisées pour guider la définition de 10 seuils de dissimilarité génétique infraspécifique. La nomenclature du typage de séquences multilocus (MLST) à 7 gènes, largement utilisée, a été cartographiée sur les SLs du MLSL (seuil : 190 mésappariements alléliques) et les identificateurs de groupes clonaux (seuil : 43) pour assurer la rétrocompatibilité de la nomenclature. La taxonomie est accessible au public via une plateforme gérée par la communauté (<https://bigsd.b.pasteur.fr/klebsiella>), qui permet également l'identification des séquences génomiques des utilisateurs externes.

La taxonomie des souches proposée combine deux systèmes de codes-barres informatifs sur le plan phylogénétique qui offrent une stabilité totale (codes LIN) et une continuité nomenclaturale avec la nomenclature précédente (MLSL). Cette stratégie de double code-barres spécifique à l'espèce pour la taxonomie génomique des souches microbiennes est largement applicable et devrait contribuer à unifier les connaissances collaboratives mondiales et intersectorielles sur l'émergence et la microévolution des pathogènes bactériens.

Contributions personnelles

- Extraction et incorporation à partir des génomes publics dans une base de données
- Prétraitement des génomes afin d'établir un jeu de données pour l'ensemble des analyses de l'article
- Analyse des données génomiques : analyse des données génomiques des isolats de l'étude, construction de la phylogénie
- Développement de méthodes et de scripts : adaptation de l'approche LIN au cgMLST, méthode d'optimisation l'ordre d'entrée pour l'encodage LIN, transformation des

codes LIN en arbre des préfixes, détection des hybrides au sein de l'espèce, héritabilité de la nomenclature ST à la nomenclature développée (MLSL)

- Réalisation de l'ensemble des figures principales et supplémentaires de l'article
- Contribution à la rédaction du manuscrit

A Dual Barcoding Approach to Bacterial Strain Nomenclature: Genomic Taxonomy of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* Strains

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Abstract

Sublineages (SLs) within microbial species can differ widely in their ecology and pathogenicity, and their precise definition is important in basic research and for industrial or public health applications. Widely accepted strategies to define SLs are currently missing, which confuses communication in population biology and epidemiological surveillance. Here, we propose a broadly applicable genomic classification and nomenclature approach for bacterial strains, using the prominent public health threat *Klebsiella pneumoniae* as a model. Based on a 629-gene core genome multilocus sequence typing (cgMLST) scheme, we devised a dual barcoding system that combines multilevel single linkage (MLSL) clustering and life identification numbers (LINs). Phylogenetic and clustering analyses of >7,000 genome sequences captured population structure discontinuities, which were used to guide the definition of 10 infraspecific genetic dissimilarity thresholds. The widely used 7-gene multilocus sequence typing (MLST) nomenclature was mapped onto MLSL SLs (threshold: 190 allelic mismatches) and clonal group (threshold: 43) identifiers for backwards nomenclature compatibility. The taxonomy is publicly accessible through a community-curated platform (<https://bigsd.b.pasteur.fr/klebsiella>), which also enables external users' genomic sequences identification. The proposed strain taxonomy combines two phylogenetically informative barcode systems that provide full stability (LIN codes) and nomenclatural continuity with previous nomenclature (MLSL). This species-specific dual barcoding strategy for the genomic taxonomy of microbial strains is broadly applicable and should contribute to unify global and cross-sector collaborative knowledge on the emergence and microevolution of bacterial pathogens.

Key words: genomic classification, strain nomenclature, microevolution, pathogen tracking, genomic library, international harmonization.

Introduction

Taxonomy is a foundation of biology that entails the classification, nomenclature, and identification of biological objects (Cowan 1965). Although the Linnaean system is organized into taxonomic ranks down to the level of species (Sneath 1992), sublineages (SLs) within microbial species can diversify as independently evolving lineages that persist over long periods of time (Selander and Levin 1980), and the broad microbial species definition and horizontal gene transfer (HGT) of accessory genes underlie extensive strain heterogeneity of phenotypes with ecological, medical, or industrial relevance (Hacker and Kaper 2000; Lan and Reeves 2001; Feil 2004; Konstantinidis and Tiedje 2005). Nevertheless, strain-level diversity is overlooked by the current prokaryotic taxonomy.

Most attempts to develop and maintain microbial strain taxonomies aimed at facilitating epidemiological

surveillance and outbreak detection (Maiden et al. 1998, 2013; van Belkum et al. 2007). Although local epidemiology can rely on vernacular type designations, the benefits of unified nomenclatures of SLs for large-scale epidemiology and population biology were recognized early (Struelens et al. 1998). By far the most successful taxonomic system of microbial strains is the multilocus sequence typing (MLST) approach (Maiden et al. 1998; Achtman et al. 2012). This highly reproducible and portable nomenclature system has been extensively used for studies of population biology and public health surveillance of bacterial pathogens (Jolley et al. 2018). Core genome MLST (cgMLST) extends the advantages of the MLST approach at the genomic scale (Jolley and Maiden 2010; Maiden et al. 2013) and provides strain discrimination at much finer scales.

Strain classification, based either on cgMLST or on nucleotide polymorphisms, can be achieved by using several

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clustering thresholds simultaneously, leading to a succession of group identifiers (“barcodes”) that provide relatedness information at increasing levels of phylogenetic depth (Maiden et al. 2013; Moura et al. 2016). This approach was recently formalized as hierarchical clustering (HierCC, based on cgMLST) (Zhou et al. 2021) and as the “single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) address” (Dallman et al. 2018), based on single linkage classifications; here, we generically refer to these approaches as MultiLevel Single Linkage (MLSL). Unfortunately, the single linkage clustering may result in the fusion of preexisting groups as additional genomes are introduced, due to the possibility of new genomes being less distant than the threshold, from two distinct groups. This approach thus suffers from instability, which led HierCC inventors to instead use ad hoc group attribution rules after an initial single linkage classification (Zhou et al. 2021).

An alternative approach, the life identification number (LIN) encoding, was proposed by Vinatzer and colleagues (Vinatzer et al. 2017; Tian et al. 2020): a multiposition numerical code is assigned to each genome based on its similarity with the closest genome already encoded. An attractive property of this procedure is that LIN codes are definitive, that is, not affected by subsequent additions of genomes, as they are attributed to individual genomic sequences rather than to groups. However, in the current implementation of LIN codes, the similarity between genomes is estimated using average nucleotide identity (ANI), which may be imprecise for nearly identical strains.

Here, we present a strain classification, naming, and identification system for bacterial strains, which is based on cgMLST and combines the MLSL and LIN code approaches. We took as a model the *Klebsiella pneumoniae* species complex, a genetically and ecologically highly diverse bacterial group that causes a wide range of infections in humans and animals (Brisse et al. 2006; Wyres, Lam, et al. 2020). Given its extensive diversity and fast evolutionary dynamics, *K. pneumoniae* is a challenging model for the development of a genomic taxonomy of strains. Moreover, the rapid emergence and global dissemination of multi-drug resistance in *K. pneumoniae*, sometimes combined with high virulence (Bialek-Davenet et al. 2014; Wyres, Nguyen, et al. 2020), have created a pressing need for an efficient *K. pneumoniae* strain definition and tracking system.

Results

Genome-Based Phylogenetic Structure of the *K. pneumoniae* Species Complex

The deep phylogenetic structure of the *K. pneumoniae* (Kp) species complex (KpSC) (fig. 1) reflects the previously recognized seven major phylogroups, Kp1–Kp7 (Brisse and Verhoef 2001; Fevre et al. 2005; Blin et al. 2017; Long et al. 2017; Rodrigues et al. 2019; Wyres, Lam, et al. 2020). The most represented phylogroup (91.7%; $n = 6,476$) is Kp1,

that is, *K. pneumoniae sensu stricto* (table 1), and its phylogenetic structure (fig. 2) revealed a multitude of SLs (note that below, we define sublineages and clonal groups [CGs] in a stricter sense in “Definition of classification thresholds for phylogroups, sublineages, and clonal groups”). There were multiple closely related isolates within some SLs, most prominently within an SL comprising genomes with 7-gene MLST identifiers ST258, ST11, ST512 (fig. 2), which represented more than one-third (33.4%) of the Kp1 data set. The abundance of this SL (and a few others, such as ST23) reflected the clinical microbiology focus on multidrug-resistant or hypervirulent isolates (Bowers et al. 2015; Struve et al. 2015; Lam et al. 2018; Wyres, Nguyen, et al. 2020). The phylogenetic structure within other *K. pneumoniae* phylogroups also revealed a multitude of distinct SLs but no predominant ones, and medically important lineages in these phylogroups are yet to be recognized.

Klebsiella pneumoniae strains can recombine large sections of their chromosome (Chen et al. 2014; Wyres et al. 2015). Large recombination events were detected in 1.9% (138/7,198) genomes (based on their cgMLST profiles) and involved the phylogroups Kp1, Kp2, and Kp4 (supplementary appendix: Detection of hybrids, fig. S1, and tables S1 and S2, Supplementary Material online). The phylogenetic impact of large-scale recombination is illustrated in figure 1, with “hybrids” occurring on misleadingly long branches.

cgMLST Analysis of the *K. pneumoniae* Species Complex

A previously defined cgMLST (named scgMLST, with 634 loci) scheme (Bialek-Davenet et al. 2014) was updated (supplementary table S3, Supplementary Material online) and defined as scgMLSTv2 (with 629 loci, as five of the original ones were removed; see Materials and Methods). cgMLST allelic profiles were then determined for 7,433 genomic sequences (including 45 reference sequences; supplementary fig. S2, Supplementary Material online). The mean number of missing alleles per profile was 8 (1.2%; standard deviation: 25; 4.0%), and most (7,198; 96.8%) isolates had a cgMLST profile with fewer than 30 (4.8%) missing alleles. Missing allele proportions did not vary significantly among phylogroups (table 1). The transcription-repair coupling factor *mfd* gene was atypical, with 778 alleles and an average allele size of 3,447 nucleotides (nt); for the other loci, the number of distinct alleles varied from 8 to 626 (median: 243) and was strongly associated with locus size (range: 123–2,826 nt; median: 758 nt; supplementary fig. S3, Supplementary Material online). Locus-by-locus recombination analyses detected evidence of intra-gene recombination (PHI test; 5% *P*-value significance) in half of the loci (318/629; 50.6%) and these exhibited more alleles than nonrecombining ones (supplementary table S3 and fig. S3, Supplementary Material online).

The distribution of pairwise allelic mismatch proportions among nonhybrid cgMLST allelic profiles was

FIG. 1. Genome-based phylogenetic tree of the *Klebsiella pneumoniae* species complex. The whole-genome distance-based tree was inferred using JolyTree. JolyTree uses *mash* to decompose each genome into a sketch of *k*-mers and to quickly estimate the *p*-distance between each pair of genomes; after transforming every *p*-distance into a pairwise evolutionary distance, a phylogenetic tree is inferred using FastME. The seven phylogroups are indicated. Red dots correspond to strains defined as interphylogroup hybrids. Scale bar, 0.01 nucleotide substitutions per site.

discontinuous (fig. 3), with four major modes centered around values 99.7% (627 mismatches; i.e., 0.3% similarity), 82.7% (520 mismatches; 17.3%), 12.4% (79 mismatches; 87.6%), and 2.0% (13 mismatches; 98%). ANI values (supplementary fig. S4, Supplementary Material online) varied from 92.8% to 100%, with two first modes at 93.5% and 95.5%, composed of interphylogroup strain comparisons. The corresponding genome pairs typically had only $\approx 2\%$ cgMLST similarity. In turn, whereas the range of ANI values was only 98–100% for intraspecies pairs, their cgMLST similarities occupied the much broader 5–100% range.

The 627-mismatch mode corresponded mostly to pairs of strains belonging to distinct species of the KpSC (fig. 3; supplementary fig. S4, Supplementary Material online), while a minor peak centered on 591 mismatches (supplementary fig. S5, Supplementary Material online) corresponded to comparisons between subspecies of *Klebsiella quasipneumoniae* and *Klebsiella variicola* (Kp2 and Kp4, and Kp3 and Kp5, respectively; supplementary fig. S4, Supplementary Material online). Whereas the 520-mismatch mode corresponded to inter-ST comparisons in 99.9% cases, the 13-mismatch mode was largely dominated by comparisons of cgMLST profiles with the same ST (68.2%; pairs of genomes within 402 distinct STs) or of single-locus variants (SLV; 30.8%). Finally, the 79-mismatch mode comprised a large proportion (48.0%) of ST258–ST11 comparisons and other comparisons of atypically closely related STs (supplementary fig. S5, Supplementary Material online).

Definition of Classification Thresholds for Phylogroups, SLs, and Clonal Groups

To determine optimal allelic mismatch thresholds that would reflect the KpSC population structure, the consistency and stability properties of single linkage clustering groups were assessed for every threshold value t from 1

to 629 allelic mismatches. The consistency (silhouette) coefficient S_t had a plateau of optimal values in the range corresponding to 118/629 (18.8%) to 355/629 (56.4%) allelic mismatches (fig. 3, blue curve). Analysis of the robustness to subsampling (W_t ; based on an adjusted Wallace coefficient; fig. 3, green curve) identified several ranges of allelic mismatch threshold values that were associated with maximal stability.

The above analyses led us to propose four deep classification levels. The two first thresholds, 610 and 585 allelic mismatches, enable species and subspecies separations, respectively. We next defined a threshold of 190 allelic mismatches, corresponding to the optimal combination of consistency and stability coefficients S_t and W_t . The single linkage clustering based on this threshold created 705 groups, which we here define as “SLs”. By design, this threshold separated into distinct groups, the pairs of cgMLST profiles corresponding to the major mode (at 520 mismatches), that is, the majority of genomes that have distinct STs within phylogroups. Finally, a threshold of 43 allelic mismatches was defined to separate genome pairs of the 79-mismatch mode. This value corresponded to the local optima of both S_t and W_t coefficients. Interestingly, this last threshold value was also located in the optimal range of compatibility with the classical 7-gene ST definitions (Rand index $R_t \geq 0.70$ was observed for $10 \leq t \leq 51$). The use of this threshold resulted in 1,147 groups, which we propose to define as “CGs”.

Overall, approximately half (547/1,147; 47.7%) of the CGs corresponded one-to-one with the SL level (supplementary table S4, Supplementary Material online): 77.6% (547/705) SLs contained a single CG, whereas 158 (22.4%) SLs comprised at least two CGs (supplementary table S5 and fig. S6, Supplementary Material online; fig. 4). Overall, CG compatibility with classical ST classification was high (i.e., $R_t = 0.72$, whereas it was only 0.50 for SLs).

The distribution of pairwise allelic mismatch values that involved hybrid genomes showed an additional peak

Table 1. Genome Dataset Phylogroup Breakdown, Quality Assessment and Diversity.

Taxonomic designation	Phylogroup	Initial no. genomes	No. QC-filtered	No. after applying filters	No. of hybrids	No. of nonhybrid genomes	No. of called alleles (mean, std)	No. of sequence types (ST)
<i>K. pneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>pneumoniae</i>	Kp1	6,737	218 (3.2%)	6,519 (90.6%)	43 (0.7%)	6,476 (91.7%)	624.6 (3.6)	705
<i>K. quasipneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>quasipneumoniae</i>	Kp2	115	1 (0.9%)	114 (1.6%)	8 (7.0%)	106 (1.5%)	604.0 (2.5)	49
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>variicola</i>	Kp3	309	8 (2.6%)	301 (4.2%)	37 (12.3%)	264 (3.7%)	615.4 (3.3)	149
<i>K. quasipneumoniae</i> subsp. <i>similipneumoniae</i>	Kp4	230	6 (2.6%)	224 (3.1%)	50 (22.3%)	174 (2.5%)	607.4 (1.9)	64
<i>K. variicola</i> subsp. <i>tropica</i>	Kp5	19	0 (0.0%)	19 (0.3%)	0 (0.0%)	19 (0.3%)	611.7 (1.8)	13
<i>K. quasivariicola</i>	Kp6	13	2 (15.4%)	11 (0.2%)	0 (0.0%)	11 (0.2%)	602.9 (1.8)	8
<i>K. africana</i>	Kp7	10	0 (0.0%)	10 (0.1%)	0 (0.0%)	10 (0.1%)	606.3 (1.6)	4
Total		7,433	235	7,198	138	7,060	mean 610.3 (2.36)	992

Fig. 2. Phylogenetic structure within phylogroup Kp1 (*K. pneumoniae sensu stricto*). The circular tree was obtained using IQ-TREE based on the concatenation of the genes of the scgMLSTv2 scheme; 1,600 isolates are included (see Materials and Methods). Labels on the external first circle represent 7-gene MLST ST identifiers (each alternation corresponds to a different ST and only ST with more than 20 strains are labeled). The second and third circles (light green and blue, respectively) show the alternation of CGs and SLs, respectively, labeling only groups with more than 20 isolates. Full correspondence between ST, SL, and CG identifiers is given in the [supplementary appendix, Supplementary Material online](#).

around 39 shared alleles (i.e., 590 allelic mismatches; [supplementary fig. S7, Supplementary Material online](#)). Therefore, these interphylogroup hybrids were placed into distinct partitions at the 585-mismatch level. However, as some of these hybrid genomes diverged by fewer than 585 allelic mismatches from two distinct phylogroups at the same time, they would cause the fusion of phylogroup partitions upon single linkage clustering. To highlight the impact of this phenomenon, hybrids

were first filtered out and next incorporated in a second single linkage clustering step ([supplementary appendix and fig. S8, Supplementary Material online](#)).

Phylogenetic Compatibility of SLs and Clonal Groups

To estimate the congruence of classification groups with phylogenetic relationships among genomic sequences, we quantified the proportion of monophyletic (single

FIG. 3. Distribution of pairwise cgMLST distances, clustering properties, and phylogenetic congruence. Values are plotted for the 7,060 genomes-data set. Threshold values (t) are shown on the X-axis, corresponding to allelic profile mismatch values up to 629 (or 100%). Grey histograms: distribution of pairwise allelic mismatches. The circles correspond to the different modes of distribution. The curves represent the consistency coefficient S_t (silhouette, blue) and stability coefficient W_t (green), respectively, obtained with each threshold t ; the corresponding scale is on the left Y-axis. To identify the two curves without reference to their colour, note that the S_t curve starts (at $X = 0$) approximately at 0.65 and the W_t

ancestor, exclusive group), paraphyletic (single ancestor, nonexclusive group), and polyphyletic (two or more distinct ancestors) groups. Regarding 7-gene MLST, 6,985 (98.9%) genomes had a defined ST, that is, an allele was called for each of the seven genes. Of the 992 distinct STs, 396 were nonsingleton STs (i.e., comprised at least two isolates). Of these, 286 (72.2%) were monophyletic, 9 were paraphyletic (2.3%), and 101 (25.5%) were polyphyletic. The monophyletic STs comprised only 22% of all genomes in nonsingleton STs.

Regarding cgMLST-based classification, there were 5 and 7 partitions at 610 and 585 allelic mismatch levels, respectively, and 100% of these were monophyletic. Among the 705 distinct SLs, 317 (45.0%) were nonsingleton, and most (310; 97.8%) of these were monophyletic (see [fig. 2](#) for Kp1); only three (0.9%) were paraphyletic, and four (1.3%) were polyphyletic ([supplementary table S4, Supplementary Material online](#)). The monophyletic SLs comprised a large majority (5,961/6,672; 89.3%) of genomes in nonsingleton STs.

Finally, 396 out of 1,147 (34.5%) CGs were nonsingleton; most (362; 91.4%) were monophyletic ([fig. 2](#)), whereas 8 (2.0%) were paraphyletic, and 26 (6.6%) were polyphyletic ([supplementary table S5, Supplementary Material online](#)). Monophyletic CGs comprised nearly half (3,030; 48.0%) of the genomes in the nonsingleton CGs, whereas 3,224 (51.1%) were in polyphyletic groups, mostly in CG258, CG340, and CG15.

Definition of Shallow-Level Classification Thresholds for Klebsiella Epidemiology

Although the scgMLSTv2 scheme comprises only 629 loci, or ~10% of a typical *K. pneumoniae* genome length

(512,856 nt out of 5,248,520 in the NTUH-K2044 genome), shallow-level classifications of genomic sequences might be useful for tentative outbreak delineation and epidemiological surveillance purposes, by ruling-out outliers. To provide flexible case cluster definitions, we classified KpSC cgMLST profiles using thresholds of 0, 1, 2, 4, 7, and 10 scgMLSTv2 allelic mismatches. Together with the four higher levels, the MSL nomenclature, therefore, comprises 10 classification levels in total. The classification groups corresponding to the 0-mismatch threshold correspond to groups of cgST profiles that only differ by missing data. We observed that profiles of isolates involved in previously reported KpSC outbreaks generally differed by no or 1 mismatch, with a maximum of five allelic mismatches ([supplementary tables S6 and S7, Supplementary Material online](#)), indicating that this classification approach may be useful for genomic surveillance and outbreak identification purposes.

Inheritance of the 7-Genes ST Identifiers into the cgMLST Classification, and Characteristics of Main SLs and CGs

To attribute SL and CG identifiers that corresponded maximally to the widely adopted 7-gene ST identifiers, we developed an inheritance algorithm to map MLST identifiers onto SL and CG partitions (see [supplementary appendix: Nomenclature inheritance algorithm, Supplementary Material online](#)). Of the 705 SLs, most (683; 96.9%) were named by inheritance and this was the case for 879 (76.6%) of the 1,047 CGs ([supplementary table S4, Supplementary Material online](#)). The resulting correspondence of cgMLST partitions with classical MLST was evident for the major groups ([fig. 4; supplementary fig. S6,](#)

FIG. 4. Concordance of SL, clonal group and 7-gene MLST classifications (Panel A: ST258 and related genomes; Panel B: ST23 and related genomes). Alluvial diagram obtained using RAWGraphs (Mauri et al. 2017) showing the correspondence between STs (7 genes identity), CGs (43 allelic mismatches threshold), and SLs (190 allelic mismatches threshold). Colors are arbitrarily attributed by the software for readability.

Supplementary Material online). For instance, the multidrug-resistant SL258 comprised isolates belonging to MLST sequence types (STs) ST258, ST11, ST512, ST340, ST437, and 25 other STs. SL258 consisted of 16 distinct CGs, of which the four most frequent were defined as CG258 (61.2%), CG340 (17.8%), CG11 (17.3%), and CG3666 (2.8%) (fig. 4). When compared with 7-gene MLST, most isolates of CG258 were ST258 (75.6%) or ST512 (22.6%), whereas CG11 mostly comprised ST11 genomes (98.0%). In turn, CG340 included a large majority of ST11 genomes (61.8%) and only 20.0% ST340 genomes, and was named CG340 rather than CG11 because CG11 was already attributed. Likewise, the majority (83/86;

96.5%) of ST23 genomes, which are associated with pyogenic liver abscess (Lam et al. 2018), were classified into SL23, which itself consisted mainly (84/90, 93.3%) of ST23 genomes (fig. 4). The well-recognized emerging multidrug-resistant KpSC populations of ST15, ST101, ST147, and ST307 each corresponded largely to a single SL and CG (supplementary fig. S6, Supplementary Material online).

The frequency of detection of virulence and antimicrobial resistance genes differed among the main SLs and CGs (fig. 6; supplementary fig. S9, Supplementary Material online). As expected (Lam et al. 2021), SL23 (median virulence score of 5) and SL86 (median score 3) were

Fig. 5. Phylogenetic relationships are reflected in cgLIN code prefixes. Left: the prefix tree generated from cgLIN codes; Right: phylogenetic relationships derived using IQ-TREE from the cgMLST gene sequences from the reference strains. The cgLIN codes are also shown. The values indicated on top of the prefix tree correspond to the cgMLST similarity percentage of the corresponding cgLIN code bin.

prominent “hypervirulent” SLs, and they were largely lacking resistance genes. In contrast, a majority of strains from SLs 258, 147, 101, 307, and 37, as well as a large number of other SLs, had a resistance score of 2 or more, indicative of BLSE/carbapenemases, but these had modest virulence scores (supplementary fig. S9, Supplementary Material online). SL231 genomes stood out as combining high virulence and resistance scores. In some cases, CGs within single major SLs had contrasted virulence and resistance gene contents (fig. 6).

Development and Implementation of a cgMLST-Based LIN Code System

Following the principle of the LIN code system, initially proposed based on the ANI similarity (Marakeby et al. 2014), we defined a cgMLST-based LIN (cgLIN) code approach. As LIN coding is performed sequentially, we first explored the impact on the resulting partitioning of cgMLST profiles, of the order in which genomes are assigned. We confirmed that the number of partitions (hence their content too) varied according to input order (supplementary fig. S10, Supplementary Material online). However, we established that the order of genomes determined by the traversal of a Minimum Spanning tree (MSTree) (Prim 1957) naturally induces a LIN encoding order that is optimal, that is, most parsimonious with respect to the number of identifiers generated at each position of the code (see supplementary appendix, Supplementary Material online). Using this MSTree traversal strategy, we defined cgLIN codes for the 7,060 non-hybrid genomes (as a first step), resulting in 4,889 distinct cgLIN codes.

Furthermore, cgLIN codes can be displayed in the form of a prefix tree (fig. 5), which largely reflects the phylogenetic relationships among genomes. In addition, cgLIN code prefixes can be used to label particular phylogenetic lineages (Vinatzer et al. 2017). For example, a single cgLIN code prefix defined each phylogroup (e.g., Kp1: prefix 0_0; Kp2: prefix 2_0; fig. 5). Likewise, a full one-to-one correspondence between prefixes and SLs was observed, and almost all (99.4%) CGs also had a unique prefix (supplementary tables S4 and S5, Supplementary Material online; fig. 6).

Effect of Hybrid Genomes Incorporation on the MSL and cgLIN Codes Classifications

Because interphylogroup hybrid genomes have smaller distances to their parental phylogroups than the interphylogroup distances resulting from vertical evolutionary events, their incorporation into the MSL classification may induce the fusion of previously distinct single linkage groups. To illustrate this chaining effect, the “hybrid” genomes were included into the MSL nomenclature in a second step, and fusions of previously existing partitions were recorded; for example, at the 610 allelic mismatch threshold, partitions 2 (Kp2 and Kp4) and 4 (Kp3 and Kp5) were merged with partition 1 (Kp1). At the 585-mismatch threshold, partitions 5 (Kp2) and 2 (Kp4) were merged with partition 1 (Kp1). At the 190-mismatch threshold, only one fusion was observed, between partitions 184 (SL113) and 465 (SL1518; supplementary fig. S11, Supplementary Material online). The partitions at other thresholds were not impacted by the addition of the hybrid genomes.

Fig. 6. cgLIN code prefixes, and virulence and antimicrobial resistance scores of some SLs and their CGs. Left (green) four first columns: LIN prefixes of selected SLs and CGs. Right: heatmaps of virulence and resistance scores of CGs, and the number of genomes in each group. For each genome, the virulence score derived from Kleborate has a value from 0 to 5; the value in the cells corresponds to the percentage of strains in the group with that virulence score (similar to a heat map). The principle is the same for the resistance score, but it varies from 0 to 3.

In contrast, the incorporation of hybrid genomes into the cgLIN code database left the cgLIN codes of the 7,060 previous genomes entirely unaffected; there were no merging of groups, as per the design of the system. In particular, the seven phylogroup prefixes corresponding to species and subspecies remained unaffected (supplementary fig. S11, Supplementary Material online); instead, additional prefixes were created for the hybrid genomes (supplementary tables S1 and S2, Supplementary Material online).

Implementation of the Genomic Taxonomy in a Publicly Accessible Database

The MLSL nomenclature was incorporated into the Institut Pasteur *K. pneumoniae* MLST and whole-genome MLST databases (<https://bigsdbs.pasteur.fr/klebsiella>) under the classification scheme functionality developed in BIGSdb version 1.21.0. In brief, the cgMLST profile of every isolate with fewer than 30 missing scgMLSTv2 alleles was assigned to a core genome sequence type (cgST), and these were next grouped into single linkage partitions for each of the 10 classification levels. For SLs and CGs, a custom classification group field (named SL or CG within the system) was additionally populated with identifiers inherited from 7-gene MLST. All cgMLST profiles and classification identifiers are publicly available.

To allow users to identify *K. pneumoniae* isolates easily, a profile matching functionality was developed, enabling them to search for cgMLST profiles related to a query

genome sequence. This was implemented on the website sequence query page (<https://bigsdbs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/administration.html#scheme-profile-clustering-setting-up-classification-schemes>). This functionality returns the classification identifiers (including MLST-inherited CG and SL identifiers) of the cgMLST profile that is most closely related to the query genomic sequence, along with its number of mismatches compared with the closest profile.

cgLIN code functionality was also incorporated into BIGSdb version v1.34.0 (<https://bigsdbs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/administration.html#setting-up-lincode-definitions-for-cgmlst-schemes>). In particular, cgST profiles can be queried by full cgLIN code or any prefix, and a nomenclature can be attached to LINcode prefixes of interest (e.g., SL258 is attached to prefix 0_0_1 and CG258 to 0_0_105_6).

Note that the identification of users' query genomic sequences is made possible either through the BIGSdb platform that underlies the cgMLST website or externally after the export of the cgMLST profiles, which are publicly accessible.

Discussion

The existence within microbial species of SLs with unique genotypic and phenotypic properties underlines the need for infraspecific nomenclatures (Maiden et al. 1998; Lan and Reeves 2001; Rambaut et al. 2020). Similar to species

and higher Linnaean taxonomic ranks, a strain taxonomy should: (1) recognize genetic discontinuities and capture the most relevant SLs at different phylogenetic depths; (2) provide an unambiguous naming system for SLs; and (3) provide identification methods for placement within the taxonomic framework. Here, we developed a strain taxonomy consisting of a dual naming system that is grounded in population genetics and linked to an identification tool. The proposed system thus complies with the three fundamental pillars of taxonomy.

Although 7-gene MLST has been widely adopted as a taxonomic system of KpSC strains, several limitations are apparent: besides its restricted resolution, MLST identifiers do not convey phylogenetic information, as a single nucleotide substitution generates a different ST with unapparent relationships with its ancestor. Further, approximately half of the ST partitions were not monophyletic. The cgMLST approach provides much higher resolution and phylogenetic precision (Maiden et al. 2013; Zhou et al. 2021). Although other metrics such as whole-genome SNPs or ANI can be used to classify strains (Marakeby et al. 2014; Dallman et al. 2018), cgMLST presents advantages inherited from classical MLST, including standardization, reproducibility, portability and the conversion of sequences into human-readable allelic numbers. The high reproducibility and easy interpretation of cgMLST are two critical characteristics for its adoption in epidemiological surveillance. Here, we showed that cgMLST, based on 629 genes, has a much broader dynamic range than ANI when considering intraspecific variation (supplementary fig. S4, Supplementary Material online), and enables defining several hierarchical classification levels (Zhou et al. 2021). The resolutive power of the 629-loci cgMLST scheme provides valuable genotyping discrimination up to outbreak resolution and is highly consistent with whole-genome SNPs (Miro et al. 2020). However, to define shallower genetic structure within SLs resulting from recent clonal expansions or outbreaks, higher resolution should be sought based, for example, on core gene sets of specific SLs.

Optimization of threshold definitions based on population structure aims at optimizing cluster stability (Barker et al. 2018; Zhou et al. 2021). The density distribution of pairwise allelic mismatch dissimilarities within *K. pneumoniae* and related species exhibited genetic discontinuities at several phylogenetic depths. We took the benefit of this multimodal distribution to define optimal intraspecific classification thresholds and combined a clustering consistency coefficient (Silhouette) with a newly developed strategy that evaluates cluster stability by subsampling the entire data set. We defined four classifications at phylogenetic depths that reflected natural discontinuities within the population structure of *K. pneumoniae*, including the deep subdivisions of *K. pneumoniae sensu lato*. The 190-mismatch SL level was designed to capture the numerous deep phylogenetic branches within phylogroups (Bialek-Davenet et al. 2014; Holt et al. 2015). In turn, the CG level was useful to capture the genetic structuration observed within these primary SLs. For example, the

CG-level nomenclature captures the evolutionary split of CG258 and CG11 from their SL258 ancestor, caused by a 1.1 Mb recombination event (Chen et al. 2014) (supplementary fig. S5, Supplementary Material online).

Seven-locus MLST is a widely adopted nomenclature system, as illustrated by the widespread use of ST identifiers associated with hypervirulent or multidrug-resistant SLs (e.g., “*Klebsiella pneumoniae* ST258”: 293 PubMed hits; ST23: 117 hits; on July 20, 2021). Backward nomenclatural compatibility is therefore critical. After applying our inheritance algorithm, most SLs and CGs were labeled according to the 7-gene MLST identifier of the majority of their isolates. Widely adopted ST identifiers will therefore designate nearly the same strain groups within the proposed genomic taxonomy of *K. pneumoniae*, which should greatly facilitate its adoption. We note that the 7-gene MLST nomenclature will still have to be expanded, as this classical approach continues to be widely used. However, for practical reasons, upcoming MLST and cgMLST nomenclatural identifiers will be uncoupled, and we suggest that the cgMLST-based identifiers of SLs and CGs (rather than their ST) should be adopted as the reference nomenclature in the future.

Instability is a major limitation of single linkage clustering, caused by group fusion known as the chaining effect (Turner and Feil 2007). This is particularly relevant over epidemiological timescales, where intermediate genotypes (e.g., a recent ancestor or recombinant) are often sampled (Feil 2004). This issue is exacerbated in *K. pneumoniae*, where large-scale recombination may result in truly intermediate genotypes (Chen et al. 2014; Holt et al. 2015), referred to as “hybrids” by analogy to eukaryotic biology. Here, this phenomenon was illustrated through our delayed introduction into our nomenclature, of 138 interphylogroup hybrid genomes. The merging of predefined classification groups can be handled by classification versioning or ad hoc rules (Zhou et al. 2021), but this is indeterminate and challenging in practice.

To address its stability issue, we complemented the single linkage clustering approach with a fully stable approach. LIN codes were proposed as a universal genome coding system (Marakeby et al. 2014; Tian et al. 2020), a key feature of which is the generation of definitive genome codes that are inherently stable. The original LIN code system was based on the ANI metric; here, we noted that the ANI values that best correspond to some of the 10 cgMLST thresholds were highly similar (supplementary table S8, Supplementary Material online), casting doubt on the reliability of this metric for small-scale genetic distances. In addition, the ANI metric is nonreciprocal and highly dependent on comparison implementations and parameters. These shortfalls may yield imprecision and nonreproducibility that are particularly impactful for comparisons between very similar genomes. We, therefore, adapted the LIN code concept to cgMLST-based similarity (i.e., one-complement of the allelic mismatch proportions) to classify strains into a cgLIN code system. This strategy leverages the benefits of cgMLST and introduces more

intuitive shallow-level classification thresholds. The multi-level similarity information embedded in MLSL and cgLIN “barcodes” provides a human-readable snapshot of strain relationships, as nearly identical genomes have identical barcodes up to a position near the right end. In contrast to single linkage clustering partitions, one important limitation of LIN codes is that preexisting classification identifiers (e.g., ST258) cannot be mapped onto individual LIN code identifiers, because these are attributed with reference to the upper levels and are set to 0 for each downstream level (Marakeby et al. 2014). However, cgLIN code prefixes may represent useful labels for particular lineages.

The cgMLST-based nomenclatures have some limitations. First, a comparison of allele numbers rather than SNPs implies the loss of information. In turn, this approach is advantageous to estimate evolutionary relationships of closely related genomes that diverged following homologous recombination events, which are common among strains within bacterial species (Feil 2004; Vos and Didelot 2009). Second, MLST-based distances saturate more rapidly than SNP distances (once a locus is affected, even by a single mutation, further mutations at this locus will change the allele but will not increase the allelic distance), and are therefore mostly meaningful within bacterial species. Third, in contrast to the original ANI-based LIN code approach (Tian et al. 2020), cgMLST-based LIN codes require prior development of cgMLST schemes, which are larger, hence more powerful for strain resolution, for single species. Therefore, the advantages of cgLIN codes for population genomics and epidemiological questions come at the expense of universality. Still, the dual MLSL and cgLIN code approach proposed here is in principle applicable to all bacterial species (or closely related groups thereof) for which large representative sets of genomes are available. The cgLIN code algorithms were incorporated into BIGSdb and should be readily portable to other existing cgMLST platforms such as Enterobase. However, the use of genetic thresholds for an entire group of organisms may not always be meaningful, depending on the population genetic structure. Whereas *K. pneumoniae* shows strong structuring with neat peaks and valleys of pairwise genetic distances, other species may have a more fuzzy structure. In the latter cases, the approach will still be applicable, but even optimally defined thresholds may be less relevant biologically.

Conclusions

A unified nomenclature of pathogen genotypes is required to facilitate communication in the “One Health” and “Global Health” perspectives. *K. pneumoniae* represents a rapidly growing public health threat, and the availability of a common language to designate its emerging SLs is therefore highly timely. The proposed unified taxonomy of *K. pneumoniae* strains will facilitate advances on the biology of its SLs across niches, time, and space, and will endow surveillance networks with the capacity to efficiently monitor and control the emergence of SLs of high public health relevance.

Here, we propose a dual barcoding approach to bacterial strain taxonomy, which combines the complementary advantages of stability provided by the cgLIN codes, with an unstable, but human-readable MLSL nomenclature rooted in the popular 7-gene MLST nomenclature. Because they are definitive, cgLIN codes can be used for the traceability of cluster fusions that will occur occasionally in the MLSL arm of the dual taxonomy (supplementary fig. S11, Supplementary Material online). We contend the stability of cgLIN codes and their use alongside MLSL approaches provide a pragmatic solution to current attempts at developing genomic taxonomies of bacterial strains that are both stable and practical for human-to-human communication.

Materials and Methods

Definition of an Updated Core Genome MLST (scgMLSTv2) Genotyping Scheme

We previously defined a cgMLST (using *strict* synteny criteria, hence name scgMLSTv1) scheme of 634 highly syntenic genes (Bialek-Davenet et al. 2014). Here, we updated the scgMLSTv1 scheme, with the following improvements. First, two loci (KP1_2104 and *aceB* = KP1_0253) were removed because they were absent or truncated in multiple strains, based on 751 high-quality assemblies available in the BIGSdb-Pasteur *Klebsiella* database on October 16, 2017 (project id 11 at https://bigsd.bpasteur.fr/cgi-bin/bigsd/bigsdb.pl?db=pubmlst_klebsiella_isolates). Second, the remaining 632 loci templates were modified so that they would include the start and stop codons of the corresponding coding sequence (CDS). This was not the case for all CDSs of the scgMLSTv1 scheme, as some loci corresponded to internal portions of CDSs. These template redefinitions were done to harmonize locus definitions across the scheme. Of note, defining loci as complete CDSs also facilitates genotyping, by enabling precise identification of the extremities of novel alleles, through the search of the corresponding start and stop codons. As a result of these locus template extensions, three additional loci (*yraR*, *rnt* and KP1_1655) had to be removed because they were called in a low proportion of the above 751 genomes. The resulting 629 scgMLSTv2 genes have a summed length of 512,856 nt (9.8% of the genome of reference strain NTUH-K2044), when compared with 507,512 nt (9.7%) for the corresponding loci in scgMLSTv1.

Definition of a Genomic Sequence Data set of 7,060 Isolates with cgMLST Profiles

The KpSC comprises seven phylogroups that have been given taxonomic status in the prokaryotic nomenclature: *K. pneumoniae* subsp. *pneumoniae* (Kp1, also known as *K. pneumoniae sensu stricto*), *K. quasipneumoniae* subsp. *quasipneumoniae* (Kp2), *K. variicola* subsp. *variicola* (Kp3), *K. quasipneumoniae* subsp. *similipneumoniae* (Kp4), *K. variicola* subsp. *tropica* (Kp5), “*K. quasivariicola*”

(Kp6) and *K. africana* (Kp7) (Rodrigues et al. 2019). We retrieved all KpSC genomes from the GenBank assembly repository on March 15, 2019, corresponding to 8,125 assemblies. We then chose high-quality assemblies by excluding draft genomes: (1) containing more than 1,000 contigs of size >200 nt; (2) for which the ANI values (estimated using FastANI v1.1) were <96% against every reference strain of the taxonomic diversity of the SC (Rodrigues et al. 2019; supplementary table S9, Supplementary Material online); (3) of size ≤ 4.5 or ≥ 6.5 Mb; and (4) with G + C% content >59%. The data of each criterion per strain are shown in supplementary table S1, Supplementary Material online. The three last criteria excluded possible contamination or non-KpSC genomes (supplementary fig. S2, Supplementary Material online).

The resultant 7,388 “high-quality” draft genomes (supplementary table S2, Supplementary Material online) were scanned for scgMLSTv2 alleles, using the BLASTN algorithm, as implemented in the BIGSdb platform (Jolley and Maiden 2010; Jolley et al. 2018), with 90% identity, 90% length coverage, word size 30, with type alleles only (as defined below). After this step, 235 profiles were excluded because they had more than 30 missing alleles.

The resulting data set comprised 36 taxonomic references of Kp1–Kp7 (Rodrigues et al. 2019) that, together with eight additional genomes of phylogroup Kp7, were considered as a reference data set of the KpSC taxa (“*K. quasivariicola*” reference strain KPN1705, SB6096, was excluded because it had more than 30 missing alleles). Besides these 44 reference genomes, 7,154 GenBank genomes were retained, resulting in a total data set of 7,198 genomes (supplementary tables S1 and S2, Supplementary Material online). For some analyses, 138 genomes were set aside, defined as “hybrids” between phylogroups (see below), resulting in a 7,060-genome data set (supplementary fig. S2, Supplementary Material online).

We estimated within-outbreak variation using previously published outbreak sets (supplementary tables S6 and S7, Supplementary Material online).

Recording Sequence Variation at the cgMLST Gene Loci

Allelic variation at scgMLSTv2 loci was determined with the following strategy. First, the sequence of strain NTUH-K2044 was used as the reference genome, with all its alleles defined as allele 1. Then, BLASTN searches (70% identity, 90% length coverage) were carried out using allele 1 as query against the genomic sequences of reference genomes 18A069, 342, 01A065, 07A044, CDC4241-71, and 08A119, representing major lineages (phylogroups Kp2–Kp6, including two genomes of Kp3 and excluding Kp7, which was not discovered yet) of the KpSC (Blin et al. 2017). Only sequences with a complete CDS (start and stop, no internal frameshift) and within a $\pm 5\%$ range of the reference size were accepted. Alleles defined from these reference genomes and from NTUH-K2044 were then defined as type alleles.

New alleles were identified by BLASTN searches using a 90% identity threshold, 90% length coverage, and a word size of 30 and the above-defined type alleles. The use of type alleles avoided expanding the sequence space of alleles in an uncontrolled way, at the cost of losing a few highly divergent alleles, which may have replaced original (vertically inherited) alleles by HGT and homologous recombination. As for type alleles, novel alleles were accepted only if they (1) corresponded to a complete CDS (start and stop codons with no internal frameshift mutations) and (2) were within a 5% (plus/minus) of the size of the type allele size. Novel allele sequences were also excluded if they came from assemblies with more than 500 contigs of size >200 nt, as these may correspond to low-quality assemblies and that might contain artifactual alleles. Genome assemblies based on 454 sequencing technology, which are prone to frameshifts, were also excluded for novel allele definitions. No genome assemblies based on IonTorrent sequencing technology were found.

In order to speed the scanning process, we used the fast scan option (-e -f) of the BIGSdb autotag.pl script (https://bigsd.readthedocs.io/en/latest/offline_tools.html). This option limits the BLASTN search to a few exemplar alleles, which are used as query to find the genomic region corresponding to the locus. In a second step, a direct database lookup of the region was performed to identify the exact allele.

Definition of MLST STs and cgST

Classical 7-gene MLST loci have been defined previously (Diancourt et al. 2005) as internal portions of the seven protein-coding genes *gapA*, *infB*, *mdh*, *pgi*, *phoE*, *rpoB*, and *tonB*. Novel alleles were defined in the Institut Pasteur *Klebsiella* MLST and whole-genome MLST database <https://bigsd.pasteur.fr/klebsiella>. In 7-locus MLST, the combination of the seven allelic numbers determines the isolate profile, and each unique profile is attributed an ST number. Incomplete MLST profiles with one (or more) missing gene(s) are recorded in the isolates database, but in these cases, no ST number can be attributed and the profiles are therefore not defined in the sequence definition database. The 7-locus MLST genes were not included in the scgMLSTv2 scheme.

Similar to ST identifiers used for unique 7-gene MLST allelic combinations, each distinct cgMLST profile can be assigned a unique identifier; however, when using draft genomes, cgMLST data can be partly incomplete due to de novo assembly shortcomings or missing loci. cgSTs were therefore defined only for cgMLST profiles with no more than 30 uncalled alleles out of the 629 cgMLSTv2 loci. In addition, we have used the -match_missing option of the define_profiles.pl script, which allows missing loci to be treated as specific alleles rather than “any” alleles. While this retains more information (because it differentiates profiles that differ only by missing data at different loci), it can result in some isolates genomes corresponding potentially to more than a single cgST; their equality can nevertheless be deduced by the last MLST level,

“mismatch 0,” as these will be grouped into the same clusters at level 0; this is because the clustering ignores loci with missing data in any of the profiles of a pair when calculating the pairwise distance. For example, cgST1 = 0–N–1–1; cgST2 = 0–2–N–1; an isolate with profile 0–2–1–1 would result in cgST3 = 0–2–1–1 being created, and this genome would equate to both previous cgSTs and would be labeled as cgST1; cgST2; cgST3.

Phylogenetic Analyses, Recombination Tests, and Screens for Virulence and Resistance Genes

JolyTree v2.0 (Criscuolo 2019, 2020) was used to reconstruct a phylogenetic tree of the KpSC. For this, first, a single linkage clustering was performed to cluster cgSTs into partitions. This clustering was applied on the pairwise distances between allelic profiles, defined as the number of loci with different alleles, normalized by the number of loci with alleles called in both profiles. A threshold of 8 mismatches was defined, resulting in 2,417 clusters. One genome from each of these 2,417 clusters was used as an exemplar for phylogenetic analysis (fig. 1).

A core genome multiple sequence alignment (cg-MSA) of 7,060 cgMLST profiles free of evidence for interphylogroup “hybridization” (see below) was constructed. The gene sequences were retrieved based on allele number in the sequence definition database, individual gene sequences were aligned with MAFFT v7.467 (missing alleles were converted into gaps), and the multiple sequence alignments were concatenated. IQ-TREE v2.0.6 was used to infer a phylogenetic tree with the GTR+G model (fig. 2).

Locus-by-locus recombination analyses were computed with the PHI test (Bruen et al. 2006) using PhiPack v1.0.

Kleborate v2.0.4 (Lam et al. 2021) was employed to identify acquired antimicrobial resistance and virulence genes in genomic sequences, based on CARD v3.0.8 database, with identity >80% and coverage >90%. Virulence score (ranges from 0 to 5) and antimicrobial resistance score (ranges from 0 to 3) were also derived from Kleborate. The virulence score is assigned according to the presence of yersiniabactin (*ybt*), colibactin (*clb*), and aerobactin (*iuc*), as follows: 0 = none present, 1 = yersiniabactin only, 2 = yersiniabactin and colibactin (or colibactin only), 3 = aerobactin (without yersiniabactin or colibactin), 4 = aerobactin and yersiniabactin (without colibactin), and 5 = all three present. Resistance scores are calculated as follows: 0 = no ESBL (Extended-Spectrum Beta-Lactamases), no carbapenemase, 1 = ESBL without carbapenemase, 2 = carbapenemase without colistin resistance, 3 = carbapenemase with colistin resistance.

Detection of Hybrid Genomes

HGT of large portions of the genome can occur among isolates belonging to distinct KpSC phylogroups (Holt et al. 2015). Additionally, MLST or scgMLST alleles may have been transferred horizontally from non-KpSC members, for example, *Escherichia coli*. For the purpose of

phylogeny-based classification, putative hybrid genomes were excluded. To define genomes that result from large interphylogroup recombination events, the gene-by-gene approach was used to define an original strategy, outlined briefly here and more thoroughly in [supplementary appendix](#) (Detection of hybrids), [Supplementary Material](#) online: for each locus, each allele was unambiguously labeled by one of the seven KpSC phylogroup of origin, if possible; next, for each profile, a phylogroup homogeneity index (i.e., proportion of alleles labeled by the predominant phylogroup) was derived. The distributions of the phylogroup homogeneity indices allowed determining hybrid genomes ([supplementary fig. S12](#), [Supplementary Material](#) online). The exclusion of such hybrid genomes resulted in a genomic data set of 7,060 isolates deemed as having a majority of alleles inherited from within a single phylogroup. Of the 44 reference genomes, one (SB1124, of phylogroup Kp2) was defined as having a hybrid origin: 414 alleles were attributed to Kp2, whereas 150 alleles originated from non-KpSC species; as a result, 73.4% of SB1124 alleles were part of the majority phylogroup, which was below the defined threshold of 78%. The quantification of recombination breakpoints was performed based on the position of cgMLST loci on the NTUH-K2044 reference genome (NC_012731), counting the number of recombination breakpoints in each successive 500 kb fragment along the reference genome. Note that hybrids had typical assembly sizes ([supplementary table S1](#), [Supplementary Material](#) online), whereas our simulations of contaminated sequence read sets between phylogroups resulted in significantly larger assemblies (not shown; available upon request).

Identification of Genetic Discontinuities in the KpSC Population Structure

The tool MSTclust v0.21b (<https://gitlab.pasteur.fr/GIPhy/MSTclust>) was used to perform the single linkage clustering of cgMLST profiles from their pairwise allelic mismatch dissimilarities, as well as to assess the efficiency of the resulting profile partitioning (for details, see [supplementary appendix](#): Minimum Spanning tree-based clustering of cgMLST profiles, [Supplementary material](#)). Briefly, for each threshold t (= 0–629 allelic mismatches), the clustering consistency was assessed using the silhouette metrics S_t (Rousseeuw 1987), whereas its robustness to profile subsampling biases was assessed using a dedicated metrics W_t based on the adjusted Wallace coefficients (Wallace 1983; Severiano et al. 2011). Both consistency (S_t) and stability (W_t) coefficients converge to 1 when the threshold t leads to a clustering that is consistent with the “natural” grouping and is robust to subsampling biases, respectively.

The adjusted Rand index R_t (Hubert and Arabie 1985; Carrico et al. 2006) was used to assess the global concordance between single linkage clustering partitions and those induced by classifications into 7-gene MLST STs, subspecies, and species.

Diversity and Phylogenetic Compatibility Indices

Simpson's diversity index was computed using the www.comparingpartitions.info website (Carrico et al. 2006). The clade compatibility index of STs or other groups was calculated using the ETE Python library (http://etetoolkit.org/{PI}docs/latest/tutorial/tutorial_trees.html#checking-the-monophyly-of-attributes-within-a-tree), in order to define whether their constitutive genomes formed a monophyletic, paraphyletic, or polyphyletic group within the recombination-purged sequence-based phylogeny of the core genome. We estimated clade compatibility as the proportion of nonsingleton STs, SLs, or CGs that were monophyletic.

Classification of cgMLST Profiles into Clonal Groups and SLs

The classification scheme functionality was implemented within BIGSdb v1.14.0 and relies on single linkage clustering. Briefly, cgSTs were defined in the sequence definitions ("seqdef") database as distinct profiles with fewer than 30 missing alleles over the scgMLST scheme, and their pairwise cgMLST distance was computed as the number of distinct alleles. To account for missing data, a relative threshold was used for clustering: the number of allelic mismatches was multiplied by the proportion of loci for which an allele was called in both strains. Hence, in order to be grouped, the number of matching alleles must exceed: $(\text{the number of loci called in both strains} \times (\text{total loci} - \text{defined threshold})) / \text{total loci}$. cgSTs and their corresponding SL, CG, and other levels partition identifiers are stored in the seqdef database and are publicly available. Here, classification schemes were defined in the *Klebsiella* seqdef database on the top of the scgMLSTv2 scheme, and host single linkage clustering group identifiers at the 10 defined cgMLST allelic mismatch thresholds (see Results). For classification groups defined using 43 and 190 allelic mismatch thresholds, scheme fields were defined and populated with the identifiers defined by inheritance from 7-gene MLST ST identifiers (see [supplementary appendix: Nomenclature inheritance algorithm, Supplementary Material](#) online).

Adaptation of the LIN Code Approach to cgMLST: Defining cgLIN Codes

Vinatzer and colleagues proposed an original nomenclature method in which each genome is attributed a LIN code, based on genetic similarity with the closest previously encoded member of the nomenclature (Marakeby et al. 2014; Weisberg et al. 2015; Vinatzer et al. 2016, 2017; Tian et al. 2020). In this proposal, the similarity between genomes was based on ANI ((Konstantinidis and Tiedje 2005; Goris et al. 2007)), with a set of 24 thresholds corresponding to ANI percentages of 60, 70, 75, 80, 85, 90, 95, 98, 98.5, 99, 99.25, 99.5, 99.75, 99.9, 99.925, 99.95, 99.975, 99.99, 99.999, and 99.9999. Here, the method was adapted by replacing the ANI metric by the similarity between cgMLST profiles, defined as the proportion of loci with identical

alleles normalized by the number of loci with alleles called in both profiles. These codes, which we refer to as cgLIN codes, are composed of a set of p positions, each corresponding to a pairwise genome similarity threshold s_p . These similarity thresholds are sorted in ascending order (i.e., $s_p < s_{p+1}$), the first positions of the code (on the left side) thus corresponding to low levels of similarity. Following the initial proposal, the codes are assigned as follows ([supplementary fig. S13, Supplementary Material](#) online): (step 1) the code is initialized with the first strain being assigned the value "0" at all positions; (step 2) the encoding rule for a new genome i is based on the closest genome j already encoded as follows, from the similarity $s_j \in]s_{p-1}, s_p]$:

- i) identical to code j up to and including position $p - 1$;
- ii) for the position p : maximum value observed at this position (among the subset of codes sharing the same prefix at the position $p - 1$) incremented by 1;
- iii) "0" to all downstream positions, from $p + 1$ included.

For each genome to be encoded, step 2 is repeated.

A set of 10 cgMLST thresholds were defined as follows: first, four thresholds were chosen above the similarity values peak observed between *Klebsiella* species ($s_p = 1 - 610/629 = 0.03$), subspecies ($s_p = 1 - 585/629 = 0.07$), main SLs ($s_p = 1 - 190/629 = 0.70$), and CGs ($s_p = 1 - 43/629 = 0.93$). Second, we included six thresholds deemed useful for epidemiological studies, corresponding to 10, 7, 4, 2, 1, and 0 allelic mismatches.

This encoding system conveys phylogenetic information, as two genomes with identical prefixes in their respective cgLIN codes can be understood as being similar, to an extent determined by the length of their common prefix. Isolates having cgMLST profiles with 100% identity (no mismatch at loci called in both genomes) will have exactly the same cgLIN code. For example, cgLIN codes 0_0_22_12_0_1_0_0_0_0 and 4_0_3_0_0_0_0_0_0_0 would denote two strains belonging to distinct species (as they differ by their first number in the code). cgLIN codes 0_0_105_6_0_0_75_1_1_0 and 0_0_105_6_0_0_75_1_0_0 correspond to strains from Kp1 (prefix 0_0) that differ by only 2 loci; they are identical up to the second bin, corresponding to 2 locus mismatches ([supplementary fig. S13, Supplementary Material](#) online); note that 0 and 1 mismatches are both included in the last bin: genomes have an identical identifier when having 0 difference, and a different identifier when having 1 mismatch ([supplementary fig. S14, Supplementary Material](#) online).

The impact of genome input order on the number of cgLIN code partitions at a given threshold was defined using the 7,060 high-quality, nonhybrid cgMLST profiles, which were encoded 500 times with random input orders (see details in the [supplementary appendix: Impact of strains input order on LIN codes, and use of Prim's algorithm, Supplementary Material](#) online).

The scripts for cgLIN code database creation were made available via GitLab BEBP (<https://gitlab.pasteur.fr/BEBP/LINcoding>).

Supplementary Material

Supplementary data are available at *Molecular Biology and Evolution* online.

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Author contributions

S.B. designed and coordinated the study. M.H. performed the genomic analyses, and cgLIN code developments and implementations. J.G. designed the novel version of the cgMLST scheme. A.C. developed the MSTclust tool (and associated metrics), and supervised cgLIN developments and phylogenetic analyses. K.A.J. and M.C.J.M. designed and developed the BIGSdb platform, with help from S. Bridel for the integration of cgLIN code functionality. S.B. and M.H. wrote the initial version of the manuscript, with input from A.C. All authors provided input to the manuscript and reviewed the final version.

Data availability

All genome assembly accessions are provided in Supplementary Tables S1 and S9. The allele sequences for each of the 629 loci of the scgMLSTv2 scheme are available at https://bigsdbs.pasteur.fr/cgi-bin/bigsdbs/bigsdbs.pl?db=pubmlst_klebsiella_seqdef&page=downloadAlleles&scheme_id=18. The source codes of MSTclust and

LINcoding are available at <https://gitlab.pasteur.fr/GIPhy/MSTclust> and <https://gitlab.pasteur.fr/BEBP/LINcoding>, respectively.

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CHAPITRE 4 : Une taxonomie génomique des souches de *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*

Titre de l'article

Genomic epidemiology and strain taxonomy of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*

Résumé

Corynebacterium diphtheriae est hautement transmissible et peut provoquer de grandes épidémies de diphtérie là où la couverture vaccinale est insuffisante. Des cas sporadiques ou de petits groupes sont observés dans les milieux à forte vaccination. La phylogéographie et l'évolution à court terme de *C. diphtheriae* ne sont pas bien comprises, en partie en raison d'un manque d'approches analytiques harmonisées de surveillance génomique et de suivi des souches. Nous avons combiné 1 305 gènes avec des appels d'allèles hautement reproductibles dans un schéma de typage de séquence multilocus du génome central (cgMLST). Nous avons analysé la diversité des gènes cgMLST parmi 602 isolats provenant de cas cliniques sporadiques, de petits groupes ou de grandes épidémies. Nous avons défini des sous-lignées en fonction de la structure phylogénétique de *C. diphtheriae* et des souches en fonction du nombre le plus élevé de mésappariements cgMLST dans les épidémies documentées. Nous avons effectué des analyses phylogénétiques à échelle temporelle des principales sous-lignées. Le schéma cgMLST a montré un taux d'appel d'allèle élevé chez *C. diphtheriae* et les espèces étroitement apparentées *C. belfantii* et *C. rouxii*. Nous démontrons son utilité pour délimiter les groupes de cas épidémiologiques et les épidémies en utilisant un seuil de 25 mésappariements et révélons un certain nombre de chaînes de transmission cryptiques, dont la plupart sont géographiquement limitées à un ou quelques pays adjacents. Les sous-cultures de la souche vaccinale PW8 différaient jusqu'à 20 mésappariements cgMLST. Les analyses phylogénétiques ont révélé un gain ou une perte évolutive à court terme de la toxine diphtérique et des gènes associés aux biovars. Nous avons conçu une taxonomie génomique des souches et des sous-lignées plus profondes (définies à l'aide d'un seuil de mésappariement de 500 cgMLST), comprenant actuellement 151 sous-lignées, seuls quelques-uns sont géographiquement répandus sur la base de l'échantillonnage actuel. L'outil de génotypage et la nomenclature cgMLST ont été rendus accessibles au public (<https://bigsd.bpasteur.fr/diphtheria>). Le génotypage normalisé des souches à l'échelle du génome aidera à retracer la transmission et la propagation géographique de *C. diphtheriae*. La taxonomie génomique unifiée des souches de *C. diphtheriae* fournit un langage commun pour les études sur l'écologie, l'évolution et l'hétérogénéité de la virulence parmi les sous-lignées de *C. diphtheriae*.

Contributions personnelles

- Héritabilité de la nomenclature ST à la nomenclature SL développé
- Réalisation du tableau S3
- Contribution à la rédaction du manuscrit

Genomic Epidemiology and Strain Taxonomy of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*

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ABSTRACT *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* is highly transmissible and can cause large diphtheria outbreaks where vaccination coverage is insufficient. Sporadic cases or small clusters are observed in high-vaccination settings. The phylogeography and short timescale evolution of *C. diphtheriae* are not well understood, in part due to a lack of harmonized analytical approaches of genomic surveillance and strain tracking. We combined 1,305 genes with highly reproducible allele calls into a core genome multilocus sequence typing (cgMLST) scheme. We analyzed cgMLST gene diversity among 602 isolates from sporadic clinical cases, small clusters, or large outbreaks. We defined sublineages based on the phylogenetic structure within *C. diphtheriae* and strains based on the highest number of cgMLST mismatches within documented outbreaks. We performed time-scaled phylogenetic analyses of major sublineages. The cgMLST scheme showed high allele call rate in *C. diphtheriae* and the closely related species *C. belfantii* and *C. rouxii*. We demonstrate its utility to delineate epidemiological case clusters and outbreaks using a 25 mismatches threshold and reveal a number of cryptic transmission chains, most of which are geographically restricted to one or a few adjacent countries. Subcultures of the vaccine strain PW8 differed by up to 20 cgMLST mismatches. Phylogenetic analyses revealed a short-timescale evolutionary gain or loss of the diphtheria toxin and biovar-associated genes. We devised a genomic taxonomy of strains and deeper sublineages (defined using a 500-cgMLST-mismatch threshold), currently comprising 151 sublineages, only a few of which are geographically widespread based on current sampling. The cgMLST genotyping tool and nomenclature was made publicly accessible (<https://bigsd.b.pasteur.fr/diphtheria>). Standardized genome-scale strain genotyping will help tracing transmission and geographic spread of *C. diphtheriae*. The unified genomic taxonomy of *C. diphtheriae* strains provides a common language for studies of ecology, evolution, and virulence heterogeneity among *C. diphtheriae* sublineages.

KEYWORDS cgMLST, diphtheria, epidemiology, genomic epidemiology, genomics, microevolution

Corynebacterium diphtheriae causes diphtheria, a severe infection of the upper respiratory tract. The most typical symptoms include the formation of pseudomembranes in the throat and toxin-induced complications such as myocarditis and neuropathy. The diphtheria toxin is produced by some strains that carry the *tox* gene, harbored by a lysogenized corynephage. Cutaneous infections by *C. diphtheriae* are common, and skin carriage or infection may act as source of respiratory infections (1). Isolates without the *tox* gene can cause invasive infections such as endocarditis and sepsis (2). *C. diphtheriae* is considered to spread predominantly through droplets among humans and is only rarely isolated from animals. Strains of the phylogenetically related species *C. ulcerans* and *C. pseudotuberculosis* can also produce the

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diphtheria toxin, but in these cases human infections always result from transmission from animals.

Diphtheria is largely eliminated in countries with high coverage rates of vaccination with the diphtheria toxoid (3). Nevertheless, the pathogen *C. diphtheriae* continues to circulate among humans and even in high-vaccination coverage countries, sporadic cases of toxigenic *C. diphtheriae* infections are reported regularly. In Europe, 139 cases were reported between 2014 and 2018, a majority of which followed introduction of *C. diphtheriae* from regions of endemicity (4). In these settings, transmission is rare, and only small clusters of patients or carriers are observed (5, 6). In contrast, in settings where public health action is disrupted and vaccination coverage has decreased, several large outbreaks of diphtheria in its typical clinical form have occurred in recent years (7–9).

Strain subtyping is used to study genotype-phenotype relationships and to define chains of transmission and the origin of outbreak strains. The subdivision of *C. diphtheriae* into four biovars is of poor resolution and has no epidemiological usefulness, and even its relevance for strain classification is questionable (10, 11). The recently described species *C. belfantii* (12) and *C. rouxii* (13) include most strains that were previously assigned to *C. diphtheriae* biovar Belfanti. Although no toxigenic strains of these two novel species have been described thus far, they are typically misidentified as *C. diphtheriae* when using reference molecular tests, biochemical diagnostic methods, and even matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization–time of flight mass spectrometry (12–14).

The highly standardized molecular methods ribotyping (15) and seven-gene MLST (14) have been developed to subtype *C. diphtheriae*, but in the genomic era their resolution power appears to be highly limited (11). Whole-genome sequencing (WGS) provides nearly ultimate resolution power, and several recent studies have used this approach for *C. diphtheriae* population biology (10, 16–18) or molecular epidemiology and outbreak investigation (5, 19–23). However, currently a shared genotyping system and strain definition standard are lacking, which limits our ability to compare strains across studies.

Among WGS analytical approaches, core genome multilocus sequence typing (cgMLST) (24) has several attractive characteristics, including high reproducibility and portability that allow strain matching across studies, geography, and time. cgMLST has been used successfully to define transmission of *C. diphtheriae* among patients (5, 20, 21). However, at present, no cgMLST scheme is provided through a publicly available web application.

The aim of this work was to address this gap by providing an accessible genotyping standard and harmonized definitions of strains and sublineages. We calibrated the discriminatory power of cgMLST by comparing this proposed standard to whole-genome single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) and illustrate how cgMLST can be used to identify strains from recent *C. diphtheriae* clusters and outbreaks. Last, we mapped seven-gene MLST sequence type (ST) identifiers to the novel cgMLST-based sublineage nomenclature, which provides backward compatibility with this previous classification framework.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Isolates and outbreak sets included in the study. A total of 440 isolates (see Table S1 in the supplemental material) were included into the study data set. First, we included and sequenced eight isolates of the French National Reference Center (NRC) collection corresponding to four available pairs of *C. diphtheriae* infection cases defined as epidemiologically linked (Table 1). The first pair (Mayotte set 1) included two isolates from a single sample, isolated 1 month apart (FRC025 and FRC030). The second pair (Mayotte set 2) included isolates from one patient and one of his contacts; the two isolates were isolated 15 days apart. The third pair (Carcassonne set 1) included isolates from two members of the same household, sampled 14 days apart. The fourth pair (Bron set 1) included two isolates from a pair of siblings, sampled on the same day. Second, we included and sequenced a random selection of 21 isolates from the French NRC collection, selected among isolates that were cocirculating temporally or geographically with each outbreak (see Table S1, “sporadic” with “FRCxxxx” isolate names). Third, 172 isolates from previously published genomic epidemiology studies in South Africa (25), Germany-Switzerland (5), Germany (20), France (22), Australia (17), and Canada (21) were included. These genomic investigations of outbreaks (or clusters of cases) together comprised 11 sets of isolates defined as related based on epidemiologically and genomic evidence (Table 1) and also included isolates considered nonrelated to the outbreak sets. Finally, all other publicly available genomic sequences from GenBank available 30 May 2019 were included (see Table S1). Of these, we removed isolates from the Canadian study (isolates CD46 to CD49 and isolates CD51 to CD56) that were of low quality. We also removed three isolates with atypical assemblies: two from Germany (KL0932 and

TABLE 1 Outbreak data sets

Data set	No. of strains	7-Gene MLST	Sublineage	Genetic cluster	Country	Yr(s)	Outbreak information	Source or reference
South Africa set 1	19	378	378	472	South Africa	2015–2016	tox positive	25
South Africa ST395	5	395	395	68;491;492;542	South Africa	1980; 2015	tox negative	25
Germany-Switzerland set 1	3	473	473	13	Germany	2015	Refugees from Eritrea, Ethiopia, Somalia, and Syria; tox positive	5
Germany-Switzerland set 2	3	183;486	486	204	Germany	2015	Refugees from Eritrea, Ethiopia, Somalia, and Syria; tox positive	5
Germany-Switzerland set 3	4	398	398	207	Germany	2015	Refugees from Eritrea, Ethiopia, Somalia, and Syria	5
Germany cluster 1	14	8	8	414	Germany	2016–2017	Hamburg, Essen, Kiel	20
Germany cluster 2	19	8	8	292	Germany	2015–2017	Berlin mostly	20
Germany cluster 3	6	8	8	411	Germany	2015–2016	Berlin, Essen, Trier	20
Germany cluster 4	2	8	8	415	Germany	2016–2017	Hannover	20
Germany ST130	10	130	130	402	Germany	2012–2017	None	20
Vancouver cluster 1	43	76;746	76	456	Canada	2017–2018	Vancouver inner city, cutaneous infection cluster	21
Mayotte set 1	3	97	97	78	Mayotte	2008–2009	Single sample, 1 mo apart	This study
Mayotte set 2	2	184	184	86	Mayotte	2009	Patient + contact, 15 days apart	This study
Carcassonne set 1	2	212	212	222	France	2011	Members of household, 14 days apart	This study
Bron set 1	2	411	411	116	France	2016	Siblings, sampled on same day	This study

KL0954) because they were highly fragmented (446 and 496 contigs, respectively) and one from a Germany-Switzerland study (Cd_14) because of a low G+C content (42.9%).

While this work was in progress, additional *C. diphtheriae* genomes were published from Austria (26), the United States (23), Yemen (9), France (11), Spain (27), and India (28). We included these 162 genomes in a joint phylogenetic analysis with the 440 genomes indicated above (see Fig. S1).

DNA preparation and sequencing. Isolates were retrieved from -80°C storage and plated on tryptose-casein soy agar for 24 to 48 h. A small amount of bacterial colony biomass was resuspended in a lysis solution (20 mM Tris-HCl [pH 8], 2 mM EDTA, 1.2% Triton X-100, and lysozyme [20 mg/ml]) and incubated at 37°C for 1 h, and DNA was extracted with the DNeasy Blood&Tissue kit (Qiagen, Courtaboeuf, France) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Genomic sequencing was performed using a NextSeq500 instrument (Illumina, San Diego, CA) with a 2×150 -nucleotide (nt) paired-end protocol following Nextera XT library preparation (11).

Genomic sequence assembly. For *de novo* assembly, paired-end reads were clipped and trimmed using AlienTrimmer v0.4.0 (29), corrected using Musket v1.1 (30), and merged (if needed) using FLASH v1.2.11 (31). For each sample, the remaining processed reads were assembled and scaffolded using SPAdes v3.12.0 (32).

Definition of the cgMLST scheme. We first selected 171 genomes representing a diversity of *C. diphtheriae* sublineages, including the 104 genomes presented in Table S1 and 67 genomes from the French NRC (11). These included 14 *C. belfantii* isolates, but no *C. rouxii* isolates were included at this step, since this species had not been identified at that time. From this set of genomes, we inferred the species core genome using the CoreGeneBuilder pipeline (<https://zenodo.org/record/165206#.WVpT7I55EQU>; see reference 33) using the NCTC13129 strain genome (GenBank accession no. NC_002935; see reference 34). CoreGeneBuilder automatically removed genomes for which the size was too divergent compared to the whole set. We applied the following quality filters: a maximum of 500 contigs and a minimum N_{50} of 10,000 bp. With these criteria, no genome was filtered out. The pipeline's next step relies on eCAMBer (35), which consists of a *de novo* annotation of the genomes (except the reference) using Prodigal (36) and in the harmonization of the positions of the stop and start codons. In the last step, the core genome is inferred using a bidirectional best hits approach, following Touchon et al. (37). We used CoreGeneBuilder default settings and considered a gene as part of the core genome if it was found in at least 95% of the 171 selected genomes. This resulted in an initial core genome containing 1,555 loci.

To obtain a set of loci that would be highly robust to genotyping artifacts, we filtered out some genes based on several criteria. First, we removed potential paralogs, since the presence of paralogs inside a typing scheme can lead to genotyping errors when a gene sequence is attributed to the wrong locus. To detect the potential paralogs, we compared each allele of each locus against all the alleles of all the other loci using the software BLAT (38). If a single hit was found between two different loci (more than 70% amino acid sequence identity between two alleles), we removed both. A total of eight loci were discarded by this process. We also removed genes that belong to the classical seven-gene MLST scheme (14) and the ribosomal protein genes that are used in the ribosomal MLST approach (39), so that they could be analyzed independently. Next, we removed loci whose length varied too much among alleles, which is useful to reduce ambiguities during the genotyping process. We aligned the amino acid sequences and removed loci for which the alignment contained more than 5% of gaps (total number of gaps compared to the total number of character states). This filter removed 107 loci. In addition, we removed three loci because at least one allele showed one or more ambiguous character state(s). Altogether, these filters resulted in a list of 1,388 remaining loci.

To filter out loci with nonreproducible allele calls at low assembly coverage depth, randomly selected read pairs representing coverage depths of $10\times$ to $50\times$ were drawn (five times for each isolate/coverage combination) from the raw sequencing data for four isolates (*C. diphtheriae* 18-093a and FRC0024 and *C. belfantii* FRC0019 and FRC0318); we included two *C. belfantii* isolates because their genome is more fragmented due to a high copy number of insertion sequences (40). After assembly and allele calling using BIGSdb, we eliminated 33 loci that showed nonreproducible allele calls from all assemblies obtained with coverage depths equal to or greater than $20\times$ in any of the four isolates.

Finally, we also removed 52 loci that were uncalled in $>10\%$ of scanned genomes. These filtering steps led to a final set of 1,305 gene loci, which together constitute the "Pasteur *C. diphtheriae* cgMLST scheme" (abbreviates here as "cgMLST scheme"). Note that a given gene locus could have been filtered out by several filters applied independently, so that the sum of numbers of loci removed by individual filters is smaller than the final number of loci that were filtered out.

Evaluation of cgMLST allele call rate. Because loci with high numbers of missing alleles were filtered out during cgMLST scheme construction, the allele call rate of the resulting scheme was assessed using an independent set of genomes, which had not been used for the above-described definition of the scheme. This entirely distinct data set of *C. diphtheriae* isolates was made of 162 genomes published after cgMLST scheme definition and described in the first Materials and Methods paragraph. Missing alleles were defined as being not called using 90% identity and 90% length coverage.

Constitution of a BIGSdb database for *C. diphtheriae*. The cgMLST scheme was incorporated into a BIGSdb seqdef database (41). Classification schemes were created at the level of 25 and 500 mismatches. The isolates provenance data and genome sequences were imported into a linked isolates database (<https://bigsd.bpasteur.fr/diphtheria>). A publicly available BIGSdb project (i.e., a browsable list of isolates) entitled "cgMLST set-up study" corresponds to the data set of 440 genomes and was created to facilitate retrieval of the data used in this work.

Inheritance of classification identifiers from seven-gene MLST. MLST alleles and profiles of the 440 genomes are defined in the PubMLST *C. diphtheriae* database. We then mapped the sequence type (ST) identifiers onto the obtained 500-mismatch cgMLST single-linkage classification groups and attributed the

dominant ST identifier to the group, using an inheritance algorithm (<https://gitlab.pasteur.fr/BEBP/inheritance-algorithm>).

Comparison to other schemes. An ad-hoc cgMLST scheme for *C. diphtheriae* was defined and used previously (19, 20, 42). In order to compare our scheme with this previous one, we took the first allele of all loci of both schemes and performed an all-against-all BLASTN analysis. Hits were defined as sequence pairs with a proportion of identical nucleotides greater than 90% and with an alignment length longer than half of both the query and the subject sequences.

Cryptic cluster detection. Cryptic clusters were defined as single-linkage groups of genomes (i) defined using a threshold of 25 cgMLST allelic mismatches but (ii) which were not initially defined as clusters based on available epidemiological data.

Phylogenetic and population structure analyses. Phylogenetic analyses were performed by first inferring a tree using JollyTree v1, an alignment-free distance-based procedure (43). The resulting tree was used as input for ClonalFrameML (44), which also requires an alignment. The alignment was obtained by translating allelic sequences of cgMLST loci of each genome into proteins. We aligned the proteins of each loci using MAFFT v7.467 (45) with default parameters and then back-translated the protein alignments to codon alignments using Galign (<https://github.com/evolbioinfo/galign>); the individual gene alignments were then concatenated into a supermatrix, also using Galign (the nucleotide positions of missing alleles were replaced by gaps in the concatenate of alignments of individual loci). We used this alignment and above defined input tree to run ClonalFrameML with default parameters. We used the software PHIPack v1.0 (46) to calculate the PHI (pairwise homoplasmy index) statistic and perform a locus-by-locus test of recombination with a *P* value threshold of 0.05. Nucleotide diversity was calculated both for the entire data set of each species and among sublineages using an in-house script relying on the *p*-distance calculation provided by Galign. The overall average Silhouette width, which estimates the overall clustering quality based on maximizing intergroup distances and minimizing intra-group distances, was used to define the clustering consistency (47).

Dating ST5 and ST8 phylogenetic tree nodes was performed using the LSD (least-squares dating) algorithm (48) as implemented in IQ-TREE v2.0.6 (49). The sampling dates were used to calibrate the trees. The subtrees were extracted from the entire tree (Fig. 1). For both analyses, the closest outgroup was also extracted and included in the analysis. This allowed for the dating of the root of the ST8 phylogeny, whereas for ST5 this analysis did not allow dating the root.

The clade compatibility index of STs or other groups was calculated using the ETE Python library (http://etetoolkit.org/docs/latest/tutorial/tutorial_trees.html#checking-the-monophyly-of-attributes-within-a-tree) in order to define whether their constitutive genomes formed a monophyletic, paraphyletic or polyphyletic group within the recombination-purged sequence-based phylogeny of the core genome. We estimated clade compatibility as the proportion of nonsingleton STs or sublineages that were monophyletic.

Whole-genome SNP calling based on a read mapping approach. We used Snippy v4.4.0 (50) with default parameters to perform SNP calling within the German and Canadian outbreak data sets, using strains NCTC13129 and CD50 (from BioProject [PRJNA563223](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJNA563223)), respectively, as references.

Saturation analysis of the number of sublineages and genetic clusters. Following the definitions of genetic clusters and sublineages (25 allelic mismatches for the genetic clusters and 500 allelic mismatches for the sublineages), we simulated 1,000 samples of 1 to 440 profiles (the 440 profiles of our initial data set), with a step of 1. For each threshold and each number of profiles, we then calculated the mean number of clusters and used the minimum and maximum values to define the range. To extrapolate the previously obtained curves, we defined the species accumulation curves using the R package *vegan*. We chose the Lomolino function (51) for its excellent fit with our data.

Data availability. Newly sequenced isolates have been deposited in the European Nucleotide Archive (accession numbers [ERS6637895](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/record/ERS6637895) to [ERS6637897](https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/record/ERS6637897)).

RESULTS

Definition and evaluation of a cgMLST scheme for genotyping isolates of *C. diphtheriae*, *C. belfantii*, and *C. rouxii*. We defined a set of 1,305 protein-coding gene loci deemed appropriate for *C. diphtheriae*, *C. belfantii*, and *C. rouxii* genotyping (see Materials and Methods). These loci were combined into a cgMLST scheme and altogether have a total length of 1,265,478 nt (calculated for allele 1 of each gene), representing 51% of the genome size of the ST8 reference strain NCTC13129. Individual locus lengths varied from 93 to 4,008 nt. The list of loci and their characteristics are presented in Table S2 in the supplemental material.

The allele call rate of the cgMLST scheme loci was determined using posteriorly published genomes from Austria (26), the United States (23), Yemen (9), France (11), Spain (27), and India (28) and was found to be 98.6% ± 1.5%. We also calculated the call rate using 337 additional, prospectively collected genome sequences from the French NRC for diphtheria (unpublished). The mean numbers of called alleles were 1,288 (98.7%) and 1,287 (98.6%) for *C. diphtheriae* and *C. belfantii*, respectively. We noted that a few *C. belfantii* genomes had a lower call rate (see Fig. S2). For *C. rouxii*, the allele call rate was lower (1,190; 91.2%), as expected, since this novel species was not included during scheme development and is

FIG 1 Phylogenetic tree of *C. diphtheriae* sublineages. A maximum-likelihood phylogenetic tree for 440 *C. diphtheriae*, *C. belfantii*, and *C. rouxii* isolates was developed based on the concatenated multiple sequence alignments of 1,305 core genome multilocus sequence typing loci. The top panel represents the unrooted topology of the three species. The bottom panel is the *C. diphtheriae* subtree. Branches with support values greater than 70% are thicker. The root of this subtree corresponds to the placement of the branch leading to *C. rouxii* and *C. belfantii* in the top panel tree. The *C. diphtheriae* subtree (Continued on next page)

genetically more distant (13). The allele call rate was not significantly different between *tox*-positive and *tox*-negative *C. diphtheriae* (98.8 versus 98.6%, respectively; see Fig. S3). The relationships between allele call rate and genome assembly fragmentation showed that high call rates (>95%) were generally obtained, even for *C. diphtheriae* genome assemblies that were fragmented into >400 contigs (see Fig. S2). Overall, these results demonstrate high typeability across the phylogenetic breadth of *C. diphtheriae* and its two closely related species, *C. belfantii* and *C. rouxii*.

Based on the study data set of 440 genomes, allele numbers ranged from 7 to 285 per locus, illustrating the large amounts of genetic diversity of the core genes within *C. diphtheriae*. As expected, the number of alleles per locus increased with locus size (see Fig. S4). Locus-by-locus recombination analyses detected evidence of intragene recombination within a majority of loci (843; 64.6%), whereas only 431 (33%) loci were deemed non recombinogenic. There were 31 (2.4%) loci with too few polymorphic sites to be tested (see Table S2). The number of alleles per locus was higher for recombinogenic loci (see Fig. S5), which reflects the contribution of homologous recombination to the generation of allelic diversity.

We compared the cgMLST scheme defined here (named the Pasteur scheme) to a previously published *ad hoc* (not publicly available for comparison) cgMLST scheme (20) and found 1,132 loci in common, representing 87% of the Pasteur cgMLST loci (see Fig. S6). Of these, 115 varied slightly in length due to alternative start codon definitions. Whereas 173 loci were unique to the Pasteur scheme, 421 were unique to the previous scheme. Three loci were not counted as common to the two schemes, even though their sequences matched, because they are encoded on opposite strands.

Population structure of *C. diphtheriae*. A phylogenetic analysis was conducted based on a recombination-purged concatenate of the individual alignments of the 1,305 loci (Fig. 1). The three deepest branches corresponded to the three species *C. rouxii*, *C. belfantii*, and *C. diphtheriae*. Whereas *C. diphtheriae* included most isolates (86.5%, 148/171), *C. rouxii* and *C. belfantii* comprised 6 and 17 isolates, respectively. MLST data (see Fig. S7) revealed 134, 10, and 3 STs within *C. diphtheriae*, *C. belfantii*, and *C. rouxii*, respectively. The nucleotide diversity values, estimated as the average SNP distance among isolates, were 0.012 for *C. diphtheriae*, 0.0025 for *C. belfantii*, and 0.0039 for *C. rouxii*. The average genetic distance between sublineages (i.e., considering only one representative genome of each sublineage, as defined below) was 0.024 polymorphism per nucleotide position.

The phylogenetic structure within *C. diphtheriae* revealed a star-like phylogeny with multiple deeply branching sublineages as previously reported (11, 18). The phylogenetic distribution of seven-gene MLST data showed that sublineages typically corresponded to a single ST (Fig. 1). Some sublineages comprised closely related isolates, likely to be the result of sampling from case clusters, outbreaks or recent clonal expansions (see Table S1).

Diphtheria toxin *tox* gene-positive isolates were observed in 19 sublineages distributed on the Southern hemisphere of the tree presented in Fig. 1, including the sublineage that includes the vaccine strain PW8, and in five sublineages in the Northern hemisphere of the tree, including the one that comprised strain NCTC13129 (11). These two hemispheres of the tree are identifiable by the distribution of the *spuA* gene, involved in starch utilization (52): the upper lineage was *spuA*-positive with the exception of six *spuA*-negative sublineages, whereas in sharp contrast, the lower lineage was almost entirely *spuA* negative, with ST5 being the single exceptional *spuA*-positive sublineage. The two major lineages of *C. diphtheriae* were therefore labeled as lineages Gravis and Mitis, respectively (11). The addition of 162 recently published genomes (see Fig. S1)

FIG 1 Legend (Continued)

contains the following annotations: the stars represent the presence (red star) or absence (white star) of the diphtheria toxin *tox* gene. The small circles represent the presence (green circle)/absence (white circle) of the *spuA* gene. The green strips represent the alternation of seven-gene MLST STs of the isolates: when the ST changes while walking along the circle, the shade of green also changes. Identifiers of the main STs are indicated. When an ST could not be attributed (because at least one of the seven genes was missing), the color is white. A strip with a visible border represents isolates with an ST that is different from the rest of the clade, and the ST number is provided below. For example, ST185 is found within the ST8 clade. The red strips follow the same alternation logic for the cgMLST sublineage identifiers. Note the strong concordance between ST and cgMLST sublineages. The position of noteworthy reference isolates is given by black arrows. Finally, the epidemic cluster positions are indicated by colored boxes on the corresponding branches (see bottom left key).

FIG 2 Saturation analysis of the number of sublineages and genetic clusters. The curves in the inset correspond to the mean number of clusters found for each clustering threshold, and the area around the curves represents the range (minimum to maximum). The main panel represents the extrapolation (see Materials and Methods).

fully confirmed these observations. In addition to ST5, sublineage ST466 belonged to the lineage Mitis and included *spuA*-positive isolates. These *spuA*-positive isolates were closely related to two *spuA*-negative isolates, and all ST466 genomes were from India, suggesting a recent acquisition in this country of the *spuA* gene, along with probable conversion of the biovar from Mitis to Gravis.

Definition of *C. diphtheriae* sublineages and their geographic distribution. To guide the definition of *C. diphtheriae* sublineages, we performed an analysis of the mathematical properties of the clustering of cgMLST profiles at all possible thresholds (Silhouette analysis; see Fig. S8). We observed optimal clustering indices on a large interval (~between 300 and 600 mismatches), with a maximum value at 554. Since the Silhouette index was almost at maximum at 500 cgMLST mismatches, we chose this value for simplicity to define *C. diphtheriae* sublineages (SL). Our data set of 440 genomes comprised 114 sublineages, and a saturation curve analysis (Fig. 2) indicates that future addition of *C. diphtheriae* genomes is expected to reveal the existence of a multitude of additional sublineages that remain to be sampled. The additional data set of 162 genomes uncovered 22 additional sublineages (see Fig. S1). The average core genome nucleotide divergence among sublineages was 2.4%.

To create continuity in the numerical identifiers of sublineages with respect to MLST, we mapped the ST nomenclature on sublineages and incorporated the resulting sublineage tags into the BIGSdb *C. diphtheriae* genotype nomenclature database (see Table S3). Note that there was a strong concordance between MLST and cgMLST sublineages (see Fig. S9) and that this correspondence was established up to ST750 (17 November 2020).

All nonsingleton cgMLST sublineages (66/66; 100%) were compatible with the phylogeny, whereas this was the case for only 53 of 66 (80.3%) of seven-gene STs: 12 STs were polyphyletic, and 1 ST was paraphyletic.

The global distribution of *C. diphtheriae* sublineages, apparent from the current sample of 602 genomes, revealed a strong phylogeographic pattern with most sublineages being typically restricted to one or a few adjacent countries (Fig. 3). For example, SL8 was restricted

FIG 3 Geographic distribution of the most frequent genome-sequenced *C. diphtheriae* sublineages. The geographic origins of *C. diphtheriae* sublineages is represented by circles, the size of which represents the number of genomes per country (see key), considering the study data set of 440 genomes, as well as the 162 additional recently published genomes. The eight main sublineages are represented by colors of the pie chart sectors (see key); the other sublineages are grouped in the “others” category and are represented in gray.

to Europe, SL405 to India and SL40 to Indonesia. A notable exception was SL32, which was observed in Australia, Italy, and the UK. SL5 was isolated in Europe except one isolate from Australia.

Frequently sampled sublineages of *C. diphtheriae*. The most frequent sublineages in our data set included seven-gene MLST genotypes ST5, ST8, ST76, and ST378; they were labeled as SL5, SL8, SL76, and SL378, respectively, by our inheritance script. These sublineages were previously reported from diphtheria outbreaks. SL378 comprised 19 *tox*-positive isolates (except for 1 *tox*-negative isolate) recovered during a 2015-2016 outbreak in the KwaZulu province of South Africa (25). Sublineage SL76 comprised isolates that were all *tox*-negative and belonged to ST76 or ST746 (a single-locus variant of ST76). Forty-five isolates were drawn from the Vancouver 2015-2018 outbreak of *tox*-negative *C. diphtheriae* (21), and five ST76 isolates were recovered from Belarus between 2004 and 2014 (see Table S1).

Sublineage SL5 comprised 39 *tox*-negative genomes belonging to ST5 (all except 6), ST728, and ST741 and 4 genomes for which the ST cannot be defined because they lack a *leuA* allele call (Fig. 4A). ST5 contributed to infections in Belarus from the mid-1990s until at least 2013 (16) and was also recovered from Italy, Australia (see Table S1), and Russia (14, 53). As noted above, whereas a majority of ST5 genomes were *spuA* negative, a distinct sub-branch within SL5 possessed the biovar *Gravis* marker *spuA*. The phylogenetic analysis of SL5 genomes suggests initial acquisition of *spuA* in the ancestral branch of SL5 (after approximately year 1834), followed by its loss in a ST5 subbranch before 1955 (Fig. 1 and Fig. 4A).

SL8 was isolated from cases of the large ex-Soviet Union outbreak (34), and the genomes of this sublineage were isolated over a period of 20 years from Belarus, Germany, Russia, and the UK (see Table S1) (34, 28, 16, 20, 54). Strikingly, SL8 isolates were grouped into two subbranches, which were either *tox* positive (subbranch A) or *tox* negative (sub-branch B; Fig. 1 and Fig. 4B). Phylogenetic sister groups of the ST8 sublineage were ST123, ST451, and ST441, which comprised only *tox*-negative isolates. These data suggest a scenario of acquisition of the *tox* gene in the branch leading to the SL8 ancestor (before ~1967) and its subsequent loss in sub-branch B (before ~1988).

FIG 4 Time-scaled phylogenetic trees of SLE and SL8 sublineages. (A) Sublineage 5; (B) sublineage 8. The phylogenies were obtained based on the LSD method using IQ-TREE v2.0.6 (see Materials and Methods). Multifurcations were created when estimated node dates were conflicting with topology. The genomes are labeled with their BIGSdb identifier followed after a space by their original strain name. Estimated dates of major nodes are given below the right end of the branch above the node. Thick branches have a bootstrap support value greater than 70%. In panel A, circles represent the presence (green filled) or absence (empty) of the *spuA* gene. All strains were *tox*-negative (see Fig. 1). In panel B, the red stars represent the presence (red filled) or absence (empty) of the *tox* gene. All strains were *spuA* positive (see main Fig. 1). In both panels, the central color strip indicates the isolate's city of isolation, while the rightmost color strip shows the ST of the isolates: majority STs in dark blue (ST5 for SLE and ST8 for SL8) or alternative STs in light blue; the latter are labeled on the right. NA, not applicable (lack of *leuA* allele call in four SLE genomes).

cgMLST variation within clusters or outbreak sets versus sporadic isolates and comparison with whole-genome single SNPs.

We aimed to assess the cgMLST variation within sets of isolates defined as epidemiologically related, i.e., described as case clusters or outbreaks (here, clusters) based on their provenance information. Fifteen such sets were colated, including four clusters identified by the French national surveillance system and sequenced for the purposes of this study (Table 1). The 15 clusters of infections were caused by diverse strains, which were largely scattered across the phylogeny of *C. diphtheriae* (Fig. 1). The distribution of allelic mismatches was clearly distinct for clusters versus nonrelated sets of isolates (Fig. 5), and whereas the number of allelic mismatches observed within clusters ranged from none to 24, allelic variation among nonrelated isolates typically had more than 1,000 mismatches.

To compare the discriminatory power of cgMLST with the expectedly higher resolution provided by whole-genome SNPs, two outbreaks for which read sets were available were investigated. The pairwise number of SNPs versus cgMLST allelic mismatches showed a strong correlation and indicated that 30 SNPs are observed between pairs of genomes that differ by ~15 to ~17 cgMLST mismatches (Fig. 6). Minimum spanning tree analysis of the genomes showed a high concordance between both methods in inferring genetic relationships of closely related genomes (see Fig. S10 and S11).

cgMLST cluster classification uncovers cryptic transmission and cryptic duplicated cultures.

We classified the 440 *C. diphtheriae* genomes into single linkage groups using a threshold of 25 cgMLST mismatches, corresponding to the maximum value observed thus far for well-described clusters. We define these groups as genetic clusters. This analysis enabled to detect 43 cryptic clusters, i.e., isolates belonging to genetic clusters

FIG 5 Density distribution of the pairwise cgMLST allelic distances among sporadic, cryptic clusters or outbreak isolates. (A) Distribution density of the pairwise distances among all pairs of isolates included in outbreak clusters (green), cryptic clusters (orange), and sporadic cases (blue). (B) Distribution of the pairwise distances among isolates within each outbreak cluster. (C) Distribution of the pairwise distances among isolates within cryptic clusters. The strains belonging to each outbreak or cryptic cluster are given in Table S1. In panels B and C, each black dot represents a pairwise distance. Red dots represent the mean of each cluster.

but for which we have no evidence of epidemiological links. The cryptic clusters were genetically more heterogeneous than the epidemiological clusters (Fig. 5). One cryptic cluster corresponded in fact to three distinct genome assemblies of the reference strain Park-Williams 8 (generally named PW8), which were deposited separately in public sequence databases (see Table S1). These genomes differed by up to 20 loci among them, suggesting

FIG 6 Relationships between the pairwise distances derived from whole-genome SNPs and cgMLST profiles for two outbreak clusters. Each dot represents one pair of genomes. The line corresponds to the linear regression between the cgMLST (y axis) and SNP (x axis) distances. The ρ value is the concordance correlation coefficient (ranging from -1 to 1). (Left) Vancouver outbreak; (right) Germany clusters.

that multiple genetic differences exist among subcultures of this historical strain, isolated in 1896 and used for vaccine production. Likewise, there were four separately submitted genome sequences of strain C7beta (see Table S1), but these showed only <3 cgMLST distinct alleles. Cryptic cluster 8 included NCTC3529 and NCTC5011 (which are synonyms) and strain c21 from India, which differed from the two others by 22 loci.

Of the remaining 40 cryptic clusters, 33 were single-country clusters and may correspond to local chains of transmission that were previously undetected or just unreported to our knowledge. Only five cryptic clusters included isolates from at least two countries. Cluster 1 (as numbered in Table S1) corresponded to isolates from Belarus and the UK isolated between 1996 and 2004, and belong to the SL8 sublineage involved in the large ex-Soviet Union countries outbreak. Cryptic cluster 26 included two isolates from year 2008, one from Belarus and one from France, and the French patient had a history of travel to Russia; this cluster also belonged to SL8. Cryptic cluster 5 involved two isolates, one from Berlin in 2017 and one from Rio de Janeiro in 1999. Cryptic cluster 15 involved isolates from 2015 and 2016 in Australia and Germany. Cryptic 38 included isolates from France, Germany, and Australia (from 2013 to 2015). Cryptic cluster 3 involved two strains from Brazil, which were isolated in 1981 and 1993. Finally, we also revisited the clades defined in a recent study of the isolates from the large diphtheria outbreak in Yemen and found 13 groups, one of which (genetic cluster 217) corresponded to the predominant Yemen sublineage A.1.1, which was estimated to have originated in March 2015 (9).

DISCUSSION

C. diphtheriae was previously described as a genetically heterogeneous species (11, 18, 55). Here, we compared all available genomic sequences and defined *C. diphtheriae* sublineages, showing that they are numerous and still largely undersampled. Sublineages are separated by large genetic distances (2.4% on average), which indicates that *C. diphtheriae* is an old species that may have existed since several million years (56). The relatively rapid evolutionary rate, which was previously estimated at $\sim 1 \times 10^{-6}$ substitutions per site year $^{-1}$ within several *C. diphtheriae* sublineages (9, 16), and the frequent homologous recombination, which drives evolutionary divergence approximately five times faster than mutation (11), both contribute to the diversification of extant *C. diphtheriae* strains. This high level of genetic variation and fast

diversification underline the need for a standard definition of *C. diphtheriae* strains and sublineages based on a precise genome-based genotyping approach. Thus far, this lack has limited our understanding of the patterns of geographical spread and of the phenotypic and clinical differences among *C. diphtheriae* sublineages.

Here, we developed a cgMLST genotyping approach, designed to be widely applicable across *C. diphtheriae* and the closely related species, *C. rouxii* and *C. belfantii*. cgMLST is recognized as a highly reproducible and discriminatory approach applicable to molecular epidemiology and population biology questions (24, 57, 58). We proposed a definition of sublineages that considers the population structure, and ensured backward compatibility with MLST identifiers through their inheritance onto cgMLST-based sublineages. In the future, novel sublineage identifiers, defined systematically using the 500-cgMLST-mismatch threshold, will not be matched to MLST for practical reasons, and we propose that the cgMLST nomenclature should be prioritized over MLST. We integrated into the nomenclature, all publicly available genomes as of April 2021. The resulting genomic library is open to future community submissions and curator contributions.

Although most sublineages appear geographically restricted, sampling is currently very limited, and the current picture is strongly biased by a focus on local transmission and outbreaks. It is striking that, excluding outbreaks, no *C. diphtheriae* sublineage is numerically predominant, suggesting an absence of globally successful clonal expansions. This contrasts with the situation observed in multiple bacterial pathogens where specific sublineages have come to predominate (57, 58). The population dynamics of *C. diphtheriae* and its ecological drivers remains largely to be understood, but the evidence so far points to a large reservoir of diversity, strong phylogeographic structure and a lack of rapid emergence and spread of predominant sublineages. Asymptomatic carriage of *C. diphtheriae* in human populations may play an important role in maintaining the large genetic pool of *C. diphtheriae*.

We used a threshold of 25 allelic mismatches to define genetic clusters. This threshold captured all documented single-strain outbreak or case clusters. However, looser transmission chains of epidemiological relevance may exist, and the threshold should be considered indicative. Cryptic cluster analysis illustrates the potential value of cgMLST for uncovering previously hidden links between *C. diphtheriae* infection cases. Using our definition, we noted that high diversity of genetic clusters exists within single outbreaks of classical diphtheria, such as in the former Soviet Union or in Yemen. These observations underline the diversity of transmission chains that can occur simultaneously during such events, consistent with local reservoirs of diversity and silent circulation of *C. diphtheriae* until disease protection vanishes following a decrease in vaccination coverage. Strain heterogeneity during outbreaks may imply variations in toxin production or antimicrobial sensitivity, which could be highly relevant in terms of patient care and infection control priorities (9). The variation observed among subcultures of strain PW8 raises the question of a possible impact on vaccine effectiveness of the use of distinct variants of this strain in vaccine formulations (59).

The 1,305 cgMLST loci cover only approximately half of the entire genome length of a typical *C. diphtheriae*. Hence, the cgMLST has an inherent limitation in capturing genetic variation. Because our main goal was classification and nomenclature, we filtered out multiple genes to prioritize genotyping robustness and call rate over strain typing resolution power. Still, our comparison of cgMLST and whole-genome SNP variation within described outbreaks shows high concordance between these methods, while illustrating that SNP calling will provide some additional resolution when needed. However, this more resolutive approach does not allow straightforward comparison of the genotypes sampled across different studies, and the two approaches should therefore be viewed as complementary.

Our phylogenetic analyses show that *C. diphtheriae* genomes can acquire and lose, at small evolutionary timescales, gene regions that underlie toxigenicity and biovar. The phyletic pattern of the *spuA* gene presence suggests that both losses and gains may be selectively advantageous given the circumstances. Likewise, the *tox* gene has been acquired or lost a large number of times in the population history of *C. diphtheriae*, and some of these events were traced here to a few years or decades back. Together with antimicrobial resistance and other instances of gene acquisition and loss (11, 55, 60), these

evolutionary patterns paint a picture of *C. diphtheriae* as a highly dynamic species in which sublineages may evolve at epidemiological timescales with respect to their medically important characteristics. This underlines the need to better understand the drivers of these changes and to monitor the emergence and spread of genotypes of concern, e.g., which would combine multidrug-resistant and toxigenic properties. Here, we did not look in detail at the accessory genome, and future genotype-phenotype relationship studies should be carried out to decipher the impact of *C. diphtheriae* diversity on the heterogeneity of clinical phenotypes.

Important evolutionary and epidemiological questions about *C. diphtheriae* remain unanswered, including the likelihood for *tox*-negative strains to turn positive during infection or short-term transmission. Asymptomatic carriage is also poorly understood, and whether *C. diphtheriae* has evolved to partially escape vaccine-induced immunity in the context of long-standing vaccination is currently unknown (59). This study provides a framework to harmonize knowledge on the infraspecific diversity of *C. diphtheriae*. The use of a unified approach to define *C. diphtheriae* strains should facilitate advances of our knowledge of the evolutionary and transmission dynamics of *C. diphtheriae* and the identification of strains with particular clinical properties or emerging behavior.

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL

Supplemental material is available online only.

SUPPLEMENTAL FILE 1, PDF file, 1.8 MB.

SUPPLEMENTAL FILE 2, XLSX file, 0.1 MB.

SUPPLEMENTAL FILE 3, XLSX file, 0.1 MB.

SUPPLEMENTAL FILE 4, XLSX file, 0.02 MB.

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To conduct the research, we used bacterial strains, which are not considered human samples. Accordingly, this research was not considered human research and is out of the scope of decree 2016-1537 (16 November 2016) implementing law 2012-300 (5 March 2012) on research involving human subjects. Therefore, no ethics approval was needed, and no informed consent was required.

All French bacteriological samples were collected in the frame of French national diphtheria surveillance and are collected, coded, shipped, managed, and analyzed according to the French National Reference Center protocols that received approval by French competent body CNIL (Commission Nationale Informatique et Libertés; approval 1474671). Other strains were obtained from culture collections.

The research conformed to the principles of the Helsinki Declaration.

We declare there are no competing interests.

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S.B. conceived, designed, and coordinated the study. E.B. and S.B. coordinated the microbiological cultures of the isolates and their biochemical and molecular characterizations. J.G., M.H., A.C., and S.B. analyzed the genomic data. J.T. reviewed the clinical source data of the isolates collection. S.B. and J.G. wrote the initial version of the manuscript. All authors provided input to the manuscript and reviewed the final version.

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CHAPITRE 5 : *Corynebacterium rouxii* sp. nov., un nouveau membre du complexe d'espèces *diphtheriae*

Titre de l'article

Corynebacterium rouxii sp. nov., a novel member of the *diphtheriae* species complex

Résumé

Un groupe de six isolats cliniques précédemment identifiés comme *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* biovar Belfanti, isolés d'infections cutanées ou péritonéales humaines et d'un chien, ont été caractérisés par séquençage génomique, analyse biochimique et spectrométrie de masse MALDI-TOF. Les six isolats étaient négatifs pour le gène de la toxine diphtérique. Les analyses phylogénétiques ont montré que les six isolats (dont FRC0190^T) se distinguent clairement de *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*, *Corynebacterium belfantii*, *Corynebacterium ulcerans* et *Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis*. L'identité nucléotidique moyenne de FRC0190^T avec *C. diphtheriae* NCTC11397^T était de 92,6 % et de 91,8 % avec *C. belfantii* FRC0043^T. *C. diphtheriae* subsp. *lausannense* souche CHUV2995^T est apparue comme un synonyme hétérotypique ultérieur de *C. belfantii* (ANI, 99,3 %). Les données de phénotypage ont révélé une réaction atypique de fermentation maltose intermédiaire négative ou hétérogène pour les six isolats. La spectrométrie de masse MALDI-TOF a différencié le nouveau groupe des autres taxons de *Corynebacterium* par la présence de pics spectraux spécifiques. Les séquences *rpoB* ont montré une identité avec les isolats atypiques, maltose-négatifs du biovar Belfanti de *C. diphtheriae* précédemment décrits chez deux chats aux États-Unis. Nous proposons le nom de *Corynebacterium rouxii* sp. nov. pour le nouveau groupe, avec FRC0190^T (= CIP 111752^T = DSM 110354^T) comme souche type.

Contributions personnelles

- Analyse des données génomiques
- Réalisation des figures S1 et S2
- Contribution aux tableaux S1 et S2
- Contribution à la rédaction du manuscrit
- Mise à disposition des nouveaux génomes en base publique

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Original Article

Corynebacterium rouxii sp. nov., a novel member of the *diphtheriae* species complex

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ABSTRACT

A group of six clinical isolates previously identified as *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* biovar Belfanti, isolated from human cutaneous or peritoneum infections and from one dog, were characterized by genomic sequencing, biochemical analysis and MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry. The six isolates were negative for the diphtheria toxin gene. Phylogenetic analyses showed that the six isolates (including FRC0190^T) are clearly demarcated from *C. diphtheriae*, *Corynebacterium belfantii*, *Corynebacterium ulcerans* and *Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis*. The average nucleotide identity of FRC0190^T with *C. diphtheriae* NCTC11397^T was 92.6%, and was 91.8% with *C. belfantii* FRC0043^T. *C. diphtheriae* subsp. *lausannense* strain CHUV2995^T appeared to be a later heterotypic synonym of *C. belfantii* (ANI, 99.3%). Phenotyping data revealed an atypical negative or heterogeneous intermediate maltose fermentation reaction for the six isolates. MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry differentiated the new group from the other *Corynebacterium* taxa by the presence of specific spectral peaks. *rpoB* sequences showed identity to atypical, maltose-negative *C. diphtheriae* biovar Belfanti isolates previously described from two cats in the USA. We propose the name *Corynebacterium rouxii* sp. nov. for the novel group, with FRC0190^T (= CIP 111752^T = DSM 110354¹) as type strain.

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1. Introduction

The genus *Corynebacterium* currently includes approximately 111 species [1–3]. The most important human pathogen of the genus is *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*, which causes diphtheria [2,4]. *C. diphtheriae* is genetically heterogeneous [5–8] and four biovars were defined: Gravis, Mitis, Belfanti and Intermedius [9–11], the latter being almost never reported in recent literature. In 2010, maltose-non fermenting strains of *C. diphtheriae* biovar Belfanti were reported from two cats in the USA, and were shown to have a divergent *rpoB* sequence [12]. In 2018, some biovar

Belfanti isolates were classified as a novel species, *C. belfantii* [3], with 94.85% average nucleotide identity (ANI) with *C. diphtheriae*. Almost simultaneously, *C. diphtheriae* subsp. *lausannense* was also proposed for strains of biovar Belfantii [13]. The *tox* gene, which codes for diphtheria toxin, is carried on a corynephage that can lysogenize strains of *C. diphtheriae*. However, the *tox* gene was rarely reported in isolates of biovar Belfanti [5,14,15] and no strain of *Corynebacterium belfantii* or *C. diphtheriae* subsp. *lausannense* was described as *tox*-positive [3,12]. The *tox* gene can also be harboured by strains of *Corynebacterium ulcerans* and *Corynebacterium pseudotuberculosis*, two species that are phylogenetically close to *C. diphtheriae* and *C. belfantii* [16]. Together, the above-mentioned species constitute a single phylogenetic clade nested within the *Corynebacterium* genus. We refer to this clade as the *C. diphtheriae* complex.

Here, we define the taxonomic status of six isolates initially identified as *C. diphtheriae* biovar Belfanti, isolated from five human infections and one dog in France.

Abbreviations: ANI, Average nucleotide identity; MALDI-TOF, Matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionisation time-of-flight.

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Article

2. Material and methods

We compared the six atypical clinical isolates, among which is strain FRC0190^T, with 13 *C. diphtheriae* strains of biovars Gravis or Mitis (including *C. diphtheriae* type strain NCTC 11397^T) and 8 strains previously [3] identified as *C. belfantii* (including the type strain FRC0043^T; Table 1; Table S1). Type strains of *C. ulcerans* (CIP 106504^T = NCTC 7910^T) and of *C. pseudotuberculosis* (CIP 102968^T = ATCC 19410^T) were also included for comparison.

Clinical samples or isolates were received at the French National Reference Centre for Corynebacteria of the *diphtheriae* complex for isolation and/or characterization, respectively. Oxoid's Tinsdale agar with supplement medium (Thermo Fisher Diagnostics, Dardilly, France) was used to isolate *C. diphtheriae* from clinical samples. Isolates were frozen in Brain-Heart-Infusion (BHI) medium containing 30% of glycerol and stored at -80°C prior to this study. After thawing, isolates were grown at 37°C on tryptose-casein soy agar plates during 24 h. DNA was extracted from a few colonies with the DNeasy Blood and Tissue kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany). The six isolates were identified as *C. diphtheriae* by multiplex polymerase chain reaction (PCR) combining a *dtxR* gene fragment specific for *C. diphtheriae* [15] and a multiplex PCR [17,18] that targets a fragment of the *pld* gene specific for *C. pseudotuberculosis*, the gene *rpoB* (amplified in all species of the *C. diphtheriae* complex) and a fragment of 16S rRNA gene specific for *C. pseudotuberculosis* and *C. ulcerans*. The *tox* gene was also detected by PCR [19]. These PCR results were confirmed using a more recent four-plex qPCR [20].

For biochemical identification, standard methods were used [14,21,22]. More specifically, strains were characterized for pyrazinamidase, urease, nitrate reductase and for utilization of maltose and trehalose using API Coryne strips (BioMérieux, Marcy l'Etoile, France) and the Rosco Diagnostica reagents (Eurobio, Les Ulis, France) following provider's recommendations. The Hiss serum water test was used for glycogen fermentation. Briefly, this test was performed as follows. Solution A was obtained by dissolving 500 mg of bacteriological peptone (Oxoid, Hampshire, UK; ref. LP0037) in 100 mL of distilled water, adding 100 mg of Na₂HPO₄ (Sigma–Aldrich, Saint-Louis, Missouri, USA; ref. S7907), and homogenizing and heating the mixture until boiling. After cooling to room temperature, 18 mL of sterile horse serum were added and mixed. In parallel, solution B was prepared by adding 430 mg of acid fuchsin (Sigma–Aldrich, Saint-Louis, Missouri, USA, ref. F8129) into 86 mL of distilled water, after which 14 mL of 30% NaOH (ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, Massachusetts; ref. S/4950/PB15) were added. Solution B was stored up to 15 days in the dark. To prepare the complete Hiss serum water sugar medium, 780 μL of solution B were added to the total volume of solution A. The pH was adjusted to 7.7 using HCl 5N (Sigma–Aldrich, Saint-Louis, Missouri, USA; ref. H1758). 100 mg of glycogen (Acros Organics, Geel, Belgium, ref: 422,950,050) were then added. The solution was mixed and distributed in 3.5 mL aliquots in 5 mL glass tubes, and sterilized at 108°C during 30 min. This medium was conserved up to 6 months at $5^{\circ}\text{C} + 3^{\circ}\text{C}$. To perform the glycogen test, a loopful (10 μL) of a bacterial culture from Columbia blood agar or Tryptose–Casein–Soy agar was introduced into a tube containing 3.5 mL of sterile Hiss serum water sugar medium. Results were read manually after homogenization of the suspension and incubation at $37^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ during 24 h. Strains NCTC 12077 and NCTC 764 were used as positive and negative controls, respectively (expected results: dark pink and light pink, respectively).

The biovar of isolates was determined based on the combination of nitrate reductase (positive in Mitis and Gravis, negative in Belfantii) and glycogen fermentation (positive in Gravis only).

Antimicrobial susceptibility was characterized by the disk diffusion method using impregnated paper disks (Bio-Rad, Marnes-la-Coquette, France) and minimum inhibitory concentrations were determined using ETEST strips (BioMérieux, Marcy l'Etoile, France). The sensitivity was interpreted using CA-SFM/EUCAST V.1.0 (Jan 2019) criteria for *Corynebacterium* (https://www.sfm-microbiologie.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/02/CASFM2019_V1.0.pdf). Susceptibility was tested for the following antimicrobial agents: fosfomicin, vancomycin, kanamycin, gentamicin, penicillin G, oxacillin, amoxicillin, imipenem, cefotaxime, clindamycin, azithromycin, spiramycin, clarithromycin, erythromycin, ciprofloxacin, trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole, trimethoprim, sulfonamide, pristinamycin, rifampicin and tetracycline.

MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry was used for identification confirmation. For this purpose, an overnight culture on Tryptone-Casein-Soy Agar (TSA) (37°C) was used to prepare the samples accordingly to the ethanol/formic acid extraction procedure proposed by the manufacturer (Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany). The cell extracts were then spotted onto an MBT Biotarget 96 target plate, air dried and overlaid with 1 μL of a saturated α -cyano-4-hydroxycinnamic acid (HCCA). 24 mass spectra per strain were acquired on a Microflex LT mass spectrometer (Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany). Re-analysis of the spectra was performed for the purpose of this work. Spectra were first preprocessed by applying smoothing and baseline subtraction with FlexAnalysis software using default parameters, exported as text files from the Bruker system and then imported and analyzed in a dedicated BioNumerics v7.6.3 (Applied-Maths, Belgium) database following the protocol described by Rodrigues et al. [23]. To allocate proteins to the specific peaks detected, we extracted all the molecular weights from the genomes of the type strains (NCTC11397^T, FRC0043^T and FRC0190^T) using a Biopython script (<https://biopython.org/DIST/docs/api/Bio.SeqUtils-module.html>) and performed sequence alignments with ClustalW for the candidate proteins.

Genomic sequencing was performed from Nextera XT libraries using a NextSeq-500 instrument (Illumina, San Diego, USA) with a 2×150 nt paired-end protocol. Contig sequences were assembled using SPAdes v3.12.0 [24] (Table S1). JSpeciesWS [25] was used to calculate the BLAST-based average nucleotide identity (ANIb). BLASTN was used to extract 16S rRNA and *rpoB* sequences from genome assemblies and to determine the presence or absence of the *narJHGK* nitrate reduction gene cluster using as query the cluster of strain NCTC 13129 (RefSeq accession number: DIP_RS13820 to DIP_RS13845) [26]. *rpoB* and 16S rRNA gene sequences of atypical *C. belfantii* strains from cats [12] were included for comparison. For genome-based phylogenetic analysis, the pairwise *p*-distance (i.e., proportion of aligned nucleotide differences) between each pair of genomes was estimated based on Mash [27] using a multiple hit correction [28] with JolyTree (<https://gitlab.pasteur.fr/GIPhy/JolyTree>). For 16S rRNA and *rpoB* gene sequences, sequences were aligned with MAFFT v7.407 [29] and the resulting alignment was used for phylogenetic tree inference with IQ-TREE v1.6.7.2 [30] using the GTR + I + G4 model. Branch support was obtained after 1000 bootstrap replicates.

3. Results and discussion

Six isolates were isolated from five cutaneous lesions and one ascitic fluid sample (Table 1). Strikingly, human cutaneous lesions were all ulcerations due to underlying chronic arteritis. Ascitic fluid was sampled on a patient with a suspicion of spontaneous peritonitis. The dog was investigated in the context of purulent orbital cellulitis.

Table 1
Strains used in this study and their characteristics.

Isolate ^b	Species	biovar ^a	Isolation year	Country	Geographic origin ^c	tox gene	Isolation source	Disease	Reference
FRC0190 ^T	<i>C. rouxii</i>	Belfanti	2013	France	Lot, Cahors	Negative	Cutaneous	Foot ulceration, chronic arteritis	This study
FRC0071	<i>C. rouxii</i>	Belfanti	2011	France	Haute-Garonne, Toulouse	Negative	Cutaneous	Leg ulceration on chronic arteritis - diabetes	This study
FRC0284	<i>C. rouxii</i>	Belfanti	2015	France	Rhone, Lyon	Negative	Cutaneous	Limb amputation - vasculitis	This study
FRC0297	<i>C. rouxii</i>	Belfanti	2015	France	Herauld, Beziers	Negative	Ascitic fluid	Spontaneous peritonitis	This study
FRC0412	<i>C. rouxii</i>	Belfanti	2016	France	Lot, Cahors	Negative	Cutaneous	Purulent orbital cellulitis (dog)	This study
FRC0527	<i>C. rouxii</i>	Belfanti	2017	France	Savoie, Chambéry	Negative	Cutaneous	Foot ulceration on chronic arteritis	This study
FRC0043 ¹	<i>C. belfantii</i>	Belfanti	2009	France	Corrèze, Brives	Negative	Pharyngeal membrane	Laryngitis	Dazas et al., 2018 IJSEM
06–4305	<i>C. belfantii</i>	Belfanti	2006	France	Rhone, Lyon	Negative	Expectoration	Bronchopathy	Dazas et al., 2018 IJSEM
00–0744	<i>C. belfantii</i>	Belfanti	2000	France	Calvados, Caen	Negative	Expectoration	Cystic fibrosis	Dazas et al., 2018 IJSEM
FRC0074	<i>C. belfantii</i>	Belfanti	2011	France	Cote d'Or, Dijon	Negative	Expectoration	Cystic fibrosis	Dazas et al., 2018 IJSEM
FRC0223	<i>C. belfantii</i>	Belfanti	2014	France	Pas-de-Calais, Coquelles	Negative	Sinusal swab	Sinusitis	Dazas et al., 2018 IJSEM
05–3187	<i>C. belfantii</i>	Belfanti	2005	France	Seine-Maritime, Rouen	Negative	Nasal swab	Rhinitis	Dazas et al., 2018 IJSEM
FRC0250	<i>C. belfantii</i>	Belfanti	2014	France	Bas-Rhin, Strasbourg	Negative	Bronchoalveolar wash	Pneumonia	Dazas et al., 2018 IJSEM
FRC0301	<i>C. belfantii</i>	Belfanti	2015	France	Calvados, Lisieux	Negative	Expectoration	n.a.	Dazas et al., 2018 IJSEM
NCTC 11397 ^T	<i>C. diphtheriae</i>	Gravis	1969	USA	New York, USA	Negative	n.a.	n.a.	Dazas et al., 2018 IJSEM
NCTC 13129	<i>C. diphtheriae</i>	Gravis	1997	United Kingdom	Unknown	Positive	Pharyngeal membrane	Diphtheria	Dazas et al., 2018 IJSEM
FRC0336	<i>C. diphtheriae</i>	Gravis	2015	France	Ille-et-Vilaine, Rennes	Positive	Cutaneous	Leishmaniasis	Dazas et al., 2018 IJSEM
FRC0304	<i>C. diphtheriae</i>	Gravis	2015	France	La Reunion, St Denis	Negative	Cutaneous	Bullous skin lesion	Dazas et al., 2018 IJSEM
FRC0375	<i>C. diphtheriae</i>	Mitis	2015	France	Oise, Creil	Positive	Cutaneous	Ankle ulceration	Dazas et al., 2018 IJSEM
FRC0432	<i>C. diphtheriae</i>	Mitis	2016	France	Seine-et-Marne, Vaires sur Marne	Negative	Cutaneous	Purulent scalp skin injury	Dazas et al., 2018 IJSEM
FRC0157	<i>C. diphtheriae</i>	Mitis	2013	France	Paris	Negative	Cutaneous	Left ankle wound	Dazas et al., 2018 IJSEM
FRC0132	<i>C. diphtheriae</i>	Mitis	2012	France	Yvelines, Le Chesnay (return from Mali)	Negative	Cutaneous	Necrotic lesions	Dazas et al., 2018 IJSEM
FRC0036	<i>C. diphtheriae</i>	Mitis	2009	France	Mayotte, Mamoudzou	Negative	Cutaneous	Burn wound	Dazas et al., 2018 IJSEM
FRC0154	<i>C. diphtheriae</i>	Mitis	2012	France	Haut-Rhin, Colmar	Positive	Cutaneous	Cutaneous infection	Dazas et al., 2018 IJSEM
FRC0049	<i>C. diphtheriae</i>	Mitis	2009	France	Mayotte, Mamoudzou	Positive	Cutaneous	Genital lesion	Dazas et al., 2018 IJSEM
FRC0430	<i>C. diphtheriae</i>	Mitis	2016	France	Rhone, Bron	Positive	Cutaneous	Leg ulcerations	Dazas et al., 2018 IJSEM
FRC0436	<i>C. diphtheriae</i>	Mitis	2016	France	Ille-et-Vilaine, Rennes	Positive	Cutaneous	Cutaneous infection	Dazas et al., 2018 IJSEM
ATCC 19410 ^T	<i>C. pseudotuberculosis</i>	not applicable	1931	n.a.	South America	Negative	Infected gland (sheep)	n.a.	PMID: 13882624 (Cummins, 1962)
NCTC 7910 ^T	<i>C. ulcerans</i>	not applicable	1948	United Kingdom	n.a.	Negative	Throat	n.a.	PMID: 7,729,671 (Riegel et al., 1955)

n.a.: not available.

^a Biovar of *C. diphtheriae* as classically defined.

^b FRC: collection of the French National Reference Center for the Corynebacteria of the *C. diphtheriae* complex; NCTC: National Collection of Type Cultures (Public Health England); ATCC: American Type Culture Collection.

^c Geographic origin for French isolates is given as "French Department, city".

The six isolates were *tox* negative (Table S1); more specifically, they were negative for amplification of the expected 910-bp PCR product encompassing fragments A and B of the toxin gene [19] and also negative for the amplification of a 117-bp region of diphtheria toxin fragment A [31] by multiplex qPCR [20]. We also confirmed by BLASTN that the *tox* gene sequence (query: *tox* gene sequence from strain NCTC 13129, RefSeq accession number: DIP_RS12515) was absent from the genomic assemblies. After species identification by multiplex PCR, the isolates were positive for *dtxR* and *rpoB* and negative for *C. ulcerans*/*C. pseudotuberculosis* 16S rDNA and *pld*, leading to initial identification as *C. diphtheriae*. Concordant with this identification, the six isolates were pyrazinamidase, urease and trehalose negative. Upon biotyping, the isolates were nitrate and glycogen negative, a pattern that corresponds to biovar Belfanti. Consistently, the *narKGHIJ* nitrate reduction gene cluster was not detected from the genomic assemblies of these isolates and those of *C. belfantii* (Table S2). The phenotypic aspect of colonies on Tinsdale or blood agar medium was undistinctive from *C. diphtheriae* Mitis and Gravis and *C. belfantii*. However, we noted that similar to the Gravis isolates, the colonies of the six atypical isolates looked dry and were friable on TCS medium. Distinctively, the maltose test was negative for the six isolates using API Coryne (Table S1). The same test was atypical using the Rosco Diagnostic method: results showed heterogeneous coloration that was neither as yellow as the typically positive strains, nor as purple as the negative strains (Fig. S3). This atypical maltose result was not observed using API Coryne strips, with which the maltose test was clearly negative for the six isolates. We noted that the four genes of the maltose

utilization pathway [32] are present and undisrupted in the six isolates, as in other members of the *C. diphtheriae* complex. Further work is required to elucidate the mechanisms of maltose utilization and its regulation, and why the two tests give different results.

Regarding their antimicrobial susceptibility (Table S3), the six isolates were resistant to fosfomicin, as is typical of *Corynebacteria* [33], and were susceptible to all other tested antimicrobial agents with the following exceptions: FRC0284 and FRC0527 were resistant to penicillin (minimum inhibitory concentration: 0.19 mg/L), and FRC0412 was resistant to penicillin and cefotaxime (0.19 mg/L and 1.0 mg/L, respectively).

Genomic sequencing results showed that the six isolates had a genome size of 2.4 Mb on average (Table S1), similar to *C. diphtheriae* biovars Mitis and Gravis isolates (average size: 2.45 Mb), but smaller than *C. belfantii* (average size: 2.7 Mb). A genome sequence-based phylogenetic tree (Fig. 1) revealed three main clades. The first one contained all *C. diphtheriae* Mitis and Gravis isolates, whereas the second comprised all *C. belfantii* isolates, and the third comprised the six maltose-atypical isolates. The mean ANiB value of atypical isolates was 92.4% with the *C. diphtheriae* clade and was 91.4% with *C. belfantii* (Table 2). These data indicate that the six isolates forming the atypical clade correspond to a distinct genomic cluster, separated by a level of nucleotide divergence that is well above the currently accepted genomic species threshold of ~94–96% [34,35]. The atypical clade was genetically homogeneous, with ANiB values among the six isolates ranging from 99.21% to 99.94% (Table 2). Phylogenetic analysis of *rpoB* and 16S rRNA coding sequences was consistent

Fig. 1. Phylogenetic relationships derived from the analysis of genomic sequences. The phylogenetic tree and branch supports were inferred using JolyTree [28] (<https://gitlab.pasteur.fr/GIPhy/JolyTree>). Strains *C. ulcerans* NCTC 7910^T and *C. pseudotuberculosis* ATCC 19410^T were used as outgroup as they are the closest phylogenetic neighbors to *C. diphtheriae*, *C. belfantii* and *C. rouxii*. Branch support is indicated using grey circles (see key; only values > 50 are shown). Each taxonomic type strain is shown in bold; note that *C. diphtheriae* subsp. *lausannense* type strain falls within *C. belfantii*. The scale bar corresponds to an estimated evolutionary distance of 0.01.

Table 2
Average nucleotide identity values.

<i>Corynebacterium</i> species	Strain identifier ^a	FRC0071	FRC0190T	FRC0284	FRC0297	FRC0412	FRC0527	NCTC11397T	FRC0043T	NCTC7910T	ATCC19410T
<i>C. rouxii</i> sp. nov.	FRC0071	100	99.60	99.89	99.21	99.37	99.94	92.30	91.22	71.34	70.94
<i>C. rouxii</i> sp. nov.	FRC0190T	99.68	100	99.75	99.24	99.34	99.68	92.41	91.36	71.40	70.93
<i>C. rouxii</i> sp. nov.	FRC0284	99.94	99.71	100	99.22	99.35	99.92	92.30	91.28	71.26	70.85
<i>C. rouxii</i> sp. nov.	FRC0297	99.26	99.28	99.27	100	99.29	99.26	92.44	91.43	71.16	70.67
<i>C. rouxii</i> sp. nov.	FRC0412	99.45	99.26	99.40	99.23	100	99.44	92.39	91.37	71.04	70.79
<i>C. rouxii</i> sp. nov.	FRC0527	99.95	99.55	99.85	99.21	99.40	100	92.30	91.27	71.27	70.99
<i>C. diphtheriae</i>	NCTC11397T	92.33	92.45	92.30	92.32	92.34	92.32	100	95.07	71.29	70.86
<i>C. belfantii</i>	FRC0043T	90.92	91.06	90.93	90.99	90.99	90.92	94.77	100	71.12	70.76
<i>C. ulcerans</i>	NCTC7910T	71.42	71.51	71.43	71.32	71.30	71.42	71.40	71.31	100	84.33
<i>C. pseudotuberculosis</i>	ATCC19410T	71.31	71.30	71.31	71.25	71.25	71.31	71.19	71.06	84.29	100

^a A trailing T after the strain identifier denotes that the strain is the type strain of its corresponding taxon.

with the distinction of the atypical isolates from *C. diphtheriae* and *C. belfantii* (Figs. S1 and S2). However, the 16S rRNA gene sequence alignment showed only 3 insertions and 4 nucleotide substitutions shared among the six atypical isolates as compared to *C. diphtheriae*, resulting in low resolution of phylogenetic relationships (Fig. S1). We noted that *rpoB* and 16S rRNA sequences of previously reported atypical biovar Belfanti isolates from cats in the USA [12] were indistinguishable from those of the atypical isolates from France, suggesting that the cat isolates from the USA belong to the same novel group. Supporting this observation, the USA cat isolates were also reported as maltose negative [12].

Recently, it was proposed that the *C. diphtheriae* taxon should be subdivided into two subspecies, *C. diphtheriae* subsp. *diphtheriae* and *C. diphtheriae* subsp. *lausannense* [13]. Here, we observed that the ANI value between the type strains of *C. diphtheriae* subsp. *lausannense* and *C. belfantii* was 99.3%. Besides, the former was positioned within the phylogenetic branch of *C. belfantii* (Fig. 1, Figs. S1 and S2), and the descriptions of both taxa are very similar [3,13]. Given that *C. belfantii* was validly published in October 2018, a few months before the taxonomic proposal *C. diphtheriae* subsp. *lausannense* was validated (<https://www.microbiologyresearch.org/content/journal/ijsem/10.1099/ijsem.0.003174>; January 2019), the latter subspecies appears to be a later heterotypic synonym of *C. belfantii*.

Based on the MALDI Biotyper Compass database version 4.1.90 (Bruker Daltonics, Bremen, Germany), the six isolates were identified as *C. diphtheriae*. However, detailed analysis of their spectra led to the identification of six pairs of biomarkers (12 peaks corresponding to the same proteins, with either single and double-charged ion forms) corresponding to three different proteins within the range 3255–9495 *m/z*, which were associated either with the group of six isolates or with *C. diphtheriae* and *C. belfantii* (Fig. S4, Table S4). We presumptively identified the specific biomarkers as two ribosomal proteins, L30 and S20, and one putative stress response protein (CsbD). Consistently, their amino-acid sequences differed between the *C. rouxii* on the one hand, and *C. diphtheriae*/*C. belfantii* on the other hand (Fig. S5). Based on the current dataset, the specificity and sensitivity of peak distribution among the three species ranged between 95–100% and 76–100%, respectively (Table S4). MALDI-TOF MS thus allows the discrimination between *C. rouxii* and *C. diphtheriae*/*C. belfantii*. These results warrant future updates of reference MALDI-TOF databases to incorporate the novel taxon.

Based on the above results, the isolates of the novel clade represent a novel species, which we propose to name *Corynebacterium rouxii*.

Description of *C. rouxii* sp. nov. (rou'. xi.i. N.L. gen. n. *rouxii*, of Roux, a French scientist and former director of Institut Pasteur who made critical contributions to diphtheria toxin discovery and antitoxin treatment).

C. rouxii conforms biochemically to the description of *C. diphtheriae* strains belonging to biovar Belfanti [2,21], except that strains are negative for maltose fermentation (API Coryne), being nearly negative or weakly positive with the Rosco Diagnostica maltose test. Key characteristics that distinguish *C. rouxii* from other members of the *C. diphtheriae* complex are specific MALDI-TOF MS biomarkers as described herein. The G + C content of *C. rouxii* genomes ranges from 53.2% to 53.3%, with a value of 53.3% for the type strain. So far, strains were isolated from 5 humans and a dog in France, as well as from two related cats in the USA.

The type strain is FRC0190^T (= CIP 111752^T = DSM 110354^T), isolated in 2013 from a foot ulceration reported in Cahors, France. The genome accession number of strain FRC0190^T is ERS3795540.

Author contributions

Conceived the study: SB. Performed the experiments: EB, CR, VP, MD, ACL. Analyzed the data: MH, CR, LP, VB, SB. Curated data: VB, MD, EB, JT, SB. Wrote the initial draft of the manuscript: SB, CR, JT. Commented on working versions of the manuscript and agreed on the final version of the manuscript: all.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resmic.2020.02.003>.

Data availability

Sequence data generated in this study were deposited in the European Nucleotide Archive database and are accessible under

project number PRJEB22103. The EMBL (GenBank/DBJ) accession numbers of the genomic sequences released in this study are ERS3795539 to ERS3795544. The annotated genomic sequence of strain FRC0190^T was deposited in the European Nucleotide Archive and is available under accession number ERZ1195831. *rpoB* and 16S rRNA gene sequences were also submitted individually under accession numbers MN542347 to MN542352 and MN535982 to MN535987, respectively.

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**PARTIE III : APPLICATIONS DE LA TAXONOMIE
GÉNOMIQUE ET DE LA RÉSISTANCE AUX
ANTIBIOTIQUES A DES ÉTUDES DE CAS**

CHAPITRE 6 : Épidémie de diphtérie au Yémen

Titre de l'article

Ongoing diphtheria outbreak in Yemen: a cross-sectional and genomic epidemiology study

Résumé

Une épidémie de diphtérie, déclarée au Yémen en octobre 2017, est en cours. Nous avons réalisé une étude transversale pour étudier les caractéristiques épidémiologiques, cliniques et microbiologiques de l'épidémie.

Les cas probables de diphtérie qui ont été définis cliniquement et enregistrés via un système électronique hebdomadaire d'alerte précoce des maladies (de 2017, semaine 22, à 2020, semaine 17) ont été utilisés pour identifier les tendances de l'épidémie (nous avons divisé l'épidémie en trois périodes : mai du 29 juin 2017 au 10 juin 2018 ; du 11 juin 2018 au 3 juin 2019 ; et du 4 juin 2019 au 26 avril 2020). Nous avons utilisé la liste linéaire des rapports sur la diphtérie pour les descriptions au niveau des gouvernorats. La couverture vaccinale a été estimée à partir des rapports annuels 2017 et 2018 du programme national élargi de vaccination. Pour confirmer biologiquement les cas, *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* a été isolé et identifié à partir de prélèvements de gorge à l'aide de procédures standard de culture microbiologique et d'identification. Nous avons évalué les différences dans la répartition temporelle et géographique des cas, y compris entre les différents groupes d'âge. Pour une analyse microbiologique approfondie, le gène *tox* et la PCR en temps réel *rpoB* spécifique à l'espèce, le séquençage génomique Illumina, l'analyse de la sensibilité aux antimicrobiens (diffusion sur disque, E-test) et le test de production de toxine diphtérique Elek ont été effectués sur des cas confirmés. Nous avons utilisé les données génomiques pour les analyses phylogénétiques et pour estimer le taux de substitution des nucléotides.

L'épidémie de diphtérie au Yémen a touché presque tous les gouvernorats (provinces), avec 5701 cas probables et 330 décès enregistrés jusqu'au 26 avril 2020. Nous avons recueilli des données cliniques pour 888 cas probables avec des échantillons de prélèvement de gorge référés pour confirmation biologique, et des données génomiques pour 42 cas positifs, correspondant à 43 isolats (deux isolats d'une culture ont été inclus en raison de morphologies de colonies distinctes). L'âge médian des patients était de 12 ans (extrêmes 0-2-80). La proportion de cas chez les enfants âgés de 0 à 4 ans a été réduite au cours de la deuxième période, après une campagne de vaccination, par rapport à la première période (19 % [IC 95 % 18-21] dans la première période vs 14 % [12-15] en seconde période, $p < 0,0001$). Parmi les 43 isolats testés, 39 (91 %) produisaient la toxine diphtérique et deux présentaient une faible résistance antimicrobienne (0,25 mg/L) à la pénicilline. Nous avons identifié six sous-lignées phylogénétiques *C. diphtheriae*, dont quatre sont génétiquement liées à des isolats d'Arabie saoudite, d'Érythrée et de Somalie. Des variations génomiques inter-sous-lignées dans les gènes associés à la résistance aux antimicrobiens, à l'acquisition du fer et à l'adhésion ont été observées. La sous-lignée prédominante (30 [70 %] de 43 isolats) était résistante au triméthoprime et était associée à des caractéristiques génomiques uniques, un gonflement du cou plus fréquent ($p = 0,0029$) et un âge plus jeune des patients ($p = 0,060$) par rapport avec les autres sous-lignées. Son taux d'évolution a été estimé à $1,67 \times 10^{-6}$ substitutions par site et

par an, plaçant son ancêtre commun le plus récent en 2015 et indiquant une circulation silencieuse de *C. diphtheriae* au Yémen avant la déclaration de l'épidémie.

Contributions personnelles

- Contribution à la recherche bibliographique des facteurs de virulence
- Analyses génomiques : recherche des gènes de résistance et virulence

Ongoing diphtheria outbreak in Yemen: a cross-sectional and genomic epidemiology study

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Summary

Background An outbreak of diphtheria, declared in Yemen in October, 2017, is ongoing. We did a cross-sectional study to investigate the epidemiological, clinical, and microbiological features of the outbreak.

Methods Probable cases of diphtheria that were defined clinically and recorded through a weekly electronic diseases early warning system (from 2017, week 22, to 2020, week 17) were used to identify trends of the outbreak (we divided the epidemic into three time periods: May 29, 2017, to June 10, 2018; June 11, 2018, to June 3, 2019; and June 4, 2019, to April 26, 2020). We used the line list of diphtheria reports for governorate-level descriptions. Vaccination coverage was estimated using the 2017 and 2018 annual reports by the national Expanded Programme on Immunization. To confirm cases biologically, *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* was isolated and identified from throat swabs using standard microbiological culture and identification procedures. We assessed differences in the temporal and geographical distributions of cases, including between different age groups. For in-depth microbiological analysis, *tox* gene and species-specific *rpoB* real-time PCR, Illumina genomic sequencing, antimicrobial susceptibility analysis (disk diffusion, E-test), and the Elek diphtheria toxin production test were done on confirmed cases. We used genomic data for phylogenetic analyses and to estimate the nucleotide substitution rate.

Findings The Yemen diphtheria outbreak affected almost all governorates (provinces), with 5701 probable cases and 330 deaths recorded up to April 26, 2020. We collected clinical data for 888 probable cases with throat swab samples referred for biological confirmation, and genomic data for 42 positive cases, corresponding to 43 isolates (two isolates from one culture were included due to distinct colony morphologies). The median age of patients was 12 years (range 0–80). The proportion of cases in children aged 0–4 years was reduced during the second time period, after a vaccination campaign, compared with the first period (19% [95% CI 18–21] in the first period vs 14% [12–15] in the second period, $p < 0.0001$). Among 43 tested isolates, 39 (91%) produced the diphtheria toxin and two had low level (0.25 mg/L) antimicrobial resistance to penicillin. We identified six *C diphtheriae* phylogenetic sublineages, four of which are genetically related to isolates from Saudi Arabia, Eritrea, and Somalia. Inter-sublineage genomic variations in genes associated with antimicrobial resistance, iron acquisition, and adhesion were observed. The predominant sublineage (30 [70%] of 43 isolates) was resistant to trimethoprim and was associated with unique genomic features, more frequent neck swelling ($p = 0.0029$) and a younger age of patients ($p = 0.060$) compared with the other sublineages. Its evolutionary rate was estimated at 1.67×10^{-6} substitutions per site per year, placing its most recent common ancestor in 2015, and indicating silent circulation of *C diphtheriae* in Yemen before the outbreak was declared.

Interpretation In the Yemen outbreak, *C diphtheriae* shows high phylogenetic, genomic, and phenotypic variation. Laboratory capacity and real-time microbiological monitoring of diphtheria outbreaks need to be scaled up to inform case management and transmission control of diphtheria. Catch-up vaccination might have provided some protection to the targeted population (children aged 0–4 years).

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Introduction

Diphtheria is a severe infection that typically affects the upper respiratory tract, potentially leading to pseudo-membrane formation, neck swelling, and suffocation.^{1,2} In addition, diphtheria toxin production by some *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* strains can cause damage to the heart and other organs. Non-toxigenic strains can also cause invasive infections. Before large-scale vaccination,

which mainly targets the toxin and is highly effective in preventing the disease, diphtheria was a major cause of death in children.¹ Large outbreaks of diphtheria are often observed after disruption to vaccination programmes, such as in ex-Soviet Union countries in the 1990s and more recently in Venezuela and the Rohingya refugee population in Bangladesh. Diphtheria is still observed occasionally in high-income countries, particularly among migrants.³

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For the Arabic (Yemenite) translation of the abstract see Online for appendix 1

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Research in context

Evidence before this study

An outbreak of diphtheria has been ongoing in Yemen since October, 2017. We did a search of PubMed and Google on March 22, 2021, with no language restrictions, using the search terms “Yemen” and “diphtheria”. This search identified that the epidemiology of the outbreak was described only up to mid-2018, and its microbiological and clinical features have not been reported. A search of PubMed for studies published from database inception up to March 22, 2021, using the term “diphtheria+outbreak+genomic”, showed that only two outbreaks of toxigenic diphtheria have been investigated using genomic sequencing: an outbreak in South Africa in 2015, and a Belarus outbreak in 1996–2014. In both outbreaks, the coexistence of diverse sublineages of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* and variable toxigenicity status were reported. Evolutionary rates were estimated for the Belarus outbreak sublineages ST5 and ST8: 5.6×10^{-7} substitutions per strain per year for ST5 and 8.9×10^{-7} substitutions per strain per year for ST8. Genomic sequences of *C diphtheriae* isolated in 2015 from refugees from Eritrea, Ethiopia, Syria, and Somalia were reported, but their relationship with Yemen isolates is unknown.

Added value of this study

To our knowledge, this is the first study to report epidemiological data collected since mid-2018 on diphtheria in Yemen, and to provide clinical features of cases of diphtheria from this ongoing outbreak. We defined three periods of the epidemic and showed that from the first period (May 29, 2017, to June 10, 2018) to the second period (June 11, 2018, to

June 3, 2019), infection risk decreased in children aged 0–4 years. We report on the microbiological characteristics of the outbreak strains, including their toxigenic status, biovar, antimicrobial susceptibility, and virulence factor gene content, indicating variation in toxigenicity status and antimicrobial resistance, iron acquisition, and adhesin genes. These data indicate high heterogeneity of the strains within a single outbreak. We also estimate the evolutionary rate of the main Yemen *C diphtheriae* lineage, ST384 (1.67×10^{-6} substitutions per site per year), and provide evidence for regional spread of *C diphtheriae* sublineages, based on genomic relatedness of *C diphtheriae* from Yemen with strains linked to Saudi Arabia and Eritrea.

Implications of all the available evidence

The combined epidemiological, clinical, and microbiological data from Yemen provide insight into one of the largest outbreaks of diphtheria in the past 20 years. Differences in the proportion of infections in children aged 0–4 years between the first and second period are consistent with some success from the mass immunisation catch-up programme. The evidence of genetic heterogeneity, antimicrobial susceptibility, and toxigenicity variation among *C diphtheriae* strains within a single large diphtheria outbreak shows the need for increased laboratory capacity and rapid testing, to improve diphtheria case management. Further investigation of both the local and regional spread of *C diphtheriae* will inform infection prevention strategies.

Genomic analysis of *C diphtheriae* isolates from outbreaks or surveillance programmes is critical in tracing transmission at local or regional scales, and in defining evolutionary rates, temporal depth of transmission, and genomic heterogeneity among strains.^{3–5} Besides vaccination, a critical component of diphtheria management is serotherapy. Unfortunately, diphtheria antitoxin is not readily available in Yemen, as in most countries.⁶ Antimicrobial treatment is also indicated for patient care and to avoid transmission, with penicillin and erythromycin being recommended as first-line therapeutic agents.¹⁷

In Yemen, where civil war has been ongoing since March, 2015, a large outbreak of diphtheria was recognised in October, 2017^{8–11} Although a vaccination campaign targeting 300 000 children began in late November, 2018, with plans to scale up to 3 million children and young adults in December, 2018, the conflict has complicated vaccination catch-up efforts.^{12,13} Before this outbreak, diphtheria was considered endemic in Yemen, with an average of 50 suspected cases reported annually since 2000.¹⁰ The last documented outbreak of diphtheria in this country occurred in 1981–82, with a total of 149 cases and no deaths. Yemen is currently also affected by other epidemic diseases, including cholera¹⁴ and

COVID-19.^{15,16} As of May, 2020, the diphtheria outbreak was ongoing.¹⁷ Although the early epidemiology of the outbreak was described,^{8,9} almost no data have been reported on the clinical and microbiological characteristics of the outbreak. Here, we report on the clinical, epidemiological, and microbiological features of the ongoing Yemen diphtheria outbreak.

Methods

Study design

We did a cross-sectional study, including a molecular epidemiology investigation, of a diphtheria outbreak across Yemen, in 2017–20. For epidemiological investigations, several national-level data sources were used. Yemen is divided into 22 governorates, which are further divided into 333 districts. In this study, the majority of districts that provided epidemiological data were located within governorates in the central and northern regions of Yemen. In each district, a rapid response team of the surveillance department was mobilised through warning reports from health facilities. This team then both investigated the clinical cases and collected the samples for confirmation. Throat swabs were done for every tenth case if there was a cluster of more than ten cases. In

parallel, the electronic diseases early warning system (eDEWS) questionnaire was filled by the eDEWS focal person in each health facility on a weekly basis.¹⁸ This sampling strategy remained stable over time.

Probable cases were defined by the rapid response team based on clinical examination showing an adherent membrane on one or more of the tonsils, pharynx, and nose, and any one of the following: laryngitis, pharyngitis, or tonsillitis.¹⁸ We compiled probable cases from eDEWS releases from 2017, week 22 (May 29, 2017), to 2020, week 17 (April 26, 2020).¹⁸ We used the line list of diphtheria reports for governorate-level descriptions. Vaccination coverage was estimated using the 2017 and 2018 annual reports by the national Expanded Programme on Immunization, obtained from the Ministry of Public Health and Population of Yemen.

Confirmed cases were defined as a probable case from which a *C diphtheriae* isolate was cultivated at the Yemen National Centre of the Public Health Laboratories (NCPHL).

To describe characteristics of the outbreak over time, we divided the epidemic into three time periods: May 29, 2017, to June 10, 2018; June 11, 2018, to June 3, 2019; and June 4, 2019, to April 26, 2020.

This work was done as part of routine case management under an emergency response mandate from the Government of Yemen and was supervised by the scientific committee of the NCPHL. The NCPHL collected samples and isolated strains and transferred some of them to the French National Reference Centre for Diphtheria for genomic sequencing.

Procedures

Throat swabs were stored in Amies transport medium (HiMedia, Mumbai, India) and transported within 24 h to the NCPHL laboratory on cold bags. Throat swab samples were analysed using standard microbiological procedures, as detailed in appendix 2 (pp 2–5). Briefly, swabs were plated on blood agar and tellurite blood agar (Sigma-Aldrich, Darmstadt, Germany). Gram and Albert stains were done to examine the presence of Gram-positive bacilli and metachromatic granules. Suspected *C diphtheriae* colonies were further sub-cultured on Tinsdale agar (Himedia, Mumbai, India), Dorset egg medium (Oxoid, Basingstoke, UK), and tellurite blood agar, followed by biochemical testing. Among stored positive cultures available in July, 2019, 100 samples were selected using a uniform random number generator. 98 of these stored samples were retrieved from storage (two tubes corresponding to selected samples had been lost) and were sent to Institut Pasteur (Paris, France) for complementary analyses that included re-isolation on Tinsdale medium, *tox* gene and species-specific *mpoB* real-time PCR,¹⁹ Illumina genomic sequencing, biovar identification, antimicrobial susceptibility (disk diffusion, E-test; interpreted using EUCAST/CA-SFM 2019 version 2.0 if available), and the Elek diphtheria toxin production test (appendix 2 pp 2–3). Phylogenetic analyses, substitution

rate, and node date estimations were based on parsnp version 1.2, SAM2MSA version 0.2.2.1, and IQTREE version 2.0.4 tools, and pangenome construction on PPanGGOLiN version 1.1.72; and known virulence and resistance genes were searched in the assembled genomes (appendix 2 pp 4–5). Sublineages were defined as deep tree branches. For the combined phylogenetic analysis of the Yemen and DIFT045 isolates with global *C diphtheriae* genomes, we used all genomic sequence assemblies that were publicly available from the National Center for Biotechnology Information database on June 1, 2020.

Statistical analysis

We tested differences in the temporal and geographical distributions of probable and confirmed cases using Fisher's exact test due to low sampling numbers in some governorates. Using a line list of patients from the first two periods, we computed the proportion of cases by age group. We calculated 95% CIs for these proportions using a binomial test. We tested differences among the proportions of cases within each age group between the two first periods using a χ^2 test. The line list was not available for the third period. Differences in clinical characteristics between cases infected with *C diphtheriae* sublineage A and those infected with other sublineages were assessed by the Mann-Whitney *U* test, the Student's *t* test, the χ^2 test, and Fisher's exact test when appropriate (eg, Fisher's exact test was used if the sample size within a category was <5). Statistical analysis was done using SPSS version 25. The diphtheria attack rate was calculated by dividing the number of cases in each age group by the size of the population within each age group (age data were obtained from the Yemen nutrition smart survey, 2019).

Role of the funding source

The funders of the study had no role in study design, data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, or writing of the report.

Results

Large numbers of probable cases of diphtheria were recorded in Yemen in 2017 (n=442), 2018 (n=2606), 2019 (n=2004), and 2020 (up to week 17: n=649). Altogether, 5701 cases, including 330 deaths, were reported up to April 26, 2020, corresponding to a case fatality rate of 5.8%. Between February, 2018, and November, 2019, we collected clinical data for 888 probable cases with throat samples referred to the NCPHL for biological confirmation (table), and genomic data for 42 positive cases corresponding to 43 isolates (figure 1). These 43 isolates were derived from 98 randomly selected samples, out of the 340 biologically confirmed cases. Some clinical data were missing (table).

We divided the epidemic into three time periods (figure 2A) and qualitatively observed incidence valleys in June, 2018, and June, 2019. In the third period

For the Yemen nutrition smart survey see <https://data.humdata.org/dataset/yemen-nutrition-smart-survey>

See Online for appendix 2

(June 4, 2019, to April 26, 2020), the recorded number of probable cases peaked in November, 2019, with more than 80 cases per week at that time. The diphtheria attack rates were 6·34 probable cases per 100 000 individuals in the first period and 6·24 probable cases per 100 000 in the second period (p=0·66).

The outbreak started in October, 2017, in Ibb and affected almost all governorates of Yemen (figure 2, appendix 2 pp 13–14, 22). The two first periods had distinct geographical distributions (p=0·0005).

The percentage of the 888 patients for whom clinical data were available who had been vaccinated did not change between 2018 and 2019 (57% vs 59%, p=0·49). The median age of vaccinated patients was lower (10 years, range 0·2–45) than that of non-vaccinated patients (13 years, range 0·2–80; p<0·0001). Most probable cases were in children aged 5–15 years (median 12 years, range 0·2–80), and their age distribution differed between the two first epidemic periods (p<0·0001). Specifically, there was a marked reduction in the proportion of cases that were in individuals aged 0–4 years (from 19% [95% CI 18–21] in the first period to 14% [12–15] in the second period, p<0·0001; appendix 2 pp 15–16). No difference in disease expression (characteristics in table) was observed between

vaccinated and non-vaccinated patients (p values ranging from 0·12 to 0·81).

Microbiological confirmation of cases was tested for 888 samples referred to the NCPHL from 2018 to 2020. Of the 836 cases with available results, 340 (41%) were microbiologically confirmed by a positive *C diphtheriae* culture. Of note, most patients (634 [80%] of 790) were reported to be receiving antibiotic therapy (mostly penicillin, erythromycin, or azithromycin) at the time of throat sampling (78% of microbiologically confirmed cases vs 82% of not confirmed; p=0·23). There was no difference in the geographical distributions of probable and confirmed cases (first period: p=0·84, second period: p=0·22).

Of 98 cultures transferred to Institut Pasteur, 47 were confirmed to contain genetic material of *C diphtheriae* by real-time PCR, among which 42 could be re-isolated. YEM0065 and YEM0070 with distinct colony morphologies were isolated from a single patient. Detection of the diphtheria toxin *tox* gene was positive in 39 (91%) of 43 isolates; four isolates were *tox*-negative by real-time PCR (appendix 2 pp 6–8), which was confirmed by genomic analyses. All *tox*-positive isolates produced the toxin. Phylogenomic analyses identified six sublineages (labelled A to F; figure 3). Sublineage A comprised

	Number of cases with available data*	Characteristic, median (range) or n (%)	p value (confirmed vs non-confirmed cases)	Cases analysed by whole-genome sequencing		
				Cases from sublineage A (n=28)†, median (range) or n (%)	Cases from sublineages B–F (n=14)†, median (range) or n (%)	p value (sublineage A vs sublineages B–F)
Age, years						
Probable cases	824	12 (0·2–80)
Not confirmed	463	11 (0·2–80)
Confirmed	313	12 (0·3–60)	0·36	8 (2–35)	14 (2–35)	0·060
Cases per age group: 0–4 years; 5–14 years; ≥15 years						
Probable cases	824	151 (18%); 346 (42%); 327 (40%)
Not confirmed	463	96 (21%); 187 (40%); 180 (39%)
Confirmed	313	48 (15%); 141 (45%); 124 (40%)	0·14	6 (21%); 17 (61%); 5 (18%)	1 (8%); 5 (42%); 6 (50%)‡	0·15
Male sex						
Probable cases	881	398 (45%)
Not confirmed	496	242 (49%)
Confirmed	340	142 (42%)	0·053	14 (50%)	5 (36%)	0·51
Female sex						
Probable cases	881	483 (55%)
Not confirmed	496	254 (51%)
Confirmed	340	198 (58%)	0·053	14 (50%)	9 (64%)	0·51
History of previous vaccination						
Probable cases	750	434 (58%)
Not confirmed	427	259 (61%)
Confirmed	281	153 (54%)	0·12	11/25 (44%)	7/11 (64%)	0·47

(Table continues on next page)

	Number of cases with available data*	Characteristic, median (range) or n (%)	p value (confirmed vs non-confirmed cases)	Cases analysed by whole-genome sequencing		
				Cases from sublineage A (n=28)†, median (range) or n (%)	Cases from sublineages B-F (n=14)†, median (range) or n (%)	p value (sublineage A vs sublineages B-F)
(Continued from previous page)						
History of antibiotic therapy						
Probable cases	790	634 (80%)
Not confirmed	455	371 (82%)
Confirmed	296	230 (78%)	0.23	13/27 (48%)	11/13 (85%)	0.040
Fever						
Probable cases	841	818 (97%)
Not confirmed	476	463 (97%)
Confirmed	322	314 (98%)	0.83	28 (100%)	14 (100%)	NA
Pseudomembrane						
Probable cases	839	787 (94%)
Not confirmed	477	453 (95%)
Confirmed	319	299 (94%)	0.55	28 (100%)	14 (100%)	NA
Neck swelling						
Probable cases	769	456 (59%)
Not confirmed	437	263 (60%)
Confirmed	297	181 (61%)	0.89	22/26 (85%)	4/12 (33%)	0.0029
Laryngitis						
Probable cases	784	548 (70%)
Not confirmed	444	311 (70%)
Confirmed	299	213 (71%)	0.79	22/26 (85%)	7/12 (58%)	0.11
Tonsillitis						
Probable cases	836	821 (98%)
Not confirmed	475	468 (99%)
Confirmed	319	313 (98%)	0.87	28 (100%)	14 (100%)	NA
Difficulty swallowing						
Probable cases	823	708 (86%)
Not confirmed	468	407 (87%)
Confirmed	315	267 (85%)	0.44	25/26 (96%)	11/13 (85%)	0.25
Difficulty breathing						
Probable cases	785	399 (51%)
Not confirmed	453	234 (52%)
Confirmed	295	148 (50%)	0.72	12/26 (46%)	8/13 (62%)	0.36

Undetermined cases (n=52) were excluded. NA—not applicable. *Total number of cases was 888; the difference between the number of probable cases and the total number of cases represents missing data (eg, for age: 888–824=64 cases with missing data). †For some characteristics, the number of cases is shown as n/N; the difference between N and the denominator values (28 for sublineage A, 14 for sublineages B-F) represents missing data. ‡Two data points were missing.

Table: Clinical characteristics of probable cases of diphtheria

30 (70%) isolates (appendix 2 pp 6–8). The six sublineages were unrelated to each other (appendix 2 p 17). Sublineages A and B were biovar gravis, whereas the others were biovar mitis (appendix 2 pp 6–8).

Sublineage A isolates were closely related to strain DIFT045 (figure 3), which was isolated in Belgium and is epidemiologically linked to Saudi Arabia.²⁰ Sublineage B isolates were closely related to isolates from migrants of Eritrean origins, sublineage C isolates were closely related to isolates from migrants of Somalian origins,³ and

sublineage E isolates were related to isolates from Somalian siblings (appendix 2 pp 17–18).²¹ Sublineages D and F were not phylogenetically closely related to *C diphtheriae* isolates with publicly available genomic sequences. Genetic network analysis confirmed the close relatedness of the Eritrea and Belgium isolates to Yemen isolates, and showed cross-governorate transmission of sublineages within Yemen (appendix 2 p 18).

We defined the pangenome diversity of isolates (appendix 2 p 19), identifying 3619 gene families,

Figure 1: Study flow chart
eDEWS=electronic diseases early warning system. NCPHL=Yemen National Centre of the Public Health Laboratories.
*Two isolates from one culture were included due to distinct colony morphologies.

1790 of which were shared by all isolates. Genomes had a mean of 2277 genes (range 2234–2427), and each of the six sublineages possessed 54–140 genes not observed in the other sublineages, underlying the potential for large phenotypic variation among them.

To evaluate the microevolution of sublineage A, we subdivided it into two branches, with branch A.1 being further subdivided into A.1.1 and A.1.2 (figure 3). The epidemiologically predominant branch A.1 was highly homogeneous genetically, with a maximum of 86 genome-wide single nucleotide polymorphisms among its members (observed between YEM0063 and YEM0089), indicating that A.1 isolates share a recent common ancestor. The amount of nucleotide substitutions observed in isolates of this sublineage was significantly associated with their isolation time (appendix 2 p 20), demonstrating measurable evolutionary divergence (figure 3), with a substitution rate estimated at 1.67×10^{-6} substitutions per site per year within A.1.1 (95% CI 3.98×10^{-7} to 2.99×10^{-6}). The last common ancestor of A.1.1 was estimated to have existed in March, 2015 (range November, 2003, to September, 2016).

Antimicrobial susceptibility data were heterogeneous among Yemen sublineages (figure 3, appendix 2 pp 9–12). Full susceptibility or very low levels of penicillin resistance were observed for all Yemen diphtheria isolates, which did not carry the *pbp2m* gene encoding for penicillin-binding protein identified in *C. diphtheriae* in 2020.²² Amoxicillin and erythromycin were active against all isolates, as were many other tested molecules. Resistance to ciprofloxacin (but not to moxifloxacin) was observed in two isolates, which both had an Asp93Gly substitution in the quinolone resistance-determining region of their *gyrA* gene. Non-susceptibility to trimethoprim was found in 32 (74%) isolates, including most members of sublineage A, but none were resistant to the combination of this agent with sulfamethoxazole. Four (9%) isolates possessed the *sul1* gene, and decreased phenotypic susceptibility to sulfonamide was observed in two of these. Resistance to tetracycline was observed in 11 (26%) isolates, which all belonged to minor sublineages, whereas sublineage A was susceptible; five of these resistant isolates had known tetracycline resistance genes encoding the Tet33 efflux pump or the TetO ribosomal protection protein. Finally, the two isolates of sublineage B had an *aadA2* gene encoding for an ANT(3') aminoglycoside modifying enzyme. This enzyme confers resistance to spectinomycin and streptomycin, which were not tested, but not to gentamicin and kanamycin, which remained active against sublineage B isolates.

Clinical features of *C. diphtheriae* infections caused by isolates from sublineage A were distinctive, with patients tending to be younger ($p=0.060$) and more frequently presenting with a swollen neck ($p=0.0029$) compared with other sublineages (table). We screened the genomic sequences for the presence of putative pathogenicity-associated genes.²³ Sublineage A isolates possessed genes *iusABC* encoding for an ABC-type iron uptake system, the *chtAB* genes that are homologous to *htaAB* genes for haemin binding, a pathogenicity island of *C. diphtheriae* called PICD-11,²³ comprising a putative collagen-binding protein, and the *spaABC-strA* and *spaDEF-strBC* fimbriae gene clusters (figure 3, appendix 2 p 17). In contrast to sublineage A, most other Yemen isolates did not have the aforementioned gene clusters; their genomes comprised genes *sidBA-ddpABC* for putative siderophore biosynthesis, *irp1ABCD* for a putative ABC-type iron transporter, and the *irp2ABCDEFGH* and *irp2JKLMN* operons. Genes encoding for SpaH fimbriae were absent from all Yemen genomes. Broader putative virulence gene variation was observed at the global scale, with a marked dichotomy between the two major lineages defined by gene *spuA* (appendix 2 p 17).

Discussion

We provide an update on the epidemiological situation of the diphtheria outbreak in Yemen, as well as a clinical description of recorded probable cases and detailed information on microbiological features of *C. diphtheriae*

Figure 2: Epidemic curve and geographical and temporal origins of the isolates (A) Weekly numbers of probable cases, probable cases with samples, and confirmed cases of diphtheria in Yemen from January, 2017, to April, 2020. Sequenced isolates are shown below the epidemic curve, coloured according to their sublineages. (B) Map of Yemen governorates. (C) Geographical location of the 888 samples of this study. (D, E) Geographical location of the suspected cases during the first and second periods. The governorate maps of Yemen were reproduced based on a shape file approved by the Humanitarian Country Team in October, 2019.

outbreak isolates. This outbreak is one of the largest contemporary *C diphtheriae* outbreaks. We defined three periods of the epidemic, which had distinct geographical distributions. Whether these periods—among which we qualitatively observed possible peaks and valleys in the number of reported probable cases—correspond to actual epidemic waves or result from variations in health-care-seeking behaviour is unclear (Ramadan and Eid occurred during May to June of 2018 and 2019). Diphtheria incidence can be affected by multiple factors, including the dynamics of internally displaced persons and active civil war.^{8,9} We note that

reporting is very likely to be an underestimate in the context of the Yemen health-care disruption, and to be unevenly distributed geographically, given the heterogeneity in the continuation of health-care facility operations. Nevertheless, the eDEWS system¹⁸ was valuable in the surveillance of diphtheria in the conflict context.

Clinical characteristics were typical of diphtheria, in terms of laryngeal manifestations, pseudomembrane presence, and neck swelling. Yemenite patients were mostly young, which is also typical, with the exception of the epidemic in ex-Soviet Union countries. Vaccination is highly effective against the clinical expression of

Figure 3: Phylogenetic analysis of Yemen isolates with their virulence and resistance characteristics
 The phylogenetic tree shows 43 Yemen isolates and strain DIFT045, with the distinction of six sublineages (A to F; sublineage A was subdivided into A.1 [A.1.1, A.1.2] and A.2). Black squares denote a resistant phenotype (based on E-test for penicillin and on disk diffusion for other antimicrobial agents). Black circles denote the presence of the *tox* gene or other virulence-associated genes. Open squares denote an intermediate resistance phenotype (observed only for trimethoprim and sulfonamides). Scale bar represents 0.001 nucleotide substitutions per site. The lower part of the figure shows a detailed phylogenetic tree of sublineage A.1. Node ages (with 95% CIs) are shown at the nodes. Bold branches denote bootstrap support >80%. Scale bar represents 0.000005 nucleotide substitutions per site (ie, 1 substitution every 200 000 nucleotides, or approximately ten substitutions per genome). Isolates YEM0065 and YEM0070 were derived from a single patient sample but were both included because they had distinct colony morphologies.

toxigenic *C diphtheriae* infections, and countries with high population coverage have almost eliminated endemic diphtheria.¹ In Yemen, the vaccination coverage of the third dose of pentavalent vaccine in 2017 and 2018 was less than 80% in several governorates (appendix 2 p 21), which is considered insufficient to reach population immunity.²⁴ We found that more than 50% of patients were reported to be previously vaccinated. We did not have access to the exact vaccination status but can assume that some individuals had incomplete vaccination without a booster, given the high effectiveness of the complete diphtheria vaccine course. This situation might also explain the median age of patients being older than 5 years, similar to other outbreaks in populations where vaccination was incomplete.²⁵ From November, 2017, to March, 2018, a mass vaccination campaign targeted nearly 2.7 million children aged 6 weeks to 15 years in 11 governorates.²⁶ We found that from the first to the second period, there was a reduction in the proportion of cases in children aged 0–4 years, consistent with some success from the mass vaccination programme. In 2019, diphtheria vaccination was also done in 186 districts of the 12 northern governorates,²⁷ with 1.2 million children aged 6 weeks to 5 years receiving the pentavalent vaccine (which protects against diphtheria and four other major diseases) and 2.2 million children aged 5–15 years receiving the tetanus–diphtheria vaccine (manufactured by the Serum Institute of India). Vaccination against diphtheria in selected districts of southern governorates and Sa'adah started in July, 2020. However, despite efforts to control the disease,²⁷ cases were still being reported in March, 2021.²⁸

This work represents a unique genomic analysis of a large outbreak of diphtheria. A prominent observation was that at least six unrelated phylogenetic sublineages contributed to the resurgence of diphtheria in Yemen, demonstrating multiple occurrences of diphtheria re-emergence or introduction. A silent diversity reservoir of *C diphtheriae* might persist despite vaccination, because vaccination is designed to protect against disease expression rather than colonisation and transmission. Antimicrobial resistance is rare in *C diphtheriae*,²⁹ and our results show that the main recommended agents (penicillin G, aminopenicillin, and erythromycin) are active against *C diphtheriae* isolates circulating in Yemen. However, antimicrobial susceptibility profiles were heterogeneous, with a strong phylogenetic sublineage effect, and a possible selection effect by previous antibiotic therapy.

Our work also uncovers a large heterogeneity in virulence-associated genomic features among circulating isolates. The diphtheria toxin-encoding gene was observed in most isolates. However, four isolates were *tox*-negative, indicating that such isolates can cause diphtheria-like respiratory symptoms. Currently, with the important exception of diphtheria toxin, the links between virulence genes of *C diphtheriae* strains and clinical expression are unknown.³⁰ Biovar *gravis* isolates have been considered

more virulent than biovar *mitis* isolates.³¹ Our genomic data suggest that inter-lineage heterogeneity in iron acquisition, adhesion, and colonisation capacities could underlie epidemiological or clinical differences. We found that patients infected with sublineage A tended to be younger and with more frequent neck swelling. However, because neck swelling is more commonly observed in young patients, we cannot separate sublineage and age effects here. The underlying mechanisms of lymph node manifestations in diphtheria, described as non-specific acute lymphadenitis,² are unknown. Future studies should investigate the effects of the genomic diversity of *C diphtheriae* on pathogenicity (including potential toxin expression level variation among sublineages) and clinical expression of diphtheria. The accessory genes that are unique for specific sublineages represent potential diagnostic biomarkers that could facilitate future genotype–phenotype relationship studies.

Genomic sequencing of bacterial pathogens is a powerful approach to define relationships across time, sources, and geography.¹⁴ Migration and trade from the horn of Africa into Yemen are major drivers of pathogenic strain spread, as observed for cholera.¹⁴ Here, two closely related *C diphtheriae* from Eritrea and Saudi Arabia were identified, and cross-governorate spread was also noted. A more systematic application of genomic sequencing would allow the geographical dynamics of *C diphtheriae* to be defined.

The estimated evolutionary rate of *C diphtheriae* is slightly faster than previous estimates⁴⁵ and implies that the diversification of the major Yemen outbreak sublineage largely predates the detection of the outbreak by the disease surveillance system. We note that our rate and age estimates have large confidence intervals, which is explained by the short time period and low number of available genomes.

Although we provide some insights into the microbiological characteristics of diphtheria in Yemen, the available samples of *C diphtheriae* sent for biological confirmation do not yet provide a complete picture of the outbreak. Samples referred to NCPHL were distributed across a large time period but governorates in southern Yemen were largely under-represented, because 91% of confirmed samples came from northern governorates (appendix 2 pp 13–14). This limitation reflects the current situation in Yemen, divided by conflict between the north and south. Laboratory work in Yemen yielded a low rate of biological confirmation (41%), which we attribute to operational and technical difficulties in doing microbiological analyses, including suboptimal transport and culture medium storage conditions. The high rate of antibiotic usage (penicillin or macrolides) before throat sampling could also have been a contributing factor. In addition, approximately half of the positive samples sent to Institut Pasteur were subsequently found to be negative. A likely reason is inappropriate culture conservation, because frozen storage could not be maintained due to

episodic electricity supply shortages. No check of identification was made upon subculture before shipment to Institut Pasteur, where many PCR-positive cultures were highly contaminated.

In summary, this work provides insight into the epidemiological and clinical aspects of the current Yemen diphtheria outbreak, and shows high phylogenetic, genomic, and phenotypic variation of *C diphtheriae*. Real-time characterisation of isolates at the level of individual patients could therefore be relevant for clinical management and to define strategies of vaccination catch-up or transmission tracing during diphtheria outbreaks. As such, laboratory capacity needs to be reinforced. Diphtheria is a largely forgotten disease, and present-day research into its pathophysiology is scarce. Furthermore, in the context of increasing disruption to vaccination campaigns and shortages of diphtheria antitoxin, studies into the determinants of local persistence of *C diphtheriae* and its spread at regional or global scales are needed to better control the re-emergence of this harmful pathogen.

Contributors

AA, AC-L, EB, MP-P, ML, and the NCPHL diphtheria outbreak working group were responsible for the microbiological cultures of the isolates and their biochemical and molecular characterisations. FD, GD, NL, KAAA, and HS collated and analysed the epidemiological data. AA, GD, and JT collated and analysed the clinical data. AC, VB, MH, JG, NZ, and SB analysed the genomic data. HM provided the DIFT045 strain. SB and GD designed and coordinated the project. SB designed the microbiological aspects of the study and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. AA, AC, NL, HS, JT, FD, GD, and SB had access to and verified all of the data. All authors provided input to the manuscript, reviewed the final version, and had final responsibility for the decision to submit for publication.

NCPHL diphtheria outbreak working group

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Declaration of interests

We declare no competing interests.

Data sharing

The whole-genome sequencing data generated in this study were deposited in the European Nucleotide Archive database and are accessible through project number PRJEB34206. Raw read data are available under the accession numbers ERR4332853 to ERR4332896. Contig sequences are available under the accession numbers CAJDXH01000000 to CAJDYY01000000.

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For data from this study see <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena>

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CHAPITRE 7 : Étude du SL453 de *C. diphtheriae*

Titre de l'article

Multidrug Resistant Toxigenic *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* sublineage 40 with two novel resistance genomic islands

Résumé

La thérapie antimicrobienne est importante pour la gestion des cas de diphtérie, mais les connaissances sur l'émergence de la multirésistance chez *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* sont rares. Nous rapportons les caractéristiques génomiques de deux isolats toxigènes multirésistants prélevés en France à trois ans d'intervalle.

Les deux isolats étaient résistants à la spiramycine, la clindamycine, la tétracycline, la kanamycine et le triméthoprime-sulfaméthoxazole. Les gènes *ermX*, *cmx*, *aph(3'')-Ib*, *aph(6)-Id*, *aph(3')-Ic*, *aadA1*, *dfrA15*, *sul1*, *cmlA*, *cmlR* et *tet(33)* étaient regroupés dans deux îlots génomiques, l'un constitué de deux transposons et d'un intégron, l'autre étant flanqué de deux séquences d'insertion IS6100. Un isolat présentait en outre des mutations dans *gyrA* et *rpoB* et était résistants à la ciprofloxacine et à la rifampicine. Les deux isolats appartenaient à la sous-lignée 453 (SL453), ainsi que 25 isolats provenant de 11 autres pays (<https://bigsd.b.pasteur.fr/diphtheriae>).

La SL453 est une sous-lignée toxigène cosmopolite de *C. diphtheriae*, dont un sous-ensemble a acquis une multirésistance aux médicaments. La surveillance de la diphtérie doit tenir compte du risque de dissémination des souches multirésistantes et de leurs éléments génétiques.

Contributions personnelles

- Aide aux analyses génomiques : recherche des gènes de résistance et virulence
- Mise à disposition des nouveaux génomes en base publique

1 **Multidrug Resistant Toxigenic *Corynebacterium diphtheriae***
2 **sublineage 453 with two novel resistance genomic islands**

3

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19

20 **Article Summary Line:** *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* SL453 is a cosmopolitan toxigenic
21 sublineage that has acquired two multidrug resistance genomic islands.

22

23 **Running title:** *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* sublineage 40

24

25 **Keywords:** *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*, diphtheria, toxigenic strains, multidrug-resistance,
26 phylogeography, genomic epidemiology

27

28 **Repositories:** All sequencing data were deposited at ENA and are available within Bioproject
29 PRJEB22103, under biosamples SAMEA6566531 (FRC0137) and SAMEA104208685
30 (FRC0375).

31

Abstract

32 Antimicrobial therapy is important for case management of diphtheria, but knowledge on the
33 emergence of multidrug-resistance in *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* is scarce. We report on the
34 genomic features of two multidrug-resistant toxigenic isolates sampled in France three years apart.

35 Both isolates were resistant to spiramycin, clindamycin, tetracycline, kanamycin and
36 trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole. Genes *ermX*, *cmx*, *aph(3'')-Ib*, *aph(6)-Id*, *aph(3')-Ic*, *aadA1*,
37 *dfrA15*, *sul1*, *cmlA*, *cmlR* and *tet(33)* were clustered in two genomic islands, one consisting of two
38 transposons and one integron, the other being flanked by two IS6100 insertion sequences. One
39 isolate additionally presented mutations in *gyrA* and *rpoB* and was resistant to ciprofloxacin and
40 rifampicin. Both isolates belonged to sublineage 40 (SL453), together with 25 isolates from 11
41 other countries (<https://bigsd.b.pasteur.fr/diphtheriae>).

42 SL453 is a cosmopolitan toxigenic sublineage of *C. diphtheriae*, a subset of which acquired
43 multidrug resistance. Surveillance of diphtheria should consider the risk of dissemination of
44 multidrug resistant strains and their genetic elements.

45

Impact statement

46 The genetic elements that carry antimicrobial resistance genes in *Corynebacterium*
47 *diphtheriae* are not well documented and, until now, phylogenetic sublineages of toxigenic strains
48 are considered as being geographically restricted.

49 In this study we uncovered the existence of a cosmopolitan toxigenic sublineage, a subset of
50 which presented multiple antimicrobial resistance genes clustered in two genomic islands. This
51 work contributes to a better understanding of the dynamics which underlie the spread of
52 antimicrobial resistance in toxigenic *C. diphtheriae*.

Introduction

54 Toxigenic *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* is responsible for diphtheria, a potentially severe
55 infection of the upper respiratory tract that may include sore throat, neck swelling and distant
56 toxic signs. The pathognomonic symptom is the presence of a pseudomembrane, which adheres
57 on the tonsils, oropharynx and pharynx. If untreated, the disease can potentially cause death from
58 suffocation or due to distal toxic damage (Sharma et al., 2019).

59 The incidence of diphtheria has dropped significantly following the Global immunization
60 initiative (Galazka, 2000). Nevertheless, outbreaks of diphtheria can still occur when vaccination of
61 populations is sub-optimal, as observed in the ex-Soviet Union countries in the 1990s (Vitek, 1998)
62 and more recently in the Rohingya (Matsuyama et al., 2018; Rahman and Islam, 2019) and
63 Yemenite populations (Badell et al., 2021).

64 Diphtheria therapy may include the timely administration of diphtheria anti-toxin (DAT), but
65 this product is in short supply (Wagner et al., 2009). Antimicrobial treatment is central in clinical
66 case management and for contacts prophylaxis, and typically comprises oral or parenteral penicillin,
67 amoxicillin or erythromycin. Even though antimicrobial resistance is more frequent in some other
68 *Corynebacterium* species (Sharma et al., 2019), *C. diphtheriae* isolates with reduced susceptibility
69 towards penicillin, cefotaxime and erythromycin as well as tetracycline, sulphonamide or other
70 agents have been reported (Benamrouche et al., 2016; Galazka, 2000; Hennart et al., 2020; Husada et al.,
71 2019).

72 Yet, knowledge on the epidemiological links and dissemination of resistant *C. diphtheriae* is
73 scarce. *C. diphtheriae* is phylogenetically structured into multiple sublineages, and most of them
74 currently appear geographically restricted (Badell et al., 2021; Guglielmini et al., 2021; Will et al.,
75 2021). However, rather than true endemism, this may reflect both under-sampling and the lack of
76 systematic genomic sequencing in microbiology laboratories. There are also large gaps in the
77 understanding of the genomic mechanisms underlying antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in this
78 species, and the physical organization of AMR genes within *C. diphtheriae* genomes is largely
79 unknown except for early work on a few strains, *e.g.* (Barraud et al., n.d.). Some recent studies have
80 reported the presence of transposons (Forde et al., 2021) or of a plasmid (Hennart et al., 2020)
81 carrying a *pbp2m* transfer unit, sometimes associated with the *ermX* methyltransferase gene. Other
82 members of the *Corynebacterium* genus harbour transposons, insertion sequences and plasmids that
83 carry AMR genes (Leyton et al., 2021; Tauch et al., 1998, 1995).

84 In a previous study of the population structure and antimicrobial resistance phenotypes of a
85 large collection of *C. diphtheriae* (Hennart et al., 2020), several multidrug-resistant (MDR) isolates
86 were observed; MDR was defined as resistance to antimicrobial agents belonging to three or more
87 categories – excluding fosfomycin to which all *Corynebacterium* are resistant (Soriano et al., 1995).
88 Here, we investigate further two MDR isolates, FRC0137 and FRC0375. After long-read

89 sequencing and genome sequence completion, a focus was put on the genomic context of their
90 resistance elements. Furthermore, we aimed to place the two isolates in their evolutionary context
91 by analysing publicly available genomes that belong to the same *C. diphtheriae* sublineage (SL),
92 SL453.

Materials and Methods

94 Isolates FRC0137 and FRC0375 were sampled in 2012 and 2015, respectively. The
95 identification took place at the National Reference Center for Corynebacteria of the *diphtheriae*
96 complex (NRC-CCD) as previously described (Hennart et al., 2020) using Polymerase Chain
97 Reaction (PCR) assays and Matrix Assisted Laser Desorption-Ionization Time-Of-Flight (MALDI-
98 TOF) mass spectrometry (Bruker). The presence of the diphtheria toxin *tox* gene was determined by
99 PCR (9) and confirmed by blastN of the DIP_RS12515 reference *tox* gene on the genomic
100 sequences and a more recent real-time PCR assay (Badell et al., 2019). The production of the toxin
101 was assessed using the modified Elek test (Engler et al., 1997).

102 In addition, the isolates were characterized biochemically for pyrazinamidase, urease, nitrate
103 reductase, for utilization of maltose and for glycogen fermentation. This allowed determining their
104 biovar, based on the combination of nitrate reductase (positive in Mitis and Gravis, negative in
105 Belfanti) and glycogen fermentation (positive in biovar Gravis only).

106 Phenotypic susceptibility to antimicrobial agents was tested by disk diffusion (BioRad,
107 Marnes-la-Coquette, France) for the antibiotics listed in **Table 1**. When possible, the results were
108 interpreted according to CA-SFM/EUCAST V.1.0 (January 2019) (“The European Committee on
109 Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing. Breakpoint tables for interpretation of MICs and zone
110 diameters. Version 9.0, 2019. <http://www.eucast.org>,” n.d.). In other cases, the interpretative criteria
111 published in Table III of the CA-SFM 2013 recommendations (“[https://www.sfm-](https://www.sfm-microbiologie.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/CASFM_2013.pdf)
112 [microbiologie.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/CASFM_2013.pdf](https://www.sfm-microbiologie.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/CASFM_2013.pdf),” n.d.) were applied.

113 The strains were previously (Hennart et al., 2020) sequenced with a NextSeq-500 instrument
114 (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA) at a minimum of 50× coverage depth; trimming was performed
115 using AlienTrimmer v0.4.0 (Criscuolo and Brisse, 2013), redundant or over-represented reads were
116 reduced using the khmer software v1.3 (Crusoe et al., 2015), sequencing errors were corrected using
117 Musket v1.1(Liu et al., 2013) and a *de novo* assembly was performed for each strain using SPAdes
118 v3.12.0 (Bankevich et al., 2012). The quality of the assembly generated by SPAdes was assessed
119 using BUSCO (Simão et al., 2015). Here, the two isolates were also subjected to Oxford Nanopore
120 Technologies (ONT) sequencing, for which genomic DNA was extracted using a phenol-chloroform
121 approach. Libraries were prepared using a 1D ligation sequencing kit (SQK-LSK-108) without
122 fragmentation and sequenced using a MinION FLO-MIN-106 flow cell.

123 ONT and Illumina short reads were combined to generate a hybrid assembly using
124 Unicycler v0.4.4 (Wick et al., 2017) (normal assembly mode, default parameters).

125 Genome annotation was performed using RAST (Aziz et al., 2008). The genomes were
126 screened for resistance and plasmid replicon genes using the ResFinder 4.1 (Bortolaia et al., 2020)
127 and PlasmidFinder 2.1 (Carattoli et al., 2014) online tools at the <https://cge.cbs.dtu.dk/services/>
128 website. Synteny between the resistance regions of the FRC0137 isolate and homologous regions

129 from other genomes was analysed by mapping blastN alignments with the Circos visualization tool
130 (Krzywinski et al., 2009). A Neighbor-Joining tree was generated based on the concatenated
131 nucleotide sequences of the 1,305 genes of the cgMLST scheme (Guglielmini et al., 2021) of SL453
132 isolates using the <https://bigsd.bpasteur.fr/diphtheria/> platform, and the tree was visualized using
133 iTOL (Letunic and Bork, 2019).

135 Characteristics of the isolates and description of resistance genomic islands RGI-I and RGI-II

136 Isolates FRC0137 and FRC0375 were sampled from wound infections of two patients living in
137 a single mainland France city of about 35,000 inhabitants. Strain FRC0137 was isolated in 2012
138 from a foot abscess in a patient with a recent hospitalization in Pakistan. The wound was first
139 treated by administration of amoxicillin-clavulanic acid for 7 days, and later on with vancomycin
140 and ceftriaxone, which was followed by the resolution of the wound infection. Isolate FRC0375 was
141 isolated in 2015 from an ankle ulceration in a patient who had also travelled to Pakistan but no
142 earlier than 10 years before the isolation of the strain; in this case the infection was treated with an
143 undefined macrolide and no further details on the outcome were available.

144 Phenotypic characterization showed that both isolates belonged to biovar Mitis (nitrate
145 positive, glycogen negative) and produced the diphtheria toxin, as determined by Elek's test.
146 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing showed that both isolates were resistant to clindamycin,
147 spiramycin, kanamycin, tetracycline and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole; furthermore, FRC0137
148 was resistant to azithromycin, rifampicin and ciprofloxacin (**Table 1**). Both isolates were
149 susceptible to erythromycin and clarithromycin even though they harboured the *ermX* gene (see
150 below). They also appeared penicillin-resistant, as do most *C. diphtheriae* using the currently
151 proposed breakpoint (Hennart et al., 2020).

152 High-quality genome assemblies of FRC0137 and FRC0375 were obtained, with a size of
153 2,549,354 bp and of 2,613,747 bp, and G+C% content of 53.63% and 53.62%, respectively. The
154 FRC0137 genome was assembled into two contigs whereas the genome sequence of FRC0375 was
155 fully circularized. No plasmid was identified. Sequence analysis confirmed the biochemical
156 characterization of toxigenicity and biovar: the two isolates carried an identical, non-disrupted copy
157 of the *tox* gene (allele 2 in the BIGSdb database, <https://bigsd.bpasteur.fr/diphtheria>) and were
158 negative for the Gravis biovar-associated *spuA* gene region (Hennart et al., 2020; Santos et al.,
159 2018).

160 The genomes of both isolates carried twelve antimicrobial resistance genes, which we found
161 were grouped on two antimicrobial resistance islands. The first one, herein named *Cd*-RGI-I, had a
162 length of 20,769 bp in strain FRC0137 (**Figure 1A**) and of 19,328 bp in strain FRC0375. The
163 difference in size is due to the loss of the remnants of an *ISCx1* in the latter isolate. The second
164 resistance island was named *Cd*-RGI-II was of size 8,570 bp in both strains (**Figure 1B**). *Cd*-RGI-I
165 contained nine antimicrobial resistance genes, plus a GCN5-related N-acetyltransferase family
166 (GNAT) gene and a truncated version of the *qacE* gene. This resistance island may be divided into
167 three distinct elements (**Figure 1A**). The first element corresponds to the transposon Tn5432, which
168 is composed by two IS1249 genes belonging to the IS256 family, and the macrolide resistance gene
169 *ermX* as well as *ISCx1*. The latter, absent in the FRC0375 strain, may be considered as a genomic

170 scar, since it is prematurely interrupted by a stop codon (Leyton et al., 2021). Transposon Tn5432
171 has already been described in other *Corynebacterium species* with some variation (15,17).

172 The second element composing this resistance island is transposon Tn5564, which is
173 bounded by an IS5564. It comprises the *cmx* gene coding for a chloramphenicol efflux pump, and
174 an IS6 family member IS1628 gene. Tn5564 also includes the *aph(3'')-Ib* and *aph(6)-Id* (formerly
175 known as *strA* and *strB*) streptomycin resistance genes and the *aph(3')-Ic* aminoglycoside
176 phosphotransferase, which was potentially imported with Tn5564 (Leyton et al., 2021; Tauch et al.,
177 1995).

178 The third element of *Cd*-RGI-I is composed by an integron flanked by two insertion
179 sequences (IS6100 and IS1628), and comprises four gene cassettes corresponding to AMR genes
180 (*dfxA15*, *cmlA*, *aadA1* and *sulI*), *ΔqacE* and a GNAT gene. Hence, this element may underlie the
181 resistance to trimethoprim, sulfamethoxazole, chloramphenicol and aminoglycosides (*aadI*:
182 streptomycin and spectinomycin). It was not possible to trace back this integron to any previously
183 described *Corynebacterium* or Actinobacteria (GenBank database, last accessed date December 7th
184 2021). Rather, it may come from Gram-negative species, given that the best sequence matches
185 (maximum 82% coverage and 99% identity) were observed with Gamma-proteobacteria such as
186 *Escherichia coli* (LT985260.1), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (CP030270.1, KX029332.1) and
187 *Acinetobacter species* (CP046045.1, CP046596.1). In *Cd*-RGI-I, transposon Tn5432 might have
188 been the first element to integrate into the chromosome of an ancestral *C. diphtheriae*, and may then
189 have served as a “hotspot” for the integration of the two other elements present in the region, as
190 already proposed (Nudel et al., 2018).

191 The second resistance island (*Cd*-RGI-II) is flanked by two IS6100 insertion sequences and
192 may thus correspond to a transposon; it was identical (100% identity, 100% length coverage) in
193 both isolates. It carries a recombinase gene followed by the *sulI* gene in a tail-to-tail configuration,
194 by a deleted IS481, and by two other AMR genes: *cmlR* and *tet(33)*, potentially contributing to the
195 observed resistance to chloramphenicol and tetracycline (**Figure 1B**). We found that this island is
196 present with the same composition but in a different genomic context in a phylogenetically distant
197 (1,050 different cgMLST alleles out of 1,305 gene loci) *tox*-positive *C. diphtheriae* isolate
198 CIP107572, which belongs to MLST sequence type ST258 and was isolated in Thailand in 1994
199 (Grimont et al., 2004; Hennart et al., 2020; Paveenkittiporn et al., 2019).

200 FRC0137 differed from FRC0375 by being resistant to two additional antimicrobial agents:
201 rifampicin and ciprofloxacin. Consistently, in FRC0137 mutations in the genes encoding for the β-
202 subunit of the RNA polymerase (*rpoB*) and for the gyrase subunit A (*gyrA*) were observed.
203 FRC0137 displayed a deduced S444F alteration of the RpoB protein, previously described in a
204 rifampicin-resistant *Corynebacterium urealyticum* (Chapartegui-González et al., 2020). However,
205 this specific mutation did not affect the *rpoB* MLST allele, as it lied outside of the *rpoB* region used

206 in MLST; three additional, synonymous changes were observed within the *rpoB* MLST template,
207 leading to allele rpoB-13 (ST136) compared to FRC0375 *rpoB* sequence (allele 2, ST389).

208 The amino acid alterations S90F and D94Y deduced from the *gyrA* gene sequence probably
209 underlie the observed ciprofloxacin resistance in FRC0137. *C. urealyticum* isolates displaying S90V
210 and D94Y amino-acid substitutions were also resistant to quinolones (38), and both phenylalanine
211 and valine have a hydrophobic side chain known to favour the disruption of the water–metal ion
212 bridge (Aldred et al., 2014).

213

214 **Evolution within sublineage 40**

215 To understand the evolutionary origins of multidrug resistance in these isolates, we
216 performed a comparative genomic analysis. According to cgMLST (Guglielmini et al., 2021), they
217 differed by 131 loci, and thus belong to the same sublineage, SL453 (Guglielmini et al., 2021). We
218 found that 25 publicly available genomes also belonged to SL453. These were sampled from 1963
219 to 2016, 9 of them from Malaysia (Ahmad et al., 2017), 2 from France (Dazas et al., 2018; Hennart
220 et al., 2020), 5 from Belarus (Grosse-Kock et al., 2017), 2 from Spain (Hoefler et al., 2021) and 1
221 each from Australia, Guatemala, India, Romania, Russia, Thailand and USA (**Figure 2B**). One
222 isolate had an unknown provenance.

223 We defined two branches within SL453 based on its phylogenetic structure (**Figure 2**). Most
224 SL453 isolates (24/27) carried the *tox* gene even though 9 isolates of branch 2, associated with the
225 1990s outbreak in Belarus (**Figure 2**), were defined as non-toxigenic toxin-bearing (NTTB) isolates
226 as deduced from *tox* gene disruption and as previously reported for some of them (Grosse-Kock et
227 al., 2017). Only 3 isolates of branch 2 harboured an intact copy of the *tox* gene, and three did not
228 carry it. Branch 1 isolates were all hypothesized as being toxigenic, based on their complete *tox*
229 gene, and had diverse geographical and temporal origins: the older isolate was from Thailand, 1996,
230 while 8 isolates were from a 2016 outbreak in Malaysia. The three other branch 1 isolates were
231 from Europe, including FRC0137, FRC0375 and isolate CS1 from Spain. CS1 was isolated from a
232 young patient having a travel history in Afghanistan (Hoefler et al., 2021) and belonged to the same
233 outbreak cluster (*i.e.*, less than 25 allelic mismatches (Guglielmini et al., 2021) as FRC0375. Thus,
234 the latter isolate from France is genetically closer from isolate CS1 from Spain, than from
235 FRC0137. Notably, isolate CS1 lacks the *Cd*-RGI-II resistance island, suggesting an initial
236 acquisition of this island in the ancestor of the three isolates, followed by its loss in the isolate from
237 Spain.

Discussion

239 Toxigenic *C. diphtheriae* outbreaks have been reported in recent years (Badell et al., 2021;
240 Lodeiro-Colatosti et al., 2018; Mahomed et al., 2017; Rahman and Islam, 2019; Strauss et al., 2021), and
241 occurred in countries with disrupted healthcare services, which do not achieve high vaccination
242 coverage (Sharma et al., 2019). Antimicrobial treatment is an important addition to diphtheria
243 antitoxin treatment, which is often unavailable and only targets the toxin effects. Therefore,
244 antimicrobial resistance in toxigenic strains is a matter of public health concern.

245 Here we analyzed two MDR toxigenic isolates and discovered two genomic islands that
246 together carry 12 resistance genes and which were previously unreported in *C. diphtheriae*, to our
247 knowledge. Even though most of the resistance genes they carried, except for *ermX*, may confer
248 resistance to antimicrobial agents that are not recommended as first line in the treatment of
249 *C. diphtheriae* infection or colonization, the resistance profile of these two isolates has public health
250 relevance. First, these genomic regions may in the future aggregate more AMR genes and
251 disseminate them to other sublineages of *C. diphtheriae* or other *Corynebacterium* species. Second,
252 these resistance genes may serve as markers for the yet untraced spread of MDR toxigenic
253 *C. diphtheriae*. The fact that the resistance islands carry genes that confer resistance to agents that
254 are not used against diphtheria, highlights the risk of long-term maintenance of resistance genes,
255 either in the absence of antimicrobial selective pressure, or due to bystander selection of resistance
256 in *C. diphtheriae* through exposure to antibiotics used to treat other infections (Tedijanto et al.,
257 2018).

258 The international spread of SL453 isolates and the evolutionary pattern of the RGI-I and
259 RGI-II provide clues as to the scenario of their dissemination. The two isolates from France, and the
260 one from Spain, could be linked to Pakistan and Afghanistan, respectively. The acquisition of the
261 resistance islands Cd-RGI-I and Cd-RGI-II might have occurred in South Asia. In fact, many MDR
262 isolates previously described in *C. diphtheriae* were linked to this region (Husada et al., 2019; Will
263 et al., 2021). Acquisition of the RGIs in SL453 must have occurred after the evolutionary split from
264 the lineage leading to the Malaysian outbreak strain, which does not carry them. We hypothesize
265 that the common ancestor of the three RGI-I carrying isolates had acquired the two RGIs, with
266 subsequent loss of RGI-II in the branch leading to isolate CS1. The three isolates have unexpected
267 genetic relationships, with a close genetic identity of isolate CS1 with isolate FRC0137, which was
268 isolated from a patient in the same French city as FRC0375. The lack of fit observed in this case
269 between epidemiology and genomics illustrates the value of genomic epidemiology and underlines
270 the need to improve the rate of *C. diphtheriae* infection reporting and microbiological
271 characterization to better trace the links between sporadic infections.

272 Another isolate belonging to SL453, of ST136 (the same ST as FRC0137), was described in
273 Canada in 2011, from a patient who returned from India with a toe infection (Mina et al., 2011); and

274 the antimicrobial susceptibility pattern of this isolate was similar to that of FRC0375. No other
275 ST136 isolate was reported from India or elsewhere (Will et al., 2021).

276 The FRC0137 isolate, isolated 3 years before the FRC0375 one, displayed a mutated *gyrA*,
277 indicating that evolution towards quinolone resistance happened in the branch leading to FRC0137,
278 potentially under quinolone selective pressure in Asia (Lundborg and Tamhankar, 2017; Sierra et
279 al., 2005). Microevolution of *Corynebacterium* quinolone resistance in defined epidemiological
280 contexts has been observed previously (Badell et al., 2021), underlying the high risk of emergence
281 of resistance to this antimicrobial class during treatment in *C. diphtheriae* and other
282 *Corynebacterium* species.

283 A previous study has shown that most sublineages harbouring the *tox* gene have a limited
284 geographical distribution (Hennart et al., 2020). Our study, instead, uncovers the existence of a
285 cosmopolitan toxigenic MDR clone. We concur with previous statements (Guglielmini et al., 2021;
286 Will et al., 2021) that *C. diphtheriae* is currently sampled at a largely insufficient rate to decipher its
287 geographical spread with confidence, and it is to be expected that, as *C. diphtheriae* genomic
288 epidemiology develops, more sublineages with broad spatial distribution will be described.
289 Genomic surveillance of *C. diphtheriae* should be strengthened globally, in order to monitor the
290 spread of sublineages of particular concern such as the MDR toxigenic SL453.

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303

304 **Authors license statement**

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307

308 **Declaration of interest statement**

309 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

310

311 **Ethical approval statement**

312 To conduct the research, we used bacterial strains, which are not considered human samples.
313 Accordingly, this research was not considered human research and is out of the scope of the decree
314 n° 2016-1537 of November 16, 2016 implementing law n° 2012-300 of March 5, 2012 on research
315 involving human subjects. Therefore, no ethics approval was needed and no informed consent was
316 required. All French bacteriological samples were collected in the frame of the French national
317 diphtheria surveillance and are collected, coded, shipped, managed and analyzed according to the
318 French National Reference Center protocols that received approval by French competent body
319 CNIL (Commission Nationale Informatique et Libertés; approval number: 1474671). The research
320 conformed to the principles of the Helsinki Declaration.

321

322 **Author contributions**

323 SB designed and coordinated the study. GA and MH performed the genomic analyses. EB
324 performed the microbiological characterization of the *C. diphtheriae* isolates. SB and GA wrote the
325 manuscript. All authors provided comments and approved the final manuscript version.

326 **Figure 1. Schematic representation of the *Cd*-RGI-I and *Cd*-RGI-II resistance islands**

327 **Panel A.** The upper part represents a map of the approximately 20 kbp which make up *Cd*-
328 RGI-I of the FRC0137 isolate. Arrows indicate the genes and are colour coded as follows: red for
329 antimicrobial resistance genes, yellow for ISs, green for integrase genes and purple for
330 miscellaneous genes. Colored horizontal bars below the genes indicate the several parts that
331 compose the resistance genomic island: blue, the fragmented Tn5432; orange, Tn5564; and green,
332 the integron.

333 In the lower part, the synteny with several other isolates retrieved from the GenBank database
334 is shown. Genes are colour-coded as in panel A. Specifically, the Tn5432 alignment with a
335 *Corynebacterium striatum* isolate is depicted in blue; the Tn5564 alignment with a
336 *Corynebacterium singulare* is depicted in orange and the one with *Corynebacterium imitans* in
337 yellow. The integron alignments region are drawn in green with the IncHI1B plasmid of *Klebsiella*
338 *pneumoniae* and in aquamarine with the chromosome of *Acinetobacter towneri*.

339 **Panel B.** The upper part represents a map of the approximately 10 kbp, which makes up the
340 *Cd*-RGI-II of isolate FRC0137. Arrows indicate the genes and are colour coded as in panel A.

341 In the lower part, is shown a synteny plot with *C. diphtheriae* CIP107572 isolated from
342 Thailand in 1994. Beyond the loss of a small portion of the recombinase gene in FRC0137, these
343 two islands have 100% sequence identity. Note that the genomic context in which the islands are
344 located is different, indicating the horizontal transfer of the island.

345

346 **Figure 2: Phylogeny of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* sublineage 40, and distribution of isolates**
347 **features**

348 **Panel A.** Midpoint-rooted neighbour-Joining tree based on the concatenated nucleotide
349 sequences of the 1,305 genes of the cgMLST scheme of *C. diphtheriae*. Nodes are colour-coded as
350 follows: Empty stars indicate the absence of the *tox* gene, orange stars indicate Non-Toxigenic
351 Toxin Bearing (NTTB) isolates, and red stars indicate *tox* positive, toxigenic isolates. Other data are
352 colour-coded according to the keys or, for resistance genes: empty squares indicate the absence of
353 the gene, filled squares indicate the presence of the gene, and a darker colour indicates isolates
354 harbouring two copies of the specific gene (*sulI* in this case). The scale indicates the number of
355 nucleotide substitutions per site.

356 **Panel B.** World map download from <https://simplemaps.com/resources/svg-world> displaying
357 the country of origin of SL453 isolates. The image was edited using the OpenSource InkScape
358 software.

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Figure 1

Figure 2

Table 1. Antimicrobial resistance phenotypes and genotypes of isolates FRC0137 and FRC0375

Antibiotic class	Antimicrobial agent	Diameter (mm) of FRC0137	Diameter (mm) of FRC0375	Breakpoint	Resistance element (FRC0137)	Resistance element (FRC0375)
β lactams	Penicillin (1 UI)	27	32	29	None detected	None detected
	Amoxicillin	46	35	23	None detected	None detected
	Oxacillin	30	26	20	None detected	None detected
	Cefotaxime	37	28	26	None detected	None detected
	Imipenem	57	44	24	None detected	None detected
Macrolides	Erythromycin	32	31	22	<i>ermX</i>	<i>ermX</i>
	Clarithromycin	42	33	22	<i>ermX</i>	<i>ermX</i>
	Azithromycin	21	27	22	<i>ermX</i>	<i>ermX</i>
	Spiramycin	22	11	24	<i>ermX</i>	<i>ermX</i>
	Clindamycin	14	6	20	<i>ermX</i>	<i>ermX</i>
Lincosamides	Pristinamycin	42	40	22	None detected	None detected
	Kanamycin	6	6	17	<i>aph(3'')-Ib, aph(6)-Id, aadA1</i>	<i>aph(3'')-Ib, aph(6)-Id, aadA1</i>
Aminoglycosides	Gentamicin	31	27	23	None detected	None detected
	Rifampicin	6	35	30	S444F in <i>rpoB</i> *	None detected
Tetracycline	Tetracycline	15	18	24	<i>tet(33)</i>	<i>tet(33)</i>
	Ciprofloxacin	7	33	25	S90F and D94Y in <i>gyrA</i> #	None detected
Folate pathway inhibitors	Sulfonamide	6	6	17	<i>sulI</i>	<i>sulI</i>
	Trimethoprim	6	6	16	<i>dfrA15</i>	<i>dfrA15</i>
	Trimethoprim-Sulfamethoxazole	6	6	19	<i>sulI, dfrA15</i>	<i>sulI, dfrA15</i>
Fosfomycin	Fosfomycin	6	6	14	Intrinsic resistance	Intrinsic resistance
Glycopeptide	Vancomycin	27	19	17	None detected	None detected
Oxazolidinone	Linezolid	34	35	25	None detected	None detected

* Same of *C. urealyticum* in Chapartegui-González2020_A

Same position, different substitutions compared with *C. urealyticum* in Chapartegui-González2020_A

CHAPITRE 8 : Épidémiologie génomique de *C. diphtheriae* en Nouvelle-Calédonie

Titre de l'article

Genomic epidemiology of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* in New Caledonia

Résumé

Un nombre croissant d'isolations de *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* a été observé ces dernières années dans l'archipel de Nouvelle-Calédonie. Nous avons voulu analyser les caractéristiques cliniques et microbiologiques des échantillons avec *C. diphtheriae*.

Tous les isolats de *C. diphtheriae* identifiés en Nouvelle-Calédonie de mai 2015 à mai 2019 ont été inclus. Pour chaque cas, une consultation rétrospective des dossiers des patients a été réalisée. Les phénotypes de sensibilité aux antimicrobiens, le gène *tox* et l'expression de la toxine diphtérique, le biovar et la séquence génomique ont été déterminés. Le typage des séquences multilocus du génome central (cgMLST), le MLST à 7 gènes et la recherche de gènes d'intérêt ont été réalisés à partir des assemblages génomiques.

58 isolats ont été inclus. L'âge médian des patients était de 28 ans. Près de neuf isolats sur dix provenaient de prélèvements cutanés, où *C. diphtheriae* était associé à *Staphylococcus aureus* et/ou *Streptococcus pyogenes* dans trois quarts des cas. Près de la moitié des cas provenaient de la ville principale, Nouméa (24%, 14/58) ou de l'île peu peuplée de Lifou (26%, 15/58). Les six cas *tox*-positifs sont survenus après un voyage sur l'île voisine de Vanuatu ; 5 de ces cas étaient liés et le cgMLST a confirmé une transmission récente. Deux cas d'endocardite chez de jeunes femmes ayant des antécédents de rhumatisme articulaire aigu ont impliqué des souches *tox*-négatives. Les 58 isolats étaient pour la plupart sensibles aux antibiotiques couramment utilisés. En particulier, aucun isolat n'était résistant aux molécules de première intention que sont l'amoxicilline et l'érythromycine. La résistance à la tétracycline a été trouvée dans un groupe génomique de 17 (29%) isolats, dont 16 portaient le gène *tetO*. Il y avait 13 sous-lignées cgMLST, dont la plupart ont également été observées dans le pays voisin, l'Australie.

Les infections cutanées peuvent abriter des isolats non toxigènes de *C. diphtheriae*, qui circulent en grande partie silencieusement dans des plaies non spécifiques. L'introduction possible de souches *tox*-positives à partir d'une île voisine montre que la surveillance de la diphtérie doit être maintenue en Nouvelle-Calédonie et que la vaccination dans les îles voisines doit être améliorée. Le séquençage génomique permet de découvrir comment les génotypes circulent localement et dans les pays voisins.

Contributions personnelles

- Réalisation de l'ensemble des analyses génomiques
- Réalisation des figures 1 et 2
- Réalisation des tableaux 1, S1 et S3
- Mise à disposition des nouveaux génomes en base publique
- Contribution à la rédaction du manuscrit

1 **Genomic epidemiology of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* in New Caledonia**

2

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28 **Keywords:** Diphtheria, *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*, epidemiology, New Caledonia, whole
29 genome sequencing

Abstract

30

31 Objectives

32 An increasing number of isolations of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* has been observed in the
33 recent years in the archipelago of New Caledonia. We aimed to analyze the clinical and
34 microbiological features of samples with *C. diphtheriae*.

35 Methods

36 All *C. diphtheriae* isolates identified in New Caledonia from May 2015 to May 2019 were
37 included. For each case, a retrospective consultation of the patient files was conducted.
38 Antimicrobial susceptibility phenotypes, *tox* gene and diphtheria toxin expression, biovar and
39 the genomic sequence were determined. Core genome multilocus sequence typing (cgMLST),
40 7-gene MLST and search of genes of interest were performed from genomic assemblies.

41 Results

42 58 isolates were included. The median age of patients was 28 years. Nearly nine in ten isolates
43 were from cutaneous samples, where *C. diphtheriae* was associated with *Staphylococcus aureus*
44 and/or *Streptococcus pyogenes* in three quarters of cases. Nearly half of cases came from the
45 main city, Nouméa (24%, 14/58) or the sparsely populated island of Lifou (26%, 15/58). The
46 six *tox*-positive cases occurred after a travel to the neighbor island of Vanuatu; 5 of these cases
47 were linked and cgMLST confirmed recent transmission. Two cases of endocarditis in young
48 female patients with a history of rheumatic fever involved *tox*-negative strains. The 58 isolates
49 were mostly susceptible to commonly used antibiotics. In particular, no isolate was resistant to
50 the first-line molecules amoxicillin or erythromycin. Resistance to tetracycline was found in a
51 genomic cluster of 17 (29%) isolates, 16 of which carried the *tetO* gene. There were 13 cgMLST
52 sublineages, most of which were also observed in the neighboring country Australia.

53 Conclusions

54 Cutaneous infections may harbor non-toxigenic *C. diphtheriae* isolates, which circulate largely
55 silently in non-specific wounds. The possible introduction of *tox*-positive strains from a
56 neighboring island illustrates that diphtheria surveillance should be maintained in New
57 Caledonia, and that immunization in neighboring islands must be improved. Genomic
58 sequencing uncovers how genotypes circulate locally and across neighboring countries.

59

60

61

Introduction

63 Once a major cause of child mortality, diphtheria has been largely controlled following
64 mass vaccination (WHO, 2018). However, 4000 to 8000 cases are reported each year worldwide
65 (Truelove et al., 2020; WHO, 2018). Large recent outbreaks have been linked to insufficient
66 local vaccination coverage rate following economic crises, political unrest and population
67 displacements (Blumberg et al., 2018; Polonsky et al., 2021; Badell et al., 2021). Classical
68 diphtheria is caused mainly by *C. diphtheriae*, which is transmitted among humans. The disease
69 has two main forms, pseudomembranous angina and cutaneous diphtheria. Other clinical
70 presentations include systemic syndromes caused by the action of diphtheria toxin, and
71 endocarditis by non-toxigenic isolates (Hadfield et al., 2000; Sharma et al., 2019). Only some
72 *C. diphtheriae* strains carry the *tox* gene, which codes for the diphtheria toxin. Although the
73 bacterium typically transmits through droplets in respiratory infections, transmission can also
74 occur through contact with infected or colonized skin lesions. Cutaneous diphtheria has become
75 more frequent than the classical respiratory form in developed countries, and probably plays an
76 important role during inter-epidemic periods in the tropics, where sporadic cases occur
77 frequently.

78 The spatial distribution, local spread and global dissemination of *C. diphtheriae* strains are
79 largely undocumented. Genomic sequencing used in the context of epidemiological
80 surveillance can help decipher the links between isolates and infer patterns of spread. So far,
81 apart from outbreak situations (du Plessis et al., 2017; Chorlton et al., 2019; Badell et al., 2021),
82 few genomic epidemiology studies of diphtheria have been performed (Grosse-Kock et al.,
83 2017; Dangel et al., 2018; Hennart et al., 2020; Schaeffer et al., 2020; Hoefler et al., 2020).

84 New Caledonia, an overseas collectivity of France, is located in the South Pacific region; it is
85 an island with tropical weather and a population of about 270 000 people (“Populations légales
86 des provinces de Nouvelle-Calédonie en 2019 – Populations légales de Nouvelle-Calédonie
87 en 2019 | Insee,” n.d.). This island system makes it an interesting case study to describe the
88 diversity of *C. diphtheriae* isolates and their spread within the island and large-scale
89 dissemination into or from it. Links with cases of diphtheria in neighboring countries such as
90 Indonesia (Arguni et al., 2021; Setiawaty et al., 2022) and Australia (May et al., 2014; Timms
91 et al., 2018) are unknown. Frequent travel between New Caledonia and mainland France may
92 be accompanied by *C. diphtheriae* dissemination (Hennart et al., 2020).

93 The aim of this study was to describe clinical, microbiological and genotypic characteristics of
94 *C. diphtheriae* strains isolated in New Caledonia during four years. We report on the clinical
95 presentations, geographical localization and microbiological features of 58 cases of infection

96 or carriage of *C. diphtheriae*, and compare the genotypes of isolates from New Caledonia
97 among themselves and with those from other world regions.

Material and methods

99 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

100 Local legislation obliges all laboratories of New Caledonia to report and send any isolated strain
101 of *C. diphtheriae* to the Centre Hospitalier Territorial (CHT) laboratory. Cases were defined as
102 an infection or carrier with an isolate identified as *C. diphtheriae*, as determined by MALDI-
103 TOF (Bruker). Inclusions began on the 1st May 2015 and stopped on May 30, 2019. We
104 included all episodes with *C. diphtheriae* isolated in culture (n=57). The cases correspond either
105 to *C. diphtheriae* isolated directly at the CHT Laboratory (n = 36), *i.e.*, isolated from a clinical
106 sample taken at the hospital, or from *C. diphtheriae* isolates sent to the CHT by other private
107 and public laboratories (in this study, two contributing laboratories) located in New Caledonia
108 (n = 21).

109 No clinical criteria for inclusion or exclusion were retained. In most cases (53/58), the
110 realization of bacteriological explorations was triggered by symptomatic manifestations. All
111 initial cases were investigated, leading to contacts sampling in five *tox*-positive cases, where
112 screening was performed by pharyngeal or skin lesion swabbing of contacts.

113 Six cases of diphtheria occurred in New Caledonia after a trip to Vanuatu, or following close
114 contact with a person returning from Vanuatu. These cases were investigated and contacts in
115 Vanuatu were screened, leading to identify one supplementary case, which was included in this
116 study. Hence, 58 cases were included in total.

117

118 Patient record and clinical data

119 For each patient at CHT, a search in the medical observations was carried out and relevant
120 information was compiled in **Table 1 (see also Table S1)**. For patients not recorded in the care
121 software or whose diphtheria episode was not registered, a manual search in the records was
122 carried out. For cases detected by the laboratories outside the CHT, the prescribers were
123 contacted in order to access the medical observations. As the two dispensaries on the island of
124 Lifou were the prescriber for a large number of cases, an on-site visit was organized and the
125 data was recovered by consulting their records. Finally, the data collected by the Direction of
126 Sanitary and Social Affairs (DASS) during each epidemiological investigation around a case,
127 were also used where necessary to supplement the initial medical data.

128

129 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing

130 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST) analyses were performed at the CHT laboratory after
131 subculture of the strain on blood agar and verification of the identification by MALDI-TOF
132 (Bruker). A 0.5 McFarland suspension was made in a saline solution (physiological serum),

133 following the recommendations of the Comité l'Antibiogramme de la Société Française de
134 Microbiologie (CASFM), 2019 version. For erythromycin, azithromycin and penicillin G at 10
135 UI, an additional dilution (1/10) was carried out as recommended by the CASFM, 2013 version.
136 The agar plates (Mueller-Hinton, BioMérieux) were inoculated by swabbing. After deposition
137 of antibiotic paper discs (BioRad) and E-test strips (BioMérieux), the plates were incubated 18
138 to 24 h at 35±2°C, under an atmosphere enriched with 5% CO₂. The reading was performed
139 manually, by the same operator, using a caliper. The names of antimicrobial agents, dosages,
140 incubation conditions and interpretation thresholds are given in **Table S2**.

141

142 **Diphtheria toxin gene presence (*tox* positivity) and toxin production (toxigenicity)**

143 All strains were tested for the presence of the *tox* gene at the CHT laboratory by real-time PCR,
144 using the primers and probe from Schuhegger *et al.* (Schuhegger *et al.*, 2008): Cdiph-RTDT_Fw
145 primer: 5'-TTA-TCA-AAA-GGT-TCG-GTG-ATG-GTG-3'; Cdiph-RTDT_rev2 primer: 5'-
146 AAT-CTC-AAG-TTC-TAC-GCT-TAA-C-3'; and Cdiph-RTDT_So probe: 6-FAM-5'CGC-
147 GTG-TAG-TGC-TCA-GCC-TTC-CCT-3'-TAMRA. Amplification conditions were modified
148 by using the Roche LightCycler 2.0 (LC 2.0) thermal cycler, with a denaturation step (10 min,
149 95°C) and 45 cycles of amplification: denaturation for 15 seconds at 95°C and
150 hybridization/elongation for 30 seconds at 60°C. For each assay, positive and negative controls
151 were used.

152 All isolates carrying the *tox* gene were tested at the national reference center at Institut Pasteur
153 for toxigenicity, using the modified Elek immuno-precipitation test (Engler *et al.*, 1997).

154

155 **Biovar determination**

156 Strains were characterized biochemically for pyrazinamidase, urease, and nitrate reductase and
157 for utilization of maltose and trehalose using API Coryne strips (BioMérieux, Marcy l'Etoile,
158 France) and the Rosco Diagnostica reagents (Eurobio, Les Ulis, France). The Hiss serum water
159 test was used for glycogen fermentation. The biovar of isolates was determined based on the
160 combination of nitrate reductase (positive in biovars Mitis and Gravis, negative in biovar
161 Belfanti) and glycogen fermentation (positive in biovar Gravis only).

162

163 **Genome sequencing and phylogenetic analyses**

164 The DNA preparation, sequencing and the *de novo* assembly follows the same protocol as the
165 previous studies (12, 22). The taxonomy of the isolates was confirmed by a MASH (v2.2)
166 genomic distance lower than 0.05 with *C. diphtheriae* type strain NCTC11397^T or *C. belfantii*
167 type strain FRC0043^T.

168 We built a core genome multiple sequence alignment (cg-MSA) from the assembled genome
169 sequences. For this, the genome sequences were annotated using PROKKA v1.14.5 (Seemann,
170 2014) with default parameters, resulting in GFF files. Panaroo v1.2.3 (“Producing polished
171 prokaryotic pangenomes with the Panaroo pipeline | Genome Biology | Full Text,” n.d.) was
172 used to define protein-coding gene clusters, with a threshold set at 80% amino acid identity,
173 then the protein-coding gene sequences of each locus were aligned using MAFFT v7.467
174 (Kato and Standley, 2013) with default parameters. Core genes were defined as being present
175 in 95% of genomes and were concatenated into a cg-MSA by Panaroo. IQtree version 2 (Minh
176 et al., 2020) with best-fit model GTR+F+R7 was used to build a tree.

177 We used AMRFinderPlus v3.10.20 to identify known resistance genes in *C. diphtheriae*
178 genomic sequences, based on the December 21, 2021 database and using the following
179 parameters to define presence of a gene: identity > 90% and length coverage > 50%. We used
180 BLASTN (identity > 90% and coverage > 50%) to search for the presence of the *tox* gene, *spuA*
181 gene (associated with biovar Gravis) and *narG* (associated with biovar Belfantii).

182 MLST and cgMLST genotypes were defined using the Institut Pasteur *C. diphtheriae* and
183 *C. ulcerans* database at <https://bigsdB.pasteur.fr/diphtheria>. We used a previously described
184 cgMLST scheme, database and associated classification schemes (Guglielmini et al., 2021) for
185 genomic clusters (25 mismatch threshold) and sublineages (500 mismatches). The isolates
186 provenance data and genome sequences were imported into a linked isolates database
187 ([https://bigsdB.pasteur.fr/cgi-](https://bigsdB.pasteur.fr/cgi-bin/bigsdB/bigsdB.pl?db=pubmlst_diphtheria_isolates&page=query)
188 [bin/bigsdB/bigsdB.pl?db=pubmlst_diphtheria_isolates&page=query](https://bigsdB.pasteur.fr/cgi-bin/bigsdB/bigsdB.pl?db=pubmlst_diphtheria_isolates&page=query)). A publicly available
189 BIGSdb project (i.e., a browsable list of isolates) entitled ‘New Caledonia 2015-2019 study’,
190 corresponding to the present dataset, was created to facilitate retrieval and analysis of the data.

Results

191

192 Demographic and clinical data

193 The demographic and clinical characteristics of the cases are presented in **Table 1**. 58
194 cases were included, with a sex ratio of 1.07 (30 men and 28 women). The median age of
195 subjects was 28; the youngest was 9 days old whereas the oldest was 78 years old. The
196 geographic distribution of cases (**Figure 1**) was uneven; the two districts with most cases were
197 Nouméa (14 cases, 24.1%) and Lifou island (15 cases, 25.9%).

198 A large majority of cases (51/58, 87.9%) corresponded to polymicrobial wounds or
199 abscesses, in association with *S. aureus* (35/58, 60.3%) and/or *S. pyogenes* (31/58, 53.4%);
200 more than three quarters of cases (45/58, 77.6%) were positive with either *S. aureus* or
201 *S. pyogenes*.

202 The remaining cases corresponded to: 1 urine, 2 throat samples, 1 implantable site, and
203 3 blood cultures; the latter isolates were found in pure culture. The urine sample was collected
204 to look for the origin of a fever, and the isolation of Cd was not associated with urinary
205 functional signs. Blood cultures confirmed an infective endocarditis in 2 cases, while the third
206 blood culture case was probably a cutaneous contamination.

207

208 Microbiological characteristics

209 The search of the *tox* gene by PCR showed that most isolates (52/58, 89.7%) were *tox*-
210 negative. The six *tox*-positive isolates corresponded to cases imported from Vanuatu. Elek's
211 toxigenicity test showed that 4 of these isolates expressed the toxin (**Table 1**).

212 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing (**Table S1**) showed that all isolates were susceptible
213 to amoxicillin, ciprofloxacin, rifampicin, cotrimoxazole, erythromycin, azithromycin,
214 vancomycin and clindamycin. For tetracycline, 17 resistant isolates were observed. Genomic
215 analysis of antimicrobial resistance genes showed the presence of *tetO* gene in the 16 isolates
216 of sublineage SL416 (**Table S1**). All isolates with *tetO* were resistant to tetracycline, and all
217 isolates without *tetO* gene were susceptible to tetracycline except one (FRC0758); for this
218 isolate, no explanation was found for its tetracycline resistance phenotype.

219 The interpretations for penicillin G depended on the reference system used: All isolates
220 were resistant based on the 2019 CASFM reference system (**Table S2**), but using the 2013
221 CASFM guidelines, only 5 isolates were classified as intermediate, the others being classified
222 as susceptible (**Table S1**).

223 The *pbp2m* gene was observed in one isolate (FRC0534), with decreased susceptibility
224 to penicillin (CMI: 0.38 g/L). This gene is typically found on a small genetic unit, sometimes
225 associated with *ermX*, in several plasmidic or chromosomal contexts, but is rare in

226 *C. diphtheriae* populations (Forde et al., 2020; Hennart et al., 2020). Here, it was not associated
227 with *ermX*, but with a nearby relaxase gene as described previously (Hennart et al., 2020). No
228 macrolide resistance gene was found among the studied isolates.

229 The genomic analyzes confirmed the MALDI-TOF species identification as
230 *C. diphtheriae* for 57 isolates, whereas one *tox*-negative isolate (FRC0723) was identified as
231 belonging to the closely related species *C. belfantii*. Biotyping showed that two isolates were
232 of biovar Belfanti (including the *C. belfantii* isolate). Among the remaining isolates, 46 were
233 of biovar Gravis and 10 of biovar Mitis (**Table S1**).

234 Biovars Mitis and Gravis are distinguished by the ability to utilize glycogen. The *spuA*
235 gene was reported as being associated with biovar Gravis isolates (Santos et al., 2018; Hennart
236 et al., 2020). We confirmed a strong association between the presence of *spuA* and the Gravis
237 phenotype: almost all (42/46; 91.3%) isolates having the *spuA* gene were of Gravis phenotype.
238 No molecular explanation was found for the ability to utilize glycogen of the four other Gravis
239 isolates, and we noted that in some of them, the *spuA* gene was truncated (**Table S1**).

240 The nitrate reductase activity differentiates Mitis and Gravis isolates from biovar
241 Belfanti isolates, which are nitrate-negative. As expected (Dazas et al., 2018; Tagini et al.,
242 2018), the *narG* gene (coding for nitrate reductase) was absent in the FRC0723 *C. belfantii*
243 strain. However, no genomic explanation was found for the *C. diphtheriae* biovar Belfanti
244 isolate (FRC0748).

245

246 **Genomic epidemiology of isolates**

247 *C. diphtheriae* isolates can be classified into 7-gene MLST sequence types (Bolt et al.,
248 2010) and phylogenetic sublineages, which represent deep phylogenetic subdivisions of the
249 population structure of this species that are highly concordant with ST classifications
250 (Guglielmini et al., 2021). The 7-gene MLST sequence type (ST) and cgMLST classifications
251 into sublineages (SL; maximum of 500 mismatches out of 1305 loci) were defined for the 58
252 isolates. Based on MLST, there were 14 distinct STs, whereas cgMLST grouped the isolates
253 into 13 different sublineages (SL). There was total agreement between ST and SL
254 classifications, except that one isolate of sublineage SL228 had ST240 instead of ST228 (**Table**
255 **1**). Sublineage SL228 was represented by 21 isolates (36.2% of the total) and sublineage SL416
256 was represented by 16 (27.6%) isolates (**Table 1**). Hence, these two predominant sublineages
257 represented more than half of the isolates circulating in New Caledonia. Isolates of these two
258 sublineages were all of biovar Gravis. Whereas SL228 was isolated in 10 administrative
259 districts, SL416 isolates were all recovered from Nouméa and Lifou except one (**Table 1**).

260 Genomic clusters (GC) are much narrower genetic subdivisions of sublineages that have been
261 defined as groups of isolates that have, among themselves, genetic distances compatible with

262 outbreaks or recent transmission (Guglielmini et al., 2021). Looking at this genotyping
263 classification level, there were 22 distinct GCs (**Table 1**). Two of these were recovered more
264 than 8 times: GC108 (16 isolates), GC312 (9 isolates), and they belonged to each of the
265 predominant sublineages (SL416 and SL228, respectively. However, whereas SL228
266 comprised 9 other GCs, SL416 comprised only GC108. The classification into genetic clusters
267 show that SL416 is genetically very homogeneous, and in fact corresponds to relatively recent
268 transmission. In contrast, SL228 is genetically heterogeneous, in line with its much wider
269 geographic distribution across the island (**Table 1**). There was no documented epidemiological
270 link between isolates in these genetic clusters. Hence, they may correspond to cryptic
271 transmission that is being revealed here by genomic analyses.

272 Genetic cluster GC499 corresponded to *tox*-positive isolates from an index isolate and isolates
273 from four contacts that were screened during investigations around the index case (Investigation
274 group 2 in **Table 1**). In this investigation, samples were obtained in the same family in New
275 Caledonia, some members of which had traveled to Vanuatu, or in Vanuatu following
276 investigations and screening at the family's travel location. Further comparisons of cgMLST
277 allelic profiles within CG499 show a max of 2 mismatches among the five isolates, strongly
278 concordant with recent transmission of a single strain. Another contact isolate (FRC0762)
279 collected in Vanuatu was in fact not related to the others based on genomic analyses: the strain
280 was *tox*-negative and belonged to a distinct sublineage (**Table 1**). Elek's test revealed that two
281 contact isolates were Elek negative, despite being *tox* gene positive by qPCR. However, no
282 explanation was found on the *tox* gene sequence for this NTTB phenotype, which might
283 therefore be attributed to the low sensitivity of the Elek test.

284 Another epidemiological investigation was triggered by a *tox*-positive isolate from a case on
285 Lifou island. Upon screening of contacts, one isolate was found (see 'Investigation group 1' in
286 **Table 1**). Unexpectedly, the isolates from the index and the contact were in fact genetically
287 unrelated, as they belong to different STs and sublineages (and of course, genetic clusters).
288 Interestingly, the contact isolate belonged to the predominant genomic cluster circulating in
289 Lifou island (GC108).

290 Genotypic data of the isolates from New Caledonia were compared with those of 876 global
291 *C. diphtheriae* isolates available in public genome data repositories. Of the 13 sublineages from
292 New Caledonia, 8 were also observed elsewhere (**Table S3**). Seven of these were also observed
293 in Australia, 2 in mainland France, and 3 in other European countries. Australian genomes
294 represent only 66 (4.5%) of comparative genomes, and are therefore clearly overrepresented in
295 sublineages shared with New Caledonia. Remarkably, two genomic clusters represented in New
296 Caledonia, GC57 and GC61, were also reported 2012-2015 in Australia (**Table S3**), indicative
297 of relatively recent transmission between the two islands.

Discussion

299 We provide clinical and microbiological data on a series of 58 infection or carriage cases
300 of isolates of *C. diphtheriae* in New Caledonia. Nearly nine in ten of the samples corresponded
301 to skin infections, and *C. diphtheriae* was found in association with the pathogens *S. aureus* or
302 *S. pyogenes* in over three quarters of these cases. Together with the fact that a large majority of
303 *C. diphtheriae* isolates were non-toxigenic, this put the pathogenicity of *C. diphtheriae* in skin
304 infections in perspective. Clearly, *C. diphtheriae* could be pathogenic itself, but can also
305 colonize a pre-existing infection caused by another bacterium. Co-infection could contribute to
306 an increase of severity, compared to the same infection without *C. diphtheriae*. The classic
307 clinical presentation is an ulcer covered with a pseudomembrane (Mofredj et al., 1994;
308 Wermuller et al., 1996). The pathogenicity of *C. diphtheriae* strains in this kind of context is
309 unsure, and the treatment should cover other pathogenic bacteria as previously observed and
310 suggested. The only two strains isolated from throat swabs were obtained from asymptomatic
311 patients, as part of a screening around a positive case. The strain of urinary origin was probably
312 a contamination during the urine collection.

313 *C. diphtheriae* endocarditis is well described (Belko et al., 2000; Patey et al., 1997).
314 These infections frequently occur in patients with predispositions, such as pre-existing heart
315 disease, prosthetic valves and intravenous drug use (Belko et al., 2000). Cases of *C. diphtheriae*
316 endocarditis have been described more often in males than in females and in subjects who are
317 generally younger than described for other pathogens. Endocarditis strains may or may not carry
318 the diphtheria toxin gene, but cases of *tox*-negative endocarditis have predominated since high
319 global vaccination coverage has been achieved (Belko et al., 2000; Patey et al., 1997). Here,
320 both cases of infective endocarditis were in young women with a history of rheumatic fever, a
321 common predominantly female condition in New Caledonia (Chatard et al., 2020). Melanesian
322 and Polynesian populations are at greater risk of developing infective endocarditis than
323 populations of European origin in New Caledonia (Chatard et al., 2020). New Caledonia is a
324 territory where part of the population is particularly susceptible to infective endocarditis. Here
325 we showed *C. diphtheriae* is a contributor. Of note, six other cases of *C. diphtheriae*
326 endocarditis were previously reported in New Caledonia, five of them between 2005 and 2011,
327 and one in 2021 (CHT laboratory data, unpublished), for a total of 8 cases, and with a history
328 of acute rheumatoid fever for 6 patients.

329 A large majority of isolates were *tox*-negative strains. The only *tox*-positive isolates
330 were from patients returning from Vanuatu. Toxin-positive isolates can cause severe respiratory
331 or skin infections, and the action of the toxin can also lead to cardiomyopathy and neurological
332 damage. In the present cases, there were no toxic symptoms.

333 Although vaccination coverage among children is improving in Vanuatu, the current
334 adult population has been poorly vaccinated. In 1982, only 22% of children aged 12-23 months
335 had been vaccinated against diphtheria (“Vanuatu DPT immunization rate - data, chart,” n.d.).
336 Improving current vaccination coverage in Vanuatu would seem important, and a study of the
337 epidemiological situation of diphtheria in this setting could guide control measures. Although
338 carriers of *tox*-positive *C. diphtheriae* in New Caledonia were properly vaccinated, this was not
339 sufficient to protect them against cutaneous forms. As the immune response is directed against
340 the toxoid, it is not considered effective at preventing colonization. No systemic complications
341 related to the action of the toxin were observed in these carriers.

342 The Elek test for production of the diphtheria toxin was performed retrospectively and
343 showed two isolates to be negative while carrying the *tox* gene, *i.e.*, non-toxigenic *tox*-bearing
344 (NTTB) isolates. These two isolates were part of the cluster of 5 *tox*+ isolates. Given the lack
345 of genomic explanation on the one hand, and the very close epidemiological and genetic link
346 between the five isolates on the other hand, we cannot exclude that the two negative isolates
347 expressed the toxin below detectable levels. In France, Elek’s test is not considered for clinical
348 management or follow-up measures, because it is of limited sensitivity and it is feared that the
349 lack of detectable *in-vitro* expression might not always be reflected by an absence of
350 toxigenicity *in vivo*. Genetic disruptions of the *tox* gene sequence provide a clear explanation
351 and therefore high confidence on the absence of toxigenicity during infection, but are not
352 assessed fast enough to be used for clinical management, as no rapid molecular test exists.

353 The isolates were all susceptible to amoxicillin, ciprofloxacin, rifampicin,
354 cotrimoxazole, erythromycin, azithromycin, vancomycin and clindamycin. For penicillin G, the
355 French CA-SFM recommendations changed dramatically in 2014, in line with the European
356 Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing (EUCAST). These changes cover
357 susceptibility testing protocols, disk loads used and interpretation thresholds. The new threshold
358 (29 mm) classifies *de facto* all isolates as "resistant", which is not the case when testing in E-
359 test. Conversely, the 2013 version classified almost all isolates in this study as "susceptible"
360 and only a few as "intermediate". The pertinence of a similar change (breakpoint from 1 mg/L
361 to 0.12 mg/L) in the Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) interpretive thresholds
362 has been questioned (Zou et al., 2020). There is a danger in over-categorizing strains as
363 penicillin-resistant, as the clinician will be tempted to use the broader spectrum macrolides,
364 even though macrolide resistance is more common. Moreover, the prescription of penicillin G
365 appears appropriate to treat multi-microbial samples with *Streptococcus pyogenes*. According
366 to the natural distribution of penicillin susceptibility values, these isolates should be considered
367 as having a natural susceptibility phenotype (Hennart et al., 2020; Marosevic et al., 2020; Zou
368 et al., 2020).

369 Tetracycline resistance was observed in this study, concordant with other reports
370 (Rockhill et al., 1982; Schaeffer et al., 2020) but is clinically less relevant. All isolates in which
371 the *tetO* gene was found, were resistant to tetracycline. This gene encodes a protein that protects
372 the ribosome from the action of tetracycline, allowing protein synthesis even in the presence of
373 high intracellular tetracycline concentration (Warburton et al., 2016).

374 The genotyping of isolates based on cgMLST provided confirmation or allowed to rule
375 out suspected transmissions. In investigation group 1, the two isolates turned out to be
376 phylogenetically very distant (as they belong to distinct sublineages), ruling-out transmission
377 among the two cases. Instead of cross-transmission, the contact had asymptomatic carriage of
378 a co-circulating *tox* negative strain. On the opposite, the isolates of investigation group 2
379 belonged to the same cgMLST genomic cluster (GC108). Although genomic clusters are
380 defined using a tolerance of 25 mismatches, the isolates of this group were separated by only a
381 maximum of 5 mismatches, underlying their very close genetic proximity.

382 Sublineage 227, to which all five isolates in the *tox+* cluster (group 2) belong, was
383 previously described only in two other isolates, one from 1995 in Finland and one isolated from
384 2015 in Australia; both belonged to other genomic clusters than GC499, illustrating the value
385 of classifying strains at both the sublineage and genomic group levels, as they provide
386 information on genetic relationships, and hence transmission, at different timescales.

387 Our genomic analyses revealing a high genetic diversity of *C. diphtheriae* circulating in
388 New Caledonia, with at least 13 different sublineages, consistent with the situation in other
389 localities (Dangel et al., 2018; Hennart et al., 2020; Hoefler et al., 2020; Schaeffer et al., 2020).
390 Nevertheless, nearly two thirds of the isolates belonged to only two predominant sublineages,
391 SL228 and SL416. Besides, the latter had very restricted genetic diversity, comprising a single
392 genomic cluster. The high frequency of these genotypes could be related to the insular nature
393 of the New Caledonia territory. The fact that all SL416 isolates belong to the same genomic
394 cluster suggests relatively recent transmission at the population scale (perhaps a few decades).
395 Interestingly, SL416 corresponded to the isolates carrying the *tetO* gene, conferring tetracycline
396 resistance; whether this phenotype has favored the spread of this group is an interesting
397 possibility, as it has already been observed for other bacteria (Da Cunha et al., 2014). The
398 SL416 was previously reported only once, isolated in France from a patient returning from
399 French Polynesia.

400 Sublineage SL228 represented 21 isolates (36.2% of our sample) and has already been
401 described elsewhere in the world, sporadically. Of all the published data available worldwide
402 (876 genomes), nine strains outside New Caledonia belong to this sublineage. Their
403 provenances are as follows: An isolate from Romania in 1966, two Australian isolates
404 respectively from 2013 and 2016, two mainland France isolates from 2011 and 2021, an isolate

405 from Wallis and Futuna from 2012, and three isolates from French Polynesia, isolated in 2017,
406 2019 and 2020. As observed for other pathogens, e.g., *Burkholderia pseudomallei* (Melot et al.,
407 2016), the predominant sublineages seem to be linked either to geographically close territories
408 (Polynesia, Australia) or from metropolitan France, consistent with human transmission and
409 dissemination.

410 In this study, cases with *C. diphtheriae* had an uneven geographic repartition across the
411 New Caledonia territory. This observation can in part be explained by the geographical
412 distribution of the population: a high population density is present in the main city of Nouméa
413 (34.7% of the population) and in the South Province (74.9 % of the population), whereas the
414 North Province and the Islands are less populated, with respectively 18.4 % and 6.8% of the
415 population (“Populations légales des provinces de Nouvelle-Calédonie en 2019 – Populations
416 légales de Nouvelle-Calédonie en 2019 | Insee,” n.d.). *C. diphtheriae* is more easily detected
417 with MALDI-TOF mass spectrometry, with which only the laboratories in Nouméa are
418 equipped, including the laboratory that processed the samples from Lifou. Whereas the Lifou
419 clinicians regularly took samples from wounds with unfavorable evolution in order to seek
420 bacteriological documentation, the other centers did so much less systematically. This bias can
421 contribute to the overrepresentation of cases in Lifou, despite a small population (9,195
422 inhabitants in 2019, *i.e.*, 3.4% of the New Caledonian population) (“Populations légales des
423 provinces de Nouvelle-Calédonie en 2019 – Populations légales de Nouvelle-Calédonie
424 en 2019 | Insee,” n.d.). This study therefore illustrates the difficulties of achieving a
425 homogeneous diphtheria surveillance given existing heterogeneities of laboratory equipment,
426 practices and awareness. Monitoring only symptomatic respiratory cases would have led to a
427 very fragmentary picture, and the surveillance of diphtheria should clearly benefit from the
428 addition of isolates from wound infections.

429

Figure legends

430 **Figure 1. Geographic distribution of *C. diphtheriae* infection cases in New Caledonia.**

431 The number of patients whose living place is in each district, is indicated as a heatmap (see
432 key). The arrow indicates the direction of the North.

433

434 **Figure 2. Diversity of *Corynebacterium diphtheriae* isolates from New Caledonia.**

435 The first column after the isolate identifier represents the locations of origin of the
436 isolates (see color key). After the year of isolation column, the *tox*-negative isolates are
437 represented by an empty star, *tox*-positive ones by a full star (red when the Elek test was
438 positive, orange for Elek-negative ones). The biovar is represented next: green for Gravis,
439 purple for Mitis, brown for Belfanti. The following columns represent the presence of genes
440 *spuA* (likely involved in glycogen metabolism; positive in biovar Gravis) and *narG* (involved
441 in nitrate metabolism; positive in biovars Gravis and Mitis). On the four next columns,
442 alternating dark and light colors indicate each sequence type (ST), sublineage (SL), genetic
443 cluster (GC) or cgST change. Sublineages are given as: internal number = alias number (derived
444 from 7-gene MLST numbers). The next column represents the tetracycline resistance
445 phenotype: red for resistant (with R letter), grey for susceptible. The presence of the *tetO* gene
446 is symbolized in orange on the next column, its absence in grey. The last two columns indicate
447 in the same way, the penicillin phenotype and presence of gene *pbp2m* (I: intermediate).

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463

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469

470 **Declaration of interest statement**

471 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

472

473 **Ethical statement**

474 This work was approved by the CHT ethics committee (Avis 2022-001).

475

476 **Authors contributions**

477 Conceptualization: ET, JC and SB; Methodology, ET, JC, EB, MH and SB; Genomic analyses,
478 MH; Validation, JC and SB; Investigation, ET and MH; Resources, JC, SB, JT and EB; Data
479 Curation, ET; Writing – Original Draft Preparation, ET, MH, JC and SB; Writing – Review &
480 Editing, all; Visualization, MH and ET; Supervision, JC and SB; Funding Acquisition, SB and
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Figure 1

Table 1. Characteristics of the isolates

Study ID	ID in BIGSdb	Isolate ID	Sex	Year	Province	Administrative district	Investigation group	Sample	Body location	Species	tox gene PCR	Elek	ST (MLST)	Sublineage (internal ID = SI, alias)	Genomic cluster
68	973	FRC0723	M	2019	North	Canala		Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. bifrontii</i>	Negative	NR	42	119 = SI226	500
86	1011	FRC0762	F	2019	NR	Vanuatu (not New Caledonia)	2	Throat	Throat	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	595	172 = SI595	514
27	497	FRC0485	F	2017	South	Mont Dore (travel from Vanuatu)		Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Positive	NR	380	192 = SI380	321
29	500	FRC0493	M	2017	Islands	Lifou	1	Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	533	193 = SI533	322
48	868	FRC0599	F	2018	Islands	Naté		Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	533	193 = SI533	322
70	975	FRC0725	F	2019	Islands	Lifou		Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	533	193 = SI533	322
73	1001	FRC0751	M	2019	South	Dumbéa		Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	533	193 = SI533	324
30	503	FRC0497	M	2017	Islands	Ouvéa		Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	522	195 = SI522	322
60	962	FRC0713	M	2019	South	Dumbéa (travel from Vanuatu)	2	Wound	Upper limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Positive	NR	120	227 = SI120	499
61	963	FRC0714	M	2019	South	Dumbéa (travel from Vanuatu)	2	Wound	Upper limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Positive	NR	120	227 = SI120	499
63	964	FRC0715	M	2019	South	Dumbéa (travel from Vanuatu)	2	Wound	Upper limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Positive	NR	120	227 = SI120	499
64	965	FRC0716	F	2019	South	Dumbéa (travel from Vanuatu)	2	Throat	Throat	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Positive	NR	120	227 = SI120	499
66	967	FRC0717	M	2019	South	Dumbéa	2	Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Positive	NR	120	227 = SI120	499
57	998	FRC0748	M	2018	South	Païta		Implantable chamber	Upper limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	687	42 = SI687	510
53	994	FRC0745	M	2018	South	Païta		Abscess	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	240	43 = SI228	232
17	434	FRC0322	M	2015	North	Poindimié		Abscess	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	228	43 = SI228	278
20	442	FRC0356	M	2015	South	Nouméa		Wound	Body trunk	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	228	43 = SI228	285
24	478	FRC0456	F	2016	South	Yaté		Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	228	43 = SI228	307
25	484	FRC0469	M	2016	Islands	Maré		Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	228	43 = SI228	312
31	515	FRC0513	F	2017	South	Mont Dore		Abscess	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	228	43 = SI228	312
41	861	FRC0577	F	2017	South	Nouméa		Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	228	43 = SI228	312
46	1406	FRC0597	F	2018	North	Hianghene		Abscess	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	228	43 = SI228	312
47	1427	FRC0598	F	2018	South	Mont Dore		Abscess	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	228	43 = SI228	312
50	1428	FRC0601	F	2018	South	Païta		Wound	Upper limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	228	43 = SI228	312
51	870	FRC0602	F	2018	South	Païta		Wound	Face	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	228	43 = SI228	312
65	971	FRC0721	M	2019	South	Mont Dore		Abscess	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	228	43 = SI228	312
74	988	FRC0718	M	2019	South	Nouméa		Abscess	Upper limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	228	43 = SI228	312
36	527	FRC0533	M	2017	South	Nouméa		Wound	Upper limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	228	43 = SI228	342
40	1463	FRC0562	F	2017	North	Koné		Blood	Blood	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	228	43 = SI228	511
52	1429	FRC0603	F	2018	South	Nouméa		Wound	Body trunk	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	228	43 = SI228	511
58	999	FRC0749	F	2018	South	Nouméa		Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	228	43 = SI228	511
82	1008	FRC0759	M	2019	North	Kaala Gomen		Abscess	Upper limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	228	43 = SI228	511
77	1004	FRC0754	M	2019	Islands	Lifou		Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	228	43 = SI228	511
84	1009	FRC0760	M	2019	Islands	Maré		Wound	body trunk	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	228	43 = SI228	513
39	1454	FRC0563	F	2017	South	Saraméa		Abscess	Upper limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	228	43 = SI228	702
38	536	FRC0547	M	2017	South	Nouméa		Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	524	45 = SI524	57
45	865	FRC0581	M	2018	Islands	Lifou		Abscess	Face	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	524	45 = SI524	57
44	863	FRC0579	F	2018	Islands	Lifou		Abscess	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	605	48 = SI605	61
43	862	FRC0578	M	2018	North	Ponerhouen		Abscess	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	232	50 = SI232	122
69	974	FRC0724	M	2019	Islands	Lifou		Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	232	50 = SI232	122
81	1075	FRC0758	M	2019	Islands	Ouvéa		Abscess	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	232	50 = SI232	122
37	528	FRC0534	M	2017	South	Nouméa		Abscess	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	86	56 = SI86	75
22	140	FRC0411	F	2016	Islands	Lifou		Wound	Body trunk	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	416	82 = SI416	108
28	499	FRC0492	F	2017	Islands	Lifou	1	Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	416	82 = SI416	108
35	523	FRC0524	F	2017	Islands	Lifou		Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	416	82 = SI416	108
42	864	FRC0580	F	2018	South	Nouméa		Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	416	82 = SI416	108
49	869	FRC0600	F	2018	South	Nouméa		Blood	Blood	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	416	82 = SI416	108
54	996	FRC0746	M	2018	South	Dumbéa		Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	416	82 = SI416	108
59	969	FRC0719	F	2019	South	Nouméa		Wound	Blood	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	416	82 = SI416	108
62	970	FRC0720	F	2019	Islands	Lifou		Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	416	82 = SI416	108
67	972	FRC0722	M	2019	South	Nouméa		Abscess	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	416	82 = SI416	108
72	1000	FRC0750	M	2019	Islands	Lifou		Abscess	Upper limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	416	82 = SI416	108
75	1002	FRC0752	F	2019	Islands	Lifou		Wound	Body trunk	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	416	82 = SI416	108
76	1003	FRC0753	F	2019	Islands	Lifou		Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	416	82 = SI416	108
78	1005	FRC0755	F	2019	Islands	Lifou		Urine	Urine	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	416	82 = SI416	108
79	1006	FRC0756	M	2019	Islands	Lifou		Wound	Upper limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	416	82 = SI416	108
80	1007	FRC0757	M	2019	South	Nouméa		Abscess	Upper limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	416	82 = SI416	108
85	1010	FRC0761	F	2019	South	Nouméa		Wound	Lower limb	<i>C. diptheriae</i>	Negative	NR	416	82 = SI416	108

NR: not relevant; ND: not documented

CHAPITRE 9 : Série de cas d'infections dues à des membres *du complexe diphtheriae* chez des animaux de compagnie en France

Titre de l'article

Corynebacterium of the diphtheriae complex in companion animals: clinical and microbiological characterisation of 64 cases from France

Résumé

Les *corynebactéries* du complexe *diphtheriae* (Cdc), qui comprennent *C. diphtheriae*, *C. ulcerans* et des espèces étroitement apparentées, peuvent provoquer la diphtérie chez l'homme. *C. ulcerans* est considéré comme une zoonose, avec les chats et les chiens qui représente la principale source. Nous avons cherché à décrire les cas d'infection des animaux de compagnie par des isolats de Cdc sur une période de 2 ans (août 2019 - août 2021) en France. 18 308 animaux (chiens, chats, chevaux et petits mammifères) présentant des rhinites, dermatites, plaies non cicatrisantes et otites ont été échantillonnés en France métropolitaine. Des données sur les symptômes, l'âge, la race et la région administrative d'origine ont été recueillies. Les bactéries cultivées ont été identifiées par spectrométrie de masse MALDI-TOF et analysées pour la présence du gène *tox*, pour la production de la toxine diphtérique, pour la sensibilité aux antimicrobiens et par typage de séquence multilocus (MLST).

C. ulcerans a été identifié dans 51 cas (0,27%), dont 24 étaient toxigènes. La rhinite était la présentation la plus fréquente (18/51, 35%). Onze cas (6 chats, 4 chiens, 1 rat) étaient des mono-infections. Les chiens de grande race, en particulier les bergers allemands (9 chiens sur 28 ; $p < 0,00001$; dont 1 était toxigène) étaient surreprésentés. Les isolats de *C. ulcerans* étaient sensibles à la plupart des antibiotiques testés, à l'exception de la clindamycine. *C. diphtheriae* a été identifié dans 2 cas (0,01 %), tous deux issus de chevaux et *tox*-positifs ; l'un provenant d'une conjonctivite et l'autre d'une dermatite du paturon. Enfin, 11 (0,06 %) cas d'infections (principalement des otites chroniques et 2 plaies) présentaient un *C. rouxii* *tox*-négatif, une espèce récemment définie. Les isolats de *C. rouxii* et *C. diphtheriae* étaient sensibles à la plupart des antibiotiques testés, et presque toutes ces infections étaient polymicrobiennes. Un chat atteint d'otite chronique présentait une mono-infection bactérienne à *C. rouxii* avec prolifération de la levure *Malassezia*.

C. ulcerans, *C. rouxii* et *C. diphtheriae* peuvent être isolés chez les animaux de compagnie, représentant un risque de transmission à l'homme. Les mono-infections avec *C. ulcerans* indiquent un potentiel pathogène primaire pour les animaux. Cette série de cas fournit des données cliniques et microbiologiques inédites sur les infections à Cdc, et souligne la nécessité de prendre en charge les animaux et leurs contacts humains, en particulier les propriétaires et les professionnels vétérinaires.

Contributions personnelles

- Réalisation de l'ensemble des analyses génomiques
- Réalisation de l'ensemble des figures
- Contribution à l'ensemble des tableaux
- Contribution à la rédaction du manuscrit

1 ***Corynebacterium of the diphtheriae complex in companion animals:***
2 **clinical and microbiological characterisation of 64 cases from France**

3

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25 **Keywords:** *Corynebacterium*, diphtheria, *C. ulcerans*, *C. diphtheriae*, *C. rouxii*, emerging
26 zoonosis, case series

27

Abstract

28 Objectives

29 *Corynebacteria of the diphtheriae complex (Cdc)*, which include *C. diphtheriae*, *C. ulcerans*
30 and closely related species, can cause diphtheria in humans. *C. ulcerans* is considered a
31 zoonotic disease, with cats and dogs representing the main source. We aimed to describe pet
32 infection cases by *Cdc* isolates over a period of 2 years (August 2019 – August 2021) in France.

33 Methods

34 18 308 animals (dogs, cats, horses and small mammals) with rhinitis, dermatitis, non-healing
35 wounds and otitis were sampled in metropolitan France. Data on symptoms, age, breed, and the
36 administrative region of origin were collected. Cultured bacteria were identified by MALDI-
37 TOF mass spectrometry and analyzed for *tox* gene presence, for production of the diphtheria
38 toxin, for antimicrobial susceptibility and by multilocus sequence typing.

39 Results

40 *C. ulcerans* was identified in 51 cases (0.27%), 24 of which were toxigenic. Rhinitis was the
41 most frequent presentation (18/51, 35%). Eleven cases (6 cats, 4 dogs, 1 rat) were mono-
42 infections. Large breed dogs, especially German Shepherds (9 of 28 dogs; $p < 0.00001$; 1 of
43 which were toxigenic) were overrepresented. *C. ulcerans* isolates were susceptible to most
44 antibiotics tested except for clindamycin. *C. diphtheriae* was identified in 2 cases (0.01%), both
45 from horses and *tox*-positive; one from a conjunctivitis and one from a pastern dermatitis. Last,
46 11 (0.06%) infections cases (mostly chronic otitis, and 2 sores) had *tox*-negative *C. rouxii*, a
47 recently defined species. The *C. rouxii* and *C. diphtheriae* isolates were susceptible to most
48 antibiotics tested, and almost all of these infections were polymicrobial. One cat with chronic
49 otitis had a bacterial monoinfection with *C. rouxii* with proliferation of the yeast *Malassezia*.

50 Conclusions

51 *C. ulcerans*, *C. rouxii* and *C. diphtheriae* can be isolated from pet animals, representing a risk
52 of transmission to humans. Monoinfections with *C. ulcerans* point towards a primary
53 pathogenic potential to animals. This case series provides novel clinical and microbiological
54 data on *Cdc* infections, and underlines the need for management of animals and their human
55 contacts, especially owners and veterinary professionals.

Introduction

57 Diphtheria is a potentially fatal infection in humans, caused mostly by toxigenic
58 *Corynebacterium (C.) diphtheriae* isolates, which may carry the *tox* gene coding for diphtheria
59 toxin. This bacterial species is phylogenetically related to 5 other *Corynebacterium* species and
60 together with these, is grouped into the *C. diphtheriae* complex (Cdc). *C. ulcerans* (Riegel et
61 al., 1995) can be isolated from humans and animals and is being increasingly reported (Elena
62 Hacker et al., 2016a; Robert Koch-Institut, 2018; Haut Conseil de la santé publique, 2019;
63 Wagner et al., 2010). *C. pseudotuberculosis* causes caseous lymphadenitis in small ruminants
64 and oedematous skin disease in buffaloes. Although this species is considered potentially
65 toxigenic, only isolates from buffalos in Egypt seem to produce diphtheria toxin, and there is
66 no evidence for toxigenicity of recent isolates from caseous lymphadenitis (Schlicher et al.,
67 2021; Selim, 2001; Selim et al., 2016; Viana et al., 2017). Two novel species, *C. belfantii* and
68 *C. rouxii*, were recently described (Badell et al., 2020; Dazas et al., 2018). Isolates of these
69 species were previously identified as *C. diphtheriae*, are mostly *tox*-negative, and are of biovar
70 Belfanti (starch and nitrate negative). Last, *C. silvaticum* was recently described from wild
71 boars; all isolates of this species carry a disrupted *tox* gene, impairing their capacity to produce
72 diphtheria toxin (Dangel et al., 2020). Hence, although all members of the Cdc may potentially
73 harbor the *tox* gene, toxigenic strains are frequently encountered only in *C. diphtheriae* and
74 *C. ulcerans*. In *C. diphtheriae*, this gene is carried on a temperate phage that has integrated into
75 the chromosome of a large variety of sublineages (Guglielmini et al., 2021; Hennart et al.,
76 2020). In *C. ulcerans*, in addition to a lysogenic phage, the *tox* gene can be carried on a
77 pathogenicity island (Dangel et al., 2019). Strains that carry the *tox* gene generally produce the
78 diphtheria toxin *in vitro*, but a short fraction of them (~10-15%) do not, due to disruptions of
79 the *tox* gene; these are called non-toxigenic, tox-bearing (NTTB) strains and are observed both
80 in *C. diphtheriae* and in *C. ulcerans* (and all *C. silvaticum*).

81 Although classically defined as a respiratory infection caused by toxigenic
82 *C. diphtheriae*, diphtheria is sometimes defined more broadly as any infection (respiratory,
83 cutaneous or else) potentially leading to manifestations due to the production of the diphtheria
84 toxin by species of the Cdc (<https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/diphtheria>). Following the recent
85 taxonomic updates, diphtheria may be defined more broadly as any infection caused by any
86 isolate of the Cdc, irrespective of toxigenic status (Haut Conseil de la santé publique, 2021).

87 The typical clinical expressions of diphtheria in human are: (i) classical respiratory
88 diphtheria with pseudo-membranous diphtheric pharyngitis, that can provoke a deadly
89 obstruction of upper airways, usually associated with fever and enlarged anterior cervical lymph
90 nodes and oedema ('bull neck' appearance); Pharyngeal diphtheria can progress to laryngeal

91 diphtheria causing hoarseness and stridor; (ii) Cutaneous manifestations, with “rolled edge”
92 ulcers usually observed on the limbs and that can be covered by a greyish pseudo-membrane;
93 and (iii) Toxicogenic complications such as polyneuropathy or myocarditis (Sharma et al., 2019;
94 UK Health Security Agency, 2022).

95 Seroprevalence studies in humans demonstrated that up to 82% of the population have
96 a very low titers of anti-diphtheria toxin antibodies (*i.e.*, under the limit of protection from
97 diphtheria toxin-linked infections) and that the proportion of non-protected persons increases
98 with age (Berbers et al., 2021; Launay et al., 2009).

99 Before 1999, no case of *C. ulcerans* were reported in France (Hommeze et al., 1999);
100 but, between 2002 and 2013, 28 cases of toxicogenic *C. ulcerans* have been reported; and between
101 January 2018 and August 2019, 11 further humans clinical cases were described; most of the
102 cases were indigenous (Haut Conseil de la santé publique, 2019;
103 National_Reference_Center_for_diphtheria_in_France, 2021) and a similar pattern of
104 increased reporting of *C. ulcerans* was reported from the UK and Germany (European Centre
105 for Disease Prevention and Control, 2021; Elena Hacker et al., 2016a; Robert Koch-Institut,
106 2018; Wagner et al., 2010).

107 While the transmission of *C. diphtheriae* is essentially inter-human, *C. ulcerans* is a
108 zoonotic pathogen (Elena Hacker et al., 2016a; Othieno et al., 2019). No transmission of
109 *C. ulcerans* among humans was reported since its description in 1995; however, the possibility
110 of person-to-person transmission cannot be totally excluded (Konrad et al., 2015). Animals
111 from which *C. ulcerans* is isolated can be asymptomatic carriers but can also present clinical
112 symptoms, such as ulcerative dermatitis and chronic rhinitis (Lartigue et al., 2005; Carfora et
113 al., 2018; Katsukawa et al., 2012; Abbott et al., 2020). Horses can also carry *C. ulcerans* and
114 sometimes show signs of respiratory diphtheria (Zendri et al., 2021).

115 Similarly, *C. rouxii* may also be zoonotic: no interhuman transmission was reported yet,
116 and in addition to human cases, it was so far identified in dogs, cats and in a fox (Badell et al.,
117 2020; Hall et al., 2010; Schlez et al., 2021; Sing et al., 2016). Strains of *C. belfantii* were isolated
118 only from human respiratory samples, to our knowledge.

119 Despite previous reports of animal *Cdc* infections *e.g.*, (Lartigue et al., 2005; Leggett et
120 al., 2010; Elena Hacker et al., 2016a; Abbott et al., 2020), to the best of our knowledge, no large
121 case series of such infections, including precise bacterial identification and genotyping, have
122 been reported. Here we present a case series of 64 *Cdc* infections in dogs, cats, rabbits, rats and
123 horses in France over 2 years, and report their clinical and microbiological characteristics.

124

Materials and methods

125 Inclusions and microbiological characterization

126 A total of 18 308 samples were analyzed during the period August 2019 to August 2021
127 (24 months), originating from sick animals (dogs, cats, horses and small mammals) from
128 metropolitan France. All samples from which isolates were identified as *Cdc* were included in
129 the present study. Although *C. pseudotuberculosis* was sometimes recorded, this species was
130 excluded because the samples received are known to be biased (samples of farmed animals are
131 generally sent to state laboratories and only occasionally to private laboratories).

132 The geographical location of the cases was recorded using the corresponding French
133 administrative Department (in metropolitan France, there are 96 geographic and administrative
134 divisions called “Départements”). Clinical data (age, sex and clinical symptoms) were collected
135 using information communicated on the order form.

136 Sterile swabs with liquid Amies culture medium were used to sample the affected
137 animals, and were sent to the laboratory under cooled conditions. There, swabs were plated on
138 solid culture media (Columbia agar additioned with 5 % sheep blood and colistine + nalidixic
139 acid (CNA) under an extractor hood. Solid culture media were incubated at 35°C under 5%
140 enriched CO₂ atmosphere during 24 to 48h. Isolates belonging to the *Corynebacteria* of the
141 *diphtheriae* complex form dry colonies of dark yellow color on the CNA culture medium. The
142 identity of the suspected colonies was confirmed by Matrix Assisted Laser Desorption
143 Ionization - Time of Flight Mass Spectrometry (MALDI-TOF MS, Bruker Daltonics,
144 Germany).

145 Antibiotic susceptibility testing was performed by disk diffusion on Mueller-Hinton
146 culture medium supplemented with 5% blood following the instructions of the French AFNOR
147 norm NFU-47. Diameters of the inhibition zone were read and interpreted according to the 2020
148 guidelines of the veterinary CASFM (committee of antibiograms of the French Society of
149 Microbiology) (“CASFM Vétérinaire 2020,” 2020) using software tool SIRWeb (i2A, France).
150 In case of missing veterinary breakpoints, the 2013 guidelines from the human CASFM were
151 applied. The antibiogram was composed of commonly used antibiotics in veterinary clinics,
152 including beta-lactams (cefalexin and amoxicillin-clavulanate), tetracyclines (doxycycline and
153 tetracycline), aminoglycosides (gentamicin and streptomycin), macrolides (erythromycin,
154 azithromycin, spiramycin, lincomycin and clindamycin), fluoroquinolones (marbofloxacin and
155 enrofloxacin) and others (fusidic acid and trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole). For cefovecin and
156 fluoroquinolones, the interpretation was based on visual evaluation and rules for Gram-positive
157 bacteria as no official interpretation is available by CASFM.

158 All *Cdc* were sent to the National Reference Center for corynebacteria of the *diphtheriae*
159 complex (NRC-CCD) for confirmation of the identification and for the detection of the
160 diphtheria toxin *tox* gene by real time PCR (Badell et al., 2019). This multiplex assay consists
161 of amplifying a fragment of the *rpoB* gene with primer sets specific for either (i) the species
162 *C. diphtheriae*, *C. belfantii* or *C. rouxii*; or (ii) species *C. ulcerans* and *C. pseudotuberculosis*;
163 in addition, a fragment of the *tox* gene is detected. The production of the diphtheria toxin was
164 assessed using the modified Elek test (Engler et al., 1997).

165

166 **Multilocus sequence typing (MLST)**

167 Isolates were retrieved from -80°C storage and plated on tryptose-casein soy agar for
168 24 to 48 h. A small amount of bacterial colony biomass was resuspended in a lysis solution
169 (20 mM Tris-HCl [pH 8], 2 mM EDTA, 1.2% Triton X-100, and lysozyme [20 mg/ml]) and
170 incubated at 37°C for 1 hour, and DNA was extracted with the DNeasy Blood&Tissue kit
171 (Qiagen, Courtaboeuf, France) according to the manufacturer's instructions. MLST was
172 performed as previously described (Bolt et al., 2010; Guglielmini et al., 2021); alleles and
173 profiles were defined using the BIGSdb-Pasteur platform (<https://bigsdbs.pasteur.fr/diphtheria>).

174

175 **Statistical analyses**

176 Dogs and cats were divided into 3 groups of age: under 2 years of age; 2 to 8 years; and
177 older than 8 years. A few dogs could not be attributed to a group because the information was
178 not available.

179 Pearson's chi-squared statistic was used to compare the different characteristics for the
180 categorical variables. Statistical tests were performed in SPSS Statistics software version 25
181 (IBM, New York, USA).

182

183 **Ethical statement**

184 Animals were sampled for diagnostic purpose. No ethics approval was requested for this
185 retrospective study.

186

Results

187 Isolation of members of the *C. diphtheriae* species complex in animals in France

188 Between August 2019 and August 2021, 18 308 sick animals (dogs, cats, horses and
189 small mammals) were sampled from veterinary clinics from across metropolitan France (**Figure**
190 **1**). There were 2732 nasal swabs, 4224 cutaneous/wound/abscess swabs and 11 352 auricular
191 swabs. A total of 64 consecutive, non-duplicated isolates belonging to the *Cdc* were identified
192 from these samples. Of these, 26 were carriers of the *tox* gene coding for the diphtheria toxin
193 (**Table 1**), including 24 *C. ulcerans* and 2 *C. diphtheriae*. Of the 38 non-toxigenic *Cdc* isolates,
194 27 belonged to *C. ulcerans* and the 11 remaining ones were *C. rouxii*. No non-toxigenic
195 *C. diphtheriae*, and no *C. pseudotuberculosis* or *C. belfantii*, were detected.

196 Toxigenic strains were analyzed using Elek's test in order to assess the production of the
197 toxin. Both toxin gene-carrying *C. diphtheriae* strains were positive in the Elek's test. Among
198 the 24 *tox*-positive *C. ulcerans* (one strain, FRC0895, was not available for testing), 20 isolates
199 (87.0%) had a positive result in the Elek's test, including 3 isolates of ST325 with a weakly
200 positive Elek test result. Three *tox*-positive *C. ulcerans* (2 of ST331, 1 of ST358) were negative
201 for the Elek test, hence corresponding to NTTB strains.

202 Of the 64 infections with *Cdc* isolates, 37 were in dogs, 21 in cats, 3 in rats, 1 in a rabbit
203 and 2 in horses. The age of dogs and cats ranged from 1 year to 13 years of age. There was no
204 statistically significant difference in prevalence of *Cdc* isolates among the different age groups.

205 The most frequent breed among the *C. ulcerans* dog cases was the German Shepherd (9
206 of 28 dogs). Dogs belonging to this breed were strongly associated with infections caused by
207 *C. ulcerans* ($p < 0.00001$).

208

209 Antimicrobial susceptibility of *Cdc* isolates

210 *C. ulcerans* isolates were susceptible to most of the antibiotics tested except clindamycin
211 (**Table 1**). Spiramycin was only tested in 22 samples, following the the publication of Abbott et
212 al. in 2020 (Abbott et al., 2020) and more than half of the isolates were non-susceptible (13
213 were intermediate, 1 was resistant). That's why azithromycin was tested at the end of the study
214 in the NRC. 15 isolates were susceptible to lincomycine, 22 were intermediate and 14 resistant.
215 All but one were susceptible to erythromycin (**Table 1**).

216 *C. diphtheriae* and *C. rouxii* were susceptible to most antibiotics except streptomycin
217 (**Table 1**).

218

219

220

221 **Genotyping of isolates using multilocus sequence typing**

222 MLST analysis showed a wide diversity of *C. ulcerans* isolates, with 15 distinct
223 sequence types (ST). *C. rouxii* was also genetically heterogeneous, with 7 STs. The two
224 *C. diphtheriae* belonged to ST59 and ST699 (**Figure 2**). Six *C. ulcerans* STs and one *C. rouxii*
225 ST comprised more than one isolate. For these STs, geographical provenance and animal source
226 were heterogeneous, indicating spread across localities and host species (**Figures 2A and 3**).
227 Two *C. ulcerans* STs (ST325 and ST690) comprised both *tox*-positive and *tox*-negative isolates
228 (**Figure 2B**), implying that the loss or gain of the *tox* gene occurred within these lineages. We
229 noted that *C. rouxii* isolates were originating mainly from South-Western France (**Figure 3**).

230

231 **Clinical characteristics of toxigenic *C. ulcerans* isolates**

232 Eleven of the 24 toxigenic *C. ulcerans* were isolated from nasal swabs. They were taken
233 from 6 cats with chronic rhinitis and 3 rats, 1 dog and 1 rabbit. Two of the rats were bought
234 from the same pet shop, and they were both coinfecting with *Staphylococcus aureus*. Euthanasia
235 was chosen because of the zoonotic potential. Four other nasal swabs also harboured
236 microorganisms other than *C. ulcerans*, including *Pasteurella multocida*, *Escherichia coli*,
237 *Bacteroides spp*, *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* and *Staphylococcus pseudointermedius*.

238 The second most frequent isolation source was skin (9 of 24 cases) and included
239 wounds, pyoderma and abscesses. Seven of these *C. ulcerans* were sampled were from dogs
240 and two from cats. In 4 of the 9 skin cases, *C. ulcerans* was the only microorganism recovered
241 from the samples, while in 5 cases there was a coinfection; organisms encountered were
242 *Pasteurella multocida*, *Pasteurella canis*, *Proteus mirabilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*,
243 *Staphylococcus pseudointermedius*, *Streptococcus canis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and
244 *Streptococcus canis*.

245 Last, there were four ear infections by toxigenic *C. ulcerans*. These corresponded to
246 three dogs and one cat. In 3 cases, otitis was also associated with at least another microorganism
247 (*Proteus mirabilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Streptococcus canis* or *Streptococcus*
248 *dysgalactiae*).

249 Three of the 24 animals infected by a toxigenic *C. ulcerans* had a bacteriological follow-
250 up examination. Two cats, here named patients 3 and 4 (**Table 1**), had rhinitis with *C. ulcerans*
251 in pure culture, and tested positive again at control screenings 1 month and eighteen days after
252 the initial visit, respectively. Patient 3 had been treated 10 days with amoxicillin-clavulanate
253 without success. No further control was performed. In patient 4, a four week cure of cefovecin
254 did not eliminate the toxigenic *C. ulcerans*. However, a 1-month treatment with amoxicillin-
255 clavulanate, to which the isolate was susceptible, was followed by a negative result for
256 *C. ulcerans* on the control sample 4 months later.

257 One rabbit (patient 21) with *C. ulcerans* and *Pasteurella multocida* co-infection was still
258 positive for *C. ulcerans* and *P. multocida* despite treatment with marbofloxacin for 7 days and
259 then trimethoprim-sulfamethoxazole for 10 more days. No further control was performed.

260

261 **Clinical characteristics of non-toxicogenic *C. ulcerans* isolates cases**

262 The 27 non-toxicogenic *C. ulcerans* were retrieved from 6 cases of dermatitis (6 dogs), 7
263 cases of rhinitis (4 cats, 3 dogs), 8 cases of otitis (6 dogs, 2 cats), 1 case of cystitis (cat) et 5
264 cases of non-healing purulent wounds (3 cats, 2 dogs). In total, there were 10 cats and 17 dogs.
265 Three monoinfections were observed and concerned two cats with chronic rhinitis and one cat
266 with cystitis. The other infections were polymicrobial.

267 For the otitis cases, the polyinfections consisted of co-infection with *Streptococcus*
268 *canis* (in 3 cases), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (n=2), *Proteus mirabilis* (n=2), *Staphylococcus*
269 *pseudointermedius* (n=2) and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (n=1). The polyinfections in the cases of
270 rhinitis were co-infections with *Staphylococcus intermedius* (n=2), *Pasteurella multocida* and
271 *Bordetella bronchiseptica* (n=1), *Klebsiella oxytoca* (n=1) and *Staphylococcus aureus* (n=1).
272 The dermatitis polyinfections were co-infections with *Staphylococcus pseudointermedius*
273 (n=5), *Proteus mirabilis* (n=3) and *Pasteurella canis* (n=1). Last, polyinfections of sores
274 comprised *Escherichia coli* (n=2), *Staphylococcus aureus/pseudointermedius* (1 case each),
275 *Pasteurella dagmatis/multocida* (1 case each) and *Streptococcus dysgalactiae* (n=1).

276 There was only one follow up available, for patient 25. It was a 5 year old cat with
277 chronic rhinitis and a *C. ulcerans* monoinfection. This patient stayed positive for non-toxicogenic
278 *C. ulcerans* during 6 months. In between, the cat was treated with doxycycline, to which the
279 strain was tested susceptible in the 2 antibiograms before and after treatment.

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281 **Clinical characteristics of *C. diphtheriae* and *C. rouxii* isolates cases**

282 The two cases of *C. diphtheriae* were toxicogenic and consisted of conjunctivitis and
283 pastern dermatitis in two horses. Both cases were polyinfections, in which *Streptococcus*
284 *dysgalactiae* (conjunctivitis) and *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Enterobacter cloacae* (pastern
285 dermatitis) were also found.

286 *C. rouxii* infections were observed in 9 dogs and 2 cats and were all non-toxicogenic. There
287 were 9 otitis cases (8 dogs and 1 cat) and two remaining non-healing wounds (one dog and one
288 cat). *C. rouxii* was identified retrospectively by MLST, as this species was only recognized as
289 a separate species during the study period (in 2020), and as MALDI-TOF still identifies *C.*
290 *rouxii* as *C. diphtheriae*, based on the MALDI Biotyper Compass database version 4.1 (version
291 (100).

292 Almost all *C. rouxii* infections were polyinfections. There was only one bacterial
293 monoinfection but in this case there was also a *Malassezia* proliferation in the ear of the cat
294 (**Table 1**). The most frequent (n=5) co-infecting bacteria was *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* as
295 expected in case of otitis. Other co-infecting bacteria were *Proteus mirabilis* (n=3),
296 *Staphylococcus sp.* (n=2), *Streptococcus canis* (n=2), *Corynebacterium amycolatum* (n=1),
297 *Citrobacter koseri* (n=1) and anaerobic bacteria (n=1).

298 The age of the animals of this group ranged from 1 year to 13 years of age with no
299 statistically significant difference between age groups.

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Discussion

329 We report on the occurrence, clinical and microbiological characteristics of infection
330 cases caused in pet animals by members of the *Corynebacteria* of the *diphtheriae* complex in
331 France. Although *C. ulcerans* was the most frequent species, *C. rouxii* and, more rarely,
332 *C. diphtheriae* were also found.

333 All isolates initially identified as *C. diphtheriae* from dogs and cats were in fact
334 *C. rouxii*, as identified by MLST gene sequences. This important observation suggests that this
335 novel species has been overlooked, and in fact appears more prevalent than *C. diphtheriae* itself
336 in animal infections. As all *C. rouxii* infections, mostly of ears, were co-infections with other
337 bacteria or the fungus *Malassezia*, this species may represent a commensal in dogs and cats. So
338 far, all *C. rouxii* isolates are *tox*-negative, with the exception of isolates from two cats from the
339 USA (Hall et al) but in these two isolates, the *tox* gene was disrupted and toxin was not
340 produced. Previously, *C. rouxii* has been isolated from cutaneous infections, vascularitis and
341 peritonitis in humans and a purulent orbital cellulitis in a dog (Badell et al., 2020). Our study
342 correspond to the largest group of infections with *C. rouxii* reported so far. We suggest that *C.*
343 *rouxii* may represent another zoonotic pathogen, as pets may clearly serve as a reservoir for
344 these human infections. However, so far, no case of transmission of *C. rouxii* between human
345 and animals was documented. *C. rouxii* was more frequently isolated in South-Western France
346 (Figure 3), but was genetically diverse. Although the sampling is still limited, this may reflect
347 the existence of local conditions that favor the infections of dogs by *C. rouxii* in this part of
348 France.

349 Toxigenic *C. diphtheriae* was isolated from 2 horses. Mixed wound infections in horses
350 were previously described (Henricson et al., 2000; Leggett et al., 2010), and colonisation with
351 *C. diphtheriae* was reported in 6.9% of slaughter horses in Romania (Stănică et al., 1968). The
352 pathogenic potential of *C. diphtheriae* in horses is questionable given its report from
353 polymicrobial infections or asymptomatic carriage. Given the well established human-to-
354 human transmission of *C. diphtheriae* and possible asymptomatic carriage, the possibility should
355 be considered that the detection of this pathogen in horses corresponds to reverse zoonosis.

356 *C. ulcerans* is now well-established as a zoonotic member of the *Cdc*. Human cases
357 have been associated with animal contacts, and in several cases the genetic fingerprinting of
358 isolates supported an epidemiological link between the animal and human isolates, strongly
359 establishing the zoonotic character of *C. ulcerans* (Lartigue et al., 2005; Othieno et al., 2019;
360 Vandentorren et al., 2014). The emergence of *C. ulcerans* has been noted in France, Germany
361 and the UK (Haut Conseil de la santé publique, 2019; Robert Koch-Institut, 2018; Wagner et
362 al., 2010).

363 This is the first study based on the systematic analysis of a very large animal cohort
364 (18 308 samples), which provides data on the frequency of *C. ulcerans* in various types of
365 clinical samples from animals. Abbott and colleagues (Abbott et al., 2020) found 7 *C. ulcerans*
366 among 804 nasal samples (0.87%), whereas Katsukawa and colleagues found 44 *C. ulcerans* in
367 583 pharyngeal samples (7.5%). We found 51 *C. ulcerans*, including 24 tox-positive ones, in
368 18 308 clinical samples, mostly in the nasal swabs (18 samples).

369 Given the wide geographic distribution we observed, the reporting of *C. ulcerans* in this
370 study does not seem affected by a bias caused by local events of transmission. In addition, the
371 genetic diversity of *C. ulcerans* isolates indicates that the reporting of this pathogen cannot be
372 attributed to the clonal spread of a single emerging strain of *C. ulcerans*. Whether the increase
373 in cases is due to changes in diagnostic practice (*i.e.*, MALDI-TOF) or increasing awareness of
374 the necessity to report and test for the presence of the diphtheria toxin, rather than a real
375 epidemiological phenomenon of emergence, remains unclear. *C. ulcerans* of animal origin were
376 only sent sporadically to the NRC before 2019. Awareness of this zoonotic bacteria remains
377 low among veterinarians and veterinary laboratories, among which it is often considered as an
378 commensal bacteria of animals.

379 The *C. ulcerans* reservoir is still unknown (Elena Hacker et al., 2016a). Whether pet
380 animals represent the primary reservoir, or (more probably) are themselves contaminated by *C.*
381 *ulcerans* from other animal species or sources, is an important question. Toxigenic *C. ulcerans*
382 infections were reported in wildlife carnivores such as foxes, otters and owls (Foster et al.,
383 2002) and insectivores (hedgehogs and Japanese shrew owls) (Katsukawa et al., 2016b),
384 whereas non-toxigenic *C. ulcerans* infection seems to be more frequent in omnivores (wild
385 boars) and herbivores (roe deer) (Berger et al., 2019a). Only wild animals with major symptoms
386 are diagnosed, while the asymptomatic carriership is rarely investigated (Berger et al., 2019b).
387 Transmission by predatory hunting was supported by a study showing high serum diphtheria
388 antitoxin titers in hunting dogs (Katsukawa et al., 2016a). A reservoir of symptomatic or
389 asymptomatic carriers in small wild mammals such as herbivores, lagomorphs or rodents, which
390 may be preys to dogs and cats, should be further investigated. Here, we reported 4 cases of
391 toxigenic *C. ulcerans* in rats or rabbits. Although the cases described in this study are from
392 symptomatic animals, an asymptomatic carrier state of *C. ulcerans* in dogs, cats, horses, rodents
393 and wild life animals has been described in other studies (Dias et al., 2010; Katsukawa et al.,
394 2016a, 2016b; Othieno et al., 2019; Vandentorren et al., 2014). Future studies should investigate
395 the presence of *Cdc* in healthy animals to better understand and control its transmission to pets.

396 There is evidence for a pathogenic potential of *C. ulcerans* in animals (Elena Hacker et
397 al., 2016a). Here, *C. ulcerans* was often isolated from nasal swabs in cats with chronic rhinitis.
398 While acute feline upper respiratory infections are mostly caused by viruses (*Feline*

399 *Herpesvirus-1* and *feline Calicivirus*) (Lappin et al., 2017) and are most of the time self-
400 limiting, chronic rhinitis is more concerning. In general, bacteriological examinations
401 performed on nasal swabs are often not useful because of the presence of commensal flora and
402 only a few bacteria are considered primary pathogens (Lappin et al., 2017). Toxigenic
403 *C. ulcerans* may be implicated in the clinical manifestation of rhinitis. Importantly in 7 cases
404 of rhinitis, *C. ulcerans* was the only infective agent retrieved from the nasal swabs, a fact that
405 strongly suggests a primary pathogenic nature of *C. ulcerans* in cats, consistent with a previous
406 study (Abbott et al., 2020). A limitation of the present study is that it was performed
407 retrospectively; hence, the final diagnosis as well as the complete clinical picture were not
408 available.

409 The pathogenicity of non-toxigenic strains is not well understood. Here, a few
410 mono-infections by non-toxigenic *C. ulcerans* (2 cases of rhinitis and 1 cystitis) are reported.
411 The infections could be favoured by other virulence factors of *C. ulcerans*, such as
412 phospholipase D (Elena Hacker et al., 2016a).

413 Large dog breeds were disproportionately affected by *C. ulcerans*, and 32% of them were
414 German Shepherds. This interesting observation might be explained by a closer contact with
415 small mammals, as large dogs are generally kept outdoors. But it could also reflect a breed
416 predisposition, as German Shepherd dogs are more susceptible to pyoderma (Rosser, 2006) and
417 other bacterial infections, for example by *Ehrlichia canis* (Nyindo et al., 1980). Six cases of
418 German Shepherd in this study presented with pyoderma or otitis. Further studies will be needed
419 to investigate a possible dog breed predisposition to *C. ulcerans*.

420 *C. ulcerans* isolates tested susceptible to most of the antibiotics tested, except
421 clindamycin. With the current clindamycin breakpoints for *Corynebacterium spp.* (0.5 mg/L)
422 this resistance can be considered as a distinctive feature of *C. ulcerans*, since most typical
423 isolates display this characteristic (“eucast: Consultations,” n.d.; Marosevic et al., 2020),
424 whereas *C. diphtheriae* isolates are clearly more susceptible to this agent, as was the case here.

425 In at least 3 cases of toxigenic *C. ulcerans* and 1 case of non-toxigenic *C. ulcerans*
426 (patient number 3, 4, 21 and 25), the infection persisted, despite antibiotic susceptibility in the
427 2 preceding testings as discussed in previous papers (Lartigue et al., 2005; Vandentorren et al.,
428 2014; Abbott et al., 2020). We can only speculate that chronic infections might involve some
429 intracellular bacteria (Moore et al., 2015), which would be more accessible to macrolides which
430 can reach high intracellular concentrations, compared to beta-lactams. Systemic infections by
431 *C. diphtheriae* suggest that this pathogen is not only able to attach to host epithelial cells, but
432 is able to gain access to deeper tissues and to live intracellularly (Ott et al., 2010).
433 *Corynebacterium* guidelines in humans recommend the use of beta-lactams or macrolides

434 (azithromycin). Yet, while chronic human carriers can be treated with azithromycin or
435 rifampicin, the use of the latter is forbidden in the veterinary field.

436 Recent data suggest to use spiramycin in cases of animal infection by *C. ulcerans*. A
437 10-day course of the combination of spiramycin and metronidazole was successful to clear
438 *C. ulcerans* from a dog, and a 6-day course of the same antibiotic combination was successful
439 in cats (Abbott et al., 2020; UK Health Security Agency, 2022). Therefore, during the study
440 period, spiramycin was added to the antibiogram. However, we found that susceptibility was
441 only intermediate in most of the cases. Therefore, azithromycin was tested at the end of the
442 study and we suggest to include this antibiotic in the antibiogram, as it is easily accessible for
443 veterinarians. Besides, the only veterinarian formulation of spiramycin is an association with
444 metronidazole, which has side effects and does not have any effect on *corynebacteria*.

445 The efficiency of the antibiotic treatment should be verified ideally by 2 samples, taken
446 5 to 7 days following completion of the antibiotic course. The use of macrolides, the kind of
447 macrolide (azithromycin rather than a spiramycin/metronidazole combination) and the optimal
448 treatment duration should be investigated by future studies.

449 These work is relevant to the development of veterinarian guidelines in case of *Cdc*
450 infections. Currently, in France no recommendations are established around the detection of
451 toxigenic *Cdc* in animals, either for their animal or human contacts. From a public health
452 perspective, the zoonotic potential of toxigenic *C. diphtheriae* or *C. ulcerans* in chronic skin
453 infections, non-healing wounds, rhinitis and otitis, justifies investigating these body locations
454 for such pathogens, and these samples should not be considered to reveal only commensal
455 organisms. This would be more in line with the fact that in case of diphtheria due to toxigenic
456 *C. ulcerans* in a human, recommendations exist in France that contact animals should be
457 sampled and treated (Haut Conseil de la santé publique, 2011, 2019, 2021).

458 Toxigenic *Corynebacteria* in animals are not mandatory to notify, and the costs of
459 treatment, clearance swabs and sampling of contact animals clearly represent a limitation for
460 the implementation of follow-up investigations and control measures. Asymptomatic human
461 carriers of toxigenic strains are treated with the same antibiotic regimen as symptomatic cases,
462 with clearance swabs to ensure eradication. From an epidemiological viewpoint, it would be
463 coherent to follow the same practice for animals, and this should be discussed between
464 veterinary and human health institutions.

465 We suggest that in case of *Cdc* detection in animals, the veterinary laboratory should be
466 encouraged to send the sample to a reference laboratory for analysis of the presence of the *tox*
467 gene. In case of positivity, animal owners and veterinary staff should be monitored for clinical
468 signs during a period of 10 days and their vaccination status should be controlled. If possible,

469 animals should be isolated until clearance is proven. Other animals of the same household
470 should also be sampled by an oropharyngeal, nasal and ear swab (and wound swab if a wound
471 is present), and antimicrobial treatment should be considered if no swabs are taken. Future
472 studies should address how to manage chronic carrier states in pet animals.

473

Figure legends

474 **Figure 1. Geographic distribution of Cdc infection cases in pets.**

475 The 51 *Corynebacterium ulcerans*, 2 *C. diphtheriae* and 9 *C. rouxii* are displayed within their
476 administrative Departement of origin, with a species-specific symbol. *tox* gene-bearing strains
477 are indicated in red, non-*tox* gene-bearing in grey. For two cases, location was not available
478 and there are therefore not represented here.

479

480 **Figure 2. MLST diversity of Cdc isolates from pets.**

481 (A) Minimum spanning tree of 7-gene MLST profiles, colored in function of animal host
482 species.

483 (B) Same, colored by diphtheria toxin gene presence .

484 The graphs were obtained using the GrapeTree tool, which is plugged onto the BIGSdb platform
485 ([https://bigsdbs.pasteur.fr/cgi-](https://bigsdbs.pasteur.fr/cgi-bin/bigsdbs/bigsdbs.pl?db=pubmlst_diphtheria_isolates&page=plugin&name=GrapeTree)
486 [bin/bigsdbs/bigsdbs.pl?db=pubmlst_diphtheria_isolates&page=plugin&name=GrapeTree](https://bigsdbs.pasteur.fr/cgi-bin/bigsdbs/bigsdbs.pl?db=pubmlst_diphtheria_isolates&page=plugin&name=GrapeTree)).

487

488 **Figure 3. Geographic distribution of the MLST sequence types (ST).**

489 Colors correspond to STs, as indicated on the Minimum spanning tree and on the key. For two
490 cases, location was not available and there are therefore not represented here.

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505

506 **Authors license statement**

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511

512 **Declaration of interest statement**

513 The authors declare that 2 authors are employees of Cerba Vet, which performs diagnostic
514 testing on a commercial basis.

515

516 **Ethical approval statement**

517 Authors declare ethics approval was not needed for this retrospective study.

518

519 **Author contributions**

520 KM and SB conceived, designed, and coordinated the study. GR and EB performed the
521 microbiological cultures of the isolates and their biochemical and molecular characterizations.
522 MH analyzed the sequence data and produced the figures. GA and KM reviewed the clinical
523 source data of the isolates. KM and SB wrote the initial version of the manuscript. All authors
524 provided input to, read, and approved the final manuscript.

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719

Figure 1

Figure 2

A.

B.

Figure 3

DISCUSSION GÉNÉRALE ET PERSPECTIVES

Les maladies infectieuses restent une menace permanente. Une raison parmi tant d'autres est le phénomène de la RAM, en raison de l'évolution des pathogènes, en particulier par l'acquisition d'éléments génétiques à partir d'autres organismes. Par conséquent, il est primordial de détecter rapidement et contrôler des maladies infectieuses. Le séquençage du génome offre un accès aux caractéristiques importantes des pathogènes comme la virulence, la RAM, l'échappement partiel aux vaccins, ou leur transmissibilité. Cependant, pour tirer pleinement parti de la précision du séquençage génomique et répondre aux différents besoins des acteurs de santé, une harmonisation des concepts et outils bio-informatiques afférents est nécessaire.

Au cours de cette thèse, un ensemble d'outils et méthodes d'analyse des séquences génomiques, ont été développés afin de combler certaines lacunes existantes. Deux axes ont formé les composantes de ce travail : (i) comprendre les mécanismes expliquant la RAM par des analyses génomiques, et (ii) développer une taxonomie des souches bactériennes robuste et stable au cours au temps.

Le **premier axe** a surtout concerné l'étude des génomes de *C. diphtheriae* à travers à la génomique comparative, qui jusqu'à présent avait été peu exploré. De nombreux génomes ont été examinés pour améliorer la compréhension de la structure génétique globale de la population, en relation avec la diversité biochimique (biovars), les mécanismes de résistance et la virulence.

Historiquement, les isolats de *C. diphtheriae* étaient discriminés selon leurs biovars, mais les liens entre les biovars et la structure phylogénétique sont restés obscurs. L'étude de Sangal *et al.* [29] a suggéré une absence de structuration phylogénétique des biovars. Les études présentées dans cette thèse étudient un grand nombre de génomes de *C. diphtheriae*, chose qui n'avait jamais été réalisée auparavant. Les résultats montrent clairement que les souches de *C. diphtheriae* sont très génétiquement diverses et qu'elles appartiennent à plusieurs centaines de lignées ('sublineages') profondes, qui sont peu organisées entre elles. En d'autres termes, la phylogénie de *C. diphtheriae* présente une structure en étoile, avec de multiples lignées qui émergent à partir d'un ancêtre commun. Cependant, les analyses phylogénétiques présentées ici ont mis en évidence que les deux biovars principaux de *C. diphtheriae*, Gravis et Mitis, sont étroitement liés à deux lignées majeurs phylogénétiques distinctes. Toutefois, l'enracinement de la phylogénie qui permettrait de déterminer l'état ancestral du biovar reste encore inconnu. Les deux lignées majeures sont également discriminées par la présence d'un groupe de gènes comprenant le gène *spuA* (positif pour Gravis et négatif pour Mitis) qui code pour une enzyme extracellulaire déramifiant le glycogène. Dans le Chapitre 1 (Figure 2), l'hypothèse a été émise que Gravis dérivait de la diversité de Mitis (qui représenterait alors l'état ancestral pour *C. diphtheriae*) étant donné que les espèces proches de *C. diphtheriae* (*C. belfantii* et *C. rouxii*), ne possèdent pas le gène *spuA*. Cependant, les analyses du Chapitre 4

(Figure 1) ont abouti à une hypothèse inverse lorsque différents génomes ont été utilisés comme groupes externes pour l'enracinement. Par conséquent, il est possible que Gravis soit en réalité la branche ancestrale à partir de laquelle la branche Mitis a évolué. Une étude spécifique du locus *spuA* devra être réalisée afin d'éclaircir cette question. Par ailleurs, il est nécessaire de poursuivre les recherches afin d'identifier d'autres déterminants moléculaires qui pourraient expliquer le biovar Gravis chez les souches dépourvues du gène *spuA*, ainsi que le biovar Belfanti dans certaines souches où aucune mutation n'a été identifiée dans le cluster de réduction de nitrates.

La RAM a rarement été considérée comme un problème majeur dans le traitement de *C. diphtheriae*. Toutefois, les études présentées ici (Chapitre 1, 2 et 7), montrent que certaines souches ont acquis une résistance à une ou plusieurs classes d'antibiotiques. La génomique a ouvert l'étude des mécanismes de résistance et permet de définir les plus prévalents. Une exposition différente aux antimicrobiens dans les régions du monde pourrait expliquer l'hétérogénéité observée de la RAM. Bien que l'érythromycine et la pénicilline soient les antibiotiques recommandés en cas de diphtérie, les mécanismes de résistance à ces antibiotiques sont mal connus chez *C. diphtheriae*.

Parmi les espèces de *Corynebacterium*, comprenant *C. diphtheriae*, le mécanisme de résistance aux macrolides le plus fréquemment décrit est la présence du gène *ermX*. Ici, le gène *ermX* a bien été trouvé, toutefois l'étude du contexte génomique de ce gène reste à être analysé. Par ailleurs, l'outil de génotypage développé a permis de détecter un second gène (*ermC*), qui semble expliquer la résistance aux macrolides chez des espèces du genre *Staphylococcus* (<https://card.mcmaster.ca/ontology/36389>). Par conséquent, une étude est à envisager afin de décrire précisément l'implication du gène *ermC* sur la résistance chez *C. diphtheriae*.

Concernant la pénicilline, bien que le génome de *C. diphtheriae* possède sept gènes de PBP chromosomiques, aucun lien n'a été fait entre la variation de ces gènes et la sensibilité à la pénicilline. Au cours de cette thèse, quelques associations relativement faibles ont été découvertes entre cette variation et la sensibilité à la pénicilline, mais elles étaient limitées. En revanche, un gène additionnel ayant été nommé *pbp2m* a été identifié comme expliquant la résistance aux bêta-lactamines chez un certain nombre de souches. À noter, ce même gène a été trouvé (simultanément à l'étude réalisée en Chapitre 1) dans un contexte génomique différent par Forde *et al.* [171]. Bien que ce gène *pbp2m* a été étudié expérimentalement chez *C. glumaticum*, il reste encore à démontrer son implication directe dans la résistance chez *C. diphtheriae*. Il a été observé que pour les souches collectées en France, la présence de *pbp2m* n'entraîne qu'une augmentation modérée de la CMI, contrairement à la souche décrite par Forde *et al.* [171] qui a une CMI beaucoup plus élevée. Cependant, la raison de cette différence n'a pas été expliquée.

La recherche dans les séquences génomiques du principal facteur de virulence, le gène codant la toxine diphtérique, montre qu'il est présent dans de nombreuses lignées ('sublineages') de *C. diphtheriae*. Les déterminants de cette distribution ne sont pas connus pour le moment et nécessitent des recherches futures. Une hypothèse est qu'un récepteur de phage présent ou absent dans les différentes lignées pourrait expliquer cette distribution. Il est intéressant de noter qu'environ 10% des lignées regroupent à la fois des souches *tox*-positives et *tox*-négatives, ce

qui suggère une dynamique évolutive relativement rapide du phage toxigène. Actuellement, aucun avantage ou coût sélectif du portage du phage n'a été démontré. Une hypothèse de gain est que la toxine confère un avantage aux souches de *C. diphtheriae*, en leur permettant de tuer des cellules hôtes et ainsi leur donner accès à certains ou plus de nutriments. À l'inverse, où la toxine et/ou le phage entraîne un coût, cela pourrait expliquer la perte de la toxine dans certaines lignées qui l'avaient acquise. La possibilité que des isolats cliniques *tox*-négatifs puissent acquérir le phage et se convertir en *C. diphtheriae* toxigène, a toujours été considérée comme un risque durant les infections à *C. diphtheriae*. Jusqu'à présent cette éventualité n'a été que rarement observée et n'a jamais été démontrée à l'ère de la génomique, c'est-à-dire avec un typage suffisamment précis des souches.

Bien qu'à première vue, le gène *tox* apparaisse distribué non-uniformément dans les différents pays, cette observation est à interpréter très prudemment dû au contexte de l'hétérogénéité des systèmes de surveillance. En France, la diphtérie est une maladie à déclaration obligatoire, impliquant une analyse systématique des isolats, ce qu'il peut expliquer une prévalence plus faible de la toxine diphtérique. Les isolats *tox*-négatifs sont souvent isolés de manière fortuite dans les prélèvements cutanés et sont envoyées au CNR pour les analyser. En revanche, historiquement, et toujours actuellement dans de nombreux pays, les souches de *C. diphtheriae* sont découvertes exclusivement sur des cas cliniques typiques de diphtérie, et il n'y a pas d'étude systématique des souches isolées fortuitement. Ceci explique un taux proche de 100% des souches portant la toxine, pour les souches de certains pays recensées dans les bases de données publiques.

Cette thèse n'a pas analysé la présence de corynéphages dans les génomes de *C. diphtheriae* ni leur point d'intégration génomique. Pour répondre à cette question, une analyse de séquençage complet en un seul contig des génomes est nécessaire, ce qui n'a pas été effectué. L'utilisation de séquençage de troisième génération permettra également une meilleure compréhension de la diversité des corynéphages. De plus, une mise en corrélation avec la phylogénie des souches permettrait éventuellement d'établir le spectre d'hôte des corynéphages.

Comprendre la dynamique du phage et de la toxine par rapport à la structure globale de la population de *C. diphtheriae* reste une question importante pour un futur proche.

L'outil DIPHTOSCAN est une première approche visant à aborder les points discutés ci-dessus sur des données Illumina, mais pourra être utilisé sur des séquences complètes. Cet outil a aussi permis de décrire les bases de la RAM chez *C. diphtheriae*. La surveillance des gènes circulant majoritairement dans les populations devient possible y compris pour des groupes peu expérimentés en bioinformatique. En outre, cet outil a également permis de compiler une liste exhaustive des facteurs de virulence impliqués chez *C. diphtheriae* en se basant sur l'étude de la littérature. Comme mentionné dans le Chapitre 2, les résultats ont révélé une distribution clairement structurée de ces facteurs de virulence, qui est associée aux deux principales lignées Mitis et Gravis. Cette compilation est la première à notre connaissance et sera utile pour les études futures de la virulence chez *C. diphtheriae*.

Cet outil présente l'avantage d'être utilisable directement sur la machine de l'utilisateur, avec une option simple pour mettre à jour les bases de données (RAM et typage MLST). De plus, la base de données spécifique de *C. diphtheriae* est évolutive, une ou plusieurs séquences

génomiques peuvent être ajoutées. Toutefois, l'outil DIPHTOSCAN demande encore quelques améliorations, par exemple au niveau « computationnel », car il reste relativement long lorsqu'une grande collection de génomes doit être analysée. Il est également prévu de le combiner avec un outil de construction d'arbre tel que *JolyTree* [140, 141], puis en présence d'un tableau de métadonnées, des templates interprétables par l'outil en ligne de visualisation d'arbre « iTOL » (<https://itol.embl.de/>) permettront être générés. Bien que la fonctionnalité permettant l'identification du regroupement et de l'organisation des gènes de résistance entre eux (l'étude du contexte génomique de la RAM), ait déjà été ajouté à DIPHTOSCAN, l'analyse n'a pas encore réalisée. De plus, la présence ou les variants de certains des facteurs de virulence dans la population de *C. diphtheriae* doivent à être analysés plus en détails.

Le **deuxième axe** principal de cette thèse a consisté en la proposition d'un système de code-barres pour la taxonomie génomiques des souches bactériennes, qui combine LINcodes et cgMLST, apportant les avantages combinés de stabilité et de robustesse. Jusqu'à présent, ces deux caractéristiques majeures des classifications ont été difficiles à réconcilier.

L'attribution d'un code cgLIN unique ou d'un préfixe à chaque souche ou lignée permet de la distinguer des autres souches ou lignées. Ce code permet également de déterminer rapidement la similitude entre les différentes souches, ce qui peut grandement aider à comprendre leur variabilité et à communiquer à leur sujet. Cette approche pourrait être bénéfique dans l'étude des épidémies et la prévention des infections, et les codes cgLIN pourraient également aider à identifier de nouvelles souches pathogènes émergentes en utilisant leur préfixe distinctif.

La méthode cgLIN offre un avantage considérable en termes de stabilité du système de nommage en attribuant à chaque génome un code unique et définitif. Elle résout également un problème critique rencontré par les méthodes de classification de type *single linkage (Slink)* souvent utilisées dans les approches MLST, cgMLST et MLSL. En effet, la méthode *Slink* est sujette à la fusion de groupes préexistants à mesure que la diversité de l'échantillon augmente, ce qui peut affecter la classification. Ainsi, la méthode cgLIN représente une réelle amélioration dans la classification des souches bactériennes.

Indépendamment de cette thèse l'approche HierCC a été développée offrant également une stabilité de la nomenclature. Cependant, cette méthode implique le développement de la nomenclature en deux étapes distinctes : la première étape utilise la méthode de classification *Slink*, puis une seconde étape dite 'production', nécessitant un échantillonnage important avant de passer au mode 'production'. Notre approche cgLIN n'a pas cet inconvénient. Une comparaison détaillée entre ces deux approches, en simulant l'évolution bactérienne sur une phylogénie donnée, devra être réalisée dans l'avenir pour mieux définir la compatibilité et les avantages de ces deux approches.

Il est essentiel de concevoir les nomenclatures de manière stratégique pour garantir leur acceptation et leur adoption par la communauté scientifique. Un élément essentiel est de créer des liens avec les systèmes nomenclaturaux précédemment établis. Pour *K. pneumoniae* et *C. diphtheriae*, une continuité avec les nomenclatures existantes a été proposée, et une méthode

a été développée qui permet d'hériter la nomenclature standard très répandue 7-gene MLST, sur la nomenclature des préfixes cgLIN codes ou single linkage (dans le cas de *C. diphtheriae*). Chez *C. diphtheriae*, les lignées définies avec un seuil de 500 mismatches, semblent peu impactés par l'instabilité des méthodes de classifications single linkage. Les résultats montrent que même avec l'ajout de quelques centaines génomes (cf. Chapitre 2) à un système précédent ([172], cf. Chapitre 4), le single linkage n'a pas souffert de fusion de groupes. Par conséquent, cela suggère qu'un système cgLIN codes ne semble pas toujours nécessaire. Bien qu'aucun problème n'ait été signalé jusqu'à présent, il serait cependant judicieux de le définir pour garantir un système robuste et stable à mesure que des milliers de génomes seront disponibles.

Le système de codes-barres génomiques est désormais disponible publiquement via la plateforme BIGSdb permettant une utilisation immédiate par la communauté. En l'intégrant dans une plateforme déjà utilisée par la communauté, cela facilite son application et à l'avenir son extension à d'autres espèces bactériennes possédant un schéma cgMLST. Cependant, la définition des seuils associées aux cgLIN codes demande un travail préliminaire sur la structure de la population. Il est fortement recommandé d'avoir une base de génomes qui représente la diversité globale de la population et d'avoir une connaissance précise de l'espèce afin connaître les pertinences cliniques et les besoins de la communauté concernée.

Dans le futur, chaque espèce bactérienne pourrait avoir une base de données publique de cgLIN codes qui devra être régulièrement mise à jour en temps réel pour inclure les nouveaux génomes séquencés quotidiennement par les réseaux de surveillance microbiologique. Ce système d'encodage automatisable, rapide et standardisé aboutirait à une nomenclature universelle qui pourrait révolutionner les études de la biodiversité, l'épidémiologie génomique internationale et la surveillance des maladies infectieuses.

Un autre point mineur de cet axe est la génomique peut être utilisée à grande échelle pour définir de nouvelles espèces. Dans le Chapitre 5 de cette thèse, une nouvelle espèce, *C. rouxii*, a été définie. Les premières analyses montrent que cette espèce est médicalement et écologiquement distincte (probablement zoonotique) de *C. diphtheriae*, toutefois un nombre limité d'isolats ont été échantillonnés. Depuis sa description, un nombre plus conséquent de génomes commencent à être disponibles, et l'étude de ceux-ci est une perspective de ce travail.

Enfin, l'ensemble des concepts et outils bio-informatiques développés dans cette thèse, ont été motivés par, et appliqués à, des études de cas. Tout d'abord, l'étude de l'épidémie de diphtérie déclarée au Yémen a été un travail précurseur pour le développement de DIPHTOSCAN. Ensuite, (i) l'étude de la sous-lignée SL453 de *C. diphtheriae*, (ii) d'une cohorte de patients en Nouvelle Calédonie et (iii) l'étude de cas de souches de corynébactéries chez les animaux, ont bénéficié de l'outil DIPHTOSCAN. De plus, une des méthodes de classification (MLSL) a été appliquée sur l'ensemble des études de cas et également révélée son utilité. Par exemple, dans l'étude de la cohorte de patients en Nouvelle Calédonie, celle-ci a permis de détecter des lignées ('sublignées') présentes également dans le reste du monde. Et, à une échelle plus fine, la classification génomique des souches a confirmé les cas groupés épidémiologiques.

En conclusion, cette thèse a contribué à répondre à des questions importantes en biologie de l'infection chez *C. diphtheriae* et *K. pneumoniae* et à développer des concepts et des outils répondant aux besoins actuels des professionnels de la microbiologie médicale et de la santé publique. Grâce à la rapidité et aux coûts réduits du séquençage, les laboratoires de microbiologie peuvent avoir accès à cette nouvelle approche en routine. Leur utilisation et interprétation avec des méthodes standardisées et automatisées faciliteront leur analyse, contribuant ainsi à un meilleur contrôle des maladies infectieuses. Nous espérons que ces avancées contribueront à améliorer la santé publique et la prévention des maladies infectieuses.

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TABLE DES FIGURES

Figure 1. Mécanisme d'action de la toxine diphtérique.....	12
Figure 2. Adhésion de <i>C. diphtheriae</i> : un processus multifactoriel.....	13
Figure 3. Les clusters de gènes de fimbriae de la souche NCTC 13129.....	14
Figure 4. Répartition des gènes pbp sur le génome de la souche NCTC13129.....	16
Figure 5. Carte physique de l'intégron de classe 1 de <i>Corynebacterium diphtheriae</i> FRC24.....	17
Figure 6. Facteurs de virulence caractérisés dans les souches classiques et hypervirulentes <i>K. pneumoniae</i>	20
Figure 7. Historique des approches taxonomiques et nomenclaturales	26
Figure 8. Système SnapperDB.....	38
Figure 9. Principe de la méthode MLST (Multi-Locus Sequence Typing).....	40
Figure 10. Minimum spanning tree des 7,388 profils MLST (Multi-Locus Sequence Typing).	41
Figure 11. Les étapes de la classification Single Linkage.....	42
Figure 12. Nomenclature MLSL (MultiLevel Single Linkage).....	43
Figure 13. Structure et concept du système de typage génomique multiniveau (MGT).....	46
Figure 14. Les LIN et leur assignation.....	48
Figure 15. Arbre phylogénétique du genre <i>Corynebacterium</i> montrant les relations phylogénétiques entre <i>C. diphtheriae</i> , les membres du groupe Cdc et plusieurs espèces représentatives.....	51
Figure 16. Arbre phylogénétique du genre <i>Klebsiella</i> montrant les relations phylogénétiques entre <i>K. pneumoniae</i> , les membres du groupe KpSC, plusieurs espèces représentatives du genre <i>Klebsiella</i> et différents autres genres de la famille Enterobacteriaceae.....	52
Figure 17. Minimum spanning tree (MSTree) sur la base des profils alléliques de <i>K. pneumoniae</i>	54

TABLE DES TABLEAUX

Tableau 1. Caractéristiques générales du génome de <i>C. diphtheriae</i> NCTC 13129.....	9
Tableau 2. Propriétés phénotypiques des biovars de <i>C. diphtheriae</i>	10
Tableau 3. Résumé des facteurs expérimentalement vérifiés impliqués dans le processus d'adhésion de <i>C. diphtheriae</i>	15
Tableau 4. Caractéristiques du génome rapportées par Kleborate.....	19
Tableau 5. Caractéristiques générales des génome de <i>K. pneumoniae</i>	21
Tableau 6. Désignations des variants.	31

Taxonomie génomique des souches bactériennes et émergence de l'antibiorésistance

Résumé :

Les maladies infectieuses font partie des préoccupations mondiales en santé publique, en particulier en raison de la résistance aux antimicrobiens chez certaines bactéries pathogènes. L'espèce *Klebsiella pneumoniae* est identifiée comme l'une des bactéries multirésistantes les plus préoccupantes. *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*, responsable de la diphtérie, reste largement sensible aux antibiotiques de première intention dont la pénicilline et peut être contrôlée par les vaccins, mais ré-émerge lorsque la couverture vaccinale est insuffisante. Parmi les moyens de contrôle des maladies infectieuses, la détection et l'identification précise de ces agents pathogènes, ainsi que leur suivi épidémiologique, jouent un rôle primordial. La mise en œuvre du séquençage génomique a révolutionné le génotypage bactérien grâce à son haut pouvoir discriminant, qui permet la distinction des agents pathogènes à l'échelle des souches. Le séquençage génomique permet également la détection de variants et de leurs caractéristiques importantes, telles que leur virulence ou leur résistance.

Les travaux de recherche de cette thèse s'articulent sur deux axes principaux.

Le premier axe apporte des analyses bio-informatiques de la structure populationnelle de la résistance aux antibiotiques chez *C. diphtheriae*. Une étude d'association génomique (GWAS) a été réalisée pour définir les bases moléculaires de la résistance, ainsi que les associations avec la production de toxine diphtérique et d'autres caractéristiques des souches. Un nouveau gène de résistance à la pénicilline a été découvert sur un élément mobile chez *C. diphtheriae*. Un outil de génotypage a été développé spécifiquement pour *C. diphtheriae*, pour laquelle les liens entre génotypes et phénotypes cliniques sont mal connus. Cet outil consolide et facilite la détection et le génotypage des principaux facteurs de virulence et des gènes de résistance, ainsi que l'usage des nomenclatures des souches à partir de génomes assemblés. Il permet également de prédire les biovars et la toxicité des souches.

Le second axe est consacré à la taxonomie génomique infra-spécifique. Une nouvelle approche de classification et de nomenclature génomiques est proposée en utilisant comme modèle l'espèce *K. pneumoniae*. Ces travaux détaillent la conception et l'implémentation d'un système de codes-barres qui combine le regroupement par *Single Linkage MultiLevel* (MLSL) et les LIN (*Life Identification Number codes*), tous deux basés sur le même schéma de typage *core-genome* MLST (cgMLST). Cette approche taxonomique innovante résulte en une nomenclature infra-spécifique précise et stable, qui est de plus largement déployable chez les autres espèces bactériennes. Une étude de la structure phylogénétique de *C. diphtheriae* a également été réalisée, avec la mise en œuvre d'un système cgMLST sur la base duquel une taxonomie génomique des souches a été proposée.

Sur la base des nouveaux apports et concepts précédemment exposés, plusieurs études de cas ont été réalisées : mise en évidence et caractérisation d'une nouvelle espèce bactérienne (*C. rouxii*), précédemment confondue avec *C. diphtheriae* ; et épidémiologie génomique de la diphtérie dans différentes régions du monde, ou à partir de sources cliniques humaines et animales. Ces applications de la taxonomie génomique associée à la détection des gènes de résistance aux antibiotiques illustrent le potentiel des méthodes et des outils développés durant cette thèse afin de contribuer à la recherche et à la surveillance génomique des bactéries pathogènes.

Mots clés : classification génomique, suivi des pathogènes, nomenclature de souches, résistance aux antibiotiques

Genomic taxonomy of bacterial strains and emergence of antibiotic resistance

Abstract:

Infectious diseases are a global public health concern, particularly due to antimicrobial-resistance in some pathogenic bacteria. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* is one of the most worrying multiresistant bacteria. *Corynebacterium diphtheriae*, which causes diphtheria, remains largely susceptible to first-line antibiotics, including penicillin, and can be controlled through vaccination, but re-emerges when vaccination coverage is insufficient. Among the effective infection control measures, the accurate detection and identification of these pathogens, as well as their epidemiological monitoring, play a key role. In the recent years, the implementation of whole-genome sequencing (WGS) has revolutionised bacterial genotyping, by providing discrimination at the strain level. Genomic sequencing also enables the detection of variants and their important characteristics, such as virulence or antimicrobial resistance.

The research work of this thesis is structured around two main axes.

The first axis provides bioinformatic analyses of the population structure of antimicrobial resistance in *C. diphtheriae*. A genome-wide association study (GWAS) was performed to determine the genetic basis behind the resistance phenotypes, as well as the associations with diphtheria toxin production and other strain characteristics. A new penicillin resistance gene was discovered on a mobile element in *C. diphtheriae*. A genotyping tool was developed specifically for *C. diphtheriae*, for which the links between genotypes and clinical phenotypes are poorly known. This tool consolidates and facilitates the detection and genotyping of the main virulence factors and resistance genes, as well as the use of strain nomenclatures from assembled genomes. It also enables the prediction of biovars and toxicity of strains.

The second axis relates to infra-species genomic taxonomy. A new approach of genome-based classification and nomenclature of strains was developed using *K. pneumoniae* as a model. This work describes the design and implementation of a barcoding system that combines *Single Linkage MultiLevel* (MLSL) clustering and *Life Identification Number* (LIN) codes, both based on the same *core-genome* MLST (cgMLST) typing scheme. This innovative taxonomic approach, widely applicable to other bacterial species, yields precise and stable nomenclatures. A study of the phylogenetic structure of *C. diphtheriae* was also carried out, with the implementation of a cgMLST scheme on the basis of which a genomic taxonomy of strains was proposed.

Based on the contributions and concepts presented above, several case studies were carried out: identification and characterisation of a new species (*C. rouxii*), previously misidentified as *C. diphtheriae*; genomic epidemiology of diphtheria in different world regions or clinical sources. These applications of genomic taxonomy in combination with antimicrobial resistance gene detection illustrate the potential of the methods and tools developed during this thesis to support genomic research and surveillance of pathogenic bacteria.

Keywords: pathogen tracking, strain nomenclature, genomic classification, antibiotic resistance